

Book of Abstracts

ACTRIS SCIENCE CONFERENCE 2024

Science Conference

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1. INTRODUCTION

In 2024 **ACTRIS** organised its **first physical scientific conference** to bring together members of the various **atmospheric science communities** to discuss the latest advances, particularly in the field of **air quality** and **climate research**, and in relation to **health effects**.

350 people from **29** countries attended the first physical edition of the ACTRIS Science Conference.

In the following document you will find the **abstracts** which were presentend at the conference.

The ACTRIS Science Conference was a success thanks to the dedicated community who made it all possible. It was the perfect opportunity to gather scientific excellence to push the boundaries of knowledge. We are already looking forward to the next edition.

Eija Juurola

ACTRIS ERIC Director General

2. COMMITTEE MEMBERS

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2. SPONSORS AND EXHIBITORS

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THEME 1 - LONG-TERM TRENDS AND VARIABILITY OF THE ATMOSPHERIC COMPOSITION

Scientific Committee Members:
Doina Nicolae and Cathrine Lund Myhre

What have we learned from 10 years observation at Chacaltaya, Bolivia?

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Located at 5240 m a.s.l. in Bolivian Cordillera and surrounded by a large variety of complex natural and anthropogenically influenced environments, the Chacaltaya GAW station is the perfect site for monitoring changes occurring in the atmosphere. From this unique observation site, it is possible to capture air masses travelling from the lowlands and the Amazon Basin loaded with biogenic emissions, influenced by regional background air masses from the Altiplano and from the Pacific Ocean, and the anthropogenically influenced air masses from the conurbation of La Paz/El Alto. It is also possible to monitor the seasonal occurrence of biomass burning emissions from the agricultural practices in the Bolivian middle and low lands.

In addition to the main CHC site, in operation since January 2011, and to better monitor the influence of the La Paz/El Alto metropolitan region (1.7 million of inhabitants) located 17 km to the south but more than 1 km below CHC, additional sites have been installed over the years, at different heights in the cities, from 3400 in the University building of Cota Cota, in central La Paz at 3600 m a.s.l. and at the international airport of El Alto (4100m). All city sites are classified as Urban background stations. Overall, the extended CHC/La Paz/El Alto facilities constitute a very unique infrastructure for atmospheric science due to the extended monitoring program comprising greenhouse gases, reactive gases, aerosol monitored with in-situ and remote-sensing techniques, but also due to the extended altitude range for the measurements (3400-5240 m), the intense radiation in a sub-Tropical region and the constantly changing environments due to anthropogenic pressures.

Since 2011, continuous observations and specific intensive field campaigns such as the SATENA (Bianchi et al. 2021) have led to several important findings about the atmospheric environment and the impact of both anthropogenic activities and of natural phenomena:

- Quantification of the positive trends of Greenhouse Gases (CO₂, CH₄) concentrations and their variability with seasons and air mass origins
- The mechanisms of new particle formation and the role and origin of condensable organic matter on the growth to CCN (Rose et al., 2017, Bianchi et al., 2021, Zha et al., 2023)
- The impact of regional scale biomass burning on the tropospheric concentrations of climate-relevant short-lived constituents, such as black Carbon (Chauvigné et al., 2019)
- The quantification of the impact of the metropolitan area of La Paz / El Alto on concentrations measured at CHC station (Aliaga et al., 2021)
- The identification of the main emission sources at CHC and in the metropolitan area (Mardonez et al., 2023)
- The first estimates of the health impact of pollution by particulate matter in the city area.

The presentation will review these findings.

Rose, C., et al., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17, 1529–1541, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-1529-2017>, 2017.

Wiedensohler et al., *Atmos. Environ.*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.09.032>, 2012.

Chauvigné, A., et al., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-19-14805-2019>, 2019

Bianchi, F., et al., *BAMS*, <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0187.1>, 2021

Zha et al., *National Science Review*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwad138>, 2023

Aliaga, D., et al., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 16453–16477, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-16453-2021>, 2021.

Mardonez, V. et al., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-10325-2023>, 2023.

Exploring causes of low single scattering albedo during autumn in central North America

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Keywords: aerosol, single scattering albedo, atmospheric processes.

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At several long-term monitoring sites in central North America the aerosol single scattering albedo (SSA) exhibits a marked decrease in October (Delene and Ogren, 2002; Sherman *et al* 2015). The SSA seasonal pattern persists over decades of measurements suggesting a persistent process or source is causing it. Various hypotheses which have been put forward to explain the decrease in SSA, including agricultural activities (e.g., harvesting or field burning) and wet scavenging by precipitation or fog droplets. This analysis explores these hypotheses in detail for one such site in the central United States.

We focus on the measurements at Bondville (BND) one of NOAA's long-term Federated Aerosol Network sites located in central Illinois. The BND sampling site is in the middle of soybean and corn fields, 100s of km from major urban areas (Chicago, St Louis and Indianapolis). Aerosol light scattering coefficient, absorption coefficient, and number concentration have been measured by NOAA at BND since 1994. Other collocated measurements include aerosol composition from both the IMPROVE network and NOAA/PMEL, precipitation composition by the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP), air quality parameters such as CO and PM by the Illinois Environmental Protection Agency, and various meteorological parameters. There is also an AERONET sun-photometer at the site and NOAA made in-situ aerosol profile measurements in an instrumented Cessna airplane over the site (365 flights between 2006-2009) so there is some information about aerosol above the surface (e.g., Andrews *et al* 2017). The National Weather Service also makes Automated Service/Weather Observing Systems (ASOS) observations nearby (~5km) which include visibility and precipitation measurements as well as indicators of the presence of fog, dust, and smoke. We use this array of collocated measurements, to see if it is possible to identify a specific cause for the decrease in SSA.

Analysis to date

Jaffe *et al* (2020) describes the impact of wildfires and prescribed burning across the US and provides seasonal maps of fire locations. Few fires were identified near the BND site, or more broadly in the state of Illinois. However, it's possible that smoke is transported to BND. Two common tracers for smoke are CO and potassium. CO at BND tends to be higher in the winter months and

lower in the summer months. October interestingly has the lowest median CO concentration which suggests smoke is unlikely to be the primary explanation for the SSA decrease in that month. In contrast, potassium tends to be higher in the summer and lower in the winter, with September and October exhibiting some of the highest K⁺ values. Atmospheric potassium can also come from dust and fertilizer, so the anti-correlation of K⁺ with CO is not completely surprising. We will further explore source contributions using wind data and trajectory analysis.

IMPROVE and NOAA/PMEL aerosol chemistry data suggest sharp declines in sulphate in October which are consistent with the observed decrease in aerosol scattering coefficient. Rather than a change in source, an increased sink such as wet scavenging could lead to a relative increase in absorption aerosol which would also result in a lower SSA. We will evaluate various measurements from ASOS and NADP to determine whether increased precipitation or fog might be contributing to the low October SSA.

Figure 1. Interannual variability of monthly median SSA at BND for 2012-2018.

This work was supported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (grant# NA22OAR4320151).

Andrews, E. *et al* (2017). *Atmos Chem. Phys.* **17**, 6041-6072.

Delene, D.J. and Ogren, J.A. (2002) *J. Atmos. Sci.* **59**, 1135-1150.

Jaffe, D. *et al* (2020). *J. Air Waste Manag. Assoc.*, 70(6), 583-615.

Sherman, J.P. *et al* (2015). *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **15**, 12487-12517.

Optical properties of supermicron aerosol particles in a boreal environment

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Keywords: long-term trend analysis, light absorption and scattering coefficients, Ångström exponent.

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This paper reports the long-term analysis of aerosol optical properties (AOPs) for the PM₁₀, PM₁ and supermicron (> PM₁ and ≤ PM₁₀) and the PM mass of super-PM₁₀ (> PM₁₀) aerosol particles from the SMEAR II measurement site in Hyytiälä, southern Finland. Some examples of these aerosol particles are dust, pollen and spores. AOPs are a function of the interaction between the aerosol particles and radiation, and affect the climate through radiative forcing. Hence, the primary motivation for this study is to quantify the AOPs of the supermicron aerosol particles. This has been done by subtracting the corresponding AOPs of PM₁ from PM₁₀. SMEAR II is located in a boreal forest and is classified as a background site, where no major local sources of aerosol particles from anthropogenic activities are observed. However, there is a seasonal release of pollen and spores which may contribute to supermicron and super-PM₁₀ aerosol particles at this site. Also, due to the size cutoff range of the two aerosol optical instruments (aethalometer and nephelometer) at 10 μm, the AOPs of the super-PM₁₀ aerosol particles cannot be analyzed. Thus, the secondary motivation of this study is to quantify and understand the PM mass of the super-PM₁₀ aerosol particles from a cascade gravimetric impactor.

We have quantified the long-term trends of the supermicron fraction in the AOPs from mid-2010 to 2022, using an aethalometer for the absorption coefficient, a nephelometer for the scattering coefficient and a cascade gravimetric impactor for the PM mass.

A statistically significant decreasing trend has been observed for the light absorption coefficient at 520 nm ($\sigma_{\text{abs}, 520 \text{ nm}}$) and the light scattering coefficient ($\sigma_{\text{sca}, 550 \text{ nm}}$). Thus, the trend in $\sigma_{\text{abs}, 520}$ for PM₁₀, PM₁ and supermicron aerosol particles have been calculated to be -0.123, -0.117 and -0.013 Mm⁻¹ yr⁻¹. The trend in the $\sigma_{\text{sca}, 550}$ is also observed to be decreasing for PM₁₀, PM₁ and the supermicron aerosol particles with rates of -0.358, -0.364 and -0.057 Mm⁻¹ yr⁻¹. The decreasing trend continues for the PM mass of the submicron and the supermicron aerosol particles with rates of -0.128 μgm⁻³ and -0.043 μgm⁻³. These rates are consistent with the decrease in the rates of $\sigma_{\text{abs}, 520 \text{ nm}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{sca}, 550}$.

To conclude, this study reports the observed scattering and absorption coefficients of the PM₁₀, submicron, and supermicron aerosol particles, and connects these findings to the seasonal characteristics of aerosol particles at SMEAR II.

Figure 1. Long-term trend of $\sigma_{\text{abs}, 520}$ for the supermicron aerosol particles from 2010-22.

Figure 2. Long-term trend of $\sigma_{\text{sca}, 550}$ for the supermicron aerosol particles from 2010-22.

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Luoma, K. et al., 2019. Over a 10-year record of aerosol optical properties at SMEAR II. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 19(17), 11363–11382.

Zieger, P. et al., 2015. Low hygroscopic scattering enhancement of boreal aerosol and the implications for a columnar optical closure study. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15(13), 7247–7267.

Detection of ozone recovery in the Arctic from ground-based measurements

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Keywords: Arctic, ozone, trends.

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Stratospheric ozone is expected to recover thanks to the reduced emission of ozone depleting substances since the Montreal protocol. This is especially important in the polar regions where the ozone levels are strongly affected by the effective-chlorine content to create the 'ozone hole' problem. Due to the high natural variability of ozone in the Arctic, the recovery is difficult to detect, which is why no evidence of positive trends has been found so far.

We aim to study the Arctic, stratospheric ozone by calculating long-term trends from ground-based stations. Additionally, we calculate tropospheric ozone trends at these locations. We report on these Arctic ozone trends from 7 different sites providing long-term ground-based ozone data from Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy as well as ozone sounding instruments from 7 sites. The involved sites are all shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. High-latitude/Arctic FTIR (blue) and ozone sounding (red) stations that are used in the project

Six of the FTIR sites are from NDACC (Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change) and provide public data that allow us to analyze four partial columns for most Arctic sites, one in the troposphere, three in the stratosphere (Vigouroux et al., 2015). The FTIR ozone concentrations from Sodankylä, however, are new data derived within this project. This site namely measures ozone in the 3040 cm^{-1} range instead of the 1000 cm^{-1} range for the NDACC sites. In this spectral

region, lower vertical information can be obtained, namely two partial columns in the stratosphere (Zhou et al., 2020).

To provide conclusions about Arctic ozone trends, we study the representativeness of the involved ground-based ozone measurements by comparing the ground-based data to model reanalysis data from CAMS (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service). Firstly, we analyze the effect of the irregular temporal sampling of the FTIR data by calculating a sampling bias following the method of Miyazaki et al. (2017). Secondly, we look at the spatial representativeness where we follow the methodology of Weatherhead et al. (2017). Here we calculate the correlation of each ground-based station with the other spatial points within the Arctic. This study enables us to assign to each site the region for which the trend at the given site is representative. Additionally, it supports the merging of data sets from different sites that are strongly correlated for improving the temporal sampling for trend detection.

The Arctic datasets are used to calculate long term trends through a multiple linear regression technique involving a set of proxies that represent physical processes influencing the natural ozone variability (Vigouroux et al, 2015). We show results for total ozone column and separate tropospheric and stratospheric columns to determine if there is a significant ozone recovery in the Arctic by studying both annual and seasonal trends. In addition to individual data set trends, we show if the trend detection can be improved by merging data sets based on the preliminary representativeness study.

Miyazaki, K. and Bowman, K. (2017) *ACP*, 17:8285–8312
Vigouroux, C., Blumenstock, T., Coffey, M., et al. (2015) *ACP*, 15:2915–2933
Weatherhead, E.C., Bodeker, G.E., Fassò, A., et al. (2017) *JAMC*, 56:3211–3228
Zhou, M., Wang, P., Langerock, B., et al. (2020) *AMT*, 13:5379–5394

This work was supported by the Belgian Science Policy Office through the IM/RT/23/DORA project.

Comparison of NO_x in the remote marine boundary layer in the Northern and Southern hemispheres

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Keywords: NO_x, MBL

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The remote oceanic atmosphere is an important region with few emissions, where the hydroxyl radical, OH, oxidises many pollutants and greenhouse gases. Nitrogen oxides (NO and NO₂, known as NO_x) are involved in the ozone cycle and due to their low mixing ratios over the oceans, their abundance determines if there is an ozone producing or destroying regime. With the photolysis of ozone leading to the formation of OH, understanding the processes involved in the production and loss of NO_x over the oceans leads to a better understanding of the factors affecting the atmosphere's oxidising capacity.

Figure 1 – The Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory

Despite the importance of understanding these atmospheric cycles, the low mixing ratios of NO_x over the oceans make it difficult to measure in this environment. The Cabo Verde Atmospheric Observatory (CVAO, Figure 1) and the Kennaook/Cape Grim Baseline Air Pollution Station (KCG BAPS,) in Tasmania are unique as sites where long-term measurements of the remote oceanic atmosphere are carried out. Both sites are World Meteorological Organisation Global Atmosphere Watch (WMO GAW) stations and have been running for many years. Since 2009, both sites have been measuring NO_x using a chemiluminescence instrument manufactured by Air Quality Design USA and a commercially available blue light converter (BLC).

Figure 2 – The Kennaook/Cape Grim Baseline Air Pollution Station

This presentation will show the first comparison between NO_x in the remote marine boundary layer (MBL) in the Northern and Southern hemispheres. Specifically, it will look at the ratio between measured NO₂ and NO₂ calculated using photostationary state equations. This ratio can be used to determine if any chemical processes are missing from our understanding of the atmospheric chemistry. This analysis has already been performed with data from the CVAO by Andersen *et al.* (2022), with the ratio close to 1 in clean background air. However, in air masses containing some aged pollution, the ratio was higher than 1, indicating that the calculated values were underestimating the measured values. This could be caused by the presence of a missing oxidant but could also be due to artefacts in the measurement. This analysis will also be performed on the NO_x data from the KCG BAPS helping to further investigate the presence of a missing oxidant or a measurement artefact.

The CVAO is funded by the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS). The KCG BAPS is funded and managed by the Australian Bureau of Meteorology, and the scientific program is jointly supervised with CSIRO Environment. This work was supported by the Wild Visiting Scholars Fund.

Andersen, S. T., Nelson, B. S., Read, K. A. Punjabi, S., Neves, S., Rowlinson, M. J., Hopkins, J., Sherwen, T., Whalley, L. K., Lee, J. D. and Carpenter, L. J. (2022) *Atmos. Chem Phys.* **22**, 15747-15765

Response of organic aerosol to Delhi's pollution control measures over the period 2011–2018

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Keywords: Particulate matter, Organic aerosol, Offline aerosol mass spectrometry, Positive matrix factorisation, Delhi, Source apportionment.

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Delhi, India, experiences some of the world's highest air pollution episodes, and studies show particulate matter (PM) is the main air pollutant that negatively affects Delhi residents' health. Over the last decade, multiple air quality mitigation strategies have been deployed in Delhi which have not been examined. Charting the sources of PM over extended time periods is essential in order to evaluate the efficacy of these strategies and effectively identify trends.

We present a novel automated offline approach for aerosol mass spectrometry (AMS) that has made it possible to conduct high-throughput analysis of PM filters using an organic solvent mix, achieving high extraction recoveries of organic aerosol (OA) ($95.4 \pm 8.3\%$). PM₁₀ filter samples taken in Delhi during 2011, 2015, and 2018 were analysed and further source apportionment analysis using positive matrix factorization (PMF) divided the OA into nine factors. These are grouped into four main source categories: burning-related (solid fuel or open burning), traffic, cooking, and coal combustion.

During the winter and post-monsoon, when total OA concentrations were at their maximum, burning-related OA contributed the most. Between 2015 and 2018, there was a 47% decrease in annual mean burning-related OA concentrations. This decrease coincides with the 2015 ban on open waste burning as well as regulations and incentives to reduce burning of crop residue. However, further compositional analysis indicates that municipal waste burning tracers are still present in 2018, suggesting further room for burning-related OA to be reduced.

A significant decrease (87%) in coal-combustion OA was achieved due to the closure of two local coal power stations, along with initiatives to reduce coal consumption in industry, businesses, and residential homes. This equates to a 17% decrease in total OA and shows the efficacy of these measures in lowering PM₁₀ concentrations.

Considering there have been rapid increases in registered vehicles in Delhi, Bharat stage emissions standards appear to suppress increases in traffic OA. However, significant increases in PM₁₀ concentrations during the post-monsoon and winter months are linked

to restrictions on HGVs entering Delhi during the daytime. This is likely due to the resultant large influx of diesel-engine HGVs entering the city when the boundary layer is particularly low during the early mornings and evenings, resulting in enhanced surface concentrations.

Figure 1. Average concentrations of PM₁₀ OA factors during each of the four seasons of the years 2011, 2015 and 2018

This work is published in *Atmospheric Environment* (Cash et al., 2023).

Cash, J. M., Di Marco, C., Langford, B., Heal, M. R., Mandal, T. K., Sharma, S. K., Gurjar, B. R., and Nemitz, E.: Response of organic aerosol to Delhi's pollution control measures over the period 2011–2018, *Atmos Environ*, 315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2023.120123>, 2023.

Multi-year high-time resolution datasets of submicron aerosols at 13 French urban sites: Chemical composition and organic aerosol source apportionment

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Keywords: Air quality, urban pollution, PM₁, organic aerosol sources, rolling PMF.

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Studying atmospheric aerosols is essential due to their significant impacts on climate and human health. In France, fine particulate matter (PM) exposure leads to 40,000 premature deaths annually (Medina et al. 2021). Their concentrations surpass the World Health Organization recommended annual PM_{2.5} concentration of 5 µg m⁻³ (EEA, 2021). In this context, Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitors (ACSMs) and aethalometers (AE33) have been continuously operating at various (sub)urban sites in France since 2015. The main goal is to acquire comprehensive, long-term datasets detailing PM₁ chemical composition and to investigate the origins of organic aerosols (OA) through the application of the recently developed rolling Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) method. In particular, rolling PMF offers the advantage of capturing potential temporal variations in source profiles across multi-year datasets.

This study first confirms that OA constitutes the main component of PM₁ in France (40-60%). Spatial and seasonal variations in both the chemical composition and OA sources are studied. Primary factors are associated with combustion processes, notably hydrocarbon-type OA (linked to road-traffic, HOA), and biomass burning OA (BBOA), consistently present at all sites (around 15% of the total OA mass). BBOA peaks in winter due to increased emissions from residential wood burning. Additionally, site-specific primary sources, such as those related to cooking (COA; 10-14%), as well as emissions from ports and/or industries (ShInd-OA and 58-OA; 4%) were identified. Oxygenated factors were differentiated into less oxidized (LO-OOA) and more oxidized (MO-OOA) fractions, dominant at all sites (74%), and highlighted the substantial impact of ageing and secondary formation processes. In winter, a strong correlation between LO-OOA and BBOA highlights the contribution of biomass combustion (37 to 50%), and its influence

during pollution episodes. In summer, LO-OOA displays an increase possibly linked to biogenic SOA.

Comparisons with the CHIMERE model and filter-based aerosol tracers are also performed, aiming to improve our understanding of OA sources in France and potentially enhance the accuracy of air quality models. The obtained results also help advance our comprehension of the health implications of particulate matter, providing a basis for future epidemiological studies and also offer valuable insights to inform public policies aimed at source mitigation.

Figure 1. OA sources and their contributions for 12 French sites.

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Influence of cloudy/clear-sky partitions and aerosols variabilities on surface solar irradiance measured in Lille, Northern France (2010-2022)

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Keywords: surface solar irradiance, aerosols, clear-sky, clear-sun with clouds, variability, trends

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The variability of solar radiation incident at the surface, vital for ecosystems and life, has also important implications for practical applications such as solar power generation. Atmospheric conditions, especially clouds and aerosols largely influence the surface solar irradiance amount and evolution, as well as its repartition into direct and diffuse components. Here we analyze coincident daytime ground-based measurements of level 2.0 aerosol optical properties from AERONET photometer and of direct and diffuse horizontal surface irradiances from a set of pyrhelimeter and pyranometer in operation at the ATOLL (Atmospheric Observations in Lille) platform in north of France over the period 2010-2022. In order to isolate the radiative effect of aerosols from that of cloud, a separation between cloudy-sun, clear-sun with surrounding clouds and clear-sky moments is performed using two cloud detection algorithms at 1-min resolution. The measurements are further analyzed with the radiative transfer code SOLARTDECO to simulate the spectrally integrated solar global horizontal irradiance (GHI) and its direct (BHI) and diffuse (DHI) components.

Our analysis highlight that on average in ATOLL over the period 2010-2022, the proportion of clear-sky conditions is relatively low (11%), whereas clear-sun with clouds and cloudy sun situations represent 22% and 67%, respectively. These sky conditions highly influence measured GHI and their repartition into direct and diffuse components. The 2010-2022 mean of GHI is minimum in cloudy-sun situations (174 W/m²) and maximum for clear-sun with clouds situations (424 W/m²), with intermediate values in clear-sky conditions (375 W/m²). Seasonal variations (Figure 1) show that spring and summer, characterized by maximum monthly mean GHI values, are associated with lower influence of clouds but relatively high levels of AOD (aerosol optical depth) due to frequent continental polluted influence. Diffuse irradiances show highly variable monthly averaged contributions from less than 20% of GHI in clear-sky conditions (from May to August) to more than 90% during winter cloudy-sun situations.

From 2010 to 2022, our measurements show significant upward trends in all-sky global GHI for both spring and summer seasons (around + 4 ± 2 W/m²/year), mainly driven by high rises in direct irradiances. Clear-sky global and direct irradiances also show upward trend in

summer only. Moreover, over these 13 years, spring 2020 exhibited record values of both mean all-sky GHI (389 W/m²) and clear-sky frequency (34%). These variabilities and trends are further interpreted in terms of clear-sky/cloudy partitions and aerosols changes. Moreover, by combining our measurements with SOLARTDECO, the direct radiative effect of aerosols is calculated for clear-sky and clear-sun with clouds conditions in Lille.

Figure 1. Monthly variations in Lille over the period 2010-2022 of (a) Sky conditions in percentages (b) Mean values of AERONET AOD₄₄₀ (c) Mean values of AERONET Angström Exponent (AE₄₄₀₋₈₇₀) (d) Proportions of the different aerosol classes derived from AOD and AE measurements. The proportion of clean situations (AOD₄₄₀ ≤ 0.1) is also represented as pink columns, (e-h) Mean irradiances for different cloud cover states: (e) All-sky, (f) Cloudy-sun, (g) Clear-sun with clouds and (h) Clear-sky. Only values during daytime between [sunrise + 30 min; sunset - 30 min] are considered. The GHI is represented as columns with the lower blue part corresponding to the diffuse and the upper yellow part to the direct components. The grey dashed lines represent the 2010-2022 annual mean GHI.

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Long term analysis of aerosol optical properties and dominant types over Europe

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Keywords: aerosol classification, AERONET, aerosol trends.

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Atmospheric aerosols play a significant role in Earth's radiative budget. Their impact on meteorology, air quality, climate, ecosystem, and human health depends on the geographic distribution, nature, and seasonality of their sources (Ramanathan et al. 2001).

This study presents a sixteen-year analysis of aerosol optical properties for different sites in Europe. It compiles results from three Western European countries (France, Italy, and Spain), four Eastern European countries (Greece, Moldova, Romania, and Ukraine), two Central European countries (Switzerland and Poland), and two Northern European countries (the United Kingdom and Norway). For all these cases, measurements were performed using the CIMEL Electronique CE318-N/T multiband sun photometer, as part of the AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK (AERONET) (Holben et al. 1998).

Daily averages of quality level 1.5 data for both direct sun measurements and inversion products have been used in this study. For the majority of the sites, the data spans from January 2007 to October 2023. The only exception is in the case of Poland, for which the available data spans from January 2017 to October 2023. In this case, the results play a role only when looking at that specific period.

Notably, elevated yearly average Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) values, measured at 500 nm, within the range of 0.17 to 0.25 are observed for urban and pre-urban sites from Western and Eastern European countries, contrasting with lower values of 0.08 to 0.1 for rural sites from Northern and Central European countries. Throughout the years, AOD values fluctuated between lower values in winter and high values in summer for all the sites, therefore suggesting a seasonal variability of this parameter.

Results consistently indicate an Angstrom Exponent, calculated between 440 and 870 nm, exceeding values of 1 across all years for all the sites. The highest measured Angstrom Exponent comes from Eastern European countries, with values larger than 1.5, and up to 2. This points out the prevalence of fine particles, a conclusion substantiated by the volume size distribution analysis, which shows a highly pronounced bimodal distribution, contrasting the slightly flat and almost flat distributions of the Western, Central, and Northern sites. Further investigation during the classification of dominant aerosol types supports these findings.

For the classification procedure, in this study, we have used the cluster method with thresholds

researched and published by Dubovik et. al (2002), and Lee et. al (2010). We have added the kernel density estimate through which is it possible to visualize the distribution of observations in our datasets. Results consistently show how large parts of the distributions are attributed to fine non-absorbing and slightly-absorbing particles (for example Kishinev site Figure 1.). Part of the data analyzed through this set of thresholds (Lee et. al 2010) comes out as uncertain. When correlating the two sets, this uncertain data is mostly composed of continental, polluted, and mixed particles. The exact reason for the existence of these uncertainties is to be discussed.

Figure 1. Dominant aerosol types for Kishinev, Moldova from January 2007 up to October 2023

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Long time series of volatile organic compounds at the German Meteorological observatory Hohenpeissenberg

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Keywords: VOC trends, HPB, ACTRIS, GAW.

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Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are key substances for the formation of tropospheric ozone, they affect the oxidation capacity of the atmosphere and play an essential role in the formation of organic aerosol. Hence, they impact our climate and their observations are utilised to study emissions, transport and chemistry processes.

Anthropogenic VOCs are emitted mostly from industrial applications and transportation by fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning and evaporation from solvents. Biogenic VOCs, which are the most abundant on the global scale, are predominately produced by plant metabolism.

Emissions of anthropogenic VOCs are regulated by the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (Gothenburg Protocol 1999) since 1999 and the European Air Quality Directive 2008/50/EC. Thus, the atmospheric burden of anthropogenic VOCs has decreased over the last 20 years. Biogenic emissions are subject to climate change with respect to rising temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns and atmospheric composition.

We will present trends of anthropogenic and biogenic VOCs observed at the Meteorological Observatory Hohenpeissenberg (HPB) in Southern Germany.

VOC measurements at HPB

Continuous measurements of anthropogenic and biogenic VOCs are performed at the GAW Global station and ACTRIS-NF candidate Hohenpeissenberg (HPB) since 1998 and 2000, respectively. Applying on-line GC/FID (Plass-Duelmer et al., 2002) and GC/MS techniques, air is sampled twice a day at 0:00 and 12:00 UTC, complemented with intensive measurement phases with a time resolution up to 1 hr. The measurements systems and the recorded data have been subject to quality control measures by WMO-GAW and ACTRIS (Hoerger et al., 2015). Over the last two decades, a comprehensive data set has been collected.

Trend analysis

Time series of NMHCs are fitted with a trend function combining an exponential decay to describe the decline of anthropogenic VOCs and a seasonal cycle.

The trend function is fitted to monthly means of the daytime (12:00 UTC) measurements by least square approximation rejecting the lower and upper 5% outliers. 12 UTC values are selected to capture the fully developed, well-mixed boundary layer.

Figure 1. Times series of Ethane 12:00 UTC amount fractions in pmol/mol (grey open circles) measured at the Meteorological Observatory Hohenpeissenberg since 1998. Black full circles represent monthly averages and the trend fit is shown with a black line. The upper right corner depicts the scheme of the fit function.

Ethane with a lifetime of 2-3 month reflects a hemispheric footprint and does not show a significant trend. Shorter-lived compounds e.g. aromatics, alkenes and higher alkanes with few hours to a few days of atmospheric lifetime provide feedback from local to regional to European changes and show negative exponential trends of 3-5%/year.

For biogenic VOCs, no significant trends are observed.

This work is made possible by the long-term commitment of the technical staff at HPB in the framework of WMO-GAW and supported by ACTRIS with its predecessor projects ACTRIS-1 (FP7/2007-2013, G.A.262254) and ACTRIS-2 (H2020, G.A. 739530).

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Methodology of long-term trend analysis: limitations in the application of parametric fitting and non-parametric Mann-Kendall methods

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Keywords: long-term trend, methodology, Mann-Kendall, autocorrelation, prewhitening.

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The methodologies to detect long-term trends must be chosen according to the properties of the analyzed time series. Fitting methods such as the least mean square (LMS) fits are powerful and flexible methods allowing e.g., detection of non-linear trends, change-points or use of proxies. They are however restricted to cases where the residuals of the fitting procedure are normally distributed. Most in-situ and columnar aerosol parameters do not fulfil such prerequisite for parametric methods, requiring the use of non-parametric methods.

The Mann-Kendall (MK) test associated with the Sen’s slope is the most widely used non-parametric method for trend analysis, but requires serially uncorrelated time series. Several prewhitening methods have been designed to overcome the presence of autocorrelation. These include a simple prewhitening, sequences of detrending /prewhitening or a combination of several methods (3PW), that can be associated with a correction of the detrended slope and the original variance. Different prewhitening methods lead to different powers of the MK tests, sensitivity to false positives trends and bias of the slope estimates. Moreover, the choice of prewhitening method influences the statistical significance (ss), the slope and the confidence limits (CL).

Figure 1. a) Variance-corrected trend free prewhitening method (VCTFPW) slope versus the time granularity for a time segmentation into four meteorological seasons for 10-y of aerosol absorption coefficient data. b) Percentage of 3PW ss trends versus normalized slope and N.

The effects of various prewhitening methods were analyzed for a variety of 10-60 y atmospheric time series: meteorology, water vapor and aerosol time series, characterized by a broad variety of distributions, ranges and autocorrelation values. The effect of choosing time granularities (one day to one year) was also evaluated since a common way to overcome the autocorrelation problem is to average time series to a coarser time granularity. The main impact of keeping a fine time granularity is to allow the computation of the trends on a larger dataset (more data points, N), which improves the power of the MK test and decreases the uncertainties in the slope (Fig. 1b).

The following best practices are recommended for MK long-term trend analysis: 1) a prewhitening method must be used if the data are autocorrelated, 2) the seasonal MK test must be used on time series with a clear seasonal cycle, 3) time series < 10 y must be handled with great caution and time series < 8 y should not be used, 4) fine time granularities should be used in order to maximize the number of data points and to yield smaller CL and larger ss, 5) the slope should be corrected in order to take into account the effect of the prewhitening on the time series mean and variance. Finally, the sign of not ss trends should not be mentioned or discussed, since they cannot be distinguished from zero trends and CL must be considered in order to assess the uncertainty in the slope.

Code availability

We provide a Matlab, Python and R implementation of the algorithm in dedicated Github repositories hosted within the “mannkendall” organization (<https://github.com/mannkendall>).

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10-year monitoring (2012-2022) of atmospheric gas composition at the Puy de Dôme research station (France, 1465m a.s.l.)

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Keywords: interannual variability, reactive gases

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The puy de Dôme Research Station (1465 m asl) (**Global GAW PUY**), central France, is located on the first mountain chain facing dominant western winds. Its main objective is to document the long-term composition of the troposphere and the dynamic, chemical and microphysical processes that govern it. The station is exposed to an oceanic climate. It is surrounded by a protected area where fields and forests are predominant. The city of Clermont-Ferrand (150 000 inhabitants) is located 16 km east of the station at 396m a.s.l. During the winter and spring months, the station is located in the open troposphere, so the air masses sampled are subject to little local pollution. During the summer months, the height of the mixing layer is such that the Puy de Dôme can be directly influenced by emissions from the Clermont-Ferrand city.

At the summit, meteorological parameters including wind speed and direction, temperature, pressure, relative humidity and radiation, atmospheric trace gases (ozone (O₃), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), volatile organic compounds (VOC)), and aerosol physical, optical and chemical properties (particle size, black carbon, mass,...) are measured since years (1995 for the ozone), coupled with a sun photometer and a LIDAR measurements and radar remote sensing instruments (vertical wind profiles (UHF and VHF profilers), spatial distribution of precipitation (band radars X and K, disdrometer) at its base. This configuration allows for the identification of the part of the atmosphere that the station is sampling (Planetary Boundary Layer, Lower Free troposphere, Nocturnal residual layer, Interfaces).

PUY site is in cloud approximately 50% of the time between November and March, which allows for multiphase chemistry studies.

This study will focus on **atmospheric gas composition** measured at PUY station and using ACTRIS procedures: The data obtained provide an opportunity to study decennial trend of atmospheric components and to understand the temporal and seasonal variability of concentrations in relation to the dynamics of the atmosphere and the origin of air masses, and to deduce

their role in the formation of secondary and photooxidising species.

The results presented here are discussed in terms of observed levels (i), diurnal and seasonal variability (ii), air mass origins (iii) and sources of these gaseous pollutants (iv).

- (i) This set of perennial measures has served as a basis for studying the diurnal, seasonal and decennial variation of the atmospheric composition.
- (ii) Because the height of planetary boundary layer (PBL) changes with a diurnal cycle and with seasons, PUY is in the different layer of troposphere during the year and it has an impact on the measured concentration.
- (iii) In order to determine the transport pathways of the air masses prior to arriving at the pdD site, the CAT model was used (Baray et al., 2020) Trajectories were classified according to their predominant transport direction prior to measurement as either continental (C), marine (M), marine modified (Mod), Mediterranean (Med), or mixed depending on their pathways.
- (iv) The method of principal component analysis (PCA) is used for the correlations of the components.

Figure 1. Mann Kendall trend applied on O₃ concentrations. The graph represents the ozone concentration from 2012 to end of 2020

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Long-term variability of black carbon concentrations at a suburban super-site near Bucharest, Romania

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Keywords: black carbon, temporal variation

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Black carbon (BC), commonly known as soot, significantly influences Earth's climate system. (Bond et al., 2013). Formed through the incomplete burning of fuels, BC stands as a pivotal atmospheric pollutant, exerting a significant positive climate forcing effect (IPCC, 2021) while also posing risks to human health (Janssen et al., 2011). The built in source apportionment aethalometer model developed by Sandradewi et al. (2008) was used for separating the traffic and biomass burning fractions of BC.

Measurements were made at a peri-urban ACTRIS National Facility located in Măgurele, Romania (44.344°N, 26.012°E, 77 m a.s.l.) using an AE33 aethalometer (Aerosol Magee Scientific). While data is available from the beginning of 2013, encompassing over a decade of continuous monitoring, the study particularly focuses on the period from 2020 to the beginning of November 2023. Openair (Carslaw and Ropkins, 2012) data analysis tools were used for the variability estimates of BC fractions.

The data reveals an expected diurnal pattern in BC concentrations, notably highlighting increased values during early morning (7-8 LT) and after the evening rush hour (21-22 LT). These fluctuations appear correlated with increased human activities such as peak hours of traffic, fossil fuel combustion, and residential heating processes. Using the source apportionment model, the biomass burning average fraction of BC was estimated to be $29.25\% \pm 13.89\%$.

An analysis of seasonal patterns was performed throughout the study years. During the colder months, concentrations are approximately twice as high, mainly due to residential heating. As observed in Figure 1, biomass burning fraction concentrations are significantly higher during this period. Furthermore, there is notably less fluctuation in BC concentrations from traffic sources, with lower values during months of reduced human activity, such as school holidays.

A comparative study with the focus on the main lockdown in 2020 was also conducted. BC aerosols during periods of reduced economic activity exhibited lower monthly concentrations than the averages from other years, particularly in March and May. The diurnal variation of BC concentrations during March-May 2020

follows a similar bimodal distribution, although with a less prominent trend, almost flat due to minimal emissions throughout the day. This observation is reinforced by the average diurnal variation of BC fractions, as the fossil fuel component is at its lowest during the spring of 2020, showcasing a weaker bimodal trend compared to other years. Conversely, the biomass burning component remains relatively constant over the years.

Figure 1. Variability of fossil fuel and biomass burning BC concentrations during 2020-2023

This work is supported by the RI-URBANS project (Research Infrastructures Services Reinforcing Air Quality Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial Areas, European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Green Deal, European Commission, contract 101036245); and by the Core Program within the National Research Development and Innovation Plan 2022-2027, carried out with the support of MCID, project no. PN 23 05 and through Program 1- Development of the national research development system, Subprogram 1.2 - Institutional performance - Projects to finance the excellent RDI, Contract no.18PFE/30.12.2021. We also acknowledge the support of the ACTRIS ERIC.

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The importance of long-term reactive trace gas remote sensing measurements for ACTRIS science and services

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Keywords: remote sensing, trace gases, long-term trends
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The Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change ([NDACC](#), De Mazière et al, 2018) became operational in 1991 under the auspices of national and international scientific agencies, including the World Meteorological Organization (WMO). Since then, NDACC has contributed to the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) programme. Today NDACC comprises about 80 active affiliated stations distributed world-wide among which many in Europe or operated by European partners. Its primary purpose of NDACC is to provide mutually consistent high-quality reference data on the variability, distribution, and long-term trends of more than 30 atmospheric variables at the global scale, from the troposphere to the mesosphere, with an emphasis on ozone, and species affecting climate change and air quality.

Building on this long heritage of coordinated observations, data quality control and fair data dissemination, the past, present and future reactive trace gas remote sensing observations that are included in the ACTRIS RI will provide an essential contribution to ACTRIS research. In ACTRIS the target variables for now are ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), formaldehyde (HCHO), ethane (C₂H₆) and ammonia (NH₃) columns and vertical profiles, measured by Fourier-transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometry, UV-Visible (MAX)DOAS type spectrometers and/or O₃ DIAL lidars, complemented with PANDORA measurements belonging to the Pandonia Global Network ([PGN](#)). The Topical Centre for Reactive Trace Gas Remote Sensing (CREGARS) will ensure a sustainable service for ensuring data quality and consistency, in compliance with the ACTRIS requirements and aligned with the NDACC and PGN data protocols whenever there is overlap.

In this presentation, the focus will be on the scientific impact of high-quality long-term data records

from the various trace gas remote sensing observations contributing to ACTRIS. In addition, the importance of continuous monitoring for enabling the identification of unexpected atmospheric processes, for the detection of anomalies, and for watching the compliance with environmental regulations will be showcased with recent examples.

Remote sensing observations are the most useful reference for satellite and global or regional model validation, as will be demonstrated with examples from the ESA Atmospheric Mission Performance Validation and Data Analysis Facility (ATM-MPC VDAF) and the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) Evaluation and Quality assurance (EQA) activities.

In addition we will discuss the scientific rationale behind the collaboration with PGN and future challenges and evolution of the observational and data analysis techniques calling for fundamental science and technological advances.

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LONG-TERM MEASUREMENT OF OZONE CONCENTRATIONS IN SEMI-NATURAL AFRICAN ECOSYSTEMS

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Keywords: long-term monitoring, ozone photochemistry, trends.

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Abstract. INDAAF, part of the Aerosols, Clouds and Trace gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS-Fr) and an official contributing network to the Global Atmospheric Watch program of the World Meteorological Organization (GAW/WMO), is a long-term monitoring network dedicated to studying the evolution of the chemical composition of the atmosphere and atmospheric deposition in Africa. In the framework of the INDAAF program, we propose (1) to document the variability of atmospheric ozone (O₃) concentrations, (2) to investigate the different contributions to O₃ formation and (3) to calculate trends in O₃ concentrations. In this study, we consider fourteen measurement sites, representative of the main African ecosystems: dry savannas (Banizoumbou, Niger; Katibougou and Agoufou; Mali, Bambey and Dahra, Senegal), wet savannas (Lamto, Côte d'Ivoire; Djougou, Benin), forests (Zoétélé, Cameroon; Bomassa, Republic of Congo) and semi-agricultural/arid savannas (Mbita, Kenya; Louis Trichardt, Amersfoort, Skukuza and Cape Point, South Africa). Over the period 1995-2020, monthly ozone concentrations were measured at these sites using passive samplers (Adon *et al* 2010). We used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Mann-Kendall tests to investigate respectively the precursor contributions to O₃ photochemical formation and the time trends per site (Aït-Sahaliaa and Xiu, 2019; Merabtene *et al* 2016). Annual averages of surface ozone range from 3.9±1.1 ppb in Congo to 29.1±8.4 ppb in South Africa (Fig.1). Ozone levels in the wet season (in dry savannas) are higher and comparable to concentrations in the dry season (in wet savannas and forests). In East Africa and Southern Africa, ozone levels are almost similar from one season to the next, with higher levels in Southern Africa. In the Sahel, under the influence of temperature, ozone formation is closely linked to biogenic Volatile Organic Carbon (VOC) emissions. It is also sensitive to nitrogen monoxide (NO) emissions in the presence of high precipitation and humidity. Biogenic VOC emissions, anthropogenic NO_x, temperature and radiation are the dominant contributors to O₃ formation in wet savannas, forests and

southern Africa. At the seasonal and annual scale, Katibougou and Banizoumbou, sahelian sites experienced a significant decrease in O₃ concentrations (around -2.3 % yr⁻¹ and -0.6% yr⁻¹) consistent with a decrease of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and biogenic VOCs. A significant upward trend at the seasonal scale is reported at Zoétélé in Cameroon and at Skukuza in South Africa, in agreement with an increase in biogenic emissions and NO₂ levels. Very few surface O₃ measurements exist in Africa, and long-term results presented in this study are the most extensive for the studied ecosystems.

Figure 1. Annual mapping of O₃ concentration levels in ppb.

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Atmospheric Microplastic in the Arctic and Mainland Norway; occurrence, composition and sources

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Keywords: microplastic monitoring, long-range transport, deposition.

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Microplastics are emerging contaminants present in all environmental compartments. After a strong focus on the presence of microplastics in aquatic environments in previous years, the occurrence of airborne microplastics finally receives increasing scientific attention. Airborne microplastics have been detected in indoor and outdoor environments, including in remote places such as the Arctic due to their potential for long-range transport.

Here we present the outcomes of a study applying passive (deposition) and active air samplers at two remote ACTRIS monitoring stations, Zeppelin in Ny Ålesund (Svalbard) in the High Norwegian Arctic, and Birkenes in mainland Norway.

Bi-weekly samples were collected during the period of June-December in 2022 and 2023. We used full metal bulk precipitation samplers and suspended air samplers (Innovation NILU's Atmospheric Microplastic Collector). All samples were handled under strict QA/QC requirements, with all sample treatment occurring in controlled conditions of clean rooms and laminar flow cabinets. After filtration on a GF/F filter, polymer determination was performed by pyr-GC/MS (Frontier lab multi shot pyrolyzer EGA/PY 3030D connected to a Frontier lab AS 1020E Auto shot sampler connected to a ThermoScience TSQ9000 GC/MS/MS). The analytical method, adapted from Gossmann *et al.* (2023), uses calcium carbonate as a catalyst for the simultaneous quantification of 10 different polymers and SBR rubber, originating from tires. With this adapted method it is possible to quantify PMMA (poly(methyl methacrylate)), Nylon-6 (polycaproamide), PP (polypropylene), PU (polyurethane), PVC (poly(vinyl chloride)), PC (polycarbonate), PET (poly(ethylene terephthalate)), PE (polyethylene), as well as PS (polystyrene), SBR (styrene-butadiene rubber) and PTFE (polytetrafluoroethene). All samples were accompanied with field and procedural blanks. Results were further analysed with respect to their spatial origin and long-range transport using the Lagrangian particle dispersion model FLEXPART.

Figure 1. Polymer composition of deposition samples collected at Zeppelin station and Birkenes station.

Figure 1 illustrates the composition of deposition samples collected at Zeppelin and Birkenes stations. While SBR and Nylon dominate in the Norwegian mainland samples, almost every of the measured polymers contribute to the samples from Zeppelin. These differences can be explained by the closeness to urban regions being a source of car tire particles and synthetic textiles for Birkenes in Southern Norway, while Zeppelin is rather impacted by long-range transport of a broad range of polymers. MP concentrations in deposition samples were more than 10-times higher than in active samples, and concentrations in Arctic samples were in general lower than in samples from the Norwegian mainland. Interseasonal variations can be found both on the Norwegian mainland as well as the high Arctic.

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Gossmann, I., Herzke, D., Held, A., Schulz, J., Nikiforov, V., Georgi, C., Evangeliou, N., Eckhardt, S., Gerdt, G., Wurl, O., Scholz-Böttcher, B.M. (2023) *Nature communications* 14:3707.

Studies of the annual aerosol circulation over Sofia, Bulgaria

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Keywords: AERONET, sun photometer, aerosol climatology

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The aerosol field is an atmospheric component impacting strongly various processes in the atmosphere over oceans and land; this impact on the air quality and, thus, human health is particularly critical. This is why it has been the subject of numerous exhaustive investigations using various experimental facilities and networks for contact probing and active and passive remote sensing.

The main purpose of the present work is to extend the climatological and typological investigations of the aerosol situations (events) over the city of Sofia, Bulgaria (Evgenieva *et al*, 2022), namely, the studies on the data acquired during the period 5 May 2020 – 28 February 2022 are complemented by the data obtained and analyzed in the period 1 March 2022 – 4 December 2023. The measurements were performed by means of an AERONET Cimel CE318-TS9 sun/sky/lunar photometer and concerned the optical and microphysical characteristics of the aerosol ensembles over the Sofia Aerosol Remote Sensing Station, which is involved in the activities of the European aerosol lidar network EARLINET and research infrastructure ACTRIS.

The results obtained show that the seasonal evolutions of the aerosol optical depth at the wavelength 440 nm (AOD_{440}) and the Ångström exponent for the wavelength pair 440/870 nm ($AE_{440/870}$) in 2022 and 2023 are similar to those in 2020 and 2021. Accordingly, AOD_{440} is a non-stationary random function of time with zones of maximum mean values from February to April and from June to September, while $AE_{440/870}$ is a stationary random function with a nearly constant mean value (Evgenieva *et al*, 2022)

The frequency distributions of the measured realizations of AOD_{440} and $AE_{440/870}$ during the periods 1 March 2022 – 28 February 2023 (P3) and 1 March 2023 – 4 December 2023 (P4) have similar characteristics to those concerning the periods 5 May 2020 – 28 February 2021 (P1) and 1 March 2021 – 28 February 2022 (P2). Indeed, the AOD_{440} distributions are bimodal, while the $AE_{440/870}$ distributions are three-modal. The peak positions of the modes of AOD_{440} and $AE_{440/870}$ for the periods P3 and P4 are near the corresponding positions for the periods P1 and P2 (Evgenieva *et al*, 2022). The mean values estimated of AOD_{440} and $AE_{440/870}$ for the periods P3 and P4 are $\sim 0.20 \pm 0.09$ and 0.22 ± 0.11 , and 1.47 ± 0.36 and 1.41 ± 0.39 , respectively, again near the ones concerning the preceding periods P1 and P2 (Evgenieva *et al*, 2022).

The scatter plot (Fig. 1) for the periods P3 and P4 of the daily-mean aerosol situations represented as daily-mean $AE_{440/870}$ - AOD_{440} aerosol events (points) outline similar aerosol typology and climatology to those during the periods P1 and P2. In Fig. 1, the seasons (winter, DJF; spring, MAM; summer, JJA; and autumn, SON) are presented in different colors. The events are naturally divided by type into six groups, roughly delineated by one vertical, $AOD_{440} = 0.32$, and two horizontal, $AE_{440/870} = 1$ and 1.3 dividing lines. They contain the same aerosol types, within near $AE_{440/870}$ - AOD_{440} boundaries, as in the periods P1 and P2, namely, biomass-burning (BB), mixed (MA), Saharan dust (SD), and urban (UA) aerosols. The aerosol types are confirmed using AERONET data, SD-forecasting and air-mass back-trajectory recovering models and satellite images of fire outbreaks. The relative occurrences of BB, MA, SD and UA from 1 March 2022 to 4 December 2023 are estimated to be 10.75 %, 17.06 %, 13.31 %, and 58.88 %, respectively, near the corresponding values obtained for the period from 2020 - 2022.

As a whole, on the basis of the results obtained in this study, one can conclude that each year, from 2020 to 2023, reproduces the “aerosol history” of the preceding year. Repeatable annual aerosol cycles are observed with similar typological, climatological and statistical characteristics, including the occurrence rate and the seasonal distribution of the aerosol events.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of $AE_{440/870}$ vs. AOD_{440} for the period 1 March 2022 – 4 December 2023.

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Emissions and chemistry of industrial and non-industrial anthropogenic terpenoids by combining worldwide urban VOC databases over the last decade : insights from the DATAbase project

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Keywords : isoprene, monoterpenes, urban pollution, emissions

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Terpenoids (isoprene and monoterpenes) are Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) known for their high reactivity in the atmosphere and for their biogenic origin. However, there is some strong evidence of their anthropogenic origin through, for instance, the most recent studies in North American cities investigating their use as Volatile Chemical Products (VCP) in indoor environments (Mc Donald et al., 2018).

As part of DATAbase project we have investigated the industrial and non-industrial anthropogenic origin of terpenoids in the urban atmosphere. We compiled and re-analyzed 14 data sets of in situ VOC observations collected over the last decade in contrasting urban areas from mid-latitudes to subtropical regions (Fig. 1).

First, we show the systematic presence of anthropogenic terpenoids in urban ambient air with clear covariations with anthropogenic compounds ($R^2 > 0.50$) even during mid-latitude winters. Despite the emerging importance of monoterpene emissions from consumer products in North American cities, there is some evidence of monoterpene emissions from tailpipe exhaust in cities of the developing world (Borbon et al., 2018)

For the first time, the industrial emissions of α -pinene, one major monoterpene, in the northern harbor city of Dunkirk, France, is estimated based on Emissions Ratios and Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF). Three and a half tons of industrial α -pinene are emitted per year in Dunkirk which is in the same order of magnitude as in Paris where the emissions of monoterpenes (11.8 tons each year). Those emissions are related alkene- petrochemical, metallurgical and coal-fired industrial activities (Farhat et al., in rev.).

While absolute anthropogenic emissions of terpenoids usually represent less than 3% of other anthropogenic VOC emissions, they dominate the reactivity of anthropogenic VOC emissions by one to three orders of magnitude regarding nighttime oxidation by NO₃ and ozonolysis, respectively.

This study raises two questions which need further investigations in the future: (a) the significance of terpene emissions from traffic, especially in urban areas of the developing world and (b) the role of anthropogenic terpenoids in nighttime and wintertime atmospheric chemistry at mid-latitudes.

For the latter, we have performed OD box modelling using the Cloud Explicit Physico-chemical Scheme (CLEPS) developed at LaMP. CLEPS is coupled to the chemical mechanism MCM v3.3.1 to evaluate the impact of anthropogenic terpenoids on atmospheric chemistry by establishing scenarios representative of contrasting urban environments.

This presentation will synthesize the recent findings of DATAbase, the added-value and challenges in combining multiple datasets and will propose future directions.

Figure 1: The worldwide DATAbase datasets

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Spatial and temporal trends of atmospheric NH₃ and aerosol NH₄⁺ concentrations inferred from low-cost sampling in rural France (2007-2023).

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Keywords: atmospheric ammonia, reduced nitrogen.

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Atmospheric ammonia (NH₃) is mostly emitted (95%) by agriculture. In addition to the environmental effects of atmospheric deposition of reduced nitrogen (NH_x) on ecosystems (soil acidification, eutrophication, loss of biodiversity, NO₃⁻ leaching, indirect N₂O emissions), NH₃ contributes to fine particle (PM_{2.5}) formation impacting human health. Estimates of NH_x dry deposition are very uncertain due to a large spatial variability, the difficulty and cost of measurement, and the lack of a rural monitoring network for NH₃ concentrations in France.

Ammonia concentrations have been monitored over a period of 15 years using the DELTA® (DENuder for Long-Term Air sampling) system (Tang et al., 2009), or ALPHA® (Adapted Low-cost Passive High Absorption) sensors at 27 French sites (25 rural, 2 urban) (Sutton et al., 2001). Aerosol NH₄⁺ concentrations were measured at 14 of these sites. The results show strong geographical and seasonal variations in NH₃ concentrations. Average NH₃ concentrations were larger at agricultural sites than semi-natural (forest, wetland) sites (mean concentrations of 3.28 versus 0.89 µg NH₃-N m⁻³). Spring peaks were systematically observed due to fertiliser inputs on cropland and grassland. Concentrations were largest in Brittany, NW France. The average for the two urban sites was 1.86 µg NH₃-N m⁻³.

Figure 1: DELTA® monitoring sites (NH₃/NH₄⁺ measurements)

The average NH₄⁺ concentration was 0.55 µg NH₄⁺-N m⁻³. Spatial variations in NH₄⁺ at the national scale were much smaller than for NH₃, but there was a small negative gradient from north to south.

Average NH₃ concentrations measured at the sites show a clear correlation to emission inventories for the relevant grid squares underpinning EMEP chemical transport modelling (average 1990-2017) (Figure 2). The Brittany sites present the largest NH₃ concentrations, consistent with very intensive livestock farming in the region and reflected in the national emission inventory. The paper analyses the spatial and temporal variations in atmospheric NH_x in relation to emissions, agricultural management and meteorology, and examines the performance of EMEP chemical transport modelling in simulating spatial concentration fields and seasonal/annual trends for France.

Figure 2: Relationship between average measured NH₃ concentrations at different monitoring sites and NH₃ emission inventories for the relevant EMEP grid squares.

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Long-term trends (>15 years) of submicron aerosol chemical composition in a remote coastal site: impacts from marine and anthropogenic sources

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Keywords: Marine aerosol, HR-ToF-AMS, source apportionment.

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Atmospheric aerosol plays a crucial role in climate effects by scattering/absorbing solar radiation and modifying cloud. In addition, aerosol have adverse impacts on human health. Marine aerosol, one of the most important parts of the natural aerosol, often dominates the aerosol loading in remote locations and plays a significant role at the global scale. Therefore, thorough understanding of marine aerosol sources, formation and chemical composition is essential for climate models. The importance of the marine aerosol has been extensively studied, and changes in marine aerosol composition are found to closely relate to the seasonal changes in marine biological activities (Ovadnevaite et al., 2014). However, long-term studies with detailed regional chemical characterization are invaluable for the evaluation of long term trends in changing fields and for the evaluation of model predictions, but still lacking.

The Mace Head (MHD) Global Atmosphere Watch station locates at the west coast of Ireland and faces westward to the northeast Atlantic, making it advantageous for the study of oceanic and continental aerosol sources. Winds from a direction between 190 and 300° reach MHD without passing over any inhabited land, thus can provide baseline data of NE Atlantic sources. While air masses originate from the continental sector are more affected by anthropogenic emissions thus more polluted. The chemical composition of submicron aerosols (PM₁) has been measured continuously by high resolution time-of-flight aerosol mass spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS) since 2008. In this study, the unique long-term dataset is used to understand the effect of season and air mass origin on the chemical composition of the atmospheric aerosol.

The results show that aerosols from marine and continental air masses have totally different characterizations. The air masses from continental sector generally have much higher PM₁ concentration than marine sector (e.g., >10 vs. 1.8 μg m⁻³, Figure 1) with carbonaceous species, i.e., Organics (Org) and black carbon (eBC) dominating PM₁ (34%), while Sulfate (SO₄, 40%) and sea salt (28%) dominate marine aerosol. Moreover, marine aerosol shows a strong and significant seasonal cycle with sea-salt dominating in winter due to higher wind speed, and biogenic organic species dominating in summer due to much stronger oceanic biogenic activities (Figure 2). The long-term trends analysis show that there is barely significant changes in

aerosol concentration and composition over the past 15 years, indicating that MHD is a regionally representative and reliable background site.

Figure 1. Location of Mace Head station and examples of aerosol composition in air masses from different origins.

Figure 2. Seasonal variations of (a) sea salt and (b) MSA mass concentrations at MHD.

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Sources and processes affecting aerosol concentrations and deposition to the sea surface of the coastal Adriatic Sea and biogeochemical implications

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Keywords: particulate matter, atmospheric deposition, source apportionment, biogeochemistry, Adriatic Sea

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The atmosphere is a significant pathway by which both natural and anthropogenic material is transported from continents to coastal and open seas. Once deposited through atmospheric deposition (AD) processing, atmospheric particulate matter (PM) provides the aqueous ecosystems with an external source of nutrients and pollutants. This, in turn, influences the phytoplankton organic matter (OM) production, changes CO₂ uptake and indirectly affects the climate. The input of AD is especially important in oligotrophic environments and it is expected to increase in the future scenarios of a warmer atmosphere with increased PM emissions and deposition rates. While most of the data related to the AD impacts generated so far in the Mediterranean have been conducted on its western and eastern regions, the impact of the AD inputs to the Adriatic Sea sub-basin was unknown. Therefore, this work aims to assess the impact of AD on the complex biochemical responses of the Adriatic oligotrophic systems, considering the sea surface microlayer (SML) that controls all exchange processes between the ocean and the atmosphere (Milinković *et al* 2021, 2022, Penezić *et al* 2021).

The field campaign was conducted during the retrieval of sea surface oligotrophic conditions (February-July 2019) at the Central Adriatic, Croatia as part of the BiREADI project. On-line equivalent black carbon (eBC) concentrations were measured while the PM₁₀, wet and total deposition samples as well as the SML and underlying water (ULW; 1 m depth) samples were collected simultaneously. The first comprehensive insight into concentration levels of inorganic N and P species, trace metals and carbonaceous material (including organic pollutants) in atmospheric samples, their transport history, source apportionment and deposition fluxes to the oligotrophic Adriatic area will be presented.

Daily and seasonal variations of PM₁₀ composition were affected by local traffic and intensive open biomass burning (BB) events as well as by local meteorological conditions and long-range transport. Biomass burning (BC_{bb}) versus fossil fuel (BC_{ff}) contribution to eBC mass changed seasonally. Source

apportionment module of LOTOS-EUROS chemical transport model enabled identification and quantification of main source areas contributing to deposition of PM. The main PM contributor is a public power sector outside Croatia while other contributing sectors are energy production, traffic, residential combustion as well as shipping.

The temporal dynamics of the biology and concentrations of inorganic and organic constituents of the sea surface enabled the assessment of sources and the nature of the enrichments taking place in the SML. The AD associated with BB emissions played an important role in OM enrichment in the SML. Changes in OM quality and quantity within the SML could in turn have strong implications for a range of global biogeochemical processes mediated by the SML. Thus, the potential BB impact on the suppression of CO₂ exchange at the sea-atmosphere interface was estimated, as being at least 3 times higher in comparison to non-BB conditions at the Adriatic coastal area. This work demonstrates the importance of studying short-term scale interactions between the atmosphere and marine compartments, which can lead to a significant improvement in understanding the ocean-atmosphere system. This study also serves as a basis of comparison for future studies addressing air quality and pollution source apportionment in the Adriatic and/or Mediterranean coastal regions in efforts of mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

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Aerosols in the Tropical Island of La Réunion (21°S, 55°E): climatology and trend of vertical distribution from multiwavelength ground-based lidar time series

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Keywords : aerosols, extinction profiles, La Réunion.

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Understanding optical and radiative properties of aerosols and clouds is critical to reduce uncertainties of climate models. This work aims to study the seasonal vertical distribution and optical properties of aerosols in the troposphere and the stratosphere over Reunion Island and the South-West Indian Ocean region (SWIO).

Three multiwavelength time-series of vertical extinction and backscatter atmospheric profiles were computed between 2013 and 2023 from the nighttime measurements of three lidars over Maïdo Observatory. Emitted wavelengths were: (i) 355nm for the 1200 (Li1200) and ozone stratosphere (LiOS) lidars, and (ii) 532nm for the ozone troposphere (LiOT) lidar with depolarization capabilities. A total of 1737 raw lidar signals were preprocessed and processed to retrieve aerosol optical products. The time-series and monthly climatologies of extinction and backscatter vertical profiles, Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and Ångström exponent ($\text{Å}_{355/532}$) were produced at 355nm and 532nm between 3 and 30km of altitude depending on instrumental performances.

There is a good correlation between the Li1200 and LiOS in terms of AOD at 355nm (Mean: 0-0.04; Correlation: $R = 92 \pm 0.5\%$) and with the LiOT in terms of $\text{Å}_{355/532}$ (0-1.4; $R = 90 \pm 12.8\%$). Results suggest the seasonal occurrence of aerosol plumes of different types and origins in the troposphere and the stratosphere, under the influence of dynamical transports. In the low stratosphere (17-23km), high extinction, AOD and $\text{Å}_{355/532}$ values between May and January are consistent with a permanent layer of sulfated aerosols (Junge et al., 1961). Lower values between February and April could suggest advection of tropospheric air masses of different composition due to reinforced convection (Evan et al., 2020).

In the high troposphere (10-14km), identification of two high extinction, high AOD and high $\text{Å}_{355/532}$ layers during the September to November and May to June periods suggest the seasonal and height-dependent influence of biomass burning (BB) aerosol plumes (Duflot et al., 2022). In the low and middle troposphere (3-10km), climatology at 532nm shows the presence of two aerosol layers during the BB season (**Figure 1**): (i) The first plume is identified between 3 and 4km with the strongest AOD in August and September (resp. 0.01 and 0.02 +/- 0.006), (ii) and the second plume is

identified between 5 and 7.5km with the strongest AOD also between August and September (0.005 +/- 0.007).

Figure 1. Climatology of tropospheric aerosol extinction profiles over Maïdo at 532nm (LiOT).

Ensemble back trajectories from the Hysplit simulation model suggest a South African and South American origin for the lowest plumes with the strongest AOD, and an influence from Indonesian fires for high troposphere plumes indicating a potential long-range transport of BB aerosols from the south-east Asian region to the SWIO region, possibly under the influence of the Asian monsoon (Duflot et al., 2010).

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Characterization of Volatile Organic Compounds in 2020-2021 and source apportionment of VOC and Organic Aerosol in the summer 2020 at the SIRTACTRIS station (Paris region)

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Keywords: Volatile Organic Compounds, Secondary Organic Aerosol

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Long-term collection of in situ atmospheric measurements is crucial for understanding the variability of atmospheric chemical composition, its sources, and patterns. Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) play a key role in atmospheric chemistry notably as precursors to secondary organic aerosol (SOA). However, long-term VOC monitoring using online mass spectrometry, such as PTR-MS, is still limited in Europe.

At the SIRTACTRIS station (Paris region), a PTR-Q-MS was established in January 2020. This set-up serves as a pilot for the implementation of continuous PTR-MS measurements and uniform data processing within ACTRIS.

The analysis of the dataset acquired during the initial two years of online VOC measurements highlights the specificities of these compounds in a suburban environment. The influence of local sources such as traffic, wood burning, and biogenic sources are reflected on the VOCs' diurnal cycle (Figure 1), as well as the effect of meteorological conditions.

It is worth noting that the seasonal and diurnal variabilities of monoterpenes, which are traditionally considered from biogenic origin in suburban areas, suggested potential influences from anthropogenic sources.

Figure 1. Diel cycles of VOCs, ambient temperature, solar radiation and boundary layer height. The line represents the 2020-2021 mean value and the shaded area is the 95% confidence interval.

The temporal variability of the VOCs in 2020-2023 shows an increase of aromatic and oxygenated compounds in the wintertime, attributed to wood-burning sources and boundary-layer dynamics. Conversely, biogenic and oxygenated VOCs increased in summer due to higher temperature and solar radiation.

The summer season is also associated with biogenic SOA formation (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Taking advantage of the co-located long-term ACSM measurements, the relationship between VOCs and organic aerosol formation was investigated through an innovative ACSM-PTRMS combined source apportionment (PMF) analysis during summer 2020.

The inclusion of VOCs as input results in an improved separation of particulate organic matter, compared to the conventional ACSM-only PMF, and a definition of secondary organic aerosol based on its precursors and processes. In particular, this approach enabled the identification of two factors related to biogenic processes during daytime and nighttime.

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Long term comparisons of aerosol optical depth measurements; differences and trends

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Aerosol optical depth (AOD) is the single most comprehensive variable to assess the columnar aerosol load of the atmosphere. AOD is the parameter that describes the aerosol column direct effect on solar radiation and the most important aerosol-related parameter for Earth energy budget related studies (WMO, 2016; IPCC, 2013). There are various instrument/networks measuring AOD worldwide, mainly AERONET (Aerosol RObotic NETwork; Holben et al., 1998) and also the Global Atmospheric Watch Precision Filter Radiometer (GAW-PFR) network (Kazadzis et al., 2018) and the sky radiometer network (SKYNET).

AOD changes in a certain location are associated with the variability of aerosol sources and atmospheric transport. Several studies have investigated long-term trends of AOD from ground-based observation using multiple instruments (e.g. Cuevas et al., 2019). The accuracy of AOD measurements and trends from ground-based instruments has a particular significance since they are used for satellite validation, climate model validation and modelling assimilation etc.

Figure 1. Long term PFR series at Izaña stations; up: monthly AOD in 4 wavelengths, middle: Ångström exponents and down: intra-annual AOD variability

In this study long term AOD measurements (more than 20 years) at Mauna Loa (USA), Izaña (Spain, fig. 1) and Davos (Switzerland) with two types of instruments (CIMEL/PFR) belonging to different aerosol networks (AERONET/GAW-PFR) has been analyzed. In addition, CIMEL and PFR parallel measurements for the past two

years at the CARS/ACTRIS sites of Ohp (France) and Valladolid (Spain) are shown and discussed.

The long-term comparison of the two instruments over the whole period for all sites, have been analyzed and differences in AOD for 500nm and 865nm were within the instrument uncertainties, while more than 95% of data were within the WMO traceability limits.

Figure 2. Long term CIMEL and PFR comparisons (differences at 500nm) at Mauna Loa, USA. Shaded area represents the WMO limits and colours represent different CIMEL instruments measuring at each period.

The link of AOD differences with the observed AOD trends calculated by each of the instruments at each site is discussed here.

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Seasonal variability of eBC and TC in atmospheric aerosol, on the example of real-time measurements conducted in the GZM Metropolis

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Keywords: carbonaceous aerosol, black carbon, air pollution, metropolitan area.

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The last two decades have been a period of significant reductions in emissions of particulate matter (PM) and its gaseous precursors, which has contributed to reducing the population's exposure to these substances. Despite these improvements, air pollution remains one of the biggest environmental problems, and the discussion on introducing effective control measures remains a priority. This is particularly important in areas such as GZM Metropolis, located in southern Poland and considered one of the European hotspots.

This work focuses on research on carbonaceous aerosol, which is often the dominant part of the PM mass, accounting for an average of 20-60% of PM_{2.5} (particles with aerodynamic diameter < 2.5 μm) (Li *et al.* 2018). This share may still increase in locations strongly influenced by anthropogenic emission sources – such as: road traffic, industrial plants, and fossil fuels combustion in households – as well as in periods of increased pollution concentrations (Błaszczak *et al.* 2023; Reizer and Juda-Rezler, 2016).

The research was conducted at the urban background station in Zabrze, located in the center of GZM Metropolis. The main aim of the work was, on the one hand, to assess air pollution of the considered area with carbonaceous aerosol in a long-term perspective, and on the other hand, to investigate the relationship between levels of total carbon (TC) and black carbon (eBC), associated with PM_{2.5} – based on the campaign conducted in the period Jun – Oct 2023. Advanced automatic equipment belonging to the research infrastructure of the ACTRIS project was used for the measurements, specifically: a) eBC – Multi-angle Absorption Photometer 5012 (ThermoScientific); b) TC – Total Carbon Analyzer TCA08 (Magee Scientific).

Figure 1. Changes in eBC concentration [μg·m⁻³] at the urban background station in Zabrze, 2010–2023.

The concentrations of eBC showed a clear downward trend. It was found that both eBC and TC concentrations displayed similar temporal variations, related to changes in the intensity of the impact of anthropogenic emission sources and fluctuations in meteorological parameters. When analyzing data from the period Jun – Oct 2023, there were very high significant correlations between TC and eBC ($r = 0.80$, $p < 0.05$). The eBC/TC ratio values varied within wide ranges (0.01–0.96) and averaged 0.18.

Figure 2. The course of the hourly concentrations of eBC and TC at the urban background station in Zabrze (1 Jun – 31 Oct 2023).

This work was supported by the IEE PAS statutory research project no. 1a-146/24 (“Variability of the physicochemical composition of atmospheric pollutants in urban and non-urban areas on the example of the Silesian metropolis and the Polish-Czech border”). The work was also prepared as a part of the research project no. POIR.04.02.00-00-D019/20-00 “ACTRIS – Infrastructure for the study of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases”, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund.

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Review of 20 years of Cloudnet observations at the Lindenberg Observatory and future directions to gain Cloudnet data consistency

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Keywords: long-term Cloudnet observations, Lindenberg Observatory, Cloudnet data consistency.

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The Lindenberg Observatory is an ACTRIS national facility for cloud remote sensing that has been providing all relevant surface remote sensing observations for the ACTRIS Cloudnet data processing (Illingworth et al., 2007 and Tukiainen et al., 2020) for 20 years now. The long-term Cloudnet monitoring at the Lindenberg site provides a unique dataset of cloud macrophysical and microphysical properties for studying, for example, the seasonal and interannual variation of mid-latitude cloud properties and trends in their characteristics as well as for improving cloud parametrizations in numerical weather prediction models at DWD using the power of the long-term statistics (Görndorf et al., 2011, Köhler and Görndorf, 2014, Khlestova, 2020).

The continuous provision of high-quality and synergetic remote sensing cloud observations with appropriate temporal and vertical resolution for the Cloudnet data portal for 20 years requires long-term deployment and optimised operations of the key remote sensing instruments, namely the cloud radar along with a disdrometer, the microwave radiometer and the ceilometer. This presents multiple challenges that include replacement of instruments (S/N or even type), changes of system configuration, operation parameters and change of software, data formats and data upload requirements. Furthermore, the continuous operation (24/7) over more than 10 years can lead to instrument failures resulting in downtime. Important for maintaining high data quality are consistent maintenance activities, regular instrument calibration, post-processing, as well as quality control by monitoring of technical parameters and comparisons against independent references.

This review focuses on our experiences from 20 years of Cloudnet observations, discusses the challenges of the long-term operation of the remote sensing instruments and provides guidance on how to incorporate continuous monitoring and data quality checks; putting special emphasis on instrument calibration issues in order to gain harmonized long-term datasets of cloud properties. Additionally, we show an example of a successful application of Cloudnet products for model improvement.

Furthermore, we discuss the reproducibility of the Cloudnet products dependent on the use of various cloud remote sensors and Cloudnet processing algorithms currently being investigated at the Lindenberg

Observatory by the establishment of two independent Cloudnet instrument complexes at one location. This is clearly needed for an error estimation of Cloudnet products and the development of harmonised processing procedures in order to obtain consistent Cloudnet products for their use in the ACTRIS network (Tukiainen et al., 2020).

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Long-term Day and Night-Time Aerosol Optical Depth Measurements at Ny-Ålesund Using Sun and Lunar Precision Filter Radiometers.

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Keywords: polar AOD, long-term AOD measurements

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Polar regions are sensitive to climate changes. During the 20th century in the Arctic air temperatures over extensive land areas increased by up to 5°C sea ice thinned and declined in extended, ocean warmed (IPCC,2007). Accurate Aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements are one of the essential parameters for radiative transfer modelling and climate prediction.

Aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements have been performed within the frame of Global Atmospheric Watch Precision filter radiometer (GAW-PFR) network in Ny Ålesund since 2002. Instrument calibration and protocols follow the ones defined by the World Optical depth Research and Calibration Center (WORCC) (Kazadzis et al. 2018a). AOD retrievals are based on direct sun solar irradiance measurements and are available yearly from March till October. To fill the gap in the AOD time series lunar nighttime aerosol optical depth measurements started in 2014 after the development of the Lunar-PFR at PMOD/WRC.

The time series of the AOD at 500 nm and Ångström exponent (AE) based on direct sun and lunar irradiance measurements are shown in Figure 1. The trend analysis of the day-time AOD time series based on the MK method (Collaud Coen et al. 2020) showed a negative trend in the spring-time aerosol load (Figure 2). The lunar-AOD measurements, filling the gap in the annual cycle, have not been considered in the analysis, since the current high uncertainty is a limiting factor in

merging the timeseries. Moreover, the frequency of observation of day and nighttime AOD is different due to the weather conditions during the polar winter and summer. In this work ways to merge the two datasets are investigated. In additions the lunar data are carefully analyzed to bring light in the observed trends.

Figure 2. Trend analysis for AOD at 862 nm for the period 2002-2019. Big cycles trends with confidence levels higher than 95%. Red squares indicate trends homogeneous for the 4 meteorological seasons. Open circles: trends calculated directly from the whole time series, assuming no seasonal cycle

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Figure 1. Time series of AOD measurements at 500 nm (upper panel) in green monthly mean AOD over the polar summer and in yellow stars daily mean AOD from lunar retrievals over the polar winter. Similarly, Ångström exponent (AE) time series from sun (monthly mean) and lunar (daily mean) AOD measurements

Vertical gradients of atmospheric aerosols chemical composition

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In spite of considerable progress in recent years, a quantitative and predictive understanding of atmospheric aerosol (AA) sources, chemical composition (CC), transformation processes and environmental effects is still limited. [1]

Mass spectrometry of AA, since it has been established, has quickly become the most essential and fastest growing area of aerosol research [2]. Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS) data analysis is widely used to determine the concentrations of chemical species in AA particles. This method deconvolves the ensemble mass spectrum into the partial spectra of distinct chemical species. [3]

Investigating vertical gradient by studying characteristic mass to charge ratio (m/z) of fragments of AA chemical constituents using direct continuous AMS is a novel approach that has not yet been used.

Also, the 230 m tall tower installation for AA sampling at National Atmospheric Observatory in Košetice (NAOK) is unique in the Czech Republic and moreover these kind of installations are scarce even globally. NAOK is a reference rural background site which offers insight into comparison of AACC from local sources and those from long-range transport.

We deployed an automated programmable switching valve that enables connection of both sampling routes (230 m long tube from the tower and 4 m above ground level) to the AMS. These two sampling routes are being switched regularly in given intervals (e.g. 10 or 15 min). This ensures that the meteorological conditions and other factors don't influence the concentration more than necessary thus providing precision and accuracy of the obtained values of measured variables.

It is known that aerosols collected at the ground level originate mostly from local sources, typically residential heating, agriculture and traffic. In Košetice area, there are no major sources of AA from industry, which is why NAOK serves as a reference rural background site for the Czech Republic.

Aerosols at a higher altitude are long-range transported, typically aged continental aerosol, marine aerosol, forest fires and volcanic eruptions. [4].

AMS data will be processed using IGOR software with its corresponding modules (e.g. Squirell). This way the overall mass spectra are deconvolved into individual chemical species that constitute AA particles. This is especially needed for organic part of the aerosol constituents. Usually, they are accounted for as a bulk of

organic phase. The organic ions are associated with several types of organics including mass spectral markers for hydrocarbon-like (m/z 57) and oxygenated (m/z 44) organics [5]. They are chosen because they are frequently the most prominent masses in the organic fraction of the mass spectrum [6].

Some of the other characteristic ionization fragments are ethyl ion (m/z 29), propyl ion (m/z 43), markers of burning (m/z 55 and 91), biomass burning markers specifically (e.g. levoglucosane) (m/z 60 and 73) or polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) (m/z 173).

Individual chemical species concentrations will be evaluated with regard to atmospheric conditions, seasonal and daily cycles but the main scope of this work is to evaluate as accurately and precisely as possible the concentrations of individual chemical species chosen as markers for AA source apportionment and compare these concentrations between the two heights.

This way we will be able to get a clearer picture about the difference of AACC at a ground level from those collected at 230 m. By doing so and correlating the results with meteorological parameters that can tell us the height of the atmospheric boundary layer, we will be able to have an idea about trends in concentration and CC in mixing air streams. It is known that the CC of AA particles is dependent not only on size but also on intensity of solar irradiation, relative humidity, wind speed and direction and, last but not least, the presence (height) of the planetary boundary layer.

With this work we improve our understanding of AACC, mainly source apportionment of AA due to quantification of individual chemical species present in AA particles. Also, comparison of CC between ground level and higher altitude AA has not yet been done this way. These data are shared within ACTRIS. This will add to the current state of general knowledge about AACC, transition processes and source apportionment.

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Trends of surface ozone and its precursors over 20 years in Southern Germany

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Keywords: surface ozone, volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, climate change, air quality

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Anthropogenic emissions, climate change and mitigation strategies alter the composition of trace gases with impact on air quality and climate. Since 1995, the Hohenpeissenberg meteorological observatory operated by the German Meteorological Service (DWD) performs observations of atmospheric key species in Southern Germany within the WMO/Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) program and recently within the European research infrastructure ACTRIS.

The atmospheric composition at Hohenpeissenberg is typical for Central Europe and is characterized by rural emissions from the surrounding farmland and forests, as well as emissions from the metropolitan area of Munich, which is located to the northeast of Hohenpeissenberg. Atmospheric trace gases including reactive species such as in-situ ozone and its precursors nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide, anthropogenic and biogenic VOCs as well as total OH reactivity are continuously monitored.

Tropospheric O₃ is controlled by photochemical production, transport, chemical reactions and dry deposition and is formed in the troposphere via the oxidation of hydrocarbons in the presence of nitrogen oxides:

biogenic VOCs are correlated with ambient air temperature.

While regulatory measures have effectively controlled anthropogenic ozone precursors through emission limits, biogenic emissions are being influenced by climate change, particularly rising temperatures. Higher temperatures also accelerate chemical reactions, leading to a more efficient and rapid ozone production. Furthermore, climate change affects surface ozone concentrations in Central Europe by inducing prolonged drought periods, resulting in heat- and water-stressed vegetation that alters its ability to absorb ozone (Lin et al., 2020). These climate-induced impacts, often referred to as 'climate penalties', need to be carefully considered in the development of air quality mitigation strategies. Despite reduced anthropogenic precursor emissions, it is anticipated that elevated surface ozone concentration will still occur in the future.

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Fig. 1: Sources and sinks of tropospheric ozone (Galbally et al., 2013)

We present the Hohenpeissenberg surface ozone observations since 1971 and the trends of its precursors during the past 20 years alongside with meteorological parameters. The timeseries of ground level ozone concentrations show an increasing trend in the 80's and 90's and has stagnated since then. Anthropogenic VOCs and nitrogen oxides show a declining behaviour whereas

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Long-term observations of ice-nucleation particle concentrations in Europe

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The formation of ice crystals in clouds is initiated by specific aerosol particles, termed ice-nucleating particles (INPs). Although they are a small subset of the ambient aerosol particle population, the presence of INPs in mixed-phase clouds can impact their radiative properties (e.g., Vergara-Temprado et al., 2018) and induce precipitation formation (e.g., French et al., 2017). Only recently, due to novel monitoring instruments (Brunner and Kanji, 2021; Möhler et al., 2021), INP concentration measurements are more frequently and continuously conducted.

Here we present INP concentration measurements from long-term observations from two methods, the offline freezing technique INSEKT (Ice Nucleation Spectrometer of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology; Schneider et al., 2021) and the online cloud chamber PINE (Portable Ice Nucleation Experiment; Möhler et al., 2021). While INSEKT provides INP concentrations at a wide temperature range (> -25 °C), it is restricted by a low temporal resolution of days to weeks. PINE detects INP concentrations at temperatures between approximately -20 °C to -30 °C. Both instruments are currently implemented in ACTRIS by its Topical Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements (CIS), aiming to establish a measurement network in Europe.

Temperature-dependent INP concentrations from various campaigns will be compared in regard to season and locations (Fig. 1): The Arctic and sub-Arctic region, the boreal forest, rural and marine impacted regions, and the free troposphere. A special focus will be placed on the impact of Saharan dust events, leading to elevated INP concentrations.

Such measurements will help to improve our understanding of the spatio-temporal variability of INP concentration, and can be used to develop parameterizations for the integration in weather and climate models (e.g., Burrows et al., 2022).

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Fig. 1: Temperature-dependent INP concentration from long-term observations using INSEKT at a coastal site (LINAM-2017), in the boreal forest (HyICE-2018), in a rural environment (CORONA), in the lower free troposphere (SBO), and in the sub-Arctic (PaCE).

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Long-term trend of non-refractory PM₁ concentrations at a background station in Central Europe

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Keywords: aerosol mass spectrometer, equivalent black carbon, ZeFir, CBPF, PSCF.

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A better understanding of the origin of atmospheric aerosols is essential to improving air quality. Assessing long-term trends in the composition and mass concentration of non-refractory submicrometric aerosol (NR-PM₁) at background locations is an important aspect of current air quality protection.

NR-PM₁ data was recorded at 10 min intervals over a period between September 2019 and November 2023 at a rural background site in Central Europe, the National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice (NAOK; N 49°35', E 15°05'; 534 m a.s.l.), which is part of the ACTRIS network. Data from an Aerosol Mass Spectrometer, namely a ToF- Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (ToF-ACSM, Fröhlich et al., 2013; Aerodyne Research Inc., Billerica, USA) was used, supplemented with 1-min equivalent black carbon (eBC) concentrations (aethalometer, AE33 Magee Scientific, Berkeley, CA).

To determine collection efficiency (CE), correlations of sulphate mass concentrations measured by ToF-ACSM against concentrations of sulphate from PM₁ filter measurements using a low volume sampler MCZ (LVS-16, IC), analysed by Ion Chromatography, were obtained. Quality control of ToF-ACSM was performed by comparison with results from filters.

Preliminary results from ToF-ACSM (Organics, Nitrate, Sulphate, Ammonium, and Chloride) are shown in Figure 1. This large dataset shows intense and time-limited pollution events observed during the winter season, indicating local or regional carbon emissions (mainly from combustion sources). However, the total concentrations of organics and sulphate were higher in summer. Total nitrate and ammonium concentrations were highest in spring chloride concentrations were highest in winter. Organic aerosols represent around 63% of the NR-PM₁ aerosol in the total average.

The daily patterns of the individual components are very similar throughout all seasons. The concentrations of organics, nitrate, ammonium, and chloride were higher at night, whereas the concentration of sulphate was higher during the day. On the other hand, the weekly trends are relatively weak, which is quite typical for this type of background site.

The individual NR-PM₁ components correlate quite strongly with each other across seasons (r_{pearson} 0.31-0.94), with the highest correlation coefficient values

calculated between ammonium and sulphate and/or nitrate (r_{pearson} 0.67-0.94). The highest correlations between organic and inorganic components were found in winter (r_{pearson} 0.63-0.74).

Figure 1. ToF-ACSM Time Series for NAOK station exhibiting the mass concentrations for **Organics**, **Nitrate**, **Sulphate**, **Ammonium**, and **Chloride**. Data are without CE correction

Meteorological conditions over the sampling area as well as back air mass trajectories (96 hrs, 500 m a g. l.) based on the NOAA-HYSPLIT model were used in ZeFir software for CBPF and PSCF analysis (Petit et al., 2017). Results were calculated for each of the major PM₁ constituents to better refine their geographic origin and assess local/regional/long-range contributions, the information of which is mandatory for effective mitigation strategies.

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Temporal trends of equivalent black carbon (eBC) components in the metropolitan area of Valencia (Spain)

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Keywords: equivalent black carbon, trend analysis, Mann-Kendall seasonal test

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According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 99% of the world's entire population is exposed to pollutant levels that exceed WHO guidelines. Anthropogenic aerosols play a major role in the observed changes in the climate system over the last decades. Black Carbon (BC) is one of the most relevant absorbing particulate components in the atmosphere. It is a fraction of carbonaceous aerosols that is mainly characterised by its strong absorption capacity and its resistance to chemical transformations. Main BC emission sources are combustion of fossil and biomass fuels processes, having an important impact on air quality, especially in urban environments.

Measurements were carried out in Burjassot, located in the metropolitan area of Valencia (eastern Spain). This location is affected mainly by local anthropogenic aerosols originated by road traffic and regional agricultural or forest fires, but also by natural aerosols from marine and desert origin. A 7-wavelength aethalometer (AE-31, Magee Scientific) has been used to obtain the equivalent black carbon (eBC) during 2011-2023 period. This instrument requires a site-specific compensation. In this work, the method proposed by Segura *et al.* (2014) was applied. The source apportionment method (Sandradewi *et al.*, 2008) was used to quantify the contribution of fossil fuel (eBC_{ff}) and biomass burning (eBC_{bb}) to the total ambient eBC. Experimental values of absorption Ångström exponents for both contributions (AAE_{ff} and AAE_{bb}) were first determined.

The seasonal MK test is the most widely used non-parametric method for trend analysis exhibited by aerosol properties (Gilbert, 1987). The seasonal modification allows to determine the existence of increasing/decreasing trend considering the seasonality of the data. Sen's slope estimator is used to quantify the annual changes (%/year).

The seasonal MK test and Sen's slope estimator were used to analyse the trends exhibited by eBC_{ff} and eBC_{bb} concentrations from 2011. Results of seasonal MK test statistics are shown in Table 1. For all seasons, eBC_{ff} concentrations show statistically significant decreasing trends, at 95% confidence level in winter and 99% for the rest of seasons. This behaviour has been observed in other European locations, according to air pollution

controls and changes in the emissions standards. On the contrary, eBC_{bb} concentrations exhibit increasing trends in three seasons, with lower slopes (absolute value) and lower confidence levels. This contribution is not directly related to anthropogenic activities. In addition, eBC_{bb} levels are also much lower than eBC_{ff} levels, due to the traffic dominance on measurements.

Table 1. Seasonal MK test statistics of eBC_{ff} and eBC_{bb}: test statistic (Z), Sen slope (Sen), trend and significance of the test (Sig). Levels of significance are $p < 0.01$ (****), $p < 0.05$ (***), $p < 0.1$ (**) and $p < 0.2$ (*)

	Z	Sen (%/year)	Sig.	Trend.
eBC _{ff}				
DJF	-2.40	-6.6	***	↓
MAM	-2.87	-10.7	****	↓
JJA	-3.89	-16.6	****	↓
SON	-3.91	-15.4	****	↓
eBC _{bb}				
DJF	1.71	8.3	**	↑
MAM	0.67			⊗
JJA	2.96	8.7	****	↑
SON	1.57	9.7	*	↑

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Variability in Aerosol Size Distribution and New Particle Formation at the Monte Cimone GAW Global Station

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Extensive, long-term observations of ultrafine particle concentrations are crucial for understanding aerosol impacts on the climate system. Monitoring particle number size distribution (PNSD) is a valuable tool for studying transformations such as coagulation and condensation, especially with the occurrence of new particle formation (NPF) as a significant source of atmospheric particles. Despite the importance of long-term PNSD observations in the free troposphere (FT), such studies are limited. The GAW global station at Monte Cimone, Italy (CMN, 2165 m a.s.l.), represents FT conditions in South Europe and the North Mediterranean basin. This observatory, within the ACTRIS framework, holds the longest Italian PNSD dataset spanning 16 years.

Since 2005 size distributions at CMN are measured using a differential/scanning mobility particle sizer (D/SMPS). PNSD were categorized into nucleation mode (9-25nm), Aitken mode (25-100nm), and accumulation mode (100-500/800nm), providing insights into aerosol total number concentrations across various time scales and size ranges. From 2021, a Neutral cluster and Air Ion Spectrometer (NAIS) detects nanoparticles and ions (0.8/2 nm to 40 nm). This work aims to gather long-term information on PNSD and NPF at CMN. The dataset is also compared with Jungfraujoch GAW global station (JFJ, 3580 m a.s.l.) to describe similarities and differences among the two mountain stations, one located south (CMN) and one north-west (JFJ) of the Po Valley.

Overall, PNSD exhibit a bimodal pattern, with Aitken mode contributing predominantly to the total concentration (59%), followed by particles in the accumulation (29%) and nucleation (12%) modes. The average CMN aerosol population holds a total number concentration of $1118 \pm 933 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, with a slight decrease over the observed period (Fig. 2). Number concentrations show significant seasonal variations, peaking during warmer months—nearly four times higher than observed in winter. On a daily scale, the maximum total particle count occurs in the afternoon, aligning with typical patterns observed in mountainous regions.

NPF events happen on 23% of days at CMN, and non-events occur 50% of the time. According to SMPS data, strong events are most frequent in spring. On the other hand, NAIS data indicates a higher frequency in winter, when the measurement site accurately represents FT and newly formed particles don't grow up to sizes detectable by SMPS. No events occurred at the two mountain stations on the same day during the overlapping acquisition period, indicating that nucleation events are triggered at the local/regional scale.

Figure 1. Yearly variation in the frequency of NPF events at CMN classified according to Dal Maso et al (2005).

Figure 2. Time variation of N_{tot} and percentage contribution to N_{tot} of nucleation, Aitken and accumulation ranges at CMN.

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Enhancing interdisciplinary Research and Innovation capacities addressing environmental societal challenges: the ITINERIS project

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Keywords: research infrastructures, integration

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Most critical issues faced by our society involve key environmental challenges. Long term observations provided by Environmental Research Infrastructures (RIs) are essential for collecting the systematic and coherent information needed for high-level research addressing societal and environmental challenges such as climate mitigation and adaptation, natural resource conservation, health, food security, biodiversity and sustainable use of the sea, freshwater and land.

The ITINERIS project (Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructure System) builds a network of 22 RIs, with the main goal to establish the Italian Hub in the environmental scientific domains. A sustainable and strategic National Access Framework (NAF) for access to distributed National ENVIRONMENTAL Research Infrastructures, will be developed.

Overall, ITINERIS will sustainably support accessible and cross-disciplinary research, through the use and re-use of existing (or pre-operational) data and services.

The project will also promote the establishment of a national integrated system for atmospheric observations, to address current national and international open issues on atmospheric processes. This will be achieved through the development of common services with high level of competences.

The synergies amongst RIs will be achieved by reciprocal support: portable and back up instruments will be available for data provision. Further complementing instruments will be deployed at observational sites for allowing the developments of synergistic approaches and advanced data products provision.

Hot topics in the atmospheric domains will be addressed as Pilot services (Aerosol Types and Sources, ABL height and impact, Natural and Anthropogenic Fires impact). The pilots will demonstrate the added value of such a synergistic approach, paving the way for further developments.

In particular, ITINERIS aims to provide advanced and robust information on the aerosol types and sources,

based on the integration of different observational platform (remote sensing, near surface and chamber techniques) distributed over the ITINERIS sites. The project will provide information about the soil/desert dust presence; an aerosol typing classification; the carbon content and the role of natural and anthropogenic combustion sources; the characteristics of marine aerosol, secondary aerosol and bioaerosol (in particular pollens).

Taking the most from the enhanced observational capability achieved at National level, ITINERIS will provide ABL height with adequate spatial, temporal, and geographical resolution accompanied by the relative uncertainty, using novel ABL height determination approach based on AI techniques. Additionally, data related to greenhouse gases, reactive gases and atmospheric aerosol provided by the environmental RIs will be integrated to provide a suite of data products able to describe the impact of ABL height on aerosol and trace gases concentration near the surface.

Finally, data, related to the different observation techniques carried out within the atmospheric environmental RIs, will be synergistically used to identify the plumes, and provide impact assessment of the emissions. The detection of the plumes will represent the basis for the assessment of the impact of open fire emissions to the variability of key-atmospheric trace gases and aerosols.

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Lidar ratio calculations from in situ aerosol optical, microphysical and chemical measurements: observations at puy de Dôme, France and analysis with CALIOP.

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Keywords: aerosols, lidar ratio, in-situ measurements.

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The ratio between lidar extinction and backscatter coefficients, also known as lidar ratio (LR), is an important parameter in atmospheric aerosol studies. LR is an intensive property which depends on the particle size distribution, shape, refractive index and relative humidity (Evans, 1988).

We have recently published (Eswaran *et al*, 2023) a method to determine the 532 nm LR using in situ measurements performed at the puy de Dôme (PUY) station, central France, located at about 1465 m altitude (Baray *et al*, 2020). This method uses a Mie code with the measured aerosols size distribution and refractive index determined from aerosols optical measurements as inputs. The LR values obtained (LR_{PUY}) have been compared to LR calculated also with a Mie code but with refractive index determined from the measured aerosol chemical composition (LR_{CHEM}). A good correlation is observed for the period 2015-2016 with an agreement which increases to 99% after a significant imaginary part refractive index reduction, corresponding to much less carbonated particles than initially estimated (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison between the LR_{PUY} and LR_{CHEM} products.

By looking the 1443 hourly mean LR_{PUY} calculated in 2015-2016, more than 50% are within the 60-80 sr range under ambient atmospheric conditions. A

statistical comparison with the CALIOP spatial lidar retrieval (Kim *et al*, 2018) gives a good agreement at the location of PUY between retrieved values (mean of 62 sr) with a negligible bias and a dispersion indicative of a similar variability of LR (about 14 sr).

The influence of air mass history on the LR has also been studied using backward trajectory analysis (Figure 2). LR are around 40-60 sr for air masses coming from oceanic sectors and around 60-80 sr for air masses coming from continental sectors. Statistical comparisons with CALIOP typing and LR retrievals show a good agreement for continental, smoke and polluted dust aerosols types. For dusty and mainly clean marine aerosols, the differences observed between both suggest that air masses coming from the Atlantic Ocean sector at altitudes lower than 2.5 km, have experienced mixing with continental air masses during their travel increasing their LR before reaching the PUY station.

Figure 2. Mean advected LR_{PUY} in $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ grid cells

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Multi-year measurements from the Atlas station in Morocco (AMV)

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Atmospheric pollution and climate change are complex problems that require in-situ atmospheric measurements, laboratory studies and multiscale modelling. In-situ measurements is a very important component for the understanding and characterization of air composition at different latitudes and altitudes worldwide. Africa, as a continent; is lacking long-term in-situ measurements with a very limited number of stations that can provide accurate and continuous atmospheric parameters such as gas pollutants concentrations and aerosol loading and their chemical composition. This type of work requires international collaboration and a sharing of resources and expertise.

The Moroccan Atmospheric Research Station has been set up within the frame of a project supported by Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015. This Station (Atlas-M5 Atmospheric Research Station, AMV) is operated by University Mohammed VI Polytechnic and Mohammed V University with the support from LSCE-CNRS (M. Ramonet, M. Lopez), TROPOS-Leipzig (H. Herrmann & W. Fomba) and University of Valladolid (C. Toledano). The station is located in the Middle Atlas Mountains in Morocco situated in the high peaks of the Michlifien, about 19 km south from downtown of the Ifrane city (33.4018N; 5.10489E; 2076m). It is in operation since July 2017. The present poster will describe the station, its achievements after four years of measurements and its future developments.

The station is equipped with a Picarro instrument to measure continuously CO₂ and CH₄. This equipment has been provided and is maintained by LSCE-CNRS (M. Ramonet, M. Lopez). Data are available at <https://icos-atc.lsce.ipsl.fr/panelboard/AMV>. To study the atmospheric aerosols, a photometer Cimel has been recently installed at the station, it was provided by University of Valladolid (C. Toledano). In addition, a Digital High Volume Sampler has been used occasionally to sample particle. The collected filters are sent to TROPOS-Leipzig (H. Herrmann & W. Fomba) for chemical characterization. Part of the work on the particles chemical composition has been already published (Fomba et al (2020), Fomba et al (2021)). The station is also equipped with a meteorological station and NO_x and O₃ analysers deployed by ICARE-CNRS.

Figure 1. The location of the Atlas Atmospheric Research Station.

Figure 2. The Atlas Atmospheric Research Station and the equipment.

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Long-term variability of satellite and ground-based aerosols in a high mountain environment

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Atmospheric aerosols play a crucial role in shaping the environment by affecting climate, human health, and ecosystems. Monitoring atmospheric aerosols is essential to understand their impact. However, accurate information on their influence over complex-orographic terrains is challenging because of intricate topography and limited ground stations. To overcome this limitation, satellites provide a wider spatial and temporal coverage that enables us to assess the influence of aerosols over larger areas.

Aerosol optical depth (AOD) is used to monitor natural and anthropogenic aerosols and provides information on the aerosol load in the vertical column of the atmosphere. We conducted a study on the long-term variations of AOD over the Sierra Nevada Mountain range in southeastern (SE) Spain, by using both ground-based and satellite-based data sources: AERONET (AErosol RObotic NETwork) and MODIS+MAIAC (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer Version 6.1 global Multi-Angle Implementation of Atmospheric Correction). AERONET provides high-quality AOD data from sun-photometers at three altitudes: Granada, at 680 m above sea level (a.s.l.), Cerro Poyos, at 1809 m a.s.l., and Albergue_UGR, at 2500 m a.s.l. (see Table 1). Meanwhile, MODIS+MAIAC has a spatial resolution of 1 km x 1 km for aerosol products from 2001 to 2022 (Lyapustin, 2022). The latter dataset has been successfully validated against AERONET. The agreement between MODIS+MAIAC at the different AERONET stations shows good correlation with R values ranging from 0.75 to 0.82, enabling the creation of an extensive AOD dataset.

Table 1. AERONET ground-based stations used for validation.

Station	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Period
Granada	680	2005-2022
Cerro_Poyos	1809	2011-2021
Albergue_UGR	2500	2016-2018

The long-term AOD dataset from the latest collection 6.1 of MODIS+MAIAC was analyzed for the period 2001-2022 through: (1) temporal evolution, (2) trends, (3) seasonality and (4) residuals, together with the long-term series from the Granada AERONET station for 2005-2022. Furthermore, the interannual spatial patterns were examined over 20-year period at the complex orography area of Sierra Nevada (Figure 1). Spatial and seasonal patterns revealed elevated AOD near valleys and urban areas, decreasing with altitude, except for rocky areas above 2700 m, which might introduce retrieval bias due to higher-reflecting surfaces.

The interactions between elevation, AOD and ecosystems were also examined by identifying significant correlations between ecosystems and AOD in the Sierra Nevada Natural Park. This study provides valuable insights into the long-term impacts of aerosols on ecosystems in a high mountain environment.

Figure 1. Spatial pattern of the interannual map of the mean AOD from MODIS+MAIAC for the period 2001-2022 in the Sierra Nevada Natural Park (SE Spain).

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Analysis of radiative fluxes and aerosol optical depths over 14 years in Barcelona, Spain

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Sun radiation drives the winds, currents, evaporation, clouds, rain, etc. (Yildiz, 2018) and, after passing through the atmosphere, this radiation can be measured by ground-based radiometers. One of these instruments is the pyranometer, which observes global Solar radiation fluxes (GSR) on a horizontal plane surface. This study analyses the GSR over 14 years in Barcelona, Spain. Also, the Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) from Sun-photometer is presented for the same study period.

The GSR and AOD trends were estimated from 2009 to 2023. The pyranometer data (Kipp & Zonen model CM21) is available at SolRad-Net (Solar Radiation Network) at level 1.5. The CM21 has a spectral range from 305 to 2800 nm, field of view of 180° and directional error $\pm 10 \text{ W/m}^2$. The AOD₄₄₀ is provided by AERONET (Aerosol Robotic Network) at version 3 level 2.0. To calculate the Aerosol Forcing Efficiency and Aerosol Radiative Forcing by solar zenith angles (SZA) and to estimate the contribution of the aerosols in the radiative fluxes, clear days were distinguished from all skies. An identification of clear sky days was done by a simple quadratic fitting of the solar radiation (Karim and Singh, 2014; Kaplan and Kaplan, 2020), in which the correlation coefficient > 0.98 , the Root-Mean Square Error $< 15 \text{ W/m}^2$, a diurnal cycle with 80% of observations and SZA $\geq 75^\circ$ were the identification criteria. This criterion guarantees a maximum correlation and a minimum error between the observations and the fitting. The aerosol broad band fluxes will be also retrieved by the GRASP algorithm (Dubovik *et al*, 2014) in case-by-case basis to compare with those ones from pyranometer data.

Over 14 years, the daily averages of the GSR for hours of sunshine show an uptrend with an increase of $+24.98 \text{ W/m}^2$ (+6.39%), while the daily averages of the AOD₄₄₀ show a downtrend with a decrease of -0.0151 (-7.95%). An AOD downtrend was also found by Lolli *et al* (2023) for Barcelona. The AOD drop is related to the efficiency of emission reduction policies in the region (Lolli *et al*, 2023). The seasonal trends of the GSR (Figure 1) show increases of $+35.05 \text{ W/m}^2$ (+13%) and $+21.72 \text{ W/m}^2$ (+4.32%) in summer and winter, respectively, and decreases of -26.25 W/m^2 (-5.57%) and -25.11 W/m^2 (-6.90%) in spring and autumn, respectively. The seasonal trends of AOD₄₄₀ (Figure 2) have decreases of -0.029 (-24.37%), -0.003 (-1.79%) and -0.058 (-31.87%) in winter, spring and autumn, respectively. But there is an AOD increase of $+0.005$ (+2.18%) in summer that it is

associated with the dust intrusions (Sicard *et al*, 2011). Additionally, the winter and summer have the greatest number of clean days (30.6% and 30.34%, respectively).

In conclusion, the fluxes in winters and summers have been rising, while those in springs and autumns show a decrease. The influence of the number of cloudy days and of the variation of the aerosol loading on the drops and rises of the radiative fluxes on the surface is under study.

Figure 1. Seasonal trends of radiative fluxes (red lines) for all skies in Barcelona, Spain, from 2009 to 2023.

Figure 2. Seasonal trends of AOD₄₄₀ (red lines) for all skies in Barcelona, Spain, from 2009 to 2023.

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Long-term trends in Volatile Organic Compounds at the Cabo Verde Atmospheric Observatory

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Continuous *in situ*, ground-level hourly measurements of a range of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) have been made at the Cabo Verde Atmospheric Observatory Humberto Duarte Fonseca (CVAO; 16° 51' N, 24° 52' W; Fig. 1) since 2006. These observations in the remote tropical atmosphere are important to improve our understanding of changes in global air quality and atmospheric oxidation capacity (Carpenter et al., 2010).

The CVAO is a World Meteorological Organisation-Global Atmospheric Watch (WMO-GAW) long term monitoring station, located on the island of São Vicente in the tropical east Atlantic. Hourly measurements of ethane, ethene, propane, n-butane, iso-butane, n-pentane, and iso-pentane have been made using gas chromatography with flame ionisation detection (GC-FID) instrumentation (Fig. 2). This long-term dataset was expanded in 2012 to include propene, benzene, and toluene. Typical ambient mixing ratios are as low as a few parts per trillion for highly reactive VOCs (e.g. toluene and butane), to parts per billion for the longest-lived species, ethane. For most measured VOCs, limits of detection are < 5 pptV, except for ethane and propane (*c.a.* 7 pptV). In addition to using a certified multicomponent laboratory standard, real air monthly target gas measurements are used to support quality assurance. The VOC measurement suite is accompanied by detailed meteorological measurements, including temperature, pressure, wind speed and wind direction.

Figure 1. Cabo Verde Atmospheric Observatory (CVAO).

Photo credit: Luis Neves,

<https://amof.ac.uk/observatory/cape-verde-atmospheric-observatory-cvaov/>

Back trajectory simulations using FLEXPART version 10.4 are used to understand the origin of the air masses arriving at the CVAO (Andersen et al., 2021). Combining these with the VOC measurement suite reveals that the CVAO region is sensitive to sources in Europe, North America, and Africa, including biomass burning and oil and gas sources. Here, the long-term trends in VOCs measured at the CVAO are explored, and source origins during high concentration periods are examined. VOC ratios, meteorological data, and an analysis of historical air mass origins will be used to separate local sources from global influences on the measurement suite. The well-defined seasonal cycles of lighter alkanes at the site will also be explored.

Figure 2. CVAO monthly mean timeseries for ethane (top) and propane (bottom).

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Aerosol properties in the last decade as measured by the EARLINET-ACTRIS lidars

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Over the past decade, there has been extensive research and measurement of both global and local features of atmospheric aerosols using both space-borne and ground-based equipment. Despite the considerable amount of research conducted on the optical characteristics of aerosols, defining mixed composition aerosols remains a complex task. The establishment of continental-scale ground-based lidar networks has been a major breakthrough in aerosol remote sensing, providing high-quality optical profiles on a wide temporal and geographical scale. The [European Aerosol Research Lidar Network](#) is not only valuable for climatology but also for events that significantly impact aerosol levels, such as Saharan dust storms, forest fires, photochemical smog, and volcanic eruptions. Many EARLINET stations joined ACTRIS at its establishment as an ERIC in 2023, others are contributing as associated.

Developed and optimized for execution on EARLINET profiles, NATALI is a Python-based method that utilizes Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to identify the predominant aerosol type from a collection of multispectral lidar data. This innovative approach leverages the ANN's ability to distinguish between overlapping values of intense optical parameters extracted from multiwavelength Raman lidar profiles (Nicolae et al. in 2016). The extended lidar dataset collected by EARLINET stations over a span of eight years (2015-2022), was utilized in this study. A total of 17 stations, each providing a full set of parameters, were included in the analysis. These stations were categorized into seven cluster regions based on their air mass transport patterns.

Figure 1. Distribution of stations across cluster regions.

For every station, season, and year, the aerosol intensive optical parameters were computed separately for the low and high troposphere, resulting in layer-specific averages. The prevalent aerosol type was determined, and the frequency of occurrence was determined by normalizing it against all layers.

Figure 2. Predominant aerosol types in cluster regions.

Low absorbing particles are detected in the low troposphere, particularly at Evora and the Mediterranean sites, which are associated with marine aerosols. On the other hand, high absorbing particles are found at Bucharest, Thessaloniki, Warsaw, and Munich, which are linked to industrial pollution and smoke. In the high troposphere, a similar pattern emerges, with Kuopio showing higher values of the lidar ratio due to long-range transported smoke, while Bucharest exhibits lower values due to long-range transport of mineral particles. Granada and Barcelona have a presence of large and medium absorbing particles, while all other stations detect smaller and medium absorbing particles. The properties of smoke particles varies greatly from region to region, especially in terms of the lidar ratio. The lowest value is observed at Lecce in South Italy and Sirta near Paris (0.9 ± 0.3), indicating the influence of nearby industrial pollution on the observation sites. Values above 1, indicating aged smoke, are measured at the other sites, with the highest values recorded in Evora (1.9 ± 0.4) and Athens (1.5 ± 0.3).

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Long-term trends of particle size-distributions and new particle formation at San Pietro Capofiume, Italy

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Keywords: new particle formation, particle growth, long-term trends

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Formation and growth of secondary aerosol particles is a major source of atmospheric aerosols. However, only few long-term datasets (over 10 years of measurements) of atmospheric new particle formation (NPF) exist. Observations in the Finnish boreal forest and at two Arctic sites in Finnish Lapland indicate very small changes in NPF over the past 25 years (Asmi et al., 2011; Kyrö et al., 2014; Nieminen et al., 2014). In Central Europe a clear decrease in NPF occurrence has been reported (Hamed et al., 2010). Comparisons with global model simulations of aerosol number size distributions show similar trends as observed in Europe (Leinonen et al., 2022).

Here we analyze trends in aerosol number size distributions and in NPF characteristics at San Pietro Capofiume in Po Valley region, Northern Italy. The number size distributions of 3–630 nm particles have been measured at the station in 2002–2017 with a twin-DMPS setup. The station is influenced by emissions of local anthropogenic pollutants (such as SO₂) as well as long-range transport from Central and Eastern Europe (Sogacheva et al., 2007), and can therefore provide important information on the impact of anthropogenic activities on aerosol number size-distributions and atmospheric NPF.

The particle number size distribution data was classified into NPF event, non-event, and undefined days (Kulmala et al., 2012). To quantify the NPF events, formation rates of nucleation mode particles (3–25 nm) were calculated from the measured number size-distribution data. Particle growth rates were calculated by fitting log-normal modes to the measured size-distribution data and following the time evolution of the geometric mean size of the fitted nucleation mode.

Figure 1 shows the number concentrations of nucleation mode particles measured in 2002–2017. An overall decreasing linear trend of –4.9 %/year is observed, although after 2010 this decrease is not as clear as in the early part of the time series. Also accumulation mode particle (100–630 nm) and

particulate matter (PM₁₀) concentrations have declined. Frequency of NPF occurrence did not show any clear trend, varying between 20% and 40% of the days in a year. Both the formation and growth rates of nucleation mode particles had decreasing trends. This indicates that while the sink for the newly formed particles has decreased (due to decrease in PM concentrations), a simultaneous decrease in precursor vapour emissions (SO₂, ammonia, amines, organics) has also occurred.

Figure 1. Number concentration of 3–25 nm particles in San Pietro Capofiume 2002–2017. Grey points show the hourly concentrations, black markers monthly medians, black line the linear trend.

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Towards a better understanding of atmospheric carbon in the free troposphere

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Particulate and gaseous organic carbon species are key players in chemical processes in the atmosphere and thereby affect climate, ecosystem and human health. While carbonaceous species mostly enter the atmosphere as volatile gases, subsequent cascades of oxidation reactions generate a plethora of chemical species that are present in the gas phase and particle phase. The resulting oxidized species are either deposited through atmospheric removal processes or fully oxidized to CO or CO₂ (Goldstein, 2007). To better constrain and reduce uncertainties of these processes in atmospheric models, a complete characterization of this dynamic chemical mixture is needed. Yet, atmospheric studies detailing the carbon balance in the atmosphere remain scarce (Hunter *et al.*, 2017).

During the carbon balance campaign 2022, we measured the chemical composition of the atmosphere at the Jungfraujoch (JFJ) High Alpine Research Station (3571 m.a.s.l.) in late summer. Both the gas and particle phase were analysed with several mass spectrometers, gas chromatographs and total carbon analyzers.

We detected air masses from the free troposphere (JFJ FT), mixed with the planetary boundary layer during the afternoons due to vertical transport (JFJ PBL). In addition, we sampled a wildfire plume (JFJ wildfire) and two short Saharan dust events as shown in Fig. 1a. Overall, the total particulate carbon measurements are consistent with the sum of black carbon and organic carbon measurements (Fig. 1a). The organic carbon content may be underestimated due to the size-cutoffs of the ACSM to PM₁.

By coupling a time-of-flight aerosol chemical speciation monitor (ToF-ACSM) with a thermal denuder (TD), we measured the chemical composition of non-refractory PM₁ for different volatility bins. From the measured thermograms, we have determined volatility distributions (Fig. 1b), which can serve as a basis to simulate the partitioning of organics between gas and particle phases under variable ambient conditions (temperature, aerosol mass concentration, relative humidity). These data from JFJ provide unprecedented

information on organic aerosol volatility from the lower free troposphere. In combination with the average carbon oxidation state, which we deduced from the recorded mass spectra (Fig. 1c), this can serve as valuable insights for “atmospheric aging” to benchmark respective model simulations. Our results suggest that i) a substantial fraction of organic aerosol is volatile enough to partition with the gas phase and ii) the organic aerosol at JFJ is more oxidized than at Manitou Experimental Forest Observatory (Hunter *et al.*, 2017). The inclusion of gas phase data into this analysis is ongoing.

Figure 1. a) Particle phase concentrations of total carbon (TC), black carbon (BC) and organic carbon measured at JFJ during the Carbon Balance Campaign. b) Volatility distribution obtained from TD-ACSM measurements for JFJ PBL. c) Average carbon oxidation state of organic aerosol for different air masses.

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The representativity analysis on the current in-situ eLTER Site network and potential for assessing the value of co-location

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Keywords: representativity, long-term observation network, social-ecology

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eLTER RI - the distributed Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure – will comprise >200 in-situ facilities (ecosystem research sites and socio-ecological research platforms) once formalized as European Research Infrastructure Consortium. Since the eLTER RI originated in a bottom-up manner from sites listed in DEIMS-SDR, it is important to perform a comprehensive representativity analysis, revealing under-, well or overrepresented conditions and locations. A similar approach can be applied to other RIs as well.

We assessed the current coverage of European environmental and socio-ecological gradients by the prospective Sites in eLTER RI (Ohnemus et al. 2023), using the geographical information and six reference parameters that collectively depict environmental and socio-ecological gradients: anthromes describing anthropogenic biomes, bioclimatic zones, economic density, land cover, landforms and biogeographical regions of Europe. Thereafter, we identified the most critical gaps in the eLTER RI coverage and derived recommendations for the further development of the eLTER RI.

Three distinct geospatial gaps were identified: the Iberian Gap, the Eastern Gap, and the Nordic Gap (Fig. 1). These gaps resulted mainly from the underrepresentation of agricultural lands, regions with low economic density, mesic and dry regions as well as the Mediterranean, Continental and Boreal biogeoregions. Closing the three major gaps is of highest priority for eLTER's spatial network development. Importantly, all gaps were distinct regarding the environmental and socio-ecological gradients they cover.

Fig. 1. Priority regions for the establishment of additional eLTER Sites in the future. Identified gaps are defined as clusters of very high and high priority cells and are highlighted.

The eLTER representativity analysis could be complemented by adding the other environmental RI's in the assessment. In addition to revealing the potential gaps in network design, the result could be useful for fertilising discussions about RI co-location, further country-specific recommendations on the most cost-efficient gap closure and for promoting the integration and RI-RI collaboration in the environmental domain.

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Trends in polar ozone loss since 1989: Potential sign of recovery in Arctic ozone column

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Keywords: trend, ozone loss, polar regions.

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The first signs of healing of the ozone layer in the polar regions linked to the decrease of ODSs were detected in Antarctica by Yang *et al.* (2008), who showed a statistically significant levelling off of the decrease in total ozone during Spring, and by Solomon *et al.* (2016), who presented evidence of a statistically significant increase of total ozone during September in the middle of the depletion period. This increase was confirmed by later studies using measurements and model simulations. In contrast, in the Arctic, the large variability in meteorological conditions prevents detection of ozone recovery as shown by the recent trend study of Weber *et al.* (2021).

This presentation is based on the new results on ozone trends in polar regions (Pazmiño *et al.*, 2023) where ozone depletion during recent winters in both hemispheres was analysed.

Data and Methodology

In order to estimate annual ozone depletion in the polar regions, ground-based SAOZ ozone columns and ozone Multi-Sensor Reanalysis (MSR2) data reanalysis as well as simulations of ozone by the SLIMCAT chemical-transport model are used. In this work, another CTM model, REPROBUS, will be also used for analysis.

The ozone loss is obtained by applying the passive tracer method (Goutail *et al.*, 1999). The loss is computed at each polar station by subtracting the measured total ozone (SAOZ and MSR2 merged dataset) when the station is inside the polar vortex, from the corresponding passive ozone column simulated by SLIMCAT.

Three metrics are used in trend analyses that aim to assess the ozone recovery rate over both polar regions: (1) the maximum ozone loss at the end of the winter, (2) the onset day of ozone loss reaching a specific threshold, and (3) the ozone loss residuals computed from the differences between annual ozone loss and ozone loss values regressed with respect to sunlit volume

of polar stratospheric clouds (VPSC). A trend since 2000 is calculated for each metric.

Main results

In the Antarctic, the three metrics present significant trends for the period 2000–2021 confirming the recovery of ozone in that region. In the Arctic, the two first metrics do not present significant results while the third one provides a significant negative trend of the residual ozone loss at the 2σ level showing a potential quantitative detection of ozone recovery in the Arctic springtime lower stratosphere.

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ACTRIS Finland – Recent results from Finland

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Keywords: ACTRIS, aerosol particles, in-situ observations, ground-based remote sensing.

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ACTRIS Finland (ACTRIS-FI) is the Finnish component of the Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS). ACTRIS is a pan-European distributed research infrastructure aiming to secure long-term atmospheric research done at the European level. ACTRIS supports the society in responding global challenges such as poor air quality and climate change.

ACTRIS Finland has six field sites in Finland (Figure 1) and one in Marambio in Antarctica. The environments include remote sites (Pallas, SMEAR I), rural sites (SMEAR II, SMEAR IV), marine environment (Utö) and urban background (SMEAR III). The sites contribute to all in-situ components of ACTRIS (aerosol, trace gases, clouds) and all but one remote sensing components (aerosol, clouds). ACTRIS Finland includes mobile and laboratory platforms contributing to ACTRIS exploratory platforms.

Figure 1. The observation network includes 6 observation sites in Finland and one in Antarctica.

As an example, the long-term, harmonized observations have provided novel insights into trends in aerosol concentration in the boreal environment. The decrease in anthropogenic SO₂ emissions has led to a

concurrent decrease in gas phase sulfuric acid and decreased the particle number concentrations in the nucleation mode (Neefjes et al. 2022). At the same time, the climate change and consequent warming has increased the biogenic volatile organic emissions, influencing the aerosol number and mass concentrations as well as cloud properties (Yli-Juuti et al. 2021; Petäjä et al. 2022; Rätty et al. 2023). The aim of this work is to introduce ACTRIS Finland and the recent summary of the scientific outcomes of our work.

The funding from ACTRIS-Finland host organizations University of Helsinki (UH), Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), University of Eastern Finland (UEF) and Tampere University (TAU) to support ACTRIS activities is acknowledged. The ACTRIS-FI projects funded by Research Council of Finland for the ACTRIS-FI National Facilities are acknowledged: INAR RI/ ACTRIS-FI 2020-2024 grant no. 328616 (UH), 328617 (UEF) and 328823 (TAU); INAR RI 2022-2025 grant no. 345510 (UH), 345527 (UEF) and 345528 (TAU). The funding from the Ministry of Transport and Communications is acknowledged (FMI ACTRIS activities). The ACCC (Atmosphere and Climate Competence Center) Flagship funding by the Research Council of Finland (grant no. 337549 (UH), 337552 (FMI), 337550 (UEF) and 337551 (TAU)) and Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation funding are acknowledged. EU funding supporting ACTRIS activities and implementation are also acknowledged: ACTRIS IMP (grant no. 871115), ATMO-ACCESS (grant no. 101008004) and RI-URBANS (grant no. 101036245).

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The Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory: A unique outpost to monitor Middle East Air Pollution and bridge observations of this region with the pan-European ACTRIS network

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Keywords: Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory, PM, chemical composition, long-term trends, Middle East.

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Cyprus is located at the south easternmost of the Mediterranean basin, a highly populated region (400 million inhabitants) threatened by exceptionally rapid urbanization and industrialization, intense dust storms, and heat extremes leading to drastic degradation of air quality, expected to exacerbate in the coming decades. Air pollution, especially particulate matter (PM), plays a crucial role in regional climate and has major adverse health effects and major economic consequences.

The Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory (CAO) is a regional background station of the pan-European ACTRIS Research Infrastructure Network. It was established in 2015 with a view to fill-in the current observational gaps in this region through high quality, long term monitoring of atmospheric pollutants of climate and health relevance. Air quality observations from CAO are crucial to connect the Middle East region with the European air quality networks, and to discriminate the long-range transported from locally produced air pollution for a better implementation of local mitigation measures.

In close collaboration with the Department of Labour Inspection and in the framework of the Horizon 2020 EMME-CARE research project, CAO has built a unique and detailed PM chemical composition database for the past decade which was further processed to investigate the long-term trends using the mann-kendall non-parametric statistical test while the identification of the geographic location of the major pollution sources affecting the island was achieved through the Lagrangian model FLEXPART.

Fig. 1. PM₁₀ trends for the period 2015–2022 at CAO.

Based on the statistical Mann-Kendall trend analysis (**Fig. 1**), an increasing trend in PM₁₀ levels was observed at the regional background (CAO) station

(+0.23 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$). It is interesting to note that the concentrations of most PM species are rising, especially mineral dust with an average increasing rate of + 0.26 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$ followed by OM (+ 0.1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$).

The source regions analysis indicates that the Middle east sector is associated not only with the most elevated concentrations for the main PM₁₀ components, both of natural (mineral dust) and anthropogenic origin (carbonaceous species (**Fig. 2a**), nitrate and nss-K⁺), but also with increasing trends for most of them. Especially for SO₄²⁻, it is worth mentioning that while rather stable levels were recorded for different source regions, the Middle East sector exhibited increasing trend (+ 0.20 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$; **Fig. 2b**), indicating increasing fossil fuel (oil and gas) emissions.

Fig. 2. Temporal evolution of (a) OM and (b) SO₄²⁻ for different source regions. The trend in SO₄²⁻ levels for the Middle East sector is shown in red.

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Long-term statistics of water vapour and clouds from microwave radiometer observations in Jülich with focus on cloud properties

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Detailed observation of water vapour and clouds is a crucial part for understanding the atmospheric water cycle, which is essential for weather forecast and climate aspects. Within the ACTRIS network for cloud remote sensing, microwave radiometers (MWR) are a mandatory instrument at all participating national facilities. These instruments provide high-quality information on integrated water vapour (IWV, also called “precipitable water”) as well as the vertically integrated cloud liquid water path (LWP). MWR are the only reliable tool to quantitatively derive liquid cloud properties from ground. From satellites, IWV and LWP can be observed as well, but these data have several disadvantages, such as coarse vertical and temporal resolutions, or blind zones close to the ground where most of the atmospheric water vapour can be found.

Ground-based MWR have been operated at several ACTRIS national facilities for many (>10) years which can give a first glimpse into the climatology of IWV and LWP as well as potential trends of these quantities. In connection with other remote sensing instrumentation, present at each site in the network, additional information on atmospheric and cloud properties, but also synergistic products, are available. The ACTRIS network covers a variety of climatological zones from the Arctic to Mediterranean Sea, which will allow to conduct comparison studies in future.

However, for these analyses, a thorough quality control, as well as common operation procedures (e.g. regular standardized calibrations), have to be applied. Assessing the quality of long-term data sets is a crucial part and consists of several steps, such as an online monitoring of critical instrument parameters to identify malfunctions and help with instrument maintenance, and the detection of long-term drifts or systematic errors. Furthermore, harmonized retrieval algorithms have to be applied to convert the observed radiances into consistent, and therefore comparable, atmospheric quantities. These tasks are part of the MWR unit of the ACTRIS Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES) at the University of Cologne.

We present statistics from observations at the JOYCE (Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution) site in Western Germany which is operated by the University of

Cologne. MWR data for JOYCE are continuously available since 2010. Applying a thorough data quality control and consistent retrieval algorithms makes it possible to study diurnal and annual cycles, as well as the inter-annual variability of cloud properties and IWV in detail. As a fully equipped CCRES national facility, further products, like the cloud classification algorithm Cloudnet, are available at JOYCE and are used to support the analysis.

In future, this type of statistics will be available for all ACTRIS cloud remote sensing stations and will prove as a useful tool for various applications, such as model evaluation or satellite validation studies.

Acknowledgments

JOYCE is part of the Cloud and Precipitation Exploration Laboratory (CPEX-LAB, <http://cpex-lab.de>), a competence centre within the Geoverbund ABC/J. We thank the Forschungszentrum Jülich for their support of JOYCE. The implementation of ACTRIS in Germany is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) under the FONA Strategy “Research for Sustainability”. The operation of the Central Facilities is supported by ACTRIS ERIC as well as the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV).

Ozone and Carbon Monoxide Trends at the Cabo Verde Atmospheric Observatory (CVAO)

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Keywords: O₃, CO, Trends

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The Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) 'Global' Observatory at Cabo Verde, an international cooperation between the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) UK, Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research (TROPOS), Germany, Max-Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, Germany, and Instituto Nacional de Meteorologia e Geofísica (INMG), Cabo Verde, is ideally located to assess the chemistry of the marine boundary layer above the North Atlantic Ocean.

95% of the time air arrives at the CVAO from the northeast open ocean sector, with FLEXPART trajectory analysis suggesting it has spent an average of 5 days over the open ocean prior to arrival.

The site, established in 2006, is one of the most highly instrumented observatories in the world. The measurements have contributed to many important scientific findings, provided the scientific community with opportunities for focussed process-based studies to understand emission and loss processes, and supported model developments (Read et al. 2008, Andersen et al., 2022, Stone et al., 2018, Van Pinxteren et al, 2020).

This presentation will demonstrate how combining the data with FLEXPART trajectory analysis together with statistical tools can be used to investigate the drivers of long-term trends in this region. A particular focus will be on the > 15-year O₃ and CO trends.

Ozone and Carbon Monoxide Trends

Ozone is increasing at a rate of 1.77 ppbV decade⁻¹ in this region. Seasonal and monthly analysis suggests this trend is driven by increasing spring concentrations of VOCs when northern hemispheric concentrations are at their highest. In addition, a strong positive trend is evident in autumn when the data is affected more by African and southern Atlantic air masses.

Carbon monoxide exhibits a decreasing trend of -6.14 ppbV decade⁻¹. The largest downward trend is observed in winter and spring, consistent with a move to cleaner fuel technologies by North America and Europe. In contrast, there is a small positive trend in summer and autumn CO concentrations, though in these seasons significant interannual variability is observed. Similar behaviour in co-located tracer species during these months suggests that CO is influenced by primary

emissions from burning with 2021 being an extreme example of this.

Figure 1. Ozone anomaly trends over 16 years measured at the CVAO split by season.

This work was supported by the Natural Environment and Research Council (NERC) through the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS).

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Implementation of long-term VOC measurement at the remote tropical background GAW station, Maïdo observatory (-21.08° S, 55.38° E)

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Keywords: VOC, tropical and background GAW site.

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Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) are key components in the atmosphere. They play a crucial role in aerosol (secondary organic aerosol or SOA) formation, atmospheric chemistry by the ozone formation, and cloud formation implying a high sanitary and climatic impact. There are gaps in the assessment of sources and sinks of VOCs in the tropical Southern Hemisphere.

This is why VOCs measurements have been set up for long-term measurements by adsorbent tubes (TENAX-TA) at the multi-instrumented GAW station: the Maïdo observatory (MO, -21.08 S, 55.38 E).

MO is an ideal place to perform coupled dynamical and chemical atmospheric studies in a tropical mountain island context (Baray et al., 2013) located in the Southern Hemisphere at an altitude of 2200 m in La Réunion Island (21° S, 55° E). La Réunion Island is often considered as a natural laboratory of the atmosphere exchange studies. Indeed, the island presents a tropical climate and strong slopes. With high temperatures and strong sunlight, tropical climates favour the emission of biogenic VOCs (BVOCs) such as isoprene, and terpenes which may lead to the formation of SOA (Dominutti et al., 2022). MO is in a convergence of local upslope and downslope winds resulting in thermodynamic processes and complex and variable local air circulation patterns. During the day, the sea breeze phenomenon combined with anabatic winds leads to significantly contributes to cloud formation. Moreover, there is an observed increase in the height of the planetary boundary layer (PBL) during the daytime, facilitating the transport of VOCs to the mountain's summit. During nighttime, as the ground cools, the air masses descend downhill.

This study presents a dataset of VOC concentrations during more than one year from April 2022 to July 2023. Concentrations of isoprene, α -pinene, β -pinene, limonene, Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene and Xylenes (BTEX) were recorded by two samplings every week (one during the day and one during the night, Figure 1). The data set represents the initial measurements of VOC concentrations that will be

implemented over time and used for future VOC assessment at MO.

We compare this precious data with previous VOC measurements (Rocco et al., 2020; Verreyken et al., 2021; Rocco et al., 2022).

Figure 1. This is a comparison between theory and experimental data.

This work was supported by the AO ACTRIS-FR 2022.

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Multi-annual characterisation of PM₁ aerosol optical properties, size distribution and chemical composition at the suburban atmospheric site ATOLL in Lille

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Keywords: scattering and absorption coefficients, particle number concentration, source identification.

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Multi-annual observations of aerosol properties are typically conducted at the PM₁₀ fractions, susceptible to be strongly affected by natural, coarse-mode particles. The aim of this study is to present aerosol scattering, absorption properties, number size distribution and chemical composition within the PM₁ fraction from January 1, 2018, to December 31, 2022, at the suburban site “Atmospheric Observations in LiLLE” (ATOLL), in the vicinity of Lille, Northern France (50.6114 N, 3.1406 E, 60 m a.s.l.). The station is part of ACTRIS and provides high-quality long-term atmospheric data.

A significant decrease of 9% per year was observed for the total scattering coefficient σ_{sp} (525 nm, Fig. 1 top), although no change was found for the backscattering coefficient σ_{bsp} , indicating an increase in the backscatter fraction relative to total scattering. The overall absorption coefficient σ_{ap} did not significantly decrease for the studied period, whatever the wavelength. However, the analysis of biomass burning (σ_{ap_BB}) and fossil fuel (σ_{ap_FF}) contributions to the absorption showed a significant decrease of σ_{ap_FF} (Fig. 1 middle), suggesting a possible reduction in fossil fuel sources in the vicinity of the site. σ_{sp} variability could not be directly explained by the chemical composition as the analysis of absolute organics, SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , NH_4^+ and Cl^- concentrations showed no substantial change. However, the mixing state or morphology of the particles could be different, leading to changes in refractive indices. PM₁ concentration did not decrease alongside decreasing σ_{sp} , however, the analysis of particle number concentration in the 20-30 nm and 30-300 nm size ranges exhibit a marked increase (Fig. 1 bottom). Crumeyrolle *et al.* (2023) previously observed a strong influence of new particle formation events (NPF) on the number concentration from 15.7 to 100 nm in summer and spring at the ATOLL site. The maximum daily diameter of particles significantly decreased which may have partially explained the decrease in σ_{sp} . Further investigation is ongoing to link NPF frequency to the results from this study.

Figure 1. Top: scattering; middle: absorption (fossil fuels); bottom: number concentrations observed at the ATOLL site from 2018 to 2022. The solid line shows the median; shadowed areas, the interquartile range; the dashed line, the trendline.

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Crumeyrolle, S. *et al.* (2023) *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **23**, 183–201.

Optical properties of mineral dust mixtures derived from a decade of lidar observations over Warsaw, Poland.

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Keywords: mineral dust, differences, depolarization.

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The Remote Sensing Laboratory (RS-Lab) at the University of Warsaw, is equipped with aerosol, polarization, and water vapor Mie-Raman lidar of PollyXT type operated automatically in 24/7 mode. Starting in 2013, RS-Lab continuously provides high-quality lidar data to the EARLINET-ACTRIS and PollyNET databases, where data are also visualized.

A decade of lidar data (2013–2022) was analysed to identify the episodes of long-range transport of mineral dust over Warsaw. The mineral dust has its typical fingerprint, such as high depolarization and raised air temperatures (Figure 1). It allows for mineral dust inflow detection based on the quick-look plots.

Figure 1. Linear Polarization Ratio at 532 nm from PollyXT lidar measurements, and the diurnal cycle of air temperature (red line) in Warsaw on 19/06/2022. Yellow strips denote times of depolarization calibration. Note that 20-years average temperature in June in Warsaw is 18°C.

For mineral dust cases lidar data analyses were carried out using the methodology as in Szczepanik *et al* (2021, 2023) and supported by three independent models: a) HYSPLIT backward trajectory model for tracing the possible aerosol sources, b) dust prediction model NMMB/BSC-Dust to check the possibility of mineral dust observation over Central Europe, and c) an aerosol prediction model NAAPS for determining the possible admixtures of different aerosol types.

The mineral dust was present during 36 episodes lasting from several hours to a few days. The model outputs indicated likely observation of clean desert dust (16 cases, D), and its mixtures with sulphates (13 cases, D+S) or with biomass burning aerosol (7 cases, D+BB).

The clean dust observed over Warsaw does not show as high values of particle depolarization as the mineral dust close to the emission source (Spain, Greece, Szczepanik *et al* 2021), which is attributed to the gravitational sedimentation processes of the coarse dust

particles. Additionally, admixtures of different aerosol types strongly affect the optical properties of the observed aerosol (Szczepanik *et al* 2023). In case biomass burning (D+BB) is mixed in, it enlarges up to 3 times the mean particle extinction coefficient compared to the values obtained for the clean mineral dust (D, both 355 and 532 nm), while reduces the mean particle depolarization values up to 80% and 71% for 355 and 532 nm. If the sulphates (D+S) are mixed in it slightly enlarges the mean particle extinction coefficient (13% at 355 nm and 2% at 532 nm) and lowers both the mean particle backscattering coefficient (down to 20%, 24%, and 46% at 355, 532 and 1064 nm respectively) and mean particle depolarization (36% for 355 nm and 31% at 532 nm).

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We acknowledge the NOAA Air Resources Laboratory (ARL) for the provision of the HYSPLIT transport and dispersion model and READY website (<https://www.ready.noaa.gov>), the NAAPS model output obtained via NRL/Monterey Aerosol Page (<https://www.nrlmry.navy.mil/>), and the BSC-DREAM8b Barcelona Supercomputing Center accessed via webpage <https://ess.bsc.es/bsc-dust-daily-forecast>, which were used for this study.

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New online services for accessing the atmospheric composition from IAGOS, ACTRIS and ICOS in the framework of ATMO-ACCESS

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Keywords: Troposphere, profiles, trends.

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In the context of the ATMO-ACCESS project (<http://www.atmo-access.eu>), several new online services have been developed to offer new facilities for data management and data access. Among the objectives of such services, an important one is to help the scientific community performing a first rapid exploration and visualisation of the data from the three European Research Infrastructures ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS. Such Virtual Access is meant to save the time of the users in order to concentrate on the scientific questions.

In particular, the so-called “Tools for analysing time series” service is meant to offer a large diversity of users (students, academics, private or public organisations, NGOs, communities of projects, etc...) a dedicated Virtual Research Environment for facilitating their exploration of multiple in situ datasets providing a long time series of different variables. The goal is to make accessible the most commonly used basic metrics (e.g. means, percentiles) and statistical analysis (e.g. trends), as well as visualisation tools to look at e.g. 2D or 3D scatter plots. The objective is also to be the first step of exploring cross-cutting issues in combining the different variables relevant for climate and air quality recorded by ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS. Figure 1 below gives an example.

Figure 1. Example of compared trends for CO₂, CH₄ (ICOS) and CO (IAGOS) data over Germany.

In addition, the “IAGOS footprint viewer” service gives access to a further understanding of the CO anomalies observed by commercial aircrafts from

IAGOS (example in Figure 2). With this new ATMO-ACCESS service, the users are able to explore tropospheric vertical profiles of carbon monoxide mixing ratios (measured by IAGOS) in conjunction with source attribution data (calculated using the SOFT-IO model). The profiles are over airports visited by commercial aircraft equipped with IAGOS' instruments. The SOFT-IO model (Sauvage et al., 2017) is based on the coupling of FLEXPART backward footprint with emission inventory databases: GFAS v1.2 for biomass burning emissions and CAMS-GLOB-ANT for anthropogenic emissions.

Figure 2. Example of biomass burning plume over Frankfurt airport in May 2023 originating from Canada.

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Mineral dust trends using 15 years of global 3D distributions from IASI

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Keywords: IASI, dust, trends

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Mineral dust aerosols are particles uplifted from bare areas (mostly deserts) by strong winds. They can be transported along thousands of kilometres, mostly within the tropical dust belt but also occasionally northwards to Europe and beyond. Dust aerosols are the most important tropospheric aerosol in annual mass burden, and a major actor in the climate: they absorb, scatter and emit radiation, impacting the Earth energy balance along the solar and terrestrial spectrum. In addition, they have indirect impacts on the Earth system leading to surface warming or cooling, atmospheric warming (in the dust layer), modification of the atmospheric circulation, modification of clouds lifetime and physical properties, modification of the amount or location of rainfalls. Finally, dust aerosols also have negative impacts on the human health and on several human activities such as aviation, solar energy, infrastructure. For all these reasons, studies of dust atmospheric load and sources, and of their changes over time, are of great scientific and societal interest.

The Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) has been flying on board the Metop platform series on a mid-morning sun-synchronous polar orbit (09:30 local solar equator crossing time, descending node), providing continuous thermal infrared radiance observations at nadir since end 2006. IASI offers almost global coverage twice per day thanks to the platform's orbital parameters, wide swath width and the availability of thermal emission radiances in presence and absence of sunlight.

Using data from the IASI instrument, we obtain vertical profiles of mineral dust aerosols (MAPIR algorithm). The previous version MAPIR 4.1 (Callewaert et al., 2019) suffered from discontinuities in the long-term time series, due to the unavailability (at the moment of MAPIR 4.1 processing) of long-term consistent IASI spectra and ancillary atmospheric data needed as input for MAPIR. In addition, the constraints on computing time imposed data filtering before processing (cloud removal, quick dust detection), resulting in missing a significant number of unusual dust events (small events out of the Tropical dust belt but also huge events within the dust belt).

We have recently developed a new version of the algorithm (MAPIR 5.1) that works faster, enabling the removal of all pre-filters and avoiding missed events. In addition, EUMETSAT now provides spectra and ancillary data that are fully consistent over the whole IASI

time series (2006-2023). We have therefore processed the updated homogeneous full IASI time series with the improved algorithm MAPIR 5.1, leading to enhanced dust event coverage and full timeseries consistency.

In this presentation, we will use 15 years of dust profile data to extract middle-term changes in the dust global distribution (source and transport areas).

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Temporal variability and aerosols source apportionment at RADO- Bucharest, Romania

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Keywords: organic aerosols, trends, aerosols sources.

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In-situ measurements performed in the last decade at RADO-Bucharest site (44.344°N 26.012°E 77 m a.s.l) are used to derive aerosols chemical composition, physical properties and identification of their sources. The site is an ACTRIS national facility located in a peri-urban area, in the Southern part of Bucharest, Romania. The knowledge of aerosol components in this part of Europe is limited, only to several studies regarding the possible aerosols' sources and their chemical, optical or physical properties being available (e.g. Chen et al, 2022; Savadkoohi et al, 2023). In this study are analysed the measurements performed at RADO-Bucharest site, between 2013 to 2022 using an aerosol chemical speciation monitor (ACSM), optical particle counters, particle light absorption and scattering instruments. The aerosols sources at ground level are retrieved from ACSM data using positive matrix factorization via the source finder (Canonaco et al., 2021).

RADO-Bucharest site is typically characterized by urban type aerosols due to their transport mostly from the Bucharest area. The Sen slope (Sun et al., 2021) is used to investigate the organic (OA) and inorganic aerosol concentrations trends over approximately 10 years. The aerosols concentrations highlighted a statistical growth trend in the case of organic aerosols of 0.29 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 2013-2022 timeframe. This concentration increase is in contrast with a very small decrease in the fraction of inorganic fractions of non-refractory submicronic aerosols, nitrates and ammonium, of 0.03 and 0.06 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. The organic non-refractory PM₁ at the site is typically composed of primary organic aerosol from fossil fuels and biomass burning (hydrocarbon-like HOA, biomass burning BBOA) and secondary organic aerosols with different levels of oxidation (less oxidised oxygenated LOOOA, more oxidised oxygenated MOOOA) (Figure 1).

Primary organic aerosols present higher proportions during cold periods, while the secondary organic aerosols (SOA) have higher contributions during warmer periods. An overall increased contribution of secondary organic aerosols and a small decrease of the primary is pin pointed for this site over the years.

The traffic related factor (HOA) represents around 10% of the organic aerosols and is almost constant over the years, with highest fraction during cold periods and lower during warmer periods. The biomass burning-

related organic aerosol presents the highest percentage during cold periods due to increased residential wood burning emissions. The BBOA represents around 20% of the organic aerosols, with small decrease in the last years of the analysed timeframe. The percentage of LOOOA varies between 14% to 30% of the organic aerosols, with highest percentage in 2016. While, the MOOOA represents the highest fraction over the years, with an increase tendency in the last ones, accounting for up to 60% (2022). The MOOOA concentrations are sometimes related to long-range transport from Central Europe during cold periods and North Eastern Europe during warmer periods.

Figure 1. Relative yearly contribution of the different sources to the total OA mass.

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Long-term trends of tropospheric ozone and its precursors (HCHO and CO) from the NDACC FTIR ground-based network, and comparisons with model and satellite trends.

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Keywords: Trends, ozone and precursors, FTIR.

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Context

Ground-based FTIR (Fourier transform infrared) remote sensing measurements are contributing to ACTRIS through the topical center CREGARS (Center for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing). The FTIR stations belonging to the Network for Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC) deliver time-series of many atmospheric species among which five are included in CREGARS: ozone (O₃), formaldehyde (HCHO), ethane (C₂H₆), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and ammonia (NH₃).

In the context of the Tropospheric Ozone Assessment Report (TOAR-II), we are studying the long-term trends derived from the FTIR tropospheric O₃, HCHO, and carbon monoxide (CO) measurements. In addition, within the ESA CCI+ Ozone Precursors project we are investigating the long-term validation of HCHO and CO satellite products.

The FTIR NDACC network provides O₃, HCHO, and CO time-series at more than 25 sites covering a wide range of latitudes and pollution conditions (see Fig. 1) and starting from the 90's for the oldest stations.

Long-term trends

We use a multiple linear regression model (Vigouroux et al., 2015) to derive trends at the sites providing at least 10 years of regular data. The regression model includes seasonal cycles and dynamical proxies explaining the species' variability such as, e.g., the tropopause height, the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), or the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO).

These trends are compared to trends coming from a chemical reanalysis model (Myazaki et al., 2019). The model helps to assess the sampling representativeness of the FTIR network for trend detection. The ground-based time-series is then used to assess the quality of long-term satellite HCHO (OMI/TROPOMI) and CO (IASI A/B/C) products.

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Figure 1. The FTIR stations measuring O₃, HCHO and CO.

Cloud vertical profiling and cloud types over Thessaloniki using active and passive remote sensing.

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Keywords: clouds, remote sensing

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In this work, we utilize 10 years of space-based radar products from the CloudSat mission (Stephens et al., 2002) to provide statistics on the geometrical and microphysical properties of the clouds observed above Thessaloniki station (40.5°N, 22.9°E), in the Eastern Mediterranean.

The CloudSat cloud profiling radar was launched on 28 April 2006, part of the A-Train constellation of satellites. It operates at 94 GHz and has a sensitivity of -30 dBZ. Radar reflectivities are sampled every 240 m and have a vertical resolution of around 480 m. In this study, we use the 2B-GEOPROF radar reflectivity product (Marchand et al., 2008) and the 2B-CLDCLASS cloud type product (Sassen, K. et al., 2008). Reflectivities with a “CPR_cloud_mask” value ≥ 30 indicating high confidence in the retrieval are selected in our analysis. The cloud geometrical and microphysical properties at a spatial resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ around Thessaloniki are processed and presented. We herein analyze the data record collected between January 2007 and December 2017 to characterize the cloud properties over the study area.

The statistics of the CloudSat target classification per month are presented in Figure 1. Clouds dominate above Thessaloniki during spring (MAM) and winter (DJF). The observed clouds are classified into eight categories: stratus (St), stratocumulus (Sc), cumulus (Cu), nimbostratus (Ns), altocumulus (Ac), altostratus (As), deep convective clouds (deep), and high-level clouds (high). Stratus, altocumulus, and high clouds are persistent in the region during all months, whilst low clouds are dominant, with an exception during the summer period.

In next steps, we plan to investigate the vertical variations of the observed cloud types and compare the CloudSat retrievals with the cloud products from passive sensors, such as the EUMETSAT Climate Monitoring Satellite Applications Facility, CMSAF, products based on Seviri/MTG and AVHRR/NOAA and Metop. Additionally, the impact of clouds on radiation above Thessaloniki, will

be studied using scenes with collocated CloudSat and ground-based radiation measurements.

Figure 1. Monthly variation of the CloudSat aerosol types observed around Thessaloniki for the period 2007-2017. Annotated are the cloud profiles per month.

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Spatiotemporal variability and representativeness of aerosol and clouds over the PANhellenic GEophysical observatory of Antikythera

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The PANhellenic GEophysical observatory of Antikythera, PANGEA, located in the centre of the Eastern Mediterranean basin, at the island of Antikythera (35.86 N, 23.81 E, elevation: 110 m a.s.l.) in Greece is the main station of National Observatory of Athens for atmospheric monitoring. PANGEA is a remote site, located in a hot-spot region in terms of climate change. In the study of Gkikas et al., (2023) the atmospheric homogeneity in the broader area around PANGEA is presented, for a radius up to 100 km away, using climatological MODIS Aqua AOD (Aerosol Optical Depth) measurements as a homogeneity tracer. In this study, the spatial AOD remain almost constant at PANGEA, revealing a horizontal homogeneity of the aerosol load in the broader area. Additionally, the analysis of the total Aerosol Mean Extinction coefficient profiles at 532 nm for different radii around PANGEA site for period Jun 2006 – Dec 2021 reveals that a radius of 100 km is representative for PANGEA.

The cloud statistics for a radius of 100 km around PANGEA from a decadal analysis of CLOUDSAT (Stephens et al., 2008) products are presented in Figure 1 bottom. The monthly variability of the 8 classes of clouds is presented (bottom right), along with their presence per height (bottom right). Maximum cloudiness conditions are observed during the winter months (>70%), while minimum conditions are observed during the summer period (<10%). High clouds (high) prevail also during all months at altitudes higher than 6 km, except for July and August above PANGEA. Nimbostratus (Ns), altostratus (As) and deep clouds are observed at all levels up to 13km.

We conclude that PANGEA is ideal for Cal/Val activities given that the location is representative of a wider region within the Mediterranean.

Figure 1. Total Aerosol Mean Extinction coefficient profiles at 532 nm for different radii around PANGEA site for period Jun 2006 – Dec 2021 (up). Frequency of cloud type occurrence (down left) per month, and (down right) per height.

This research was funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.) under the “3rd Call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Acronym: REVEAL, Project Number: 07222). K.V. and E.M. was financially supported by PANGEA4CalVal (Grant Agreement 101079201) funded by the European Union .

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Extended Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) time series analysis in an Alpine Valley: A Comparative Study from 2007 to 2023

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Alpine Climatology, Long-term Trend Analysis, Environmental Statistics

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This study presents an extended analysis of aerosol optical depth at 501 nm (AOD) in the Alpine valley of Innsbruck, Austria, spanning from 2007 to 2023, and offers a comparative analysis with the Alpine station of Davos, Switzerland [Karanikolas et al. 2022]. Building upon previous research conducted until 2012 [Wuttke et al. 2012], the presented study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the long-term trends and seasonal variations in aerosol characteristics in Central Alpine regions.

Figure 1. AOD time series from 2007 to 2023 in Innsbruck

Utilizing a robust dataset collected over 17 years (see figure 1), we employ advanced statistical methods [Sayer et al. 2019] to analyse the AOD time series, focusing on identifying significant trends, patterns, and anomalies. We calculated daily median values only for days that have at least three measurements (also standard in AERONET processing). From these values the monthly geometric mean was calculated if there are at least five valid days available. With this approach we calculated the monthly AOD from 168 out of 202 months (83.2 %) and 154 out of 194 (79.4 %) in Innsbruck and Davos respectively (table 1). The study also deals with a comparative analysis, highlighting the similarities and differences in aerosol behavior between the two locations. Our findings reveal statistically significant negative trends in AOD (table 1).

Table 1. AOD trends at the two stations derived from the time series [2007 - 2023]

Station	Trend per decade	Number and data coverage
Innsbruck	-2.79×10^{-2}	202/83.2%
Davos	-9.90×10^{-3}	194/79.4%

Furthermore, the extended timeframe (17 years) makes it possible to calculate an AOD diurnal cycle / climatology (figure 2) for Innsbruck (and Davos) for the first time.

Figure 2. Monthly AOD climatology [2007 - 2023] in Innsbruck and Davos. Error bars indicate the standard error.

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Size distributions and number concentration of ultrafine particles in a suburban station in southeastern Spain.

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Keywords: Ultrafine particles, particle number concentration, atmospheric particulate matter.

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The ultrafine particles (UFP) are able to penetrate deep into the respiratory system and even reach the cardiovascular system, causing major diseases in humans. The monitoring of these particles is essential in order to establish their main sources and to try to apply abatement techniques to reduce their concentrations. The particularity of these UFP is their size, which makes their measurement more complex. In this study, aerosol particle size distributions (PNSDs) from 10 to 800 nm, with a time resolution of 5 min, were collected using a TROPOS-type custom-built MPSS (mobility particle size spectrometer), designed and manufactured according to EUSAAR/ACTRIS recommendations. It is a closed-loop system, with a 5:1 ratio between the sheath and aerosol flow, where the sample air is drawn into the instrument at a flow rate of 1 L min⁻¹, while the sample humidity is regulated below 40% by a Nafion dryer. The MPSS consist of a bipolar diffusion charger (Ni-63), a differential mobility analyzer (Vienna-type DMA, length 28 cm), and a condensation particle counter (CPC, model TSI 3772, TSI Inc., USA).

The main objective of this work is to characterize ultrafine particles at an urban background station in southeastern Spain. The behavior of the different modes (Nucleation, Aitken, and Accumulation) will be studied. The measurements were taken in the city of Elche between 1 July 2022 and 8 June 2023.

The average value of the total particle number concentration (PNC) was 169000 ± 2000 while the averages of the different modes were 68100 ± 1300 , 78400 ± 100 and 22400 ± 500 for the nucleation, Aitken and accumulation modes respectively.

Figure 1 shows the particle size distribution averaged over the whole period. The maximum values are reached in the nucleation mode, followed closely by those obtained in the Aitken mode. This characterizes the urban background station where fresh aerosols emitted close to the station by the surrounding traffic are found at the same time as aerosols that have already started to age since their emission. In comparison, the contribution of aerosols of regional origin does not seem to be very important.

Figure 1. Average particle size distribution during the study period.

The distribution of PNC over the day is shown in figure 2. The maximum is reached in the late hours of the day, related to the reduction of the mixing layer. The minimum is reached in the early morning before traffic starts in the city.

Figure 2. Average daily total particle concentration.

In addition, studies were carried out to classify the measurements by days of the week and/or seasons of the year. A comparison of the results obtained in Elche with other European metropolises was carried out.

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Decreasing or increasing pollution in the Mediterranean atmosphere? 16 years of black carbon observations at the Monte Cimone GAW Global Station

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Keywords: aerosol, long-term, Mediterranean

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Black carbon (BC) is an absorbing carbonaceous aerosol emitted by combustion processes. Due to its strong absorption of visible light, BC contributes to global aerosol absorption up to 84% and represents the strongest anthropogenic aerosol warmer (Samset et al., 2018). The climatic impact of BC depends on its atmospheric concentration, which varies significantly in space and time. This is particularly relevant in regions such as Europe and the Mediterranean basin, a hot spot for air quality issues and climate change. Thanks to the improvement of European air quality standards, the emission of aerosol, including BC, constantly decreased in Europe since the 1980s (Smith et al., 2011). Otherwise, Mediterranean climatic anomalies such as drought and heat waves might alter the removal, emission and transport of BC particles in the near and far future (MedECC, 2020). Therefore, recording the variability of aerosol particles, including BC, became crucial by conducting continuous and long-term atmospheric observations in background conditions.

Within the framework of ACTRIS, continuous observation of equivalent BC (eBC) has been performed continuously since 2007 at the GAW-WMO global station on the top of Monte Cimone in Italy (CMN). With an elevation of 2165 m asl the site is representative of the Mediterranean troposphere background and is influenced by Mediterranean climatic anomalies, Po Valley emission and free-tropospheric conditions. eBC mass concentration (M_{eBC}) was calculated from the aerosol absorption coefficient measured with a Multi-Angle Absorption Photometer using a mass absorption cross-section of $10 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (Zanatta et al., 2016). A total of 4478 valid days of M_{eBC} observations have been collected, with a minimum of 53% and a maximum of 98% of valid measuring days per year. This work aims to trace the phenomenology of eBC at the CMN from 2007 to 2022. First, we identify and quantify the linear long-term trends as a function of seasons and day-time cycles. Second, by using ERA-5 reanalysis data we investigate the impact of boundary layer dynamic and heat waves on the frequency and intensity of eBC anomalies at CMN.

Overall, eBC observations have displayed a decreasing trend in M_{eBC} (Figure 1). Based on yearly medians, the long-term trend was approximately $-0.09 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ per decade. A decreasing trend was also calculated for the more polluted summer season ($-0.08 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ per decade) and the more pristine winter season ($-0.04 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ per decade). Despite this common

decreasing trend, the yearly median M_{eBC} did not decrease monotonically, showing a maximum of $0.31 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and a minimum of $0.12 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ recorded in 2010 and 2016, respectively. A similar feature was observed for the winter seasons. Figure 1 suggests that M_{eBC} has been increasing since 2016-17 at a relative fast rate ($+0.19 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ per decade).

This increasing tendency since 2016-17 might be connected with the intensifying warming recorded in the last decade, which might alter the dynamic of the boundary layer and promote the injection of anthropogenic pollution from the boundary layer into the free troposphere at CMN. This Hypothesis will be verified by combining additional in-situ observation at CMN and ERA5 reanalysis data, and extending the long-term analysis by using other methods or strategies.

Figure 1. Time series of eBC mass concentration (M_{eBC}) at CMN station with yearly resolution.

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**THEME 2 - ATMOSPHERIC
PROCESSES IN THE NATURAL OR
CONTROLLED ATMOSPHERES,
INCLUDING AEROSOL-CLOUD-
CLIMATE INTERACTIONS**

Scientific Committee Members:
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Modelling the effect of biogenic NO emissions from soils on atmospheric chemistry simulations over Africa

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Keywords: Adon, Yao, Solmon

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In a context of climate change and increasing anthropogenic pressure in Africa, it is crucial to understand the interactions between atmospheric chemistry, climate, and biogeochemical cycles. This study aims at improving and evaluating the regional coupled climate-chemistry model RegCM5-CHEM from RegCM5 (Giorgi et al., 2023), for further application to the study of important atmospheric compounds in Africa: O₃, NO₂, and HNO₃. Improvements to the model in key processes such as anthropogenic and biogenic emissions, dry and wet deposition processes have been discussed.

Then, the paper focuses on simulation validations of both regional climate (precipitation, monsoon activity, temperature) driven by the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020), and atmospheric chemistry in terms of surface concentrations. In particular, 5-years monthly average of the tropospheric nitrogen dioxide, nitric acid, and ozone cycle photo-chemistry, which notably regulates the level of atmospheric nitrogen, are analyzed with reference to in-situ INDAAF ACTRIS-Fr observations and chemical reanalyses. Model simulations capture the main features of seasonal and daily mean of temperature, precipitation, and wind field.

For long-term simulations of chemistry, the model shows good agreement with the INDAAF observation for NO₂ and HNO₃ with slight underestimation, while it tends to overestimate surface seasonal ozone. Finally, a special focus is given to the NO emissions influence on the regional and local atmospheric chemistry. We find that additional biogenic NO emissions improve O₃, NO₂, and HNO₃ seasonal cycles and concentrations magnitudes, reducing the main biases. Overall, the species evaluation shows the feasibility of using RegCM5-CHEM for long-term simulations of climate-chemistry interactions.

Figure 1: Surface observed NO₂ concentrations (INDAAF) vs simulated with RegCM5. Biogenic NO emissions are considered (BioNO_x)

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Physical and optical properties of primary wood combustion particles and secondary formed aerosol in the EUPHORE experimental chamber

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Keywords: nucleation, condensational growth, photochemistry, smog chamber.

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Wood combustion is an important source of black carbon (BC) and primary organic aerosol (primary OA, POA). Moreover, organic precursors emitted by wood combustion play role in gas-particle partitioning and contribute to the secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation.

In this work we studied the primary emission of wood combustion and the secondary formation of organic aerosol via photochemical, and aqueous phase (dark) reactions in a controlled experiment implemented at the EUPHORE simulation chamber. The combustion source was a fireplace fuelled by vine tree, orange or beech wood. Flaming and smouldering combustion modes were studied separately. The emission was introduced into the dark chamber. After several hours of dark aging the shutter was opened, and the pollution mixture was exposed to sunlight.

BC, total carbon (TC) and organic carbon (OC) measurements were performed with 30 minutes time resolution using the CASS (Aerosol Magee Scientific). SMPS (TSl) measurement was performed by 4 minutes time resolution in the 10-1000 nm size range. Aerosol optical properties (absorption and scattering) were measured with the newly released 9λ Aethalometer model AE36s (Aerosol Magee Scientific). CO₂ mixing ratio was measured by Vaisala GMP343 NDIR sensor. BC and OC emission factors (EF) were determined for each wood type and burning mode. For the EF calculation the burnt fuel mass was determined from the CO₂ increment of the emission. Table 1 summarises the EFs for two different wood types, combustion modes and aging conditions.

Table 1. BC and OC EFs (mg/kg fuel) for beech and orange wood. F – flaming, S – smouldering modes. D – daylight, N – night aging conditions.

Combustion	BC	OC _{prim}	OC _{sec}
Beech FD	0.92	0.40	1.33
Beech SD	0.23	4.31	5.26
Beech SN	0.14	2.71	0.87
Orange FD	0.84	0.23	0.40
Orange SD	0.69	14.4	20.2
Orange SN	0.62	13.9	9.76

The secondary OC EF was calculated from the total OC amount that formed following the emission until the end of the experiment normalised by the burnt fuel mass. Regarding the primary emissions, flaming combustion generally emits more BC and less OC than smouldering emission. Especially high OC_{prim} EF was found at orange wood combustion. Regarding the secondary OC formation, we can see that the EFs always exceed the OC_{prim} EF in the cases of daylight aging. Daylight aging of orange smouldering emission produced extreme, 20.2 mg secondary OC per kg of burnt fuel.

Since the precursors of the secondary OC are emitted together with the primary OC, its production rate is expected to be proportional with the primary OC concentration. Figure 1 shows the production rate of secondary OC as a function of the primary OC concentration for all fuel types, combustion, and aging modes. The coloured symbols refer about the fuel type and the combustion mode for daylight aging. The slope of the regression line is close to 1, which means that almost the same OC mass was formed secondary during each hour as the primary OC emission was.

Figure 1. Secondary OC production rate vs. primary OC concentration for daylight and nighttime aging. Colourful symbols refer about the fuel type and combustion mode (F – flaming, S – smouldering, only for daylight aging).

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Wildfire smoke in the climate system: Impact on ice nucleation in mixed-phase and cirrus clouds

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Keywords: aerosol-cloud interaction, remote sensing

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Since the summer of 2017, the number of wildfire smoke layers in the lower and middle free troposphere as well as in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) increased significantly in the northern hemisphere. The smoke affected the stratospheric ozone layer (Ohneiser et al., 2021, Ansmann et al., 2022) and triggered cirrus formation (Engelmann et al., 2021, Ansmann et al., 2023) in the High Arctic. Meanwhile, a clear impact of wildfire smoke on cirrus formation was also observed over Limassol, Cyprus, in the Eastern Mediterranean (Mamouri et al., 2023).

In the summer of 2019, extreme and long-lasting wildfires in central and eastern Siberia developed and were responsible for the UTLS smoke layer that was observed with lidar aboard the ice breaker Polarstern during the MOSAiC (Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate) campaign in the central Arctic between autumn 2019 and spring 2020 (Ohneiser et al., 2021). Based on combined lidar radar observations, numerous cirrus events could be characterized in terms of ice-nucleating particle concentration (smoke particles mainly consist of organic material) and ice crystal number concentration in the developed virga below the cirrus generation cells. Clear indications were found that heterogeneous ice nucleation on smoke particles dominated the ice formation processes in the High Arctic and suppressed homogeneous ice nucleation, i.e., freezing of background sulfate particles.

Strong ice nucleation and virga evolution events were observed over the Cyprus Atmospheric Remote Sensing Observatory (CARO), at Limassol, Cyprus, from 28 October to 1 November 2020 (Mamouri et al., 2023). The smoke originated from large wildfires in California, USA, and traveled for 8 days before reaching Europe. The cirrus generation cells coincided with the lower part of the dense wildfire smoke layer in the UTLS height range. The pronounced virga structures pointed to a relatively small number of comparably large ice crystals that grew fast and formed these well-organized virga signatures. The smoke layer sufficiently overlapped with the humid region in which the ice clouds formed and served as a non-depletable reservoir of INPs over days.

Regarding the ice nucleation mode, we hypothesize that the smoke particles were glassy so that deposition ice nucleation (DIN) dominated ice formation. In support of the lidar observations, we performed simulations of gravity-wave-induced lofting of air parcels, the related temperature decrease and respective RH increase, and the impact of this lofting on ice nucleation via DIN. Lofting by about 100–200 m was found to be sufficient to initiate significant ice nucleation on the wildfire particles (Mamouri et al., 2023).

In the summer of 2023, smoke layers from North America and southern Europe were frequently observed over Leipzig, Germany, with a powerful aerosol lidar equipped with aerosol fluorescence channels (Gast et al., 2024). Many mixed-phase clouds (in the lower and middle free troposphere) and ice clouds in the upper troposphere were observed. It remains an open question to what extent smoke particles can influence ice nucleation (via immersion freezing) at relatively high temperatures from -25 to -35°C under mixed-phase cloud conditions. Furthermore, it remains unclear whether the observed ice formation in mixed-phase clouds was triggered by smoke particles or by soil dust particles that may have been injected together with the smoke into the atmosphere by the wildfires.

We will discuss and summarize the ACTRIS observation with focus on ice nucleation in smoke layers, performed in the High Arctic, the Eastern Mediterranean, and central Europe, in this ACTRIS conference contribution.

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Ground-based Remote Sensing of Aerosol, Clouds, Dynamics, and Precipitation in Antarctica - First results from a one-year campaign at Neumayer Station III in 2023

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Novel observations of aerosol and clouds by means of ground-based remote sensing have been performed in Antarctica at the German Neumayer Station III (70.67°S, 8.27°W, Wesche et al., 2016) for a full year. The deployment of mobile exploratory platform OCEANET-Atmosphere brought full ACTRIS aerosol and cloud profiling capabilities next to meteorological, radiation, and air chemistry in-situ observations at the Antarctic station. Neumayer is also the only station on a floating ice shelf, where personal is present year-round, providing excellent conditions for studies atmospheric impacts on an Antarctic ice shelf.

For the deployment the standard instrumentation of OCEANET-Atmosphere (PollyXT Raman polarization Lidar, a HATPRO microwave Radiometer, a Cimel sun and lunar photometer, and Radiation sensors) was extended by a Mira-35 cloud radar, a scanning Doppler lidar LITRA-S and an optical disdrometer Parsivel². This combination of instruments allows the application of the standard ACTRIS retrievals, such as Cloudnet and the Single Calculus Chain, as well as advanced retrievals for cloud-relevant aerosol properties (Mamouri and Ansmann, 2016), liquid droplet properties (Jimenez et al., 2020) and ice crystal concentrations (Bühl et al., 2019, Mason et al., 2023).

While data analysis is ongoing, three scientific highlights have already been identified during austral fall and winter, namely:

1. Observations of a persistent shallow mixed-phase cloud embedded in a plume of advected marine aerosol. State of the art microphysical retrievals are used to obtain aerosol and cloud microphysical properties. Closure between cloud-relevant aerosol particles and sedimenting ice crystals was achieved and demonstrated that the cloud formed in an aerosol-limited environment.

2. Two extraordinary warm air intrusions: One with intense snowfall produced the equivalent of 10% of the yearly snow accumulation, a second one with record-breaking max temperatures and heavy icing due to supercooled drizzle.

3. Omnipresent aerosol layers in the stratosphere, which contributed almost 50% to the aerosol optical depth of around 0.06 at 500nm. The lidar-derived optical

signatures revealed sulphate aerosol in the stratosphere - most likely linked to the Hunga Tonga eruption in 2022.

Scientific analysis will continue, for example, once the filter samples taken at the air chemistry observatory are analysed for ice activity, they will be put into context provided by remote sensing.

Figure 1. OCEANET-Atmosphere as deployed 380 m south of Neumayer Station III. Air chemistry observatory in the background.

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Identification of instrumental artefacts in terpene detection: field studies and follow-up chamber campaign ACROSS-HECTIC

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Terpenes, a subset of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs), are major emissions that strongly affect the air chemistry of forested environments. Despite this, their quantification and speciation remain challenging. As a recent example, we take an extensive suite of field measurements that took place in the Rambouillet forest during the ACROSS (Atmospheric ChemistRy Of the Suburban foreSt) campaign (Cantrell *et al* (2023)).

Among the instruments deployed, 8 were used to measure VOCs, including two different technologies: Proton Transfer Reaction Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry (PTR-ToF-MS) and Thermal Desorption Gas Chromatography with Flame Ionization / Mass Spectrometry detections (TD-GC-FID/MS). As shown in figure 1, the comparison of these instruments from different teams revealed a strong disagreement in monoterpene measurements: from tens of ppt to low ppbs measured by GCs and PTR-MS respectively.

Figure 1: Time series of monoterpenes obtained by PTR-ToF-MS and TD-GCs above the canopy during the ACROSS 2022 campaign

There are several possible causes for these differences, including: miscalibrations, sample decomposition, interferences and effects of environmental conditions.

To help resolving these discrepancies, we invited the participants of ACROSS to the HELIOS platform, situated at CNRS-Orléans, in a measurement campaign called HECTIC (HElios Chamber Terpenes Instrumental Comparison). This consisted of a series of experiments which were designed for investigating analytical

responses of the different instruments to isoprene and monoterpenes and identify the systematic differences observed during ACROSS. Of the two groupings, it is expected that the GC instruments tend to underestimate terpene concentrations for the following reasons: miscalibration, trap breakthrough, oxidation of trapped species by ambient ozone, sample decomposition and/or isomerization, and sample line conditions. Conversely, PTR-MS may be susceptible to overestimation of terpene concentrations due to: miscalibration and fragmentation and interfering masses on m/z 69, 81 and 137. For this purpose, we designed a hybrid setup (presented in figure 2) whereby stable concentrations of the targeted species in the chamber could be perturbed with various different conditions (humidity, ozone, interferences).

Figure 2 : Experimental set-up of the HECTIC campaign

Some sampling line effects were encountered. In some cases, humidity effects were observed in the GC techniques, leading to sample degradation and/or isomerization. Similarly, a sensitivity to ozone concentrations was suspected.

These results highlight a potential problem of ambient measurements of an important class of compounds, whereby, depending on the analytical technique and manner in which it's used, significant differences in concentrations and speciation could be observed.

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Regional nitrogen budget in the Lake Victoria catchment (East Africa)

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Abstract

Nitrogen (N) is an essential nutrient for life, but when it is in excess, it pollutes the atmosphere, the soil and the water, threatening the health of ecosystems and humans. A lack of nitrogen can also pose a threat to food security. It is therefore useful to be able to determine whether an ecosystem has a nitrogen deficit or a surplus, in order to assess the performance of nitrogen management and to implement regulatory policies concerning food safety, human health and environmental protection.

In this study, the N budget for Lake Victoria and its catchment is estimated using in situ measurements collected at the tropical rural site of Mbita (Kenya) on the shores of Lake Victoria for the period 2018-2019. We performed original measurements of atmospheric deposition and leaching that were supplemented by published data and model outputs. Nitrogen inputs to terrestrial areas include total atmospheric deposition (wet and dry deposition), N₂ fixation (natural and agricultural), the application of nitrogen fertilisers and livestock effluents. Nitrogen outflows from land areas include gaseous nitrogen emissions (NO_x, NH₃, N₂O, N₂) from agriculture, natural soils, fires and urban areas, nitrogen leaching and nitrogen extraction from food and feed imports. Nitrogen inputs to the lake include atmospheric deposition, nitrogen imports from rivers, urban wastewater pollution, runoff and industrial activities. Nitrogen outputs from the lake include exports from the Nile and fisheries. Nitrogen emissions from the lake have not been assessed due to a lack of data.

The results obtained provide an estimate of the budget (Bakayoko et al., 2021). Therefore, the N critical load could be assessed for the terrestrial part of the catchment, which was, never calculated before using in situ measurements. The deposition of dry gaseous nitrogen (N-NH₃ + N-NO₂ + N-HNO₃) above the water surface of Lake Victoria is 1.95 kgN.ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ with 72.82 % N-NH₃, 21.54 % N-HNO₃ and 5.64% N-NO₂. On the land surface of the catchment, it is 3.52 kgN. ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ with 47.47% N-NH₃, 26.79% N-HNO₃ and 25.74% N-NO₂ for 2018. Total nitrogen deposition (dry + wet) is estimated at 12.95 kgN.ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ with a wet deposition contribution of 72.81% (27.19% for dry deposition) over land and 11.38 kgN.ha⁻¹.yr⁻¹ with a wet deposition contribution of 83% (17% for dry deposition) over water for 2018. The nitrogen budget was therefore estimated between -366.41 and +43.76 GgN.yr⁻¹ for the Lake Victoria catchment (terrestrial part) and between 1084.87 and 1107.01 GgN.yr⁻¹ for Lake Victoria (aquatic part) (Figure 1). The negative value of

the budget in the terrestrial part indicates a depletion of the nitrogen stock in the soil. However, the positive budget in the lake indicates an accumulation of nitrogen that could explain the eutrophication observed on the shores of the lake. The critical load calculated in this study (46.08±2.93 kgN ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) remains higher than the total atmospheric deposition (12.95 kgN ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹).

The main conclusion of this paper is that the terrestrial part of the catchment is not yet threatened by an excess of nitrogen deposition, but that the nitrogen budget is unbalanced and favours soil nitrogen depletion.

Figure 1. Estimated regional nitrogen budget for Lake Victoria and its catchment in East Africa.

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Investigation of HOMs and aerosol formation using the Atmospheric Research Vessel SAPHIR*

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Keywords: chamber, HOM, aerosol.

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Aerosols represent one of the largest uncertainties in our understanding of the climate system. The processes and pathways involved in their formation and processing are very complex and involve a multitude of atmospheric constituents and mechanisms. A very important part within this complex system are organic aerosols.

Of particular interest is to understand how their gaseous precursors are oxidized and changed, until they find their way into the aerosol phase, where the resulting organic components can affect crucial parameters like radiative scattering on aerosols (direct climate effect) as well as cloud formation (indirect climate effect).

SAPHIR* (STAR: STirred Atmospheric tank Reactor) is a continuously stirred tank reactor designed for mechanistic studies of aerosol formation under steady state conditions. SAPHIR* is the newest addition to the SAPHIR NF (National Facility) exploratory platform within the ACTRIS-D framework and extends the capabilities of the existing atmospheric research chamber SAPHIR (e.g., Fuchs et al., 2018) and the plant chamber SAPHIR-PLUS (Hohaus et al., 2016) by delivering complementary measurements.

One of the important features of this new atmospheric simulation chamber is that conditions during a steady state are stable and constant for hours, giving one the possibility to explore a chemical system at low precursor concentrations like those found in the atmosphere.

Here we present results from studies conducted in this new atmospheric simulation chamber using its unique capabilities. One of these studies (Baker et al., 2023) investigated the change in the chemical system of α -pinene photooxidation due to a shift in the ratio of hydroperoxyl radicals and organic peroxy radicals and the effects on the HOMs and in consequence the formation of secondary organic aerosol. This study was performed with collaborators from the University of Gothenburg and the University of Manchester.

Figure 1. The SAPHIR* reactor during a photooxidation experiment.

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Study of cirrus and contrail formation at Clermont-Ferrand (France) with lidar, ADS-B aircraft detection and full-sky camera

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The end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century saw an increase in anthropogenic activity, causing an accumulation of greenhouse gases in the troposphere and then a global warming. Another aspect is linked to the impact of increased air traffic on the formation of contrails which are artificial ice clouds in the upper troposphere formed by aircraft engine emissions (Kärcher, 2018). Contrails trap outgoing longwave radiation inducing a short-term warming effect on the Earth surface. They can persist and spread to form cirrus clouds, inducing a complex longer term impact on the Earth's radiation balance (Minnis et al., 1999). Studies of this scientific theme require the use of high quality data, with a fine vertical resolution provided for example by lidar instruments.

The CO-PDD ACTRIS site (Clermont-Opme-Puy De Dôme, Baray et al., 2019) is equipped with COPLid (Figure 1), a high-power lidar in operation since 2008 (Fréville et al., 2015), modified in 2022 to integrate 3 wavelengths channels (355, 532 and 1064 nm), some of them with polarized and Raman channels. The site is also equipped with a ADS-B device which records aircraft information (position, altitude, speed and identifier) around the lidar location (Peyrin et al., 2023). A full-sky camera records photos of the sky every minute (Figure 2).

Figure 1. COPLid instrument.

The objective of this study is to provide an updated description of the remote sensing instrumentation deployed at Clermont-Ferrand, and a preliminary analysis of the lidar measurements and camera photos

recorded at Clermont-Ferrand on 2 June 2023 with signatures of cirrus and contrails.

Figure 2. Full sky images of contrails over Clermont-Ferrand on 2 June 2023.

CO-PDD is an instrumented site of OPGC observatory and LaMP laboratory, supported by Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS-INSU) and Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES). The project BECOM has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation actions programme under grant agreement 101056885.

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Levoglucosan Volatility in Biomass Burning Organic Aerosol: Persistent non-idealities

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Keywords: biomass burning, volatility, non-idealities

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Emissions from biomass burning aerosols make up a considerable fraction of the organic aerosol present in the atmosphere, especially downwind from wildfire plumes and during residential heating seasons. The emissions from various biomass sources therefore play a critical role in air quality, climate, and human health. Levoglucosan represents a key organic aerosol marker for many different biomass burning sources (Zhang et al., 2023) and is ubiquitous close to burning sources. Though, many days downwind the presence of levoglucosan steadily diminishes and can no longer be used as a tracer molecule for biomass burning aerosol. The usefulness of levoglucosan as a marker is tied to its atmospheric stability either in terms of reactivity with atmospheric oxidants or through its volatility / evaporation (Bertrand et al., 2018).

In the atmospheric simulation chambers present at the Paul Scherrer Institute, the volatility of levoglucosan was investigated for the pure system (i.e. only levoglucosan), known mixtures with pure compounds (e.g. PEG-300) and within complex biomass burning organic aerosol from a residential wood stove (pre- vs. post- aging). The aging investigated represents either UV radiation aging with biomass burning organic aerosol in the absence of volatile organic compounds or OH aging in the presence of volatile organic compounds thus forming SOA on the pre-existing particles. The volatility was investigated by evaporating the aerosol in a thermal denuder (TD) and measuring the chemical species left in the aerosol with an extractive electrospray mass spectrometer (EESI-MS).

The combined TD-EESI-MS data provides volatility information that can be extracted via mass transfer equations. Given the well-established ΔH_{vap} of levoglucosan the pure component saturation vapor pressure (C^0) can be extracted for the pure component system and compared against the C^*_{eff} for the relevant mixtures including levoglucosan mentioned above. The differences between the C^0 and C^*_{eff} relate to non-idealities experienced by levoglucosan in the relevant mixtures. In simplistic terms two are related where: $C^*_{\text{eff}} = \gamma_{\text{eff}} C^0$, where γ_{eff} is the effective activity coefficient.

Figure 1 shows the extracted γ_{eff} for levoglucosan when mixed with PEG-300 or within biomass burning aerosol. In all cases, levoglucosan in these mixtures has γ_{eff} that are greater than 1, indicating there are repulsive

intermolecular interactions between levoglucosan and the components in which it is mixed. Therefore, levoglucosan's volatility increases when present in these mixtures. To contrast these results, we will also present how the γ_{eff} changes with simulated atmospheric aging with UV radiation and coatings of SOA.

Figure 1: Effective activity coefficient (γ_{eff}) for levoglucosan (LG) in mixtures with PEG-300, and biomass burning aerosol generated from a wood stove.

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MOCCA : a new platform to assess the multiphasic atmospheric organic chemistry with a Combipal - CHARON-PTR-ToF-MS

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Keywords: Multiphasic, Organic Matter, Mass Spectrometry.

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The atmospheric organic matter is ubiquitous and dominant in the atmosphere over the globe (Nozière et al 2015). One major question is the multiphasic fate of organic compounds in relation with the cloud life cycle. Indeed, during the cloud lifetime, chemical compounds can be efficiently transformed through physico-chemical and biological processes that control their distribution between the different phases (cloud water or rain, particle phase and gaseous phase).

Our understanding of the fate of organic matter in the multiphasic atmosphere like the aqueous pathways controlling the Secondary Organic Aerosol formation is still limited because of (1) the difficulty to sample cloud and the discrete nature of cloud events, (2) the scarcity of observations at molecular levels in the uncontrolled atmosphere and (3) organics compounds have been found in supersaturation inside cloud water at different latitudes (Wang et al (2019) & Dominutti et al (2022)).

MOCCA (Mass spectrometry for the multiphasic Composition of the Cloudy Atmosphere) is a new, single, mass spectrometry platform to characterize the organic composition of the three atmospheric phases (gas, particle, cloud water). MOCCA combines a high-resolution PTR-ToF-MS (model 6000X2 IONICON Analytik GmbH, Austria) to, a CHARON inlet and a temperature-controlled auto sampler (Combipal) to access to molecular-level composition of the organic matter. The cloud water is sampled with the cloud collector BOOGIE (Deguillaume et al 2024, in prep.) before analysis. The PTR-ToF-MS has been used in H₃O⁺ mode from 20 to 400 amu.

MOCCA has been deployed in a temperate suburban environment (suburban Paris, SIRTA NF, ACROSS project), a subtropical forest site (São Paulo, RMG, BIOMASP+ project) and for the analysis of the cloud water samples collected in the cloudy atmosphere of the CO-PDD NF (Cézeaux-Aulnat-Opme-puy de Dôme (1465m a.s.l.) platform).

First, we will present the performances of MOCCA in those contrasting environments, and its consistency with some of the long-term organics monitored within ACTRIS. We have quantified the gas/particle phase partitioning of species of interest in those environments. Secondly, we will highlight the analytical capacities of MOCCA to explore the cloudy atmosphere. For the cloud

water analysis, headspace measurement of the cloud water from CO-PDD NF site has been developed based on the work of Perkins and Langford (2021). Finally, gas/cloud phase partitioning of those cloud samples will be shown.

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Hygroscopicity-driven light-scattering enhancement in Lille

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Keywords: $f(\text{RH})$, hygroscopicity, scattering.

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The scattering enhancement factor $f(\text{RH})$ characterises the alteration in aerosol particle light scattering as a function of relative humidity (RH). Specifically, it quantifies the influence of water uptake on light scattering, mostly depending on particle chemical composition and diameter, and provides valuable insights on the hygroscopicity of aerosols. The $f(\text{RH})$ is determined by measuring the particle scattering coefficients under different humidity conditions, often performed using tandem nephelometer systems. We present an overview of $f(\text{RH})$ based on an ongoing field campaign over the ATOLL (Atmospheric Observation in Lille) platform located on the rooftop of a University of Lille building (50.6111 °N, 3.1404 °E, 70 m a.s.l.).

Dry (RH < 40%, Nafion, performed since 2004) and **wet** (RH > 80%, using a Vapour Delivery Module SW-100 Bronkhorst, performed since September 2023) scattering coefficient (σ_{scat}) measurements are performed using ECOTECH Aurora 3000 and TSI 3563 nephelometers. Both nephelometers are running with a dryer (Nafion or desiccant) upstream of both instruments and downstream a PM₁ cyclone. Both nephelometers are calibrated daily using filtered air and calibrated every 3 months using CO₂. Data from both instruments have been corrected from angular truncation errors and illumination intensity non-idealities based on Müller et al. (2009) and Anderson and Ogren (1998). Moreover, on a weekly basis, the wet nephelometer is set on dry mode for comparison to the dry nephelometer. These dry mode periods were used to (1) check the operational status of both instruments and to (2) correct the drifts and reduce uncertainty of comparison of the wet scattering coefficients.

The dry and wet scattering observed during September as well as the $f(\text{RH})$ are presented in Figure 1. The dry scattering coefficients are ranging from 4 to 165 Mm⁻¹. The $f(\text{RH})$ values range from 0.65 to 3.71. During this short period available nowadays (1 month), no relation was found between the Scattering Angström Exponent (SAE) with the $f(\text{RH})$. However, a clear dependency on the wind directions has been observed. To confirm and understand this tendency, more data will be performed and compared to ACSM and AE33

measurements. Moreover, some $f(\text{RH})$ values are observed below 1 that might be attributed to aerosol restructuring or a change in the mixing state after water absorption. This will be further investigated.

Figure 1. $f(\text{RH})$, dry and wet scattering coefficients evolution with time. The dashed line corresponds to $f(\text{RH})=1$. Grey areas correspond to dry mode periods.

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Latent Heat Flux and TKE are computed during WALINEAS Campaign with a Raman Lidar and Wind Lidar system

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Introduction

The latent heat flux (LHF) is a fundamental parameter to describe the energy exchange between the Earth's surface and atmosphere within the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL). It represents the rate at which the energy stored as latent heat in water vapor molecules is transported in the ABL due to convective turbulent air motion.

The combination of both lidar measurements can provide a comprehensive view of atmospheric processes related to latent heat flux, helping to improve our understanding of the water cycle and related meteorological phenomena. During *WaLiNeAs Campaign (Water vapor Lidar Network Assimilation)*, a consortium of French, German, Italian and Spanish research groups has deployed a network of 6 autonomous Lidar WVs on French territory to provide measurements with high vertical resolution and accuracy across the western Mediterranean, starting in autumn 2022, filling critical gaps in WV observations of the lower troposphere by current operational networks and satellites. As part of the *WaLiNeAs* initiative, a Lidar system developed by the University of Basilicata is placed in proximity to a Wind Lidar with the aim of obtaining heat flow measurements and TKE (turbulent kinetic energy) measurements. The two systems operated continuously for three months starting from the end of September 2022, to cover most favorable period in the south of France, acquiring high resolution measurements (10sec 30m).

Methodology

Water vapor (q) was obtained from UV rotational Raman lidar measurements (355nm) while vertical wind (w) measurements were made with a Doppler Wind lidar, through the eddy covariance method the vertical turbulent flow (Q) was computed see (Figure 1). By (u,v,w) wind component also a TKE was computed (Figure 2)

Figure 1. Latent heat Flux (Q) computed for selected cases 31st-2nd Nov 2022

Figure 2. TKE computed for selected cases 31st October by Doppler Lidar data.

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Black carbon in the Arctic: Connecting Bely Island with MOSAiC observations

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Keywords: BC, wildfires, flaring.

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The Arctic climate has been reported to warm 2–3 times faster than the global average due to Arctic amplification, caused by simultaneously-acting mechanisms such as ice–albedo feedback and aerosol–cloud radiative forcing (AMAP, 2021). Globally, aerosol and cloud processes lead to a net cooling (IPCC, 2021). However, aerosol–cloud interactions in the Arctic can lead to warming that is comparable in magnitude to the warming associated with greenhouse gases, depending on the season.

Black carbon (BC) is an important short-lived climate forcer that has been demonstrated to exert warming in the Arctic. Much of our knowledge on BC in the Arctic stems from land-based observatories in the western Arctic. However, a key source region is the Siberian Arctic (with a variety of different sources) and a key impact region is the central Arctic. In both locations only sparse measurements are available. Importantly, to obtain an overview of the pollution in the Arctic, records must be taken over the same period of time.

In 2019, a new aerosol station was developed in the Bely Island (Kara Sea, Western Siberian Arctic). The region was chosen because it is close to the air pathway of large-scale emission plumes from populated industrial regions of Eurasia and Siberian wildfires to the Arctic. We present here the ground-based continuous BC (equivalent BC, EBC) measurements from 2019 – 2022. For the overlapping time period, we complement measurements at Bely Island with measurements taken onboard the Polarstern RV during the MOSAiC expedition from October 2019 to September 2020.

The MOSAiC expedition was designed to address the scarcity of data available from the Arctic Ocean region. It is considered the most comprehensive expedition in the Arctic in history, in which researchers evaluated the Arctic environment for a full year from various perspectives. The possible insights from the MOSAiC expedition are numerous, as the collocated measurements of various Arctic system processes allow for interdisciplinary analyses of interlinked environmental processes (Boyer et al., 2023).

The connection between possible sources and measurements was assessed with the Lagrangian Particle Dispersion model FLEXPART v10.4 (Pisso et al., 2019) driven with the most recent assimilated meteorological fields. The model was coupled with

emissions as described in Popovicheva et al. (2022). Monthly average contribution of various sources to surface BC at Bely for 2019–2022 period are shown in Fig. 1.

We find that spring and early fall exhibits higher concentrations at Bely Island compared to the central Arctic, while interestingly concentrations are higher in the Central Arctic in January and February. This might be an indication that other important source regions contribute to the central Arctic pollution, not from Eurasia. Investigation of specific transport events, so called Lagrangian cases, is relevant to understand the spatiotemporal Arctic BC distribution and geolocating sources.

Figure 1. Averaged monthly means EBC and contribution of various sources to surface BC at Bely Island 2019–2022.

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Investigation of the ozone formation of anthropogenic VOCs in the atmospheric simulation chamber SAPHIR

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The hydroxyl radical (OH) is the most important daytime oxidant in the troposphere, initiating chemical degradation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and hence contributing to the formation of secondary pollutants. In the oxidation process of VOCs, peroxy radicals (RO₂) and hydroperoxy radicals (HO₂) are formed. In polluted areas, characterised by the presence of nitric oxide (NO), RO₂ radicals preferably react with NO forming an alkoxy radical (RO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), with the latter producing ozone after its photolysis. The ozone formation rate is sensitive to the chemistry of the formed RO radical which can either form HO₂ or another RO₂ radical in its unimolecular reactions, where the latter can lead to the formation of an additional ozone molecule. Another ozone molecule is formed from the reaction of HO₂ with NO via the formation of NO₂ and at the same time regenerating the OH radical, enhancing atmospheric oxidation.

Large discrepancies (Tan, 2017,2018; Slater, 2020; Whalley, 2018, 2021) between measured and modelled HO₂ and RO₂ radical concentrations were found in particular during daytime in urban environments, at both, low (< 1 ppbv) and high (> 3 ppbv), NO. As measured and modelled radical concentrations are commonly used to determine the instantaneous ozone production rate (P(O_x)), a large model-measurement discrepancy was also found for P(O_x) at high NO.

A systematic study of the photo-oxidation of straight and branched alkanes (propane, iso-pentane, n-hexane) and alkenes (propene, trans-2-hexene) was conducted in the atmospheric simulation chamber SAPHIR at Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany, for NO mixing ratio below 1 ppbv and between 3 and 5 ppbv.

The aim of this study was to mimic current chemical regimes in cities (high NO) but also expected future regimes (low NO) in a controlled environment. Furthermore, different types of RO radical chemistry were tested: propane, propene, and trans-2-hexene form RO radicals that form HO₂, while iso-pentane and n-hexane also form RO radicals which produce one additional RO₂ radical before HO₂ is eventually formed.

Measured radicals as well as precursors and oxidation products are compared with results from a zero-dimensional box model using the Master Chemical

Mechanism (MCM v3.3.1) which is complemented by recent structure-activity relationships (SAR). When including recent SAR, an improved model-measurement agreement of HO₂ and RO₂ radical concentrations was specifically found for n-hexane and trans-2-hexene.

In addition, the O_x (= NO₂ + O₃) formation per oxidised VOC (P(O_x)_{VOC}) was determined for propane, iso-pentane, and trans-2-hexene. This was derived from modelled radical concentrations and compared with the P(O_x)_{VOC}, derived from measured O_x and also from measured radical concentrations for NO < 1 ppbv (Fig. 1). For both groups of VOCs, forming either HO₂ or RO₂ in the unimolecular reaction of first-generation RO radicals, a good agreement was found for P(O_x)_{VOC}, derived from modelled radical concentrations and from measured O_x concentrations for NO < 1 ppbv and 3 < NO < 5 ppbv.

Figure 1. O_x production per oxidised VOC for NO < 1 ppbv. It is distinguished between average values of propane and trans-2-hexene, which form RO radicals which immediately produce HO₂, and iso-pentane, forming RO radicals which also produce one additional RO₂ before HO₂ is eventually produced.

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Simulation chamber study of the spectral optical properties of Secondary Organic Aerosol produced by the photooxidation of Naphthalene under atmospherically-relevant conditions

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Keywords: Secondary organic aerosols (SOA), Brown carbon, photooxidation of naphthalene, NO_x, spectral optical properties, aerosol light absorption

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Light-absorbing organic aerosols, commonly referred to as “brown carbon” (BrC), have important climate effects (Laskin et al., 2015; Moise et al., 2015; Andreae and Gelencsér, 2006). BrC has been observed in secondary organic aerosol (SOA) from the oxidation of VOC precursors, including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) which are usually associated with combustion emissions (Zhang et al., 2012). Among the PAHs, naphthalene is one of the most abundant gas-phase species and an effective precursor for SOA aerosols (Liu et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2016). The naph-SOA has been identified to have a significant impact on the radiative transfer of UV-Visible radiation and its light absorption to be affected by NO_x level (Klodt et al., 2023; Simens et al., 2022; Lambe et al., 2013). Additionally, the mixing of anthropogenic or biogenic precursors can influence the absorption capability of the formed aerosols but to our knowledge, there are no data in literature reporting the influence of VOC-mixing on naph-SOA. In this study, we investigate the spectral optical properties of naph-SOA, including the absorption Ångström exponent (AAE), mass absorption cross section (MAC), single scattering albedo (SSA) and complex refractive index (CRI), based on simulation chamber experiments in the large CESAM chamber (4.2 m³). The naph-SOA were generated from the OH photo-oxidation of naphthalene under atmospherically relevant conditions, i.e. relative humidity of 30 to 40%, and in the presence of ammonium sulfate seeds. Experiments in presence/absence of NO_x

and different naphthalene/NO_x ratios were examined to address the effects of NO_x on naph-SOA properties. Also, an anthropogenic VOC (toluene) and a biogenic one (limonene) were mixed with naphthalene to investigate the effect of mixing VOCs on the properties of the generated aerosols. The optical properties of naph-SOA generated under low- and high-NO_x conditions and under different VOC mixtures will be presented and discussed.

Figure 1: A graphical abstract for this research work

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Cloud properties in Southeast of Spain: a 6-year statistical study using ACTRIS-CCRES remote sensing measurements

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Cloud radiative forcing and its climate feedback has a pivotal role to grasp climate change. However, they still have the greatest uncertainty compared to the other atmospheric processes. This is partially due to the complexity of the cloud-aerosol indirect effects, and the lack of cloud measurements on global scale. In this framework, this study contributes with a 6-year statistical study on cloud coverage and its properties in the ACTRIS-CCRES AGORA observatory (Granada, 37°2'N, 3°6'W, 680 m), using a synergistic combination of ground-based remote sensing instruments. This station, equipped with a microwave radiometer (RPG-HATPRO), a ceilometer (CHM15k) and a cloud radar (RPG-FMCW 94 GHz Cloud Doppler Radar), is continuously operated since 2018.

Here, the analysis covers the 2018–2023 database processed by CloudnetPy (Illingworth *et al* 2007), using target classification, liquid water path (LWP) and ice water path (IWP) variables. Target classification is used to classify single cloud layers (i.e., only one cloud layer in the whole atmospheric column), according to Pîrloagă *et al* (2022), in the following groups: liquid, ice, mixed phase (ice-liquid), liquid with precipitation (Pre-Liquid) and mixed phase with precipitation (Pre-Mixed-Phase). Multiple layers in the atmospheric column were excluded from analysis to avoid misclassification due to errors in LWP partitioning.

The cloud occurrence frequency for different cloud types in 2020 is shown in Figure 1, with gray bars representing the absence of clouds. A seasonal pattern is identified, where summer (Jun-Aug) shows less than 13% of total cloud occurrence and an absence of precipitation. On the contrary, cloud occurrence in winter (Dec-Feb) and spring (Mar-May) increases up to 47% and 60%, respectively. Also, mixed phase clouds are dominant, with liquid clouds generally below 10%. Precipitation is exclusively associated with mixed phase clouds.

Regarding six years worth database, Ice and mixed-phase clouds mean geometric thicknesses across the seasons are 1.2 ± 1.3 km and 2.0 ± 1.6 km, respectively, contrasting with the 0.2 ± 0.2 km observed in liquid clouds. Their monthly thickness

variability is wide enough to hide seasonal differences. Same analysis for cloud base height shows mean values of 1.9 ± 2.0 km (excluding summer), 4.8 ± 2.2 and 7.0 ± 2.4 km for liquid, mixed phase and ice clouds, respectively.

Figure 1. Monthly time evolution of cloud frequency for 2020.

To conclude, this is the first study tackling cloud properties in Southeast of Spain, in a region marked by its sensibility to climate changes.

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Refractory Black Carbon Measurements from Mace Head *versus* the Southern Ocean

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Keywords: black carbon, Mace Head, Southern Ocean.

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Black carbon (soot) is a product of incomplete combustion that is universal in anthropogenic pollution and hence often used as a tracer for polluted or continentally influenced air. Over oceans, most measured black carbon is a result of continental outflow with long-range sources (e.g. from forest fire or fossil fuel emissions) or has a local origin (e.g. ship emissions).

Here we take a look at refractory black carbon (BC) measurements made by a single-particle soot photometer (SP2) at one-minute temporal resolution. The submicron aerosol organic matter (OM) was also measured at high time resolution. The same instrument was deployed in the Southern Ocean (PEGASO Cruise, January 2nd – February 12th 2015) and at Mace Head (MHD) Atmospheric Research Station (April 2nd – 20th 2015). MHD is a Northeast Atlantic coastal Global Atmospheric Watch (GAW) station (located 53.3253°N, 9.9044°W) in Ireland, with prevailing winds that advect over the North Atlantic Ocean for several days (marine sector wind direction filter: 190-300°). Due to the different expected levels of anthropogenic influence in each location, the Southern Ocean considered as having low influence, and a coastal station in the Northern Hemisphere with higher influence, the two measurements make for an interesting comparison.

The BC mass concentrations ranged largely from 0–1000 ng m⁻³ and was analysed in terms of frequency-of-occurrence (Figure 1). The fitted lognormal distribution modes are mathematical representations of BC mixing and subsequent dilutions in the atmosphere (Limpert *et al*, 2001). Thus, the lower concentration modes in the frequency-of-occurrence distribution should represent the BC ubiquitous to the clean marine background, or natural marine aerosol. Both frequency distributions from MHD and the Southern Ocean were fitted by a series of eight lognormal distribution modes. The Southern Ocean had four modes with BC concentrations <0.1 ng m⁻³, while MHD had only one mode (Figure 1). Both frequency distributions had similar peak BC modes ~270 ng m⁻³.

Figure 1 shows that both oceans have low background concentrations of BC, although this occurs more often in the Southern Ocean. While the Southern Ocean had pristine conditions more frequently, there were still significant occurrences of pollution, so measurements in both environments must undergo

filtering to isolate natural marine aerosol and its properties. Since BC is only a tracer for anthropogenic or continental influence, the addition of regression and correlation analysis of OM against BC can help distinguish natural marine air from anthropogenic or continentally influenced air. When there is a significant correlation between the two species (OM and BC) then the sources of the aerosol may be considered linked, and the aerosol having a significant anthropogenic or continental influence. The concentration of BC that amounts to being a threshold for this influence can differ significantly in different regions.

Figure 1. Frequency distribution plots of BC dataset from the SP2 instrument. Frequency of occurrence (left axis # and right axis %) are shown against BC mass concentrations in black for log space bins. Fitted lognormal modes are in red. (a) Southern Ocean and (b) MHD marine air.

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Characterisation of heterogeneous ice nucleation with in situ measurement, and study on its impact in deep convective cloud system using a 3D bin microphysics model

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Keywords: INP, in situ, bin model.

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INPs (Ice Nucleating Particles) are responsible for initiating the formation of ice crystals within clouds at temperatures above -35°C . Their concentrations in the atmosphere varies widely depending on the considered air masses. Thus, INP are presumed to play a crucial role in influencing cloud properties, particularly in mixed-phase clouds. In this work, we analyzed their impact on a deep convective cloud system.

The characterization of heterogeneous ice nucleation was conducted through in situ measurements of INP concentrations at the Puy de Dome station in France using Portable Ice Nucleation Experiment instrument (PINE), a new-generation ice nucleation chamber (Möhler et al. 2021). The analysis of back trajectories throughout the entire campaign allows us to identify INP concentration as a function of the sampled air mass origin (fig. 1).

Figure 1. INP concentration measured at -32°C at the PUY station depending on the air mass origin determined by back trajectories analysis (data averaged over a 0.5° grid).

Results, conclusion and perspectives

By applying a multi-parameter based classification (origin, physical properties) on the sampled air masses, we generated a set of parameterizations that make it possible to represent the high variability of the INP concentrations measured during the campaign (fig. 2). The obtained values and the classification regarding the different airmass types is consistent with what can be found in the literature (Kanji et al., 2017)

Figure 2. INP concentration predicted by the newly developed parametrizations for four different classes of air mass.

These parametrizations were then implemented in a 3D bin microphysics model (Flossmann and Wobrock, 2010) to simulate an idealized case of a deep convective cloud system. The results show that heterogeneous ice nucleation has a significant effect on ice phase initiation during the early stages of cloud development at lower levels ($<10\text{ km}$). Nevertheless, the results did not indicate a significant gap in cloud properties (ice water content, precipitation rates, etc.) between the different cases, as the cloud developed.

As perspectives for this work, we plan to simulate real cases of deep convective systems and other types of clouds (shallow convective, stratiform, etc.). Also, we will measure INP concentrations for samples taken from background sites to expand the diversity of air masses measured and to develop parametrizations for more specific environments.

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Determination of temperature dependent rate coefficients of the reaction of hydroxyl radicals with volatile organic compounds using a new OH reactivity instrument

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Keywords: Atmospheric chemistry, Kinetic study, Gas-phase degradation of organic compounds.

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Accurate knowledge of the rate coefficient of the reaction of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) with the hydroxyl radical (OH) is fundamental for understanding atmospheric chemical processes and for predictions of air quality forecasting models. Nevertheless, the temperature dependence of reaction rates of many organic compounds is not well investigated as measurements are challenging.

In this work, we present absolute measurements of reactions rates with the OH radical for a series of VOCs for different temperatures. An OH reactivity instrument previously used for field and chamber measurements was further developed to enable these accurate measurements of reaction rates. The OH reactivity (k_{OH}) is the inverse lifetime of the OH radical expressed by the product of the OH reactant concentrations and its reaction coefficient with OH. In this instrument, OH reactivity is measured by the direct observation of the decay rate of OH that is produced in a flow tube by ozone laser flash photolysis at 266 nm. The decay of OH radicals is measured at a high time resolution of 1 ms. If a known concentration of an organic compound is added to the bath gas (humidified synthetic air) the decay time directly gives the rate coefficient. As the air temperature can be controlled, the Arrhenius expression of the rate coefficient can be determined.

VOC mixtures in synthetic air were prepared in canisters. The concentration was determined by the total organic carbon method, in which all carbon atoms are combusted to CO₂ on heated catalysts and the CO₂ concentration is measured by a commercial cavity ring-down instrument.

The method was validated with several alkanes for which reaction rates are well-known (Fig. 1). Excellent agreement within a few percent with recommendations by IUPAC and NASA-JPL demonstrates the high accuracy of the new method. The Arrhenius expression of OH reaction rates was determined for several monoterpenes and aromatic hydrocarbons.

This new method, which requires a comparably low experimental effort, enables measurements at atmospheric conditions with respect to pressure and bath gas. It will be used for the measurements of the temperature dependence of reaction rates required for the interpretation of data collected from observational as well as exploratory facilities within ACTRIS. In addition,

reaction rates can be implemented in models to improve the accuracy of air quality predictions.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of the rate coefficient of the reaction of methane with OH demonstrating excellent agreement of recommended values with the absolute rate measurements using an OH reactivity instrument in this work.

Iron mediated changes in α -pinene secondary organic aerosol composition

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Keywords: aerosol aging, α -pinene, secondary organic aerosol, mineral dust, photochemistry
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Atmospheric aerosols play a key role for air pollution, health and climate. Secondary organic aerosol (SOA) makes up the majority of submicron atmospheric aerosol particles by mass, (depending on location and season; Jimenez *et al*, 2009). In the atmosphere, SOA often become internally mixed with other particles such as salts in the form of secondary inorganic aerosol, mineral dust or particles emitted from combustion and industrial processes. When these particles contain transition metals, such as iron, they can initiate aging processes that can alter physical and chemical SOA properties (Al-Abadleh, 2021). Furthermore, when SOA components mix with metal containing particles, they facilitate dissolution of minerals and form iron-organic complexes (Deguillaume *et al*, 2005). Such iron-organic complexes are common in atmospheric particles (Tapparo *et al*, 2020). They can further generate reactive oxygen species within the condensed phase through dark peroxide and photochemical reactions, i.e., Fenton chemistry. This leads to further aging of the SOA material by functionalization or fragmentation of organic species (Deguillaume *et al*, 2005 and Daumit *et al*, 2016). The exact reaction pathways and resulting particle properties depend on the chemical structure and functional groups of the aerosol components. Given the chemical complexity of atmospheric organic aerosols, a detailed understanding of these condensed phase aging processes is lacking to date. Thus, considerable uncertainties still exist regarding the impact aged particles have on air quality, health and climate.

Here, we present detailed information on the chemical composition of iron-containing SOA particles and how it evolves over time. Particles were produced by forming SOA via α -pinene (C₁₀H₁₆) ozonolysis on both ammonium sulfate or iron-containing seed particles in an atmospheric simulation chamber under dark conditions. This allowed us to probe the impact of dark e.g., peroxide, reactions on aerosol aging. Additionally, the impact of photochemical aging was studied by irradiating the formed SOA+seed particles with UV-light. To capture the atmospheric variability in humidity, experiments were conducted under both high relative humidity (RH; >80%) and low RH (<10%) conditions. Aerosol bulk composition was determined using extractive electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, allowing for high chemical and temporal identification of oxidation products, i.e., monomers and dimers.

Under low RH conditions, particles (both with and without iron) were found to contain a higher fraction of monomers, compared to dimers. Monomers (e.g., C8 to

C10 species) are degradation products formed from the oxidation of α -pinene, whereas dimers (e.g., C18 to C20 species) are formed via the subsequent reaction of monomers. In contrast, under high RH conditions the monomer/dimer ratio was smaller when iron was present. This suggests that iron-catalyzed functionalization reactions are favoured under high RH conditions. Furthermore, when iron was present in the seed particles the lifetimes of monomers and dimers varied greatly, where the signal for some organic species (e.g., C19s and C20s) was observed to decrease rapidly ($t_{1/2} \sim 25$ min.) following SOA formation under high RH conditions, while only slow decay was observed under low RH conditions ($t_{1/2} \sim 110$ min.). This suggests that iron-catalyzed reactions are limited by diffusion of organic molecules under low RH conditions. Furthermore, the monomer/dimer ratio varied following photolysis of particles, emphasizing that both dark and photochemically induced Fenton reactions play a unique role in aerosol aging.

Overall, our results elucidate the key role of iron in altering the chemical composition of SOA particles during atmospheric transport. Such aging effects are also expected for other transition metals and need to be considered when predicting the role of SOA for air pollution and climate in chemistry-climate models.

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Study of radiative properties and forcings of high-altitude cirrus clouds in Barcelona, Spain with 4 years of lidar measurements

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Keywords: cirrus clouds, radiative forcings, ARTDECO

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Aerosol-radiation and aerosol-cloud interactions still drive large uncertainties in weather and climate models. In particular, high-altitude cirrus clouds play a fundamental role in the global radiation budget (Liou, 1986; Lolli et al., 2017). They were identified as poorly understood by (IPCC, 2021) because of a lack of knowledge of their dynamic, microphysical and radiative properties. Indeed, cirrus cloud critical role in the climate comes from the fact that 1) they are the only cloud that can readily cool or warm the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) and the surface, during daytime (Campbell et al., 2016) and 2) they have a high occurrence frequency globally (Holz et al., 2008). In this context, a study of radiative properties and forcings of cirrus clouds based on 4 years of continuous lidar measurements in Barcelona is analysed.

First, a new approach of a self-consistent scattering model for cirrus clouds is presented to get the radiative properties for cirrus clouds at different wavelengths with only the particle extinction coefficient and cloud temperature. Applying this method to cirrus clouds measured in Barcelona during November 2018 to September 2022 at 00 and 12 UTC, the average of the cloud-integrated ice water content is $4.97 \pm 5.53 \text{ mg/m}^3$, the single scattering albedo is 0.99 ± 0.05 and the asymmetry factor is 0.76 ± 0.00 at $0.55 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Second, the radiative forcings of cirrus clouds have been calculated with the ARTDECO radiative transfer model. Aerosols found in the lower atmospheric layer have been considered in this study to make the simulations as realistic as possible.

Third, shortwave downward radiative fluxes at the surface have been validated with a pyranometer of the SolRad-Net network and the longwave upward radiative fluxes at TOA have been validated with data from CERES satellite.

Fourth, radiative forcings have been calculated for cirrus clouds discerning between nighttime and daytime. At nighttime, cirrus clouds warm the atmosphere with and, as expected, thicker clouds produce higher forcings. At daytime, cirrus clouds generally cool the surface and warm the TOA.

Fifth, the variation of the radiative forcing of the cirrus clouds at daytime has been analysed as a function of the solar zenith angle. The results show that at TOA the radiative effect changes from warming to cooling around a solar zenith angle of 60° and at the surface the cirrus clouds generally cool the atmosphere for all solar zenith angles.

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Characterization of ultrafine particles at a rural site in Switzerland

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Keywords: aerosol growth, airport emissions, particle sources, new particle formation, black carbon

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Atmospheric aerosol particles are known for their adverse effects on human health and Earth's climate. Among those, a class, namely ultrafine particles (UFPs), is critical given the particles' high number concentrations in the atmosphere and their capability to travel deep into the human body and to deposit onto sensitive body parts e.g. brain and heart (Schraufnagel, 2020). Therefore, scientists dedicated a large fraction of research to advance the understanding of the chemical composition, source and sinks of UFPs.

UFPs are found to be more abundant close to source area, e.g. traffic and industry compared to more remote locations subject to limited anthropogenic activity. However, UFPs can also form in the atmosphere from gaseous precursors via a secondary process known as new particle formation (NPF).

Studies conducted in Switzerland have highlighted the presence of UFPs in urban areas, with transportation-related emissions being a significant primary source (Hussein et al., 2006). Additionally, Switzerland's proximity to various industrial regions in Europe underscores the role of transboundary pollution in contributing to UFP levels (Weber et al., 2018).

In this study, we will delve deeper into the outdoor sources of UFPs observed in Payerne, an ACTRIS (The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) and NABEL (National Air Pollution Monitoring Network) site at a typical rural location in Switzerland. We aim to quantify the primary and secondary fractions of UFPs.

Our results show comparable UFP levels throughout the year. Besides traffic (visible in Fig. 1 during rush hours) and residential heating, we explore the roles of airport emissions and long-range transport of black carbon aerosols from forest fires in increasing UFP concentrations. Besides primary emissions, we observe local NPF events evident from the increase in cluster ions and nucleation mode particles concentrations, especially in spring and summer (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). In this work, we further explore the contributions of ammonia and amines from agriculture in enhancing NPF rates in Payerne.

Figure 1. Hourly average seasonal variations of ultrafine, nucleation mode and Aitken mode particles and cluster ions (positive) in Payerne.

Figure 2. Particle (upper) and ion (bottom) number size distributions on April 11, 2021 in Payerne.

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15 years of fog life cycle investigations based on cloud remote sensing measurements and modelling at the SIRTA Atmospheric Observatory

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Keywords: cloud remote sensing, fog macrophysics, fog microphysics.

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While considerable progress has been made in numerical weather prediction in recent years, time of onset and dissipation, as well as the exact location of fog events remain difficult to predict. In the past 15 years, three national and international field campaigns have been conducted at the SIRTA atmospheric observatory to advance our understanding on processes that affect fog life cycle (Haeffelin et al. 2010). These campaigns showed in particular the added value of cloud remote sensing techniques such as Doppler cloud radar and backscatter lidar to document the temporal evolution of fog vertical structure and vertical profiles of fog microphysics (Dupont et al. 2012).

In this presentation, we will review how clouds above fog layers affect radiative cooling at fog top, which is the largest production term of fog liquid water content (Wærsted et al. 2017), and how temperature inversions at fog top affects the fog dissipation time (Wærsted et al. 2019) based on measurements and simulations (radiative transfer and LES). We will present a fog conceptual model that allows us to derive fog fog adiabaticity (stable vs adiabatic fog) and evaluate if the fog liquid water path is critically low (Toledo et al., 2021). We will present a novel analysis method of fog life cycle (Dione et al. 2023) applied to ten years (2013-2022, 100 fog events) of measurements of fog liquid water path, fog top height, temperature, lidar backscatter, radar reflectivity and turbulence profiles, and fog adiabaticity, at the SIRTA observatory. Fig. 1 presents one case study illustrating twenty different variables derived from collocated Doppler Cloud radar, Doppler Wind Lidar, Microwave Radiometer, Backscatter Lidar, visibility meter, sonic anemometer and standard weather station measurements combined with our conceptual model.

The analysis allows us to characterize the conditions of fog formation (particle activation in radiation fog, stratus to fog transitions; Ribaud et al. 2021), to distinguish between shallow stable fog and deep adiabatic fog, and to explain the conditions that lead to transition from stable to adiabatic fog (in general due to increase in turbulence in the fog layer).

This multi-parameter analysis provides an in-depth understanding of the fog dissipation phase, that can be

explained by reduced radiative cooling, enhanced mixing in the fog layer (mechanically or thermally induced turbulence), droplet deposition, or advection of warmer and dryer air, leading to subcritical fog liquid water content and fog base lifting.

We will discuss why it is useful to monitor processes at the top of the fog layer to anticipate what will happen at the base of the fog. We will also discuss how measurements analyzed in real time could support nowcasting of fog events.

Figure 1. Illustration of multi-parameter analysis of fog event on 23 Nov 2018 at SIRTA observatory.

Continuous cloud remote sensing at the SIRTA observatory has been supported by ACTRIS FP6 and ACTRIS-2 FP7 EU projects.

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How are newly formed particles impacting low-level Arctic clouds?

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Keywords: new particle formation, Arctic

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The secondary formation of particles in the atmosphere provides about half of the cloud condensation nuclei, as such the process of nucleation plays a significant role determining the aerosol effect on the climate. New particle formation (NPF) events have been studied at the ACTRIS mountain-site, Zeppelin, situated on the western edge of Svalbard. For the first time, a Neutral cluster and Air Ion Spectrometer (NAIS, Airel) has been used at the observatory to measure NPF events starting from 0.8 and 2nm for ions and particles respectively. In this study, the initial stages of a process with the potential to lead to CCN have been studied. Two years (2022-present) of measurements have now be processed and analysed.

Building on the work of Lee, H. et al., (2020) and Beck et al., (2021), here, we explore the links between dimethyl sulphate (DMS) and NPF events, and look into the CLAW hypothesis in the Arctic. Furthermore, we examine the role of NPF in relation to CCN, and the activation of these particles on site. At Zeppelin Observatory, given the range of instrumentation and the unique setup, we are able to explore aerosol processes and aerosol-cloud interactions from phytoplankton blooms and initial formation of particles, through to their respective growth and then the activation of CCN.

The two years of measurements are classified (see Fig. 1) and the formation, seasonality and coinciding environmental parameters behind the different respective classifications are explored. We also show the degree to which precipitation is required in preconditioning the atmosphere for NPF, as well as, the importance of solar irradiance in the appearance of NPF events at the site.

Our research is able to estimate the initial site at which nucleation occurs (see Fig. 2), by tracing the particle growth and initialising back trajectories that characterise the transport path of growing particles.

For at least one year, we are able to present NAIS collocated measurements at the surface and atop a mountain at 474 m asl, allowing for the exploration of

case studies in which the two measurement sites are decoupled from one another.

Figure 1. Classification of two years of Neutral cluster and Air Ion Spectrometer using the Dal Maso (2005) classification system.

Figure 2. Estimated site of nucleation for class Ia events

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The spectral mass absorption, scattering, and extinction cross-sections (MAC, MSC, MEC) of combustion aerosols and their evolution during ageing: a simulation chamber study

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Carbonaceous combustion aerosol particles, commonly referred to as soot, form during the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biofuels, and biomass. These soot particles are known to contain the light-absorbing carbon fractions of 'Black Carbon' (BC) and 'Brown Carbon' (BrC), which both scatter but more importantly absorb shortwave radiation of the solar spectrum. While BC is known to absorb relatively homogeneously over the ultraviolet and visible range of the spectrum, BrC is characterized by its strongly wavelength-dependent absorption. As part of anthropogenic emissions and based on their absorbing properties, they are considered to be the largest non-gaseous anthropogenic climate forcer (e.g. Ramanathan & Carmichael, 2008). The exact contribution of these particles is however an ongoing point of discussion due to large uncertainties in the parameterization of their spectral optical properties, like the mass absorption/ scattering/ extinction cross-sections (MAC/MS/MEC, in m^2g^{-1}). Reasons for these include significant uncertainties in the measurements of the optical properties and the mass fractions. But even more importantly in the variability of the spectral optical properties of the combustion particles due to the variable physico-chemical properties of the atmospheric aerosol like composition, size distribution, morphologies, mixing state and more which are dependent on (1) the combustion source and conditions as well as (2) changes during atmospheric lifetime like ageing and mixing processes.

This work presents the results of an experimental work on measuring the spectral optical properties of soot and their dependence on the physico-chemical state of the aerosol. The results were retrieved from a set of experiments performed using the 4.2 m^3 atmospheric simulation chamber CESAM (<https://cesam.cnrs.fr/>) and soot aerosol generated using a commercial propane diffusion flame soot generator (miniCAST model 6204 TYPE C, JING). In order to measure physico-chemical properties (mass concentration, size distribution, effective density, particle morphology, refractory, and non-refractory composition) and the spectral optical

properties (absorption, scattering, extinction coefficients) of the soot a range of state-of-the-art techniques were utilized. The optical properties and absorption, in particular, were measured by combining indirect (extinction minus scattering techniques) with filter-based absorption measurements utilizing a combination of online and offline techniques including multiple cavity attenuated phase shift (CAPS)-monitors, a nephelometer, an aethalometer, a Multi Angle Absorption Photometer (MAAP), a Multi-Wavelength Absorbance Analyzer (MWAA), and a Polar Photometer from the University of Milano (PP_UniMi).

In order to characterize the dependency in the optical and physico-chemical state, these techniques were used to monitor the properties of soots with varying chemical compositions, size distributions, and mixing states. Composition and size distribution were varied by generating soot under different combustion conditions covering both fuel-lean and fuel-rich conditions which generated ultimately five different soot aerosols with varying EC/TC-ratios ranging from 0.8 ± 0.1 to 0.0 ± 0.1 and size distributions with median diameters between 70 and 120 nm. A selected soot was further subjected to simulated atmospheric ageing including exposure to humidity, radiation, and additional gaseous phases (O_3 , SO_2). A key focus of this study was set on determining and characterizing potential enhancement of absorption due to the formation of a coating by a second scattering aerosol phase produced via the photo-oxidation of SO_2 or the ozonolysis of α -pinene.

The MAC, MSC and MEC datasets retrieved from the chamber experiments and the variability of these parameters in link with variations of the particles' physico-chemical properties in particular composition and coating will be presented together with their key uncertainties.

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Instrumental Upgrades Towards a Better Understanding of Particle Wall Loss in the AURA Atmospheric Simulation Chamber

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Simulation chambers are widely used to investigate atmospheric processes e.g. chemical reactions interacting with atmospheric aerosols or forming new aerosol particles. One experimental challenge arising from the use of atmospheric simulation chambers is the loss of gases and particles to the walls of the simulation chamber. While the atmosphere is not enclosed by walls, the losses observed in atmospheric simulation chambers experiments may change the atmospheric implications if not accounted for.

Particle wall loss in atmospheric simulation chambers depends strongly on particle properties as size, mass, and charge. However, the properties of the simulation chamber such as surface area, volume, local electric fields are also important for the particle wall loss (e.g. Crump and Seinfeld, 1981, McMurry and Rader, 1985, Mahfouz and Donahue 2020).

Here we present developments and upgrades to the Aarhus University Research on Aerosol (AURA) atmospheric simulation chamber (Kristensen et al., 2017). The goal was to provide improved comparison between measured particle wall loss rates and numerical models. A set of mixing fans was installed to ensure that the interior of the chamber is sufficiently mixed. A method was developed to be able to measure the volume of the AURA simulation chamber and how it changes during experiments. This was done using two laser distance sensors to measure the expansion and retraction of the chamber walls. Combined with a calibration of the absolute volume, this yielded a parametrization of the volume as a function of measured distance from the sensors to the chamber wall.

An electric field meter was for the first time used to measure the electric field inside an atmospheric simulation chamber. The magnitude of the electric field was controlled using ion fans (Jorga et al., 2020) to discharge the walls of the simulation chamber.

The wall loss rate of ammonium sulfate particles in the size range of 10-350 nm was experimentally determined for different conditions inside the AURA simulation chamber including increased turbulence from the mixing fans and electric field strengths at different orders of magnitude.

The experimentally determined wall loss rates of particles were compared to theoretic calculations based on the theory of McMurry and Rader (McMurry and Rader, 1985). At low electric field strengths, the experimentally derived particle wall loss rates were captured by the theoretical model. However, at high electric field strengths, the theory fails to represent the measured data, possibly due to increased significance of the spatial movement of the particles currently not included in the theoretical model.

Figure 1. Experimentally derived particle wall loss rates as a function of particle size at three different conditions in the AURA atmospheric simulation chamber.

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Using the *Virga Sniffer* tool to identify precipitation evaporation in trade wind clouds

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The dominant cloud type in the subtropical Atlantic is the trade wind cumulus with a cloud base located near the lifting condensation level (LCL) below 1 km. Other common clouds in this region with their base above 1 km are stratiform cloud layers or cloud edges near the trade wind inversion at 2–3 km. Precipitation in all these clouds mainly forms at temperatures above freezing point by collision and coalescence. Therefore, precipitation generally occurs as light rain/drizzle from stratiform cloud layers or as showers from well-developed trade wind cumuli. Precipitation underneath a cloud base is often visible as fall streaks. If the precipitation evaporates before reaching the ground, these fall streaks are called virga.

Combined continuous long-term ground-based remote-sensing observations with vertically pointing cloud radar and ceilometer are well-suited to identify these precipitation evaporation fall streaks. Here, we show the first application of our new open-source tool, the *Virga-Sniffer* (Kalesse-Los and Witthuhn *et al*, 2023), which was developed within the frame of RV Meteor observations during the EUCLIDating the RoIE of Cloud–Circulation Coupling in ClimAte (EUREC⁴A; Stevens *et al* (2021)) field experiment in Jan–Feb 2020 in the Tropical Western Atlantic. The *Virga-Sniffer* Python package is highly modular and configurable and can be applied to multilayer cloud situations. In the simplest approach, it detects virga from time-height fields of cloud radar reflectivity and time series of ceilometer cloud base height. Optional parameters like lifting condensation level, a surface rain flag, and time–height fields of cloud radar mean Doppler velocity can be added to refine virga event identifications.

The *Virga Sniffer* was applied to RV Meteor observations during EUREC⁴A and statistical results as well as an evaporation case study will be presented. About 42 % of all detected clouds with bases below the trade inversion (i.e. warm clouds) were found to produce precipitation that fully evaporates before reaching the ground. A proportion of 56% of the detected warm-cloud virga originated from trade wind cumuli. These results substantiate the importance of complete low-level precipitation evaporation in the downstream winter trades. The *Virga-Sniffer* performance was assessed by comparing its results to the Cloudnet target classification (Illingworth *et al.*, 2007). A total of 86 % of pixels identified as virga correspond to Cloudnet target classifications of precipitation. The remaining 14 % correspond to Cloudnet target classifications of aerosols and insects (about 10 %), cloud droplets (about 2 %), or

clear sky (2 %). Cloudnet mostly classified aerosols and insects at virga edges, which points to a misclassification caused by Cloudnet internal thresholds.

Spectral W-band radar data from a fall streak observed on Jan 25, 2020, identified as virga by the *Virga-Sniffer*, was used to calculate evaporative cooling rates as done in Tridon *et al* (2017). Sensitivity studies were performed to investigate the influence of vertical wind and relative humidity uncertainties on cooling rate retrievals.

Future applications of the *Virga-Sniffer* include studies on distinguishing moist processes based on water vapor isotopic observations, contrasting precipitation evaporation climatologies in the dry and wet season in the trade cloud regime and characterizing snow sublimation in the polar regions.

Figure 1. Radar reflectivity and virga sniffer results for Jan 25, 2020 based on RV Meteor observations

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Cloud types and geometrical properties above the Mediterranean using decadal dataset

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Earth's climate system and weather are affected by clouds, which play an indispensable role in modulating the global radiative budget. Uncertainties attached to cloud properties lead to uncertainty in climate projections. Thus, monitoring the vertical structure of clouds is crucial (Stephens, 2018). In this work, we utilize space-based radar mask products from the CloudSat mission (Sassen, 2008) to provide statistics on the cloud properties observed above the Mediterranean region (Med herein) during 2007 – 2017. Three domains are selected as shown in Fig.1. and the statistics are provided in Fig. 2 per month (left column) and per height (right column).

Figure 1. Cloudsat domains used above West, Central, and East Mediterranean

The cloudiest months in the West, Central, and East Med, are February, November, and January respectively, while August presents the least cloud abundance overall (15 – 32%). Maximum cloudiness conditions are observed during the winter months above the West Med (77%), while minimum conditions are observed above the East Med during summer period (<25%). September and October are much less cloudy (<40%) above East Med than they are above West and Central Med (60 – 70%), in which the majority of the deep convective clouds (deep) are observed, indicating the effect of the Atlantic systems and the mid-latitude cyclones on the Med weather conditions.

Stratocumulus (Sc) dominate above the Med region especially during winter and spring periods, appearing mainly up to 4 km altitude. High clouds (high) prevail also during all months at altitudes higher than 9 km, except for July and August above the East Med, where they are almost absent. In the East Med, more cumulus (Cu) are observed during the summer period (<4

km), while altostratus (As) are almost absent, contrary to the rest of the region. Nimbostratus (Ns) are observed at all levels. Future work includes the comparison of the observed clouds with modeled cloud datasets in the Med.

Figure 2. Frequency of cloud types occurrence (left) per month, and (right) per height, for (top) West Med, (central) Central Med, (bottom) East Med, 2007 – 2017.

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Aerosol-cloud interactions in the Arctic studied at Zeppelin station, Svalbard

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The Arctic is particularly sensitive region with respect to global environmental change. It is warming significantly faster than rest of the globe. One of the key drivers of this process is cloudiness, where effects of sea ice melt, changes in atmospheric water vapor content, meteorology and aerosol physical and chemical properties, sources and sinks are combined.

Zeppelin station (474 MSL, 79 N, 14 E), part of the Ny Ålesund Research Station at Svalbard provides unique opportunity to study processes and changes in aerosol-cloud interaction on various temporal scales. It is also hosting ACTRIS-Sweden and ACTRIS-Norway. The

Comprehensive data sets of aerosol size distributions, cloud condensation nuclei, cloud residual properties and aerosol and cloud residual chemical composition available from Zeppelin station provide observational basis to study the aerosol-cloud interactions and how it changes during the year through the Arctic seasons: the Arctic Haze, summer and clean fall period.

We will present major findings what we have learned during last decade. These include 1) links between aerosol size distribution seasonal cycle and cloud condensational nuclei, 2) changes in CCN properties driven by microbial activity in surrounding ocean. 3) cloud residuals and their seasonal changes in microphysical and chemical properties 4) activation of newly formed aerosol particles into cloud droplets down to 20 nm in size, 5) partitioning of light absorbing aerosol between clouds and interstitial aerosol, 6) chemical

composition of activated and non-activated aerosol particles.

Figure 1. Counterflow Virtual Impactor (CVI) and whole air aerosol inlet on top of the Zeppelin station at Ny Ålesund

New particle formation upwind of the ATOLL field site in northern France

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New particle formation creates a large pool of newly formed particles around 1 nm diameter. In the favorable conditions of photochemical activity, meteorology, and available vapors for the formation, these can be growth-activated via condensation of precursor vapors to larger sizes. In cases, this growth can proceed even to cloud condensation nuclei sizes around 100 nm diameter, significantly affecting climate via cloud formation.

However, the particles which have grown to larger sizes are not formed at the field site, where they are measured with a particle number size distribution instrument (for example at ATOLL - ATmospheric Observations in Lille - field site, Figure 1). Instead they are formed a certain distance upwind of the field site. By using the knowledge of the condensation growth rate and tracing the origin of the air mass with back trajectories, it is possible to calculate over which area the 1 nm diameter particles were originally formed ("NanoMap", Kristensson et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Example of 2-D contour plot of particle number size distribution at ATOLL field site, April 24, 2021 during a new particle formation event clearly seen as enhanced particle levels above 10 000 cm⁻³.

Nanomap has been used at the ATOLL field site (Northern France, 50.6114 N, 3.1406 E, 60 m a.s.l.) to estimate the place of formation of 1 nm diameter particles for clear new particle formation events such as those in Figure 1 between 2017 and 2021. Low PM1 Single Scattering Albedo (SSA) values (0.75, Velazquez-Garcia et al., 2022) and large particle number concentrations (6140 cm⁻³) suggest that ATOLL is comparable to sites classified as urban (Laj et al., 2020; Rose et al., 2021). ATOLL is also part of the ACTRIS

network providing high-quality long-term atmospheric data in Northern France.

ATOLL NPF analysis (Crumeyrolle et al., 2023) highlighted a seasonal variation of NPF occurrences with a maximum frequency observed during spring (15%) and summer (18%). It was found that high temperature ($T > 295$ K), low Relative Humidity ($RH < 45$ %) and high solar radiation are ideal to observe NPF events over Lille.

NanoMap shows that the formation of 1 nm diameter particles rarely happens over the open, less polluted sea. Clear and strong events happen preferably over ship traffic routes. Like over the English channel and North Sea coast lines, possibly since these provide emissions of sulphur from ship traffic. They also quite frequently take place over polluted continental areas.

Figure 2. Place of formation of 1 nm diameter particles according to NanoMap using input from air mass back trajectories and size distribution data at ATOLL. X denotes, the location of ATOLL field site.

Relatively high Condensation Sink (CS) values (i.e., $\sim 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) are reported during event days suggesting that high CS does not inhibit the occurrence of NPF over ATOLL. Further analysis is planned to include weaker events. We encourage to use NanoMap also at other field sites to investigate the real area of formation of particles during new particle formation events.

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The aerosol chase

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If you measure the particle number size distribution at a fixed rural field site, it is virtually impossible to correctly apportion aerosol particles in certain sizes to their source place of original emissions. The particles have undergone changes in concentration, size, and chemistry during long-range transport, which leads to the difficulty of observing where they came from. This is one of our greatest conundrums in aerosol science.

However, this can be tackled by following the movement of the wind in the lowest aerosol layer of the atmosphere and measure particles and precursor gases in a mobile platform. In this way, one never loses sight of where particles were emitted, and can study how they are affected by aerosol processes. This can be called an “aerosol chase” in a Lagrangian framework.

Figure 1. Prognostic forward trajectory on May 24, 2021, Scania, Sweden, with designated measurement spots once each hour for the chase experiments.

In this pilot project, measurements of particle number size distribution, ozone, NO_x, CO₂, PM₁ mass levels were made with a road vehicle in southernmost Sweden. The instruments were operated with a battery and not the combustion engine of the vehicle to avoid self-contamination. To avoid isokinetic sampling issues, the measurements were performed during short stops with the vehicle. These stops were a few kilometres away from major emission sources, to avoid pollution peaks.

The first pilot chase took place on May 24, 2021, where the air was followed for hours along an air mass

path as decided by a prognostic trajectory (Figure 1, Draxler and Hess, 1997). Measurements were validated at the ACTRIS infrastructure station Hyltemossa, close to measurement spot no. 5.

Figure 2 shows the measured particle number size distribution along the planned route. It can be proven by the stability at each measurement spot and the gradual change of the size distribution that this first set of experiments was successful.

Figure 2. Measured particle number size distribution at designated stops no. 1 to 7 according to Figure 1 (each stop is encompassed by blue rectangles).

One particularly interesting observation on this day is the transformation of a marine boundary layer aerosol at measurement spot no. 1 with high Aitken mode aerosol concentration into a continental type of aerosol with more convective mixing further inland, when leaving measurement spot no. 1. Upon creation of a nocturnal layer towards evening, Aitken levels again increased.

These kinds of measurements could mean a paradigm shift in source apportionment and in process studies of aerosol particles if repeatedly applied at different environments.

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Using ACTRIS to advance our understanding of the climate effects of forests

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EU policies rely on forests to partly counteract global warming through for example the carbon dioxide uptake via photosynthesis and increased productivity in forests. However, in earth system and other models many interacting processes are neglected and the true extent of climate effects remains unknown. Emissions of greenhouse gases other than carbon dioxide, short-lived climate forcers (SLCF), biophysical effects from albedo changes and latent and sensible heat fluxes all affect climate (Figure 1). Research is not yet mature to consider all the different climate effects in a holistic manner.

Figure 1. Climate-relevant processes involving forest ecosystems.

The Horizon Europe CLIMB-FOREST (The CLimate Mitigation and Bioeconomy pathways for sustainable FORESTry) project attempts to tie up loose ends and provide a common platform for this holistic view. At first, CLIMB-FOREST will analyze the current level of understanding of the radiative forcing due to afforestation in Europe.

Other attempts to include climate effects in a holistic way are initiated also via modelling exercises like the CarbonSink+ model, which can account for albedo, SLCF, and carbon sequestration during afforestation or feedbacks in a changing climate (Kulmala et al., 2020). Although Earth System models (ESM) have the capacity to account for the variety of climate effects, land-

atmosphere interactions, feedbacks and coupled processes, this work has not yet been attempted in a dedicated effort.

Other platforms that can be utilized to help estimate climate effects of forests are the ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases InfraStructure) and ICOS (Integrated Carbon Observation System) research infrastructures. We will show examples of how co-located sites can offer the most complete, synergistic view on the complex processes within the same forest ecosystem.

It will be demonstrated that even in the absence of co-location, data from ACTRIS can be used for Earth-system or small-scale process model validation purposes. In addition, if there are towers available or other suitable infrastructures, ACTRIS sites can be exploited to perform forest emission and uptake measurements of aerosol and trace gases such as terpenoids to assess the role of forests in climate effects.

Unfortunately, there is a limited number of SLCF exchange sites available. Nevertheless, we will promote how one can summon forces for a dedicated action within the ACTRIS network to build up an infrastructure at least for a few selected sites, that can measure SLCF emissions and uptakes; especially if they are co-located with ICOS ecosystem stations.

With such infrastructures and model development, a holistic view on forest climate effects, and at a later stage, understanding of climate effects due to changes in forest management can be advanced. This provides a way to really understand how EU policies can be used to mitigate climate change via forestry.

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CIAO - CNR-IMAA Atmospheric Observatory: first in-situ measurements in conjunction with aerosol profiling

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Atmospheric aerosol particles represent a major environmental risk factor for human health and its study in the short- and long-term is of crucial importance to understand weather and the climate system.

At the Istituto di Metodologie per l'Analisi Ambientale of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-IMAA) the advanced atmospheric observatory, named CIAO (Madonna *et al.*, 2011), has recently been upgraded with the aerosol in-situ observational component, thus complementing the high-quality long-term remote sensing observations of aerosol gained over more than two decades of research activity.

CIAO is located in Tito Scalco, Potenza, Southern Italy (40.60° N, 15.72° E, 760 m asl) in a plain surrounded by low mountains (<1100 m asl), less than 150 km from the West, South and East coasts. It operates in a typical mountain weather strongly influenced by Mediterranean atmospheric circulation, resulting in generally dry, hot summers and cold winters. Due to its features, the site is particularly interesting for studying aerosol properties, especially those of natural origin such as desert dust (e.g. Mona *et al.*, 2014), volcanic aerosol (e.g. Pappalardo *et al.*, 2004, Mona *et al.*, 2012) and biomass burning (e.g. De Rosa *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1. Location of CIAO (CNR-IMAA Atmospheric Observatory).

The new aerosol in-situ facility at CIAO observatory, funded by the Italian project (PER-ACTRIS-IT) has been proposed as ACTRIS National Facility observational platform in November 2023 which allows the measurements of the obligatory ACTRIS aerosol in-situ variables: Particle number concentration > 10 nm; Particle number size distribution – mobility diameter 10

to 800 nm; Particle light scattering & backscattering coefficient; Particle light absorption coefficient and equivalent black carbon concentration and particle chemical - elemental composition. In situ measurements at the CIAO site, started from December 2023, in conjunction with aerosol profiling will allow to investigate aerosol characteristics at the ground for special cases like desert dust, volcanic eruption, biomass burning as identified by lidar measurements; to characterize the typical aerosol chemical and dimensional properties at CIAO, to enhance the aerosol typing methods developed by CIAO team, to better understand the processes of vertical transport of the particles to the surface.

The first measurements at CIAO observatory using the in-situ instruments in synergy with remote sensing instruments will be presented and discussed at the conference.

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Overview of results from the BIO-MAÏDO campaign (Réunion Island, Indian Ocean)

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The BIO-MAÏDO (Bio-physicochemistry of tropical clouds at Maïdo (Réunion Island): processes and impacts on secondary organic aerosols formation) campaign was conducted from the 13th of March to the 4th of April 2019 on the tropical Réunion Island (Leriche, 2023).

The campaign was part of the BIO-MAÏDO project with the main objective is to improve our understanding of cloud impacts on the formation of secondary organic aerosols (SOA) from biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC) precursors in a tropical environment.

Instruments were deployed at five sites along the slope of the Maïdo mountain to characterize the development of the boundary layer, the microphysical properties of clouds, the atmospheric composition of gases and particles and the bio-physico-chemical properties of cloud aqueous phase formed during moist oceanic air ascent. Four on-line devices were deployed during the campaign: three proton-transfer-reaction mass spectrometers (PTR-MS) for online analysis of VOCs, one of which was operated at high frequency and coupled to an ultrasonic anemometer allowed measurements of BVOCs fluxes, and an aerosol chemical speciation monitor (ACSM), which provides online measurements of the non-refractory submicron chemical composition (NR-PM1).

Dynamical analyses using back-trajectories showed two preferred trajectories routes for air masses arriving at MO during the daytime both corresponding to the return branches of the trade winds associated with the up-slopes thermal breezes, and both influenced by marine boundary layer and endemic forest below the Maïdo observatory (Rocco *et al*, 2022). Combining cover land footprint and backward trajectories, provided information on the nature of the ground-surface during the few days and hours before the air mass arrives at the sampling sites. This analysis showed that, during daytime, the major category contributions were the

ocean, the biogenic area (mixed forest) and the cultures area (Rocco *et al* 2022).

Chemical composition of particles during the daytime shows that organic aerosol is more oxidized at the highest site than at other sites along the slope. This is a signature of photochemical aerosols aging along the slope. During the second part of the campaign, cloud processing of aerosols was more likely as shown by a high concentration of oxalic acid in PM₁₀ during daytime at the highest site (Dominutti *et al* 2022b).

Chemical in depth analysis of cloud water revealed the presence of amino acids and, for the first time in cloud waters, of sugars that clearly indicated that biological activities contribute to the cloud water chemical composition. Despite an effort in analysis of organic compounds in cloud water, around 80% on average of dissolved organic compounds was undefined (Dominutti *et al* 2022a). Three cloud water samples were analysed by FT-ICR MS (Fourier Transform – Ion Cyclotron Resonance Mass Spectrometry) for molecular characterization.

This work was supported by the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (grant no. ANR-18-CE01-0013). The deployment of the BIRA-IASB PTR-MS at the Maïdo observatory was supported by the Belgian Federal Science Policy Office (grant no. BR/175/A2/OCTAVE) with additional funding from Horizon 2020 (ACTRIS-2, grant no. 654109)

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Two-year observations of aerosol size distributions: investigating new particle formation at coastal and rural sites in the Netherlands

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Keywords: particle size distribution, new particle formation, long term observations.

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This study presents a comprehensive analysis of aerosol field observations over a two-year period, focusing on the dynamics of particle number size distribution (PNSD) in contrasting coastal and rural environments in the Netherlands. By integrating extensive observational data, we aim to illustrate the underlying mechanisms and environmental factors influencing aerosol behaviour, especially new particle formation (NPF) events in these distinct geographic settings.

The main methodology employed involved using two identical Mobility Particle Size Spectrometers (MPSS, TROPOS) at Cabauw and Lutjewad to measure PNSD from 8 to 800 nm. The data from Cabauw encompassed the entire period from 2021 to 2023, while observations at Lutjewad commenced in July 2021 and continued until March 2023. Cabauw, located in the central-western Netherlands, is a suitable location to study how NPF events are affected by anthropogenic pollutions. Lutjewad, located on the northern coast, experiences more natural NPF events, especially when the wind comes from the north.

Our results show that the average total particle number concentration at Cabauw was approximately twice as high as at Lutjewad ($6,782 \pm 4,021$ and $3,385 \pm 2,554 / \text{cm}^3$, respectively) during the time overlap period, primarily attributed to Ultrafine Particles (UFPs, $\text{PM}_{0.1}$). Wind rose analysis reveals a strong association between elevated UFPs levels and wind from the direction of Amsterdam airport and Rotterdam port area. The daily average concentrations of accumulation mode particles were comparable at both sites, a linear correlation was observed ($R^2 = 0.62$) for daily average data. This indicates that accumulation mode particles concentrations come primarily from regional pollutants rather than local events.

Figure 1 shows the monthly average PNSD in the day over two years for two sites. Both sites exhibit distinct seasonal variation trends, with nuclei mode particle concentrations peaking in summer and diminishing in winter. Furthermore, the occurrence of these nuclei mode particles in the day varied monthly, most likely aligning with sunlight intensity. Notably, two distinct NPF episodes in the morning and at noon were observed at Cabauw. Suppressed growth of morning particles often coincides with higher NO_x concentrations in the morning in agreement with findings by C. Yan et al. (2020). we will discuss the role of NO_x and other possible causes. In contrast in our presentation. Lutjewad often

experienced noon NPF events, which demonstrated a sustained growth in particle size until the following day.

We delve into an extensive analysis of PNSD clusters and NPF classes across two sites. The first results suggest that NPF events are typically associated with high solar radiation, lower relative humidity, higher temperature, higher SO_2 and O_3 , but lower NO_x . The growth of these newly formed particles often relies on stable diffusion radiation conditions, while frequent cloud occurrence impedes particle growth. Additionally, particle size growth is often accompanied by increased concentrations of organics, nitrate, and ammonium at both sites. We will offer a comprehensive comparison of NPF events at two sites and aim to contribute to the understanding of aerosol dynamics under varying environment conditions.

Figure 1: Comparative monthly average particle number size distributions in the day observed at two different sites: (a) Cabauw and (b) Lutjewad.

The infrastructure used in this project is from the Ruisdael Observatory, funded by the Dutch Science Foundation NWO (grant number 184.034.015).

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108.14 - BATCH experiments to study the formation yields of C₇H₈O isomers in the toluene-OH-reaction

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Keywords: Isomers, Photooxidation, Formation Yields, SPME-GC-MS, PTR-ToF-MS

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Toluene is one of the most abundant aromatic hydrocarbons in the atmosphere (Cabrera-Perez *et al*, 2016). Its main loss process is by reaction with OH radicals, either via addition of OH to the aromatic ring or via H abstraction from the methyl group. The addition pathway leads amongst others to the formation of ring-retaining *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-cresol isomers (Figure 1). Cresols are highly reactive and important for the secondary chemistry of the system. Consequently, they have been studied extensively, but their analysis has often been restrained to the sum signal (e.g. Zaytsev *et al*, 2019). Meanwhile, the abstraction pathway yields another less renowned isomer, benzyl alcohol. With the hydroxy group attached to the methyl group, benzyl alcohol differs from the cresols both structurally and chemically (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structures of the three cresol isomers and benzyl alcohol.

To better understand reaction mechanisms, the formation of specific secondary products, and the overall reactivity of the system, isomer-resolved studies are needed but so far scarce. Here, we aimed to better constrain the formation yields of the individual isomers under different conditions.

In the Bayreuth Atmospheric simulation CHambers (BATCH) Teflon chamber, we studied the formation of the cresols and benzyl alcohol from the reaction of toluene with OH radicals in a controlled setting. We focused on NO_x-free conditions at T = 298 ± 1 K, but also evaluated temperature variations between 278 and 308 K, and initial NO mixing ratios between 0 and 25 ppbv. We carefully evaluated and corrected for compound-specific wall losses, photolysis rates, and OH reaction rates in the chamber prior to calculating the formation yields.

The cresol isomers and benzyl alcohol were measured using two on-line analytical techniques. We used solid phase microextraction – gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (SPME-GC-MS) to resolve the

different isomers after silylation with *N*-trimethylsilyl-*N*-methyl trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA). Additionally, we used a proton-transfer-reaction – time-of-flight – mass spectrometer (PTR-ToF-MS) to monitor toluene and the sum of isomers on a high temporal resolution.

Both instruments were calibrated specifically for the on-line analysis by measuring standards that were injected into the BATCH Teflon chamber. For the PTR-ToF-MS, we used the relative distribution of the isomers as derived by the SPME-GC-MS in order to perform a weighted calibration which takes into account isomer-specific sensitivities and abundances. We observed that benzyl alcohol is insensitive at the protonated mass, and that the sensitivity is highest for *o*-cresol. Using the isomer-corrected calibration factor improved the agreement between the two instruments, which was within the measurement uncertainty.

Here, we present the temperature- and NO_x-dependent formation yields for the three cresols and benzyl alcohol. We show that the physical and chemical sinks within the chamber differ among the studied compounds, and that an isomer-specific correction of these losses is therefore needed to derive accurate formation yields. Knowledge of the isomeric distribution is not only essential for constraining the follow-up chemistry, but in this case also for the differentiation of the abstraction and addition channel in the primary chemistry of toluene. Additionally, evaluating the responsiveness of these yields towards changes in the ambient conditions allowed us to gain further insight into the chemistry of each of the isomers.

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Development and operation of AIDA cloud simulation chambers for atmospheric research

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Keywords: Atmosphere, ice, aerosol, cloud, simulation

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The proper formulation of primary ice formation processes by different atmospheric aerosol types is key to better assess their roles in cloud and precipitation formation, and thereby also to improve the representation of aerosol-cloud processes in weather and climate models. The AIDA (Aerosol Interaction and Dynamics in the Atmosphere) atmospheric simulation chamber at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) is in operation since more than 25 years for a wide range of trace gas, aerosol, cloud and climate research related experiment series. It is also used as an expansion-type cloud simulation chamber to investigate ice nucleation processes at simulated mixed-phase cloud and cirrus cloud conditions.

In 2022, the new expansion-type dynamic cloud simulation chamber AIDA_d came into operation at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). Its development and construction is based on AIDA, but AIDA_d has a double-chamber design (Figure 1), similar to the design of the dynamic cloud chambers of the Colorado State University (Demott and Rogers, 1990) and the Meteorological Research Institute in Tsukuba, Japan (Tajiri et al., 2013).

Figure 1.: Construction of the AIDA_d outer vacuum and inner, wall-cooled, cloud chamber.

The walls of the cloud chamber located inside a vacuum chamber can actively be cooled at constant rates up to 10 K min⁻¹ (equivalent to an updraft velocity of about 15 m s⁻¹ in the atmosphere) within the temperature range of +30°C to -55°C. This unique technical design enables the simulation and investigation of tropospheric cloud processes in a wide range of cooling rates and liquid condensation levels. The cloud chamber is made of five segments with independent temperature control. Therefore, the chamber can be operated at either isothermal or controlled temperature gradient conditions.

The performance of AIDA_d was demonstrated in series of test runs with cooling rates between 1 and 10 K min⁻¹ (Figure 2). In this contribution, results will be shown for the test runs as well as for first experiment series on homogeneous freezing of water droplets and the immersion freezing behaviour of mineral dust aerosols at simulated convective cloud conditions.

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Quantification of aerosol cloud interaction from a combined ceilometer and cloud radar dataset

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Keywords: aerosol remote sensing, aerosol cloud interaction.

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The Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution (JOYCE) provides a dataset of cloud radar and ceilometer measurements starting in the year 2012 (Löhnert et al., 2015). This study aimed to use these data to calculate aerosol cloud interaction (ACI) indices.

In a first step the attenuated backscatter coefficients of a Lufft CHM15k ceilometer were used to calculate the aerosol mass concentrations utilizing the calibration and processing of the European network E-Profile (Haeefe et al., 2016). From the processed Level 2 data, aerosol mass concentrations were then derived with the publicly available tool A-Profiles (Mortier, 2022).

For the same period, data of a Doppler cloud radar MIRA-36 (METEK GmbH Deutschland) at JOYCE were used to derive cloud droplet number concentrations and cloud droplet effective radii. For this cloud property retrieval, the algorithm of the ACTRIS Cloudnet project (Illingworth et al., 2007) was used, which contains an implementation of water cloud properties retrieval (Frisch et al., 2002).

Aerosol cloud interaction can be quantified by a set of indices describing the relation of cloud properties (number concentration and effective radius) to a proxy of the aerosol concentration (Feingold et al., 2001). A first implementation of these indices for ceilometer-based aerosol remote sensing was already demonstrated using the attenuated backscatter as a proxy for the aerosol concentration. (Sarna and Russchenberg, 2017).

In this study we calculate the ACI indices from the aerosol mass concentrations, derived with a ceilometer aerosol retrieval. The calculated indices are analysed as a function of different liquid water path (LWP) bins. This method is applied to a multiyear dataset of measurements from JOYCE. A detailed correlation analysis of cloud droplet number concentrations, cloud droplet effective radii and integrated aerosol concentrations will be presented. The approach can be transferred to all ACTRIS cloud remote sensing stations, emphasising the value of the quality controlled ACTRIS measurements for the understanding of aerosol cloud interactions.

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Exploring the relationship between isoprene concentration and air temperature at the National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice

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Keywords: isoprene, air temperature, VOCs

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Isoprene is one of the main representatives of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC). It plays a key role in the interaction between the biosphere and the atmosphere. Isoprene concentrations increase with higher temperatures until reaching a maximum at around 40 °C, after which emissions rapidly decrease (Guenther 1993). Isoprene is primarily produced by plants, through chemical processes, and is also found in the human body. Therefore, it has a significant impact on atmospheric chemistry and air quality (Sharkey 1996).

Isoprene concentrations and air temperature are measured at the National Atmospheric Košetice Observatory (NAOK) (49°34'24" N, 15°04'49" E, 534 m a.s.l., background station). Isoprene and other VOC concentrations (31 elements) are measured as part of the Czech Republic's participation in the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP) at the Libuš and Košetice stations (measurement results from the Libuš station are not part of this work) and under The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS RI). Air samples are taken according to the EMEP manual (EMEP 1996) using specially evacuated stainless steel canisters on Mondays and Thursdays each week at 12:00 UTC with a 10-minute interval. Samples are analysed using gas chromatography (GC). Samples from the transport canisters are pre-treated by cryogenic concentration before GC analysis (CHMI 2022). Air temperature is measured by an automatic HMP 155 sensor (Vaisala) located in the observatory area according to WMO regulations.

Table 1. Comparison between isoprene mean concentration and annual mean air temperature at NAOK.

Year	Isoprene conc. ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Air Temperature (°C)
1995	0.14	7.7
2022	0.37	9.3

Long-term measurement results show that the air temperature has increased by 1.1°C between the last two normal periods (1961–1990 = average air temperature 7.1 °C, 1991–2020 = average air temperature 8.2 °C). Concurrently, isoprene

concentrations have increased since the beginning of the measurements. Isoprene has been measured at the Košetice Observatory since 1995. In the first year of measurement, the average annual concentration was $0.14 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. In 2022, the average annual concentration of isoprene was $0.37 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. Isoprene concentration emerges as a distinctive VOC demonstrating an upward trajectory. This makes isoprene a notable exception among its counterparts. The annual mean of all VOC, excluding isoprene, over the period from 1995 to 2022 declined (Fig. 1.). This comparative analysis focuses on the unique behavior of isoprene within the broader spectrum of VOCs.

Figure 1. Average Isoprene concentrations compared to average Total VOC concentrations at NAOK, 1995–2022. Dashed lines indicate the linear trend of concentrations.

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Intense snowfall event over Munich observed with new ACTRIS multi-frequency, polarimetric, and Doppler spectral radar instrumentation

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Keywords: extreme snowfall event, radar remote sensing, ice microphysics
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Though the majority of global precipitation is generated via the ice phase, cloud and precipitation microphysics that lead to growth of precipitable particles are still not well understood. Modern cloud radar methods and especially a combination of: multi-frequency, polarimetry, Doppler spectra opens a new avenue to explore the fingerprints of these processes in unprecedented detail (von Terzi et al., 2022 and Kneifel and Moisseev 2020).

Very recently, the ACTRIS site at the Meteorological Institute at the Ludwig-Maximilians University (LMU) has been facilitated with a dual wavelength Doppler radar (KaMacs and WMacs) including W-Band polarimetry and full Doppler spectrum capabilities. Besides this highly sensitive radar measurements, the site is accommodated with Parsivel Disdrometer and a number of auxiliary in-situ and remote sensing instruments. In this contribution, we demonstrate the new observational capabilities by analysing a recent heavy snowfall event which produced 46 mm liquid equivalent snow accumulation (ca. 50 cm snow height) and unusually strong radar signatures:

During the snowfall event on the 1-2 Dec. 2023, we find a persistent “slow-down” of Mean Doppler Velocity (MDV) at around 4 km height (Fig. 1) which coincides with the dendritic growth region (-12..-15°C). Just above this layer, we find indications of new particle formation both in the Doppler spectra and in KDP values up to 4 °/km that persist down to the surface after 18 UTC (Fig. 2a). During this time, we also find negative ZDR (Fig. 2b) most likely caused by differential attenuation confirming the presence of a large amount of horizontally aligned ice plates. The dual-wavelength ratios are further in good agreement with the median volume size of particles measured at the ground by Parsivel.

The mass weighted mean diameter of snow aggregates ranges from 3 to 8 mm with mostly dominating around 6mm during the event. Hence, the strong indication that snow was mostly comprised by unrimed aggregates and process responsible behind it, is unraveled and will be discussed in detail in the upcoming conference.

Figure 1. Mean Doppler Velocity from kaMacs on 01 December 2023. Height is above ground.

Figure 2. (a) Differential reflectivity and (b) specific differential phase from WMacs on 01 December 2023. Height is above ground.

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Organic aerosol from an urban and suburban area of Paris during the summer 2022

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Keywords: chemical composition, secondary organic aerosol.

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Secondary organic aerosol (SOA) can be formed by the oxidation of volatile organic compounds (VOC) and can contribute up to 90% of the OA. However, its chemical composition is not well understood (Zhang *et al* 2007). This work aims to determine the contribution of different VOCs precursors to the atmospheric SOA by combining field measurements during the ACROSS (Atmospheric ChemistRy Of the Suburban foreSt) (Cantrell and Michoud, 2022) campaign and chamber experiments in CESAM (Multiphase Atmospheric Experimental Simulation Chamber) (Wang *et al* 2011).

Chamber experiments allow to retrieve the ratio between SOA generated from toluene photo-oxidation and its specific oxidation products (tracers). Field measurements allow to describe the chemical composition and quantify tracers' concentrations in the urban and sub-urban areas (Rambouillet forest) of Paris during the summer 2022. The filters collected were analyzed by thermal-optical method, Orbitrap, UPLC-QTOF-MS (Ultra-Performance-Liquid-Chromatography Time-of-Flight Mass-Spectrometry) and SFE-GC-MS (Supercritical fluid extraction gas chromatography and mass spectrometry).

Thermal-optical analyses show similar organic carbon concentrations for Paris and Rambouillet although their different environments, with mean values of 3.2 and 2.8 $\mu\text{gC}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. Orbitrap analyses show the abundance of compounds containing CHO and CHON and highlight the presence of organosulfur compounds at m/z 294 ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{NSO}_7$) and 216 ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_{12}\text{SO}_7$), probably associated to α -pinene and isoprene oxidation products. Aromaticity analysis by orbitrap (cf. Table 1) shows the important contribution of polyaromatic compounds for Paris (between 22 to 30 %) and Rambouillet (from 16 to 36 %).

Table 1. Aromaticity contribution of the organic species identified by Orbitrap analysis.

	Paris mean (max-min)		Rambouillet mean (max-min)	
	day (%)	night (%)	day (%)	night (%)
Non aromatics	41 (36-45)	40 (34-45)	39 (33-50)	36.6 (31-43.2)
Monoaromatic	33 (29-36)	31 (21-36)	34 (32-36)	37.0 (33.5-39.8)
Polyaromatic	26 (22-30)	29 (24-33)	27 (15-34)	26.5 (18.7-35.5)

Among the anthropogenic species identified with the UPLC-QTOF-MS, 2-methyl-4-nitrophenol and 2-nitrophenol were detected in Paris (0.25 and 1.33 ng/m^3) and Rambouillet (0.07 and 0.34 ng/m^3). The presence of nitro-phenol compounds and the contribution of aromatic compounds show the influence of the urban emissions in the forest area.

Finally, combining the tracer concentrations observed in the field and the chamber experiments, the SOA tracer method is applied to estimate the SOA from different VOC precursors (cf. figure 1). It is observed that nitro-aromatics (tracer 2-methyl-4-nitrophenol) can represent up to 36 % from the SOA in Paris. Further analyses of biogenic and anthropogenic SOA tracers are ongoing to improve the SOA description

Figure 1. Comparison of SOA composition for the urban area of Paris and the Rambouillet forest.

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Investigation of the reactivity of monoterpenes with NO₃ radicals in simulation chambers

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Keywords: nighttime chemistry, terpenes, simulation chamber, SOA

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Vegetation emits large amounts of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs) which represent ~90% of total non-methane VOCs emissions to the atmosphere. Terpenes are an important class of BVOCs which react rapidly with atmospheric oxidants (OH, NO₃, O₃) and significantly contribute to the formation of secondary organic aerosol (SOA) at the global scale. The NO₃ radical is a major oxidant of terpenes during nighttime, but also during daytime under low sunlight conditions, e.g. below the forest canopy (Brown and Stutz, 2012). These reactions lead to the formation of a variety of functionalized products, including organic nitrates (ONs) which act as NO_x reservoirs and are important components of the organic aerosol (Kiendler-Scharr et al, 2016). Furthermore, global modelling studies suggest that a large fraction of SOA is due to BVOC+NO₃ reactions (Ng et al, 2017). NO₃ radicals are formed in polluted air masses from the reaction of NO₂ with O₃ and their reactions with BVOCs represent an interesting and important coupling of anthropogenic with and biogenic emissions which affects both air quality and climate.

For these reasons, BVOC+NO₃ reactions have received increased attention in the literature. However, many studies investigated the reactivity of the most common terpenes, such as isoprene, α-pinene and β-pinene whereas a number of other terpenes remain poorly documented. In this study, we investigated the reactivity with NO₃ radical of five monoterpenes (C₁₀H₁₆) which are shown in Figure 1. These compounds have very similar chemical structures, the only difference being the positions of the C=C bonds. The objective of this study is therefore to investigate how minor differences in the terpene chemical structure may affect the rate of the reaction, the nature of the products at the molecular and functional scale and the SOA yields.

Experiments were conducted at LISA using two atmospheric simulation chambers: Kinetic experiments were performed in the CSA chamber which is a 1 m³ Pyrex reactor equipped with *in situ* long path FTIR and PTR-ToF-MS for the terpene measurement, as well as *in situ* IBB-CEAS for NO₃ radical monitoring. Mechanistic experiments were performed in the CESAM chamber which is a 4 m³ stainless steel reactor equipped with a large panel of analytical techniques for the characterization of both gaseous (FTIR, PTR-ToF-MS, ToF-CIMS, NO_x and O₃ analyzers) and condensed phases

(SMPS, TEOM, ACSM). Gas-phase products including ONs and Highly Oxygenated Molecules (HOMs) have been measured and SOA yields have been determined. The aerosol chemical composition at the molecular scale was also investigated thanks to LQT Orbitrap mass spectrometry at the University of Cambridge. Kinetic data, oxidation schemes and SOA yields obtained for the five monoterpenes will be compared and discussed.

Figure 1. Monoterpenes studied in this work.

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Primary sources of submicron organic aerosol in the Eastern Mediterranean. How and why are they different from the rest of Europe

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The first step in mitigating the adverse health effect of airborne particulate matter is to identify its sources. For this purpose source apportionment was applied on unit mass resolution spectrometric information of submicron organic aerosol (OA) obtained by an Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (ACSM, Aerodyne Inc) at an urban (35°08'26" N, 033°22'50" E) and a remote location (35°02'17" N– 33°03'28" E) in the island country of Cyprus.

At both sites, secondary OA dominated the organic fraction accounting for at least half of it in the urban site and more than 85% in the remote one. At the urban site three primary sources of OA were identified; a traffic related hydrocarbon OA (HOA) the concentrations of which correlated well ($r^2=0.59$) with black carbon (BC) concentration from fossil fuel combustion (BC_{ff}), a biomass combustion source observed only during cold period and a second HOA-like source the origin of which is yet to be determined. The latter was persistent throughout the study period (December 2018 – June 2019) and exhibited a diurnal pattern and source profile indicative of cooking sources. However, this source accounted for 15% and 21% of the OA during the warm and cold period of the study, respectively, which was deemed too high for cooking alone. Additionally, this HOA source exhibited good correlation ($r^2=0.62$) with particulate chloride, which is not a typical feature of cooking OA.

At the remote site, positive matrix factorization (PMF) was applied for each season separately but additionally the rolling PMF technique (Canonaco et al., 2021) was utilized in order to identify shorter-lived episodes of pollution. Only one HOA-like source was identified, on top of the secondary OA that dominated, which exhibited

- similar spectrometric characteristics as the HOA source identified at the urban site. (Figure 1)
- a very distinct seasonal cycle maximizing during winter, reaching up to 13% of the OA, and minimizing during summer. This pattern was similar to the one observed in the urban site.

- a correlation with BC, the level of which depended on the time of the year, indicating as origin a combustion source.
- it was identified throughout the 2-year study period (2015-2016) using both seasonal and rolling PMF techniques, suggesting a continuous source.

Figure 1. Spectral profiles of HOA-like source at the urban and remote sites in Cyprus.

Our results suggest of a year round combustion source, which affects at least the island of Cyprus and is not related to domestic heating or cooking. The potential origins and regional extent of this HOA-like source will be discussed.

This study has been supported financially by the AQ-SERVE (RIF INTEGRATED/0916/0016) and the H2020-EMME-CARE (GA #856612) research grants

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Observation of secondary aerosol precursors over the Antarctic Peninsula

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Keywords: Condensing Vapors, New Particle Formation, Antarctica

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Introduction

Antarctica is one of the most pristine regions on Earth. Its landscape, which is principally lacking vegetation and is covered by snow, ice, and permafrost, is critically impacted by climate change. In absence of direct anthropogenic activities, the Antarctic Peninsula is predominantly influenced by the marine ecosystem as well as from the fauna seasonally settling locally. Earlier studies have revealed intense aerosol activity at the coast of the peninsula with frequent new particle formation (NPF) events observed during summertime (e.g., Quéléver et al. 2022; Brean et al. 2021). Sulfuric acid, ammonia, and possibly different type of amines were identified to be the key gases at the origin of NPF at site, however many uncertainties remain on the gas concentrations needed to trigger nucleation.

Methods

Herein, we present the results of gas phase measurements from two field campaigns performed (1) at the Argentine research station Marambio (64°14'S, 56°37'W) during Jan. - Apr. 2023, and (2) in the research vessel *B.I.O. Hesperides* owned by the Spanish armada during the Polar Change expedition from Feb.-Mar. (Figure 1).

Results

Key precursor vapors (Sulfuric Acid-SA, Iodic Acid-IA, and Methane Sulfonic Acid-MSA) were measured simultaneously at Marambio and on *B.I.O. Hesperides*. Preliminary results suggest that SA concentration is typically higher on land, and MSA is more abundant at sea, especially on the western side of the peninsula. Surprisingly, IA concentrations were higher on land, however, but its concentration increases when close to the ice edge on the ship. Many NPF (nucleation and growth) were observed in Marambio, whereas only a couple of (transported) events were seen during Polar Change. The NPF observed in Marambio occurred simultaneously with high ammonia concentration during periods with winds originating from the direction of local penguin colonies. The atmospheric ion composition during NPF in Marambio suggests a nucleation process involving SA, ammonia and amines, confirming the observations of Quéléver *et al.* (2022). These stabilizing bases, however, were not seen from at sea, which likely explain why NPF did not occur at sea.

Conclusion

The on-going analysis of the gas and ion composition during multiple aerosol events observed in Marambio contribute to understand the Antarctic NPF regionally. With consistent observations, we highlight the importance of natural mechanisms involved in Antarctic NPF where compounds like ammonia play a critical role.

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Figure 1: Trajectory of *B.I.O. Hesperides* during Polar Change.

Biomass burning: assessment of emission and its chemical transformation at the EUPHORE chambers

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Keywords: Organic aerosols, biomass burning, atmospheric aging, aethalometer, simulation chamber

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Residential wood burning is a renewable method widely used for domestic heating and is considered CO₂-neutral. Nevertheless, biomass burning (BB) is the largest combustion-related source of volatile organic compounds and organic aerosols in the atmosphere, and has a concerning impact on air quality, human health and climate. The chemical evolution of the emissions remains under-represented in air quality and climate models and is poorly understood, as well as their contribution to the SOA burden. The burning conditions, i.e. flaming or smoldering, affect the combustion efficiency and temperature and therefore have an important effect on the emissions and their subsequent transformations, however, they are not always considered in many chemical models. Additionally, most of the studies have only focused on the characterization of the emissions rather than on their chemical aging.

This work shows and discusses the results of a series of experiments conducted at the EUPHORE chambers (Muñoz et al., 2011) within the ATMO-ACCESS and ATMOBE projects to study the emissions from different wood burning (orange tree, beech, and vineyard), their chemical transformations under day and night conditions, and optical properties. These scenarios were also used to test the new AE36s aethalometer, and a TC-BC method to determine organic aerosols (Rigler et al., 2020). The instruments employed also included OPC, PM_{2.5} sampler, nephelometer, filters for offline analysis, SMPS, TEOM, optical equipments, chromatographs, monitors and high-resolution state-of-the-art spectrometers such as PTR-ToF-MS and API-ToF-CIMS+Figaero inlet. This suite of instruments allowed a detailed examination of the optical properties and of the chemical composition, both in the particle and gas phases, of the emissions and their transformation when exposed to oxidants simulating real day and night conditions.

Results showed the capacity of the TC-BC method for apportionment of carbonaceous aerosol and an excellent correlation between the new aethalometer AE36s and AE33 (Pearson's correlation coeff. r : 0.996, slope: 0.984).

The analysis of the data allowed to examine tracers for identifying sources of BB. The untargeted analysis, using dimensionality reduction techniques (e.g., principal component analysis - PCA) and clustering, revealed similarities in the air mass composition but also different patterns as a function of the emission source, burning phase (flaming and smoldering), and aging conditions (night and day). As an example, Figure 1 shows two clusters identified by PCA, based on the variance, when applied to data from aging of the emissions from beech wood burning in the smoldering phase, indicating underlying patterns in the aerosol composition.

Figure 1. PCA analysis of particle phase composition from daytime aging of biomass burning emissions.

Such knowledge is essential as inputs for detailed science and policy modeling tools to gain insights into their impact on health, air quality and climate.

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O₃ chemistry of furan derivatives

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Keywords: chemistry of biomass burning plumes, atmospheric simulation chamber studies, O₃ chemistry.

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The chemistry of biomass burning plumes (BBP) became one of the major topics in atmospheric chemistry during the last decade. Yet, predicting the evolution of such plumes, particularly towards formation of ozone, remains challenging. Current research is focused mainly on the OH (e. g. Coggon *et al*, 2019) and NO₃ reactivity (e. g. Decker *et al*, 2019) inside plumes, whereas the O₃ chemistry received up to now less attention. As a result, kinetic studies on the ozonolysis of furan derivatives, found in large quantities in biomass burning smoke (Hatch *et al*, 2015), were seldom performed. As well, no complete mechanism has been postulated to date.

This investigation addresses the ozonolysis of 2,5-dimethylfuran (kinetics and mechanistic aspects), chosen as model compound for reactive furan derivatives. It is intended to provide a ground to understand the importance of the O₃ chemistry of furans, not only for the BBP composition but also for the troposphere, generally.

All experiments were performed in a 1080 L quartz glass atmospheric simulation chamber (Illmann *et al*, 2021) at atmospheric pressure and room temperature, under dry conditions. The reaction mixtures were concurrently monitored by long-path FTIR spectroscopy and proton-transfer reaction time-of-flight MS. The rate coefficient for the ozonolysis reaction of 2,5-dimethylfuran was determined using the relative-rate method.

A number of compounds formed in the gas-phase reaction system were identified by cross-referencing IR spectra of genuine standards and PTR-MS data. Accordingly, a reaction mechanism is proposed in accordance with the classical 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition and the subsequent decomposition of the primary ozonide (POZ).

Additionally, molar yields were determined for the products those absorption cross section values were available. These data suggest that pathways resulting in fragmentation of the C₆ core structure are significant. Several products are shown to arise from peroxy radical (RO₂) chemistry, the relative importance of the unimolecular and bimolecular pathways being illustrated by results obtained varying the conditions of the experiments. However, the carbon balance is scant. Yet, residuals in the FTIR spectra and PTR-MS data allow to tentatively assign further products.

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Formation and aging of SOA from mixtures of isoprene and α -pinene studied in the AIDA simulation chamber between 213 and 313 K

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Keywords: Secondary organic aerosol, mixed precursors, ageing, volatility, simulation chamber

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Organic aerosol (OA) makes up 20-90 % of the total fine particulate mass in the troposphere. A major contributor is secondary organic aerosol (SOA) from the condensation of organic compounds formed by oxidation of volatile organic compounds (VOC). Key precursors for global SOA formation are biogenic VOC of which isoprene and α -pinene are the most abundant (Kanakidou et al. 2005). Many simulation chamber experiments have been performed to study SOA formation and aging processes but they merely cover typical atmospheric aerosol lifetimes or temperatures (Takeuchi et al., 2022).

Therefore, we studied the oxidation of a BVOC mixture with α -pinene and isoprene in the AIDA (Aerosol Interaction and Dynamics in the Atmosphere) simulation chamber at 313 K, 298 K, 273 K, 248 K, and 213 K to investigate SOA formation and ageing for whole tropospheric temperature range. The SOA composition, volatility, and ageing was investigated at each temperature. The SOA was characterized by a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS), different condensation particle counters (CPC), and a high-resolution time-of-flight aerosol mass spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS). The SOA compositions were measured by the Filter Inlet for Gas and Aerosols (FIGAERO) coupled to an iodide high-resolution time-of-flight chemical ionization mass spectrometer (HR-ToF-CIMS). Furthermore, a PTR-MS was used to measure the VOC. The initial ratio of α -pinene to isoprene (initially 7 ppb) in the mixture was 1.0 ± 0.1 . The VOC were oxidized with an excess of ozone as well as OH radicals formed in the dark by oxidation of tetramethylethylen. After complete oxidation of the VOC the resulting aerosol was irradiated by a solar simulator (Vallon et al., 2022) for one hour and subsequently warmed up to the next higher temperature over 10-12 hours. This results in total experiment times of 21-24 hours. The effective saturation concentrations values of individual compounds are determined according to their measured elemental formulas applying a parameterization using molecular corridors (Li et al., 2016) and used to generate a one-dimensional volatility basis set (1D-VBS).

Cross dimers (C_{14-15}) from oxidation of isoprene and α -pinene mixtures were identified as $C_{15}H_{20}O_{3-7}$, $C_{15}H_{22}O_{3-9}$, $C_{15}H_{24}O_{4-9}$, $C_{15}H_{26}O_{5-9}$, $C_{15}H_{28}O_{5-9}$, $C_{14}H_{20}O_{6-8}$, $C_{14}H_{22}O_{5-9}$, and $C_{14}H_{24}O_{6-8}$, by using ^{13}C labelled isoprene and by

comparison with pure α -pinene SOA. The formation of C_{14-15} cross dimers and the corresponding suppression on C_{18-20} dimers from α -pinene is greatest at 213 K and 3.5 times higher than at 313 K. C_{14-15} cross dimers are important especially at colder conditions as they contribute substantial fractions (52% at 213 K and 38% at 243 K) to ultra/extremely low volatile species. Furthermore, being subsequently warmed up, particles formed at different temperatures underwent distinct aging processes: e.g. evaporation for particles from 273 K to 298 K, water loss in conjunction with evaporation for particles from 298 K to 313 K.

Figure 1 Signal fraction of volatility groups (ULVOC, ELVOC, LVOC, SLVOC, IVOC, and VOC) in the particles before (solid bars) and after (striped bars) warming by 30°. Volatilities were calculated by the VBS framework at the temperatures before and after warming.

Particles formed at higher temperatures are generally higher oxidized, but they are still more volatile than the particles that are formed at colder temperatures and subsequently warmed up. We will discuss the role of SOA formation from biogenic emissions at different altitudes in the troposphere.

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The first ACTRIS intercomparison workshop of chemical ionization mass spectrometry to measure condensable vapours

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CiGas-UHEL is a unit of the Central Facility of reactive trace gases in situ measurement focusing on measurements of condensable vapours and hosted by University of Helsinki. The key-mission of CiGas-UHEL is to offer operational support for continuous long-term measurements of condensable vapours and aerosol precursors such as sulphuric acid and oxygenated organic molecules (OOMs) in the atmosphere. The core activity of CiGas-UHEL is to ensure sustainable and traceable high-quality data and quantification of in-situ measured atmospheric reactive trace gases with known uncertainty and reproducibility. Intercomparison workshops provide crucial information about the individual functionality of the different instruments and understanding of their characteristic sensitivity and selectivity. Thus, the intercomparison workshops are a great tool towards the general goal of CiGas-UHEL to standardize and harmonize the different measurement methods.

CiGas-UHEL arranged the pilot intercomparison workshop of chemical ionization mass spectrometers (CIMS, Jokinen *et al.* 2012) at the twin chamber facility ACDC (Atmospheric Chemistry Department Chamber) at TROPOS in March 2023 in collaboration with the ACTRIS OrGanic Tracers and Aerosol Constituents - Calibration Centre (OGTAC-CC). The intercomparison workshop gathered ten instruments measuring condensable vapours with different setups that include an inlet where the chemical ionization occurs with specific reagent ions and ionization methods, and a time-of-flight mass spectrometer that detects the ions with a defined resolution. The variety of the instruments included various combinations of inlets (EISELE, MION, AIM, FIGAERO, Aircraft inlet) and different ionization methods (corona discharge, x-ray, visible UV, Am²⁴¹, Po²¹⁰).

In these experiments, we focused on the detection of sulfuric acid and different OOMs which are also the main target compounds of CiGas-UHEL unit. Further, we were particularly interested in the effect of different relative humidities (RH) on the detection and quantification of the mentioned target compounds. Beside some offline calibration (Kürten *et al.* 2012) we used two calibration compounds in the chamber: 4-nitrophenol and 1,2-ISPOOH at different concentration

steps and various RH conditions. We measured oxidation products of α -pinene by ozone and OH radicals including different RH and NO concentrations in the chamber. Furthermore, we measured various sulphuric acid concentrations under different RH conditions as well as with the addition of α -pinene in the chamber.

The response of the instruments to the changes in chamber conditions did not show a uniform agreement, highlighting the importance of this form of intercomparison workshops and further discussion within the network. The knowledge gained will help us to better understand and evaluate the sampled data of condensable vapors in the atmosphere and can provide defined measurement standards and operating procedures of CIMS instruments for the broader atmospheric science community.

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A radiative characterization of aerosol-cloud transition zone by means of HDR imagery

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Keywords: Aerosol-cloud, transition zone, partially cloud, radiative properties.

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In recent years, an increasing interest to better understand the phenomena behind the aerosol-clouds interactions have been boosted. Some research from ground-based stations has been mainly devoted to estimate the extension of the transition zone between clouds and free sky. This region extends from the border of the clouds to the portion of sky characterized by free air properties. Within this transition region, aerosol particles grow towards the cloud's edges because of the increasing humidity and the hydrophilic property of the particles.

This work is focused to radiometrically analyse the aerosol-cloud transition zone and determine its extent. To do it we use geometrically and radiometrically calibrated HDR images from an all-sky camera (Valdelomar et al. 2021a). From the whole dataset, we built a benchmark dataset that contains around 300 images in three different scenarios: clear-sky, partially cloudy and overcast. Moreover, each of them is subdivided in three different aerosol sub-scenarios in terms of AOD at 500 nm and AE. Only partially cloudy scenes are used in this work.

In a given partially cloudy image, cloudy pixels are identified using an adaptive threshold method based on the probability density function of the blue-to-red ratio (BRR) (Valdelomar et al. 2021b). In addition, while the clear sky is characterized by null spatial gradients of the red band, we define the transition zone as the area of the image that shows non-zero spatial gradients (Scarlatti et al., 2023).

We calculate the median extent of the transition zone for all of the partially cloudy images in the benchmark dataset. It is obtained from the variation of the BRR along all the segments that cross it perpendicularly to the cloud's edges. Our results indicate that the median of the BRR incremental ratio ($\Delta BRR/2\sigma$) exponentially decreases with the AOD at 500nm when the extent of transition zone is normalized to the length (in pixels) of the chosen segment (2σ) (Figure 1). As a global result a clear dependence of radiative signatures has been found with respect to aerosol loads more than aerosol types. The median extent measured of the transition zone in the benchmark images ranges between 400 and 900 meters.

Figure 1. Variation of BRR with normalized transition zone extent with the AOD at 500 nm. Colorbar represents the AE.

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A machine learning cloud-regime identification from ground-based remote sensing observations: seasonal analyses of cloud properties and radiative impact at BASS station

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Keywords: cloud properties, cloud identification, radiative forcing.
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Clouds play an essential role in climate through their impact in the radiative budget of the Earth, atmospheric circulation and hydrological cycle. In particular, clouds are the main atmospheric agent modulating the solar radiation reaching the Earth surface, which has significant implications in climate and in the available solar energy. Cloud information is critical to evaluate the performance of solar energy plants since they reduce the energy production due to fluctuations in the incident radiation. All these impacts are dependent on the cloud cover (CF) and type. Therefore, better knowledge of cloud properties, types and variability is extremely important to improve the confidence of their radiative impact.

This work is first focused on presenting an automated cloud-regime identification method. Then, we analyse the seasonal behaviour of cloud properties and radiative impact at Burjassot Atmospheric measurements Station (BASS). BASS is sited in Spain, in a coastal environment in the Western Mediterranean. It hosts a large set of instruments devoted to aerosol, cloud and radiation monitoring.

We use ground-based zenith observations of cloud optical depth (COD) and cloud base height (CBH), at 1-minute intervals, to develop a semi-supervised clustering. It is inspired on the WMO-ISSCP cloud classification (WMO, 2017), which uses 9 cloud classes depending on the COD and CBH. Our method is based on the Supporting Vector Machine algorithm (SVM) with a 5-fold cross validation (Madhulatha, 2012). It means that we use 5 randomly chosen samples with the 20% of the data for training and validating the SVM model. Then, we have derived the seasonal averages of cloud occurrence, different cloud properties (CF, COD, CBH, cloud albedo) and the daily shortwave radiative forcing (CRF) for the different cloud types (Salgueiro et al., 2014).

Our algorithm classifies the data in three COD classes (thin, mid-thick and thick clouds) with boundaries at $COD = 3.80 \pm 0.04$ and $COD = 23.9 \pm 0.3$ separating between thin and mid-thick clouds; and between mid-thick and thick clouds, respectively (Figure 1). The data are also divided in three CBH. The CBH limit between low and mid cloud is 2021 ± 6 m, and $CBH = 6975 \pm 12$ m separates the mid- and high clouds. The SVM model shows an overall accuracy higher than 98%.

In BASS, cloud occurrence is greatest in spring for all cloud types and medium CBH clouds are the most

frequent. The CF for mid-thick and thick clouds is always greater than 75%, and thin clouds cover the entire CF range (0-100%). None of the classes present a significant seasonal trend.

The CRF ranges from -600 to 100 W/m^2 depending on the COD. Considering all the cloud types, CRF decrease linearly with increasing $\log_{10}(COD)$ with a negative slope of -196 ± 3 W/m^2 . Its indicates that main radiative impact of clouds is the reduction of solar radiation on surface. However, there is a non-negligible number of cases in which clouds enhance the solar radiation reaching the surface. It is only observed for thin clouds since allow the radiation passing through them with multiple reflexions.

Figure 1. SVM cloud-regime identification based on cloud base height (CBH) and optical depth (COD).

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Simultaneous retrieval of AOD and COD from all-sky imagery

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Keywords: Aerosol, cloud, all-sky camera, radiative properties.

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Aerosol and clouds are key atmospheric components with relevant implications in climate. The impact the Earth radiative budget by means of absorption and scattering of solar and terrestrial radiation (direct radiative forcing). In addition, aerosol can act as cloud condensation nuclei modifying the radiative properties of clouds and triggering several aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI). The mechanisms associated with ACI are dependent on several parameters such aerosol load and type, their hydrophilic properties and the amount of water available in the atmosphere. From the radiative point of view, the optical depth is the most important parameter to characterize both, aerosols and clouds. Usually, aerosol and clouds are treated separately however in recent years there is an increasing interest to improve the understanding of their interaction mechanisms. In this sense, we have developed a methodology to determine the aerosol and cloud optical depth (AOD and COD) from measurements provided by an all-sky imager. It can be considered a first step to test the potential of an all-sky imager to address the study of the ACI processes.

Our method combines geometrically and radiometrically calibrated HDR images from an all-sky camera (Valdelomar et al. 2021a) and look-up tables previously built by radiative transfer simulations, inspired on Mejia et al., (2016). Given an image, cloudy pixels are identified using an adaptive threshold method based on the probability density function of the blue-to-red ratio (BRR) (Valdelomar et al. 2021b). Then different LUTs, for aerosol and clouds, are used to derive the optical depth for clear (AOD) and cloudy (COD) portions of the sky, respectively. We have applied our method to a benchmark dataset that contains around 300 images in three different scenarios: clear-sky, partially cloudy and overcast. Moreover, each of them is subdivided in three different aerosol sub-scenarios in terms of AOD at 500 nm and AE. Therefore, pixelwise optical depth has been derived in different atmospheric conditions regarding to aerosol and clouds.

Our results have been compared against AERONET collocated measurements of AOD (direct sun) and COD (cloud mode) for the complete benchmark data set. We have averaged our COD results around the zenith, using the AERONET field of view (1.5 °), for the cloud comparison. In case of aerosols, an AOD averaged for the whole image has been used. Our results show a good general agreement with AERONET measurements

for both, aerosols and clouds with correlation coefficients higher than 0.90 (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison between our results and AERONET measurements for aerosol and cloud optical depth (OD).

	OD	Slope	intercept	R
aerosols	AODblue	0.76 ± 0.01	0.012 ± 0.001	0.90
	AODred	1.08 ± 0.01	0.005 ± 0.001	0.96
clouds	CODblue	0.81 ± 0.01	5.8 ± 0.2	0.96
	CODred	0.89 ± 0.01	7.9 ± 0.2	0.96

In clear sky images we observe some AOD inhomogeneity which is more relevant in the circumsolar region and near the horizon. In partially cloudy conditions, different patterns associated with the increase of AOD from the clear sky areas of the image towards the cloud boundaries are observed. These patterns seem indeed dependent on the aerosol load and type, and the illumination geometry of each image. These results are promising and indicate the potential of our methodology as a new tool to improve the study of the ACI. However further investigation is required to study it in detail.

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Vertical distribution of aerosol activation in low-level stratiform clouds

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Keywords: cloud activation, atmospheric aerosol, cloud base, isobaric cooling.

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In the current IPCC report, the highest value of atmospheric aerosol radiative forcing was attributed to the interaction between aerosol and clouds. Five in situ campaigns focused on aerosol-cloud interactions were conducted at Mount Milešovka in the Czech Republic (50.55 N, 13.93 E, 830 m.a.s.l.) to gain more insight into size-dependent aerosol activation and its dependence on meteorological parameters, mainly vertical air velocity and position within the cloud.

Low cloud episodes coded as fog at the station were studied with respect to aerosol particle activation, cloud properties, and their interactions. The activated fraction (a fraction of activated particles in all available particles) was calculated from the difference of aerosols measured behind the whole air inlet and the PM_{2.5} inlet (Zíková et al., 2020, 2021). The liquid water content (LWC) was calculated from visibility (Fišák et al., 2006), cloud base position was estimated from ceilometer data (Ceilometer CL51, Vaisala, Finland), with the lowest cloud layer considered. Ceilometer data from Milešovka and Kopisty stations were used, with Kopisty (50.54 N, 13.62 E, 240 m.a.s.l.) being 20 km west of Milešovka. As the elevation difference of the stations is 590 m, the Kopisty ceilometer was used for cloud base estimation for the event when the Milešovka top was in clouds and thus the Milešovka ceilometer data were not usable.

Vertical air velocity w_{air} was estimated from the vertically pointing cloud radar (MIRA35C, METEK, Germany) situated at the Milešovka top. The lowest radar gate available, however, is 100 m above Milešovka top so the vertical velocity is only a proxy of the state of the atmosphere at the hill top.

No strong dependence was found between visibility and upward vertical velocity – downward movement was observed in the cloud (-1 to -2 m/s), while zero vertical velocities at the cloud edges, suggesting that the clouds at the station are mostly of advection or inversion origin, not connected to orographic wind structures or adiabatic cooling. If w_{air} reaches over 1 m/s, the visibility is often larger than 1000 m at the station.

Both visibility and LWC depend strongly on the position within the cloud, although not increasing “almost linearly with height above cloud base, reaching a maximum at about 80–90% of the cloud thickness” (Acker et al., 2002). The highest LWC values were found

when the station was between 100 and 400 m above the cloud base (Fig. 1), independently of the actual height above it. This confirms that the activation is due to isobaric cooling rather than the adiabatic one.

Figure 1. Dependence of liquid water content on the position above cloud base (cloud base height - CBH).

The lower LWC detected more than 400 m or between 0 and 100 m above cloud base may be connected with the vertical range of the clouds – at the cloud edges, the LWC is lower, and thus we can infer that the clouds at the station were mostly stratiform ones, with vertical depth of several hundred meters. This is confirmed by the cloud radar data, showing often no measured targets at 200 m above station if the fog was coded at the station.

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Evolving atmospheric chemistry: transition between nighttime and daytime chemical regimes associated with biomass burning

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Keywords: Biomass burning, simulation chamber, guaiacol, atmospheric chemical mechanisms

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Biomass burning, encompassing wildfires, agricultural burning, and domestic combustion, releases large quantities of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) to the atmosphere. These emissions, their gas-phase degradation products and resulting secondary organic aerosol (SOA) have significant but still uncertain impacts on air quality, human health and climate. Furthermore, the less-explored nighttime chemistry, involving NO₃ chemistry and dark aging, contributes to the intricate and evolving composition of atmospheric constituents during the night.

Some of the most reactive VOCs emitted during biomass burning are oxygenated aromatic compounds such as phenols and furans. Atmospheric chamber experiments can be used to study how these compounds react in the atmosphere. However, few studies have investigated the transition of reactivity between night and day which is important for nighttime sources of biomass burning, for example, residential combustion.

A series of chamber experiments were conducted at the 200m³ outdoor European PHOtoREactor (EUPHORE) in Valencia, Spain, during May 2023 via a Transnational Access (TNA) initiative. The experimental design aimed to replicate, among other experiments, the night-to-day reactivity transitions of multiple compounds from biomass burning. However, the study mainly focused on guaiacol, a methoxy-phenol, which is understudied and an important SOA precursor.

The replication of night-to-day was achieved via smooth transitions between daylight, using natural sunlight to attain near-real conditions, and dark conditions. The highly instrumented EUPHORE facility enabled measurements of O₃, NO_x, NO₂, HONO, HCHO, JNO₂ and particle mass and size distribution (SMPS). In addition to real-time measurements of VOCs via FTIR and advanced mass spectrometers (PTR-ToF-MS, API-ToF-CIMS+Figaero inlet) were used. This suite of instrumentation allowed detailed insights into the real-time chemical composition of both gas and particle

phases for the understanding of the degradation products and chemical reaction processes of guaiacol. Further comprehensive analysis of particulate composition was obtained via offline liquid chromatography (UHPLC) coupled with high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) using filter samples collected at the end of the night or day ageing period.

During the night guaiacol decayed exclusively via NO₃ chemistry forming nitro-guaiacol which upon exposure to daylight rapidly photolysed to background levels within one hour. This highlights the selectivity of the nighttime chemistry and nitro-guaiacol as a key daytime source of SOA. However, in the day, the degradation of guaiacol can proceed via multiple routes. For instance, OH addition, OH loss or hydrogen abstraction yielding possible benzoquinone and phenolic derived products. These different pathways between night and day can influence the resulting SOA composition. LC-HRMS data indicated nighttime derived aerosol consisted of at least 7 carbons suggestive of aromatic ring retaining species. Whereas compounds with 7 or less carbons increase during the day from the photochemical induced fragmentation of aromatic species.

Overall, we highlight the evolving chemistry and composition of a biomass burning plume within the atmosphere.

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Temperature Effect on Secondary Organic Aerosol Formation from Ozonolysis of Δ^3 -carene

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Keywords: secondary organic aerosol, atmospheric simulation chamber, Δ^3 -carene
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Organic aerosol contributes 20-90 % to the submicron aerosol mass, with secondary organic aerosol (SOA) constituting a significant portion (Jimenez *et al.*, 2009). A considerable source of SOA over boreal forests originates from monoterpenes such as Δ^3 -carene, which is sparsely studied. Atmospheric simulation chambers are used to investigate SOA formation processes but struggle to mirror the low volatile organic compounds (VOC) loadings found in ambient air. This work comprehensively explores the SOA formation and properties from Δ^3 -carene ozonolysis focusing on temperature effects and VOC loadings effects.

The temperature-controlled Aarhus University Research on Aerosol (AURA) atmospheric simulation chamber (Kristensen *et al.*, 2017) was used to investigate the aerosol formation from ozonolysis of Δ^3 -carene. SOA formation was studied at three temperatures (0, 10, and 20 °C) and two VOC loadings (10 and 50 ppb). The SOA was investigated in terms of physical properties, e.g. particle size distributions, and chemical composition using both online and offline mass spectrometric techniques.

The formation of SOA from Δ^3 -carene ozonolysis exhibits a limited temperature dependency. Particle number concentrations remain consistent across all three temperatures at both 10 and 50 ppb of Δ^3 -carene. While the particle mass concentration slightly increases with decreasing temperature at 50 ppb, this effect is less pronounced at 10 ppb (Thomsen *et al.* 2021, Thomsen *et al.* 2024). This is in contrast to the temperature dependence of other monoterpenes, e.g. α -pinene (Kristensen *et al.*, 2017, Thomsen *et al.*, 2021). Detailed offline analysis of the particle phase reveals a slight temperature dependency. At both 10 ppb and 50 ppb, the total concentration of tentatively identified oxidation products increases as temperature decreases (Fig. 1A). Carboxylic acids, e.g. *cis*-3-caric acid and *cis*-3-caronic acid, and one covalently bound dimer show the same trend. Two other covalently bound dimers are formed in largely the same amounts at 10 and 20 °C but are absent at 0 °C thereby exhibiting another temperature dependence. The discrepancy between the three covalently bound dimers likely arises from different formation pathways (Kenseth *et al.*, 2023). Time-resolved offline analysis indicates continuous condensation of carboxylic acids at 0 °C, while

evaporation or further reaction occurs at 20 °C supporting the larger concentration of semi-volatile products in the particle phase at 0 °C compared to 20 °C (Fig. 1B,C). This is also supported by online mass spectrometry using a filter inlet for gases and aerosol chemical ionisation mass spectrometer (Thomsen *et al.*, 2024). Highly oxygenated organic molecules (detected by a nitrate chemical ionisation mass spectrometer) exhibit a reverse trend, where the signal intensity decreases with decreasing temperature. This is due to the reduced formation of highly oxygenated organic molecules through autooxidation of RO₂ at lower temperatures (Thomsen *et al.*, 2024).

Figure 1 (A) Concentration of *cis*-3-caric acid and *cis*-3-caronic acid in SOA from 50 ppb Δ^3 -carene. (B) Time evolution of the mass fraction of *cis*-3-caric acid. (C) Time evolution of the mass fraction of *cis*-3-caronic acid.

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Seasonal ozone production rate measured during the JULIAC campaign

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Keywords: Ozone production, SAPHIR, RO_x radicals

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The atmospheric simulation chamber SAPHIR of the Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Germany, was used as a large photochemical flow reactor to study tropospheric chemistry in a rural environment (Jülich Atmospheric Chemistry Project campaign, JULIAC). From an inlet at 50 m height above ground, ambient air was continuously flushed through the chamber at a residence time of ~1.13 hours and exposed to natural solar radiation (Fig. 1). A large set of instruments allowed for the measurement of NO, NO₂, NO₃, N₂O₅, ClNO₂, HCHO, HONO, RO₂, HO₂, OH, OH-reactivity, CO, CO₂, CH₄, H₂O, VOCs, aerosols, and O₃ in the sampled air. Seasonal intensive measurement phases were performed and analysed to verify the current understanding of the chemistry of tropospheric ozone formation.

Figure 1. Experimental setup of the JULIAC system and the P(O_x) measurement approach using SAPHIR as a continuous stirred flow reactor.

To evaluate the atmospheric photochemical net ozone production, the concentration of O_x (O₃ + NO₂) was measured in the inlet and inside the well-mixed SAPHIR chamber using commercial instruments. By carefully characterizing the stirred flow reactor, an O_x concentration transported into the chamber was determined from continuous inlet measurements, excluding photochemical effects (Fig. 2, top panel: O_x transport). A comparison between chamber and transport O_x concentrations revealed loss reactions in the chamber at night, whereas daytime concentrations in

the chamber were elevated due to photochemical O_x production. The difference was used to determine diurnal profiles of the net ozone production (P(O_x)) with 1 hour running averages (Fig. 2, bottom panel), observing production rates up to 15 ppbv/h with 1 ppbv/h accuracy.

Measured net ozone production rates were compared to rates derived from concurrent measurements of peroxy radicals (HO₂, RO₂) reacting with NO and corrected by the main loss reaction of NO₂ with OH radicals. A good agreement (± 10%) during the spring and summer campaigns confirmed that in the rural environment studied, daytime O_x production and destruction were primarily governed by the reactions mentioned above. An extended analysis of P(O_x) also including other chemical reactions that may produce or destroy O_x in the lower troposphere will be discussed.

Figure 2. Measured O_x concentrations from the inlet and inside of the chamber (top panel) and the derived diurnal profile of P(O_x) (bottom panel)

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Humidity and seed particles affect secondary organic aerosol formation

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Keywords: secondary organic aerosols, air pollution, monoterpenes, atmospheric simulation chamber, mass spectrometry, dimer formation

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Aerosols particles are ubiquitous in the atmosphere, and play a key role in climate, air pollution and health.

Secondary organic aerosols (SOA) make up between 20 and 90% of atmospheric aerosol by mass (Jimenez *et al.* 2009). SOA mostly form when volatile organic compounds (VOCs), emitted from sources such as vegetation, are oxidized. This results in lower volatility oxidation products that enable gas-particle partitioning. Gas-particle partitioning takes place either by direct nucleation of the condensed phase from a supersaturated vapour phase or by condensation of the oxidation products onto pre-existing aerosol particles. These particles can include inorganic salts, such as ammonium sulphate, that make up a considerable fraction of atmospheric particulate matter. Furthermore, the phase state of these seed particles and thus the gas-particle partitioning of the SOA precursors, depends on ambient humidity which often cycles from low to high values in the troposphere.

Despite substantial efforts (Stirnweis *et al.* 2017, Clafin *et al.* 2018, Qin *et al.* 2021), the effect of relative humidity (RH) on the gas-phase partitioning is poorly understood to date. Thus, there remains considerable uncertainty on how RH affects conversion of volatile organic species to the condensed phase via nucleation or (equilibrium) gas-particle partitioning. As such, the influence this has on total ambient organic particulate matter composition, which ultimately affects air pollution, health, and climate, remains unclear.

To address this, we investigated the influence of both RH and the presence of ammonium sulphate seed particles on the formation of α -pinene SOA. SOA was formed by dark ozonolysis of α -pinene ($C_{10}H_{16}$) in an atmospheric simulation chamber. Using a state-of-the-art extractive electrospray ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometer (EESI-ToF) (Lopez-Hilfiker *et al.* 2019) we obtained molecular level composition measurements of condensed phase α -pinene oxidation products (i.e., monomers and dimers). These high chemical and temporal resolution measurements, together with a suite of standard aerosol characterization instruments, were used to chemically elucidate differences between SOA formed in the absence and presence of seed particles, and under high (>80%) and low (< 10%) RH conditions, respectively.

We found that gas-partitioning, and thus the total SOA mass formed, strongly depended on RH and the presence of seed particles. In addition, we observed

substantial differences in the chemical composition, where the dimer (C_{17-20}) to monomer (C_{8-10}) ratio is enhanced at high RH compared to low RH conditions. Furthermore, we found that the formation speed of dimers is increased under the presence of seed particles. Finally, we found relative composition of monomers shifted more strongly towards fragmentation products (i.e. $C_{10} \rightarrow C_{7-9}$) under high RH conditions.

Overall, our results demonstrate the key role of ambient conditions, e.g. humidity and/or presence of seed particles, on the formation of SOA. We believe that our results will help to better constrain the formation of SOA particles in atmospheric models, and hence better predict their impact on air pollution, health, and climate.

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Figure 1. CH-O plot showing the aerosol composition one hour after VOC injection for high RH + ammonium sulphate seed conditions, as determined by EESI-ToF.

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Simulations of Cloud Radar Spectral Polarimetric Variables with T-matrix

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Keywords: spectral polarimetry, cloud, radar, T-matrix.

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Cloud radar observations and simulations are crucial for advancing our knowledge on cloud microphysics. The T-matrix method has emerged as a powerful tool for computing the electromagnetic scattering properties and simulating the radar response of complex ice and water particles. This work focuses on generating simulations of a 94 GHz cloud radar observations with T-matrix and comparing between the simulated results and observations.

Figure 1. 94 GHz Doppler Radar pointing at 45 degrees. Spectral differential reflectivity sZ_{DR} (red line) and spectral differential phase $s\delta_{hv}$ (blue line).

Spectral polarimetry is to combine Doppler and polarimetric measurements in order to obtain the distribution of polarimetric variables as a function of radial velocity (Yanovsky, 2002, Unal, 2001, Unal, C. and Van den Brule, 2023). The 94 GHz frequency is particularly relevant for probing clouds with a high sensitivity to small particles, making it an ideal choice for investigating cloud microphysics in detail. In this study, we produce spectral polarimetric variables and compare them with real measurements of a 94GHz cloud radar pointing at 45 degrees. The T-matrix method (Mishchenko, 2000) is employed to accurately capture the complexities of cloud particles, enabling realistic simulations. Spectral differential reflectivity sZ_{DR} , copolar correlation coefficient $s\rho_{hv}$ and differential phase $s\delta_{hv}$ are

the variables of interest. The study explores diverse conditions, allowing for the modification of rain rate, white and spectral noise, and turbulence parameters within the simulation tool.

An example is presented in Figure 1, where the spectral differential reflectivity (red line) and differential phase (blue line) are simulated by using the T-matrix method. These variables are also affected by atmospheric turbulence, by blurring of the spectral features. Simulating the impact of atmospheric turbulence is a complex task. The attempt for inclusion of turbulence in the simulations is also discussed.

Comparisons between simulations and measurements reveal a good correlation, validating the efficacy of the T-matrix method in reproducing spectral polarimetric variables.

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Seasonal and spatial variation of fine aerosol acidity in the Eastern Mediterranean

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Keywords: fine aerosol, acidity, distribution.

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Acidity is a key property of water, aerosol and gas phases in the atmosphere. It affects the properties of aerosols and thereby their effect on climate, and their toxicity for humans and ecosystems (Pye et al., 2020). While rain water acidity is directly measured, aerosol acidity is mainly calculated using concurrent aerosol and gas phase composition measurements in thermodynamic models (Pye et al., 2020).

In this study we investigated the acidity levels of fine aerosol (PM_{2.5}, aerosol with diameter equal or smaller than 2.5 μm) and its potential seasonal variation in six regions across Greece in the East Mediterranean during winter 2019-2020 and summer 2019. The measuring sites were Ioannina, Thessaloniki, and Xanthi, to the North of Greece from West to East; Patras and Thissio/Athens in the middle of Greece; Finokalia to the South on Crete island. They thus provide a representative coverage of the country.

Daily observations of aerosol chemical composition were performed during two PANACEA (PANhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climatE chAnge) campaigns in summer 2019 and in winter 2019-2020. Among others, carbonaceous aerosols (OC/EC) and inorganic species (both cations NH₄⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and anions SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻) were determined using ion chromatography (Kaskaoutis et al., 2022). These data together with concurrent gas phase observations were used in the thermodynamic model ISORROPIA-lite (Kakavas et al., 2022) to calculate the aerosol water content and PM_{2.5} aerosol acidity.

We find summertime aerosol pH to be by 1 to 2 pH units lower (more acidic aerosol) than during winter. However, even during winter the fine aerosols across Greece are acidic to moderately acidic with an overall mean aerosol pH 3.5 ± 0.4 units in the urban areas, while

in remote regions aerosols are more acidic (mean pH of 3.0 ± 0.5). The less acidic aerosol was found in Ioannina due to, among others, high K⁺ levels from biomass burning emissions, associated with domestic heating. Different seasonal profiles of aerosol pH were observed across the studied sites. Non-sea-salt sulphate, non-volatile cations, and temperature were identified among the main factors that drive the seasonality of aerosol pH at different locations. In most cases, the organics were not found important for aerosol water and aerosol pH.

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Atmospheric Simulation Chamber and bioaerosol: first data on bacteria viability versus NO_x concentration in the atmosphere.

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Keywords: atmospheric simulation chamber, bioaerosol, viability.

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Bioaerosols are airborne particles that contain living organisms or substances of biological origin. Bioaerosols are a complex and dynamic component of the atmosphere with implications for public health, agriculture, and environmental processes. The study of their sources, behaviours and impact is crucial for managing associated risks.

Here, we present the results of several experiments, performed inside a confined and controlled artificial environment, such as the Atmospheric Simulation Chamber, providing valuable information on bio-aerosol viability, dispersion, and impact. At ChAMBRé (Chamber for Aerosol Modelling and Bio-aerosol Research), managed by INFN at the Physics Department of the University of Genoa, Italy, the research on bioaerosol is focused on the investigation of the airborne bacteria behaviour in different atmospheric and air quality conditions (Massabò et al., 2018).

A multi-step protocol was developed (Vernocchi et al, 2023) and thoroughly tested to cultivate a suitable bacteria population (*E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *B. licheniformis*, and *P. fluorescens*). Then, bacteria are nebulized, and injected inside ChAMBRé, where they were exposed to different gas concentrations. The viability variation, due to the pollutant exposure inside ChAMBRé, was determined by monitoring the concentration of viable bacteria.

Results

The bacteria survival rate inside ChAMBRé is first evaluated in a set of baseline experiments (clean air condition). A WIBS-NEO instrument measured bacteria total concentration inside ChAMBRé while the viable concentration was determined by active sampling on petri dishes by an Andersen impactor and then counting the formed Colonies Forming Units (CFU). In other experiments, bacteria were exposed to NO₂ and NO concentrations of 900 and 1200 ppb for both pollutants. Viable concentration $V(t)$ trend can be calculated by fitting the data with an exponential function as:

$$V(t) = V(0)e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}$$

where $V(0)$ is the viable concentration just after the injection ($t=0$), and τ is $V(t)$ lifetime. In Figure 1 the τ

average results, obtained in a set of 37 experiments led from separate *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* cultures, are shown.

Figure 1. Average and standard deviation of viable concentrations lifetime (τ) at different pollutant concentrations for *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*. P-value was calculated between pollutant experiments and baseline condition for each bacteria strain. "NS" stands for "not significant".

The average $V(t)$ lifetime in the baseline experiments was about 35 minutes for both bacterial strains. For NO, a concentration of 900 ppb does not affect the viability of either *E. coli* or *B. subtilis*, while a concentration of 1200 ppb reduces the lifetime to about 25 and 21 minutes, respectively. For NO₂, the same reduction in viability was measured for *B. subtilis* for both concentrations, while for *E. coli* a higher NO₂ concentration resulted in a greater reduction in viability. These are very preliminary data and results for the four bacterial strains will be presented at the Conference.

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Cloud observations in the most south-eastern ACTRIS cloud remote sensing station

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Keywords: clouds, remote sensing
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The most south-eastern cloud remote sensing station (CCRES) recently labelled as ACTRIS has been set up starting with 2021 in Galaţi, SE of Romania, as a part of the REXDAN – UGAL research centre which is a result of a project whose implementation ended in December 2023. The station fulfils the criteria of an ACTRIS CCRES and is equipped with five equipments that started to work synergistically as a cloud observation platform in the beginning of February 2022: cloud radar (RPG, dual polarization, FMCW, operating at 94 GHz), multichannel microwave radiometer (RPG HAPTRO), ceilometer (LUFFT backscatter lidar), disdrometer (Otto Parsivel) and a built in meteorological station. All instruments are mounted on a large open terrace at the third floor of the building hosting the instruments, i.e. about 10 m height (40 m altitude ASL). Data is continuously fed into the Cloudnet site. We present here some cloud observation and associated statistical results, diurnal variation, as well as observed characteristics during the first two years of observations, i.e. 2022 and 2023. Comparisons with model results are also analysed and discussed.

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Figure 1. One of the best fit between data and model (20.01.2022)

Figure 2. One of the worst fit between data and model (09.04.2022)

Secondary organic aerosol production at a coastal site upwind of New York City

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Keywords: coastal, megacity, SOA.

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Coastal sites upwind of large metropolitan regions and megacities often experience poor air quality. These sites are impacted by a combination of biogenic and anthropogenic emissions, including primary organic aerosol, volatile and semi-volatile organic compounds (VOCs, and SVOCs), and secondary pollutants formed via chemical processing of primary emissions as they travel over nearby bodies of water.

Located downwind of megacity New York City (NYC), the Yale Coastal Field Site (YCFS) in Guilford, CT (Figure 1) is impacted by these conditions. Pollution from NYC is transported over the Long Island Sound before reaching the YCFS. The site regularly experiences ozone non-attainment events which are often coupled with aged emissions from nearby metropolitan areas and to local emissions (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2021). The site is also impacted by marine air masses traveling over the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 1. Map of the YCFS (orange star) in relation to the nearby megacity of NYC (red star)

During the summer of 2023, the AEROMMA (Atmospheric Emissions and Reactions Observed from Megacities to Marine Areas) campaign took place, with a suite of measurements at a site in NYC and the YCFS. Ambient measurements of organic, nitrate, sulfate, ammonium, chloride, and black carbon aerosol concentration along with supporting gas-phase measurements were taken at both sites. This study focuses on the aerosol composition at the YCFS and the processing which occurs during over-water transport.

A Time-of-flight Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (TOF-ACSM) was deployed to the YCFS to measure the real-time mass and composition of non-refractory aerosol particles smaller than 1 μm in diameter ($\text{PM}_{1.0}$). In a TOF-ACSM, aerosol particles are

vaporized at 600°C, ionized by electron impact ionization, and analyzed with time-of-flight mass spectrometry. A fragmentation table is then applied to calculate the contributions of organics, nitrate, sulfate, ammonium, and chloride (Fröhlich et al, 2013).

During July and August of 2023, particulate matter at the YCFS was dominated by organic aerosol (OA) (Figure 2), which comprised 80% of the total $\text{NR-PM}_{1.0}$. There were varying contributions of nitrate, sulfate, and ammonium and a minor chloride presence (<1%).

Figure 2. Time series of organic, nitrate, sulfate, ammonium, and chloride aerosol mass concentrations

Positive matrix factorization (PMF) analysis of the OA reveals several oxygenated organic aerosol (OOA) factors, some hydrocarbon-like organic aerosol (HOA) contribution, and influence from biomass burning. A majority of the OA is highly oxygenated and secondary in nature with the most oxygenated OA being associated with over-water transport. Analysis of the sources of primary aerosol and chemical processes associated with SOA production will be presented. Insights into the links between SOA and ozone formation as well as the influence of NYC emissions on SOA production during the measurement period will be highlighted.

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The influence of forest management (clearcutting) on volatile organic compound emissions and secondary organic aerosols from a boreal forest

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Keywords: forest management, volatile organic compound emissions, secondary organic aerosol

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Clearcutting is a prevalent forestry practice characterized by the uniform removal of most or all trees in an area. This process not only transforms forests from carbon sinks to sources but also leads to substantial emissions of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs). BVOCs play a crucial role in numerous atmospheric chemical reactions, including the formation of aerosol particles, which can impact cloud properties and ultimately affect the climate.

Our research, conducted from 2020 to the present, utilizes the 2022 clearcutting event at the Norunda ACTRIS and ICOS station in the Swedish boreal forest. This event provides a unique opportunity to study the entire cycle of forest clearcutting, replanting, and establishment. Our focus is on the BVOC emissions, their secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation, and the subsequent effects on climate and air quality (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 The plan of the clearcutting and regeneration of the area close to the Norunda station and the measured (2021-2023) and projected (2024-2026) VOC concentrations from a measurement tower in the middle of the clearcutting area.

We conducted two summer pre-clearcut campaigns in 2020 and 2021, followed by an intensive ongoing campaign beginning just before the clearcutting in July 2023. We have augmented the permanent measurements at the station with additional instruments for online and offline analyses of BVOCs, their oxidation

products, and particles, such as a VOCUS proton transfer reaction time-of-flight mass spectrometer (VOCUS-PTR-ToF-MS), a chemical ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometer with a filter inlet for gases and aerosols (FIGAERO-CIMS) and a Neutral cluster and Air Ion Spectrometer (NAIS).

Preliminary findings highlight that clearcutting significantly altered BVOC emissions, both in terms of total amounts released and emission rates of individual VOC species, during and post-clearcutting. Notably, we observed a stark increase in monoterpene concentration from about 2-3 ppb to over 40 ppb during the active clearcutting, while isoprene levels remained stable (Fig. 2). Corresponding shifts in the gas- and particle-phase oxidation products of these compounds were also noted, underscoring their significant effects on aerosol formation.

Fig. 2 Time series of major BVOC groups isoprene and monoterpenes pre and during clearcutting.

Our future work will utilize a footprint model to quantify the source footprint of observed BVOC concentrations. Additionally, we will employ chemical transport models to simulate the impact of various BVOC emissions scenarios on regional aerosol formation. This research will contribute significantly to our understanding of how forestry practices impact atmospheric composition and climate dynamics, informing future forest management and environmental policies.

Evolution of climate-relevant properties of black carbon under Arctic transport ageing conditions in the AIDA simulation chamber

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Keywords: black carbon, Arctic, ageing, simulation chamber

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Black carbon (BC) is an absorbing carbonaceous aerosol particle emitted by combustion processes and is considered among the strongest anthropogenic atmospheric warmers (Bond et al., 2013). Among other variables, the BC radiative forcing is directly proportional to its mass absorption cross-section (MAC) and atmospheric load. While MAC quantifies the amount of light absorbed by BC mass, the atmospheric load is inversely proportional to the ability of BC to act as a cloud condensation nucleus (CCN) and as an ice nucleating particle (INP). These three climate-relevant properties strictly depend on more fundamental properties such as diameter, morphology and mixing state, which evolve with suspension time in a process called atmospheric ageing. Considering that global models show difficulties in reproducing the temporal evolution of fundamental and climate-relevant properties of BC during northward transport (Samset et al., 2018), estimates of radiative forcing of BC in the Arctic are particularly uncertain.

Considering the scarcity of field and laboratory studies, the ARCTEx (Aida arCTic Transport Experiment) project aims to investigate the ageing time scale of fundamental and climate-relevant properties of BC during Arctic transport conditions by reproducing near-real conditions in the AIDA (Aerosol Interaction and Dynamics in the Atmosphere) simulation chamber. ARCTEx experiments aimed to reproduce arctic transport at low and high altitudes in winter and summer. 10 years of reanalysis data from ERA5 and CAMS were used to define the latitudinal profile of meteorology (temperature and relative humidity), chemistry (BC and trace gas concentrations), and sunlight duration from 40°N to 90°N, with a latitude resolution of 10°. Over the duration of 5 experimental days, meteorology, chemistry and light were adjusted daily in AIDA, so that 24 hours of experiment would correspond to 10° of northward transport. The instrumental setup allowed us to monitor the temporal evolution of size, density, mixing state, chemical composition, optical properties and cloud activation behavior of BC.

Beginning with the injection of soot, generated with a mini-CAST burner, the summer low-altitude experiment lasted a bit less than 120 hours. AIDA was cooled from 22°C to 0.0°C, ozone and nitrogen dioxide

were injected every 24 hours, while illumination time was increased from 8 to 24 h day⁻¹.

Figure 1 shows the experiment reproducing the arctic summer transport at low-altitude.

While the total number concentration decreased from approximately $5.0 \cdot 10^4$ to $5.0 \cdot 10^2$ cm⁻³, density, coating mass fraction and fractal dimension increased during the experiment indicating a morphological restructuring of BC agglomerates towards more spherical and coated BC-containing particles. As a consequence, the MAC, calculated from the absorption coefficient and refractory BC mass increased by a factor of two, while the number fraction of CCN increased from zero to 90% (Figure 1). The evolution of fundamental and climate-relevant properties differed substantially between the various experiments suggesting that the ageing time scale might be completely different from winter to summer and from low to high altitude conditions.

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**THEME 3 - OBSERVING EXTREME
EVENTS IN A CHANGING CLIMATE:
HEAT WAVES, DUST EVENTS,
FOREST FIRES, STRONG
PRECIPITATION, DROUGHTS ETC.**

Scientific Committee Members:
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Intensive measurement of VOCs and organic tracers during the summer heat wave 2022

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Keywords: VOCs, Organic tracers, Ozone, Heat wave.

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Tropospheric ozone poses significant environmental and health challenges in Europe with high ozone episodes, often being underestimated by models. The cause of this underestimation remains unclear and could stem from either inaccuracy in predicted ozone precursor emissions or shortcomings in understanding physio-chemical processes. Additionally, formation of secondary organic aerosol (SOA) becomes a concern during heat wave episodes, contributing to adverse health effects.

To improve understanding of ozone and SOA formation during heat waves, the EMEP Task Force on Measurement and Modelling (TFMM) organized an intensive measurement period (IMP) at a total 27 global, regional, and urban sites across Europe. The extensive measurement program included a wide range of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and organic tracers, in addition to monitoring NO_x, O₃ and OC/EC. This collaborative measurement campaign took place during a heat wave from July 12-19, 2022, in collaboration with ACTRIS and RI-URBANS.

Participants expanded their regular EMEP/ACTRIS observations to include a comprehensive range of VOCs. For sites where routine monitoring or specific component groups were not covered, manual VOC sampling devices were distributed and subsequently analysed at centralized laboratories. Furthermore, aliquots of OC/EC filters were analysed for selected tracers for biogenic SOA. The devices and analyses conducted at central laboratories comprised:

- Canister air samples for non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHC)
- DNPH cartridge analysed for oxygenated VOCs (OVOCs)
- Tenax tubes analysed for monoterpenes
- SOA tracer analyses at from quartz filters

In July 2022, an ozone episode coincided with an extended European heat wave with record high temperatures, and wildfires. The high-pressure system initially influenced the southwest, leading to elevated ozone concentrations in the Iberian Peninsula and parts of France. As the heat wave intensified, hot polluted air masses were transported to northwest Europe.

Temporal variations in NMHC and OVOCs mirrored the episode's progression across the continent. Absolute NMHC levels correlated with station type, showing a higher fraction of long-lived species such as ethane at clean regional sites and more reactive NMHC near source areas. The relative OVOCs distribution was remarkably similar among stations. For monoterpene, the forest-adjacent sites exhibiting the highest concentrations, α -pinene was the predominant component at all locations.

During the IMP, up to 80% of organic aerosol (OA) was identified as SOA, surpassing the long-term July mean SOA/OA fraction. Approximately one-third of the SOA was estimated originating from oxidation of α -pinene contributing approximately 20% of the organic aerosol.

Figure 1. Overview of the sites participating.

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Wildfire plumes in the Paris region (France) during 2022 showcase the much-needed interconnections between ACTRIS and ICOS observations

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Keywords: Wildfires, aerosol chemistry, ozone, Volatile Organic Compounds, urban air quality

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In July 2022, Western Europe experienced an intense heatwave, with daily temperature anomalies reaching up to +12°C. The combination of prolonged droughts and the influence of global and regional warming created favourable conditions for wildfires. France witnessed therefore unprecedented events of burning, exceeding 60,000 ha, primarily concentrated in the Southwestern region. The impact of wildfire plumes even extended to areas in France which typically remained unaffected by such events, including the Paris region.

As part of the ACROSS project, alongside ongoing monitoring initiatives (ACTRIS, ICOS, Airparif), the Paris region benefited during the summer of 2022 from a comprehensive atmospheric characterization at different sites: SIRTa (SIR, peri-urban background), Chatelet (urban background), Rambouillet (RAM, forest site), and PRG (Paris downtown). This characterization notably encompassed PM₁ chemical composition (ACSM and AE33), aerosol size distribution (SMPS), speciation of Volatile Organic Compounds (PTR-ToF-CHARON, PTR-MS), as well as concentrations of CO and CO₂.

On July 19th, a substantial increase in PM concentrations was recorded at all sites, with PM₁ reaching up to 80 µg/m³ at SIRTa (Fig. 1). The dominant contributors were carbonaceous aerosols, accompanied by biomass-burning tracers (e.g. acetonitrile m/z42, levoglucosan m/z60, particulate levoglucosan m/z 163.06).

Figure 1. A complex mixture of flaming (local) & smouldering (advected) wildfire plumes were observed at SIRTa on 19th July 2022. The top panel represents the VOCs, while the bottom panel depicts the NR-PM₁ compositions.

While Paris downtown experienced only one main event, a detailed analysis unveiled the event's complexity, allowing it to be separated into two distinct sub-events noticeable at SIR and RAM. Within a one-hour time difference, sharp shifts in aerosol properties have been observed, such as particle number size distribution (PNSD). The first event (E1) showed indeed a major contribution of Aitken mode (75nm), while the second one (E2) contained mostly particles in the accumulation mode (160nm). The absence of any clear growth between them underlines the singularities of both events. Combined with the synchronicity of E2 with the event observed in Paris downtown, as well as similar PNSD (mode around 160nm), pointed that event towards an advected plume from South-Western France (approximately 500 km from the Paris region). E1 at SIR and RAM were related to local combustion (around 10 km from the sites), respectively stubble and forest wildfires, located a few kilometers from the sites.

Both events are associated with a clear increase of ozone (around +10 ppb) while NO_x concentrations remained low. This highlights the chemical burst induced by the plumes within a NO_x-limited environment.

Interestingly, oxidation properties of organic aerosols also showed a clear change between E1 and E2. Although E2 is associated with an aged plume, organic matter showed less oxidized characteristics than local E1 event. This feature has been related to the CO to CO₂ ratios in the Modified Combustion Efficiency (MCE), revealing that E1 and E2 can be respectively associated to flaming (MCE=0.94) and smoldering (MCE=0.79) regimes. Previous wildfire observations have indeed highlighted the role of combustion regime towards emissions and oxidation state of organic aerosols.

Given the anticipated rise in severe wildfires and heatwaves in France, this study underscores a unique opportunity to foresee the complementary monitoring and scientific capabilities of ICOS, ACTRIS, and other operational monitoring networks infrastructures for the comprehensive analysis of such events.

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Extreme pollution with tropospheric sulfate at Cabo Verde originating from Cumbre Vieja volcano at La Palma – a case study analysis by means of lidar aerosol extinction, backscatter and depolarization profiles at 355, 532 and 1064 nm

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Keywords: lidar, volcanic eruptions, air quality, extreme events.

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From 19 September to 13 December 2021, volcanic eruptions took place at the Cumbre Vieja ridge, La Palma, Canary Islands. Thereby, fine ash and volatiles, like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), were emitted and transported up to thousands of kilometers away from the island.

Continuous lidar measurements with a multiwavelength-Raman-polarization lidar Polly^{XT} have been performed at the foreseen ACTRIS site at the Ocean Science Center at Mindelo, Cabo Verde, since June 2021 to support the Joint Aeolus-Tropical Atlantic Campaign (JATAC) held in 2021 and 2022. A novel feature of the system operated at Mindelo compared to other lidar deployments is, that measurements of the particle extinction coefficient, the particle extinction-to-backscatter ratio (lidar ratio) and the particle linear depolarization ratio are available at 1064 nm as. Having measurements of these quantities at all three wavelengths (355, 532 and 1064 nm) is a major advantage as the lidar ratio and the particle linear depolarization ratio are key parameters for the aerosol characterization and for the characterization of the atmospheric state above Mindelo during the eruption period of Cumbre Vieja.

Outside this period, typical aerosol conditions over Mindelo during the northern hemispheric summer and fall are a clean marine planetary boundary layer (PBL) up to approx. 1 km and a Saharan dust layer (SAL, up to 6 km) above. The lidar measurements from 16 September 2021, before the start of the eruptions, will be presented as reference observation for the aforementioned aerosol conditions. Particle extinction coefficients less than 200 Mm⁻¹, a lidar ratio below 30 sr and a particle linear depolarization ratio close to zero are typically observed at 355 and 532 nm under such conditions in the marine PBL. In the SAL above, lidar ratio values between 40 and 60 sr and linear depolarization values between 0.2 and 0.3 have been typically observed.

In contrast, during the time of the volcanic eruptions, strong pollution was observed in the PBL, e.g., on the 24 September 2021. On that day, the aerosol optical depth, determined by an AERONET (Aerosol Robotic Network) sun photometer, was as high as 0.9 and

1.1 (daily averages at 500 and 340 nm). The strong pollution in the PBL was characterized by an unusual high particle extinction coefficient of 718, 547 and 126 Mm⁻¹ and an enhanced lidar ratio of 66.7, 60.1 and 33.7 sr (mean values at 355, 532 and 1064 nm, respectively). The particle linear depolarization ratio was ≤ 0.03 at the respective wavelengths. In the SAL, Saharan dust as the major contributor but probably contaminated with smoke, anthropogenic pollution and/or sulfate was identified. Compared to the 16 September, a slightly higher lidar ratio and a lower particle linear depolarization ratio were observed. The lidar analysis also revealed that the PBL contributed about 60 % to the total AOD while for the typical background conditions it is usually less than 15 %.

HYSPLIT (Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory) trajectories indicate air mass transport from Canary Islands to Mindelo at heights below 2 km on 24 September. The observed pollution in the PBL over Mindelo was attributed to sulfate aerosol from the volcanic eruption at La Palma as the particle linear depolarization ratio was close to zero and, thus, does not indicate non-spherical particles, such as Saharan dust or volcanic ash. We thus conclude that sulfate aerosol formed from gaseous precursors during the transport (2–3 days for a distance of 1500 km) from La Palma towards Cabo Verde. No indications of volcanic ash over Mindelo were found in the SAL. This finding is supported by the HYSPLIT trajectories, which show that air masses at higher altitudes originate from the African continent and not from the Canary Islands.

An elaborated presentation of this study is provided in Gebauer *et al* (2023).

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Characterization of the optical and polarimetric properties of Saharan dust during two extreme events in March 2022

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Mineral dust particles constitute one of the major contributions to the total aerosol burden in the atmosphere, being mineral dust emissions from the Sahara Desert and the Sahel region almost 50% of the global dust emissions (Kok et al., 2017). In particular, the Iberian Peninsula (IP), located in Southwestern Europe, is greatly affected by dust outbreaks from long-range transported Saharan dust, which worsens the air quality in this region (Querol et al., 2019).

Mineral dust also affects the Earth's radiative budget by means of scattering and absorption processes and affecting cloud formation. In fact, aerosol-radiation and aerosol-cloud interactions are the processes with the largest uncertainty in global radiative forcing estimations (Forster et al., 2021). Satellite remote sensing techniques are key to provide wider spatial coverage. The determination of aerosol properties with satellite remote sensing is accomplished by inversion algorithms. However, these algorithms need information about the scattering matrix elements of aerosol particles, in particular phase function (F_{11}) and polarized phase function ($-F_{12}/F_{11}$). These parameters depend on the scattering angle, on the wavelength of the incident light and on several aerosol microphysical properties, such as particle size distribution, refractive index and morphology of the particles. Therefore, multiwavelength measurements of F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ of mineral dust will allow a better characterization of aerosol properties with the use of satellite remote sensing techniques.

In this work, we present the analysis of two extreme Saharan dust events that reached Europe in March 2022. The UGR urban background station of the Andalusian Global ObseRvatory of the Atmosphere (AGORA), included in ACTRIS, registered PM_{10} values over $1000 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during those extreme events. The UGR station counts with a Polarized Imaging Nephelometer (PI-Neph; Bazo et al., 2024) that measures F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ at three different wavelengths (450 nm, 515 nm, 660 nm). The combination of measurements from the PI-Neph and the multiwavelength filter-based absorption photometer (aethalometer AE33, Magee Scientific) that operates at UGR allows to derive additional aerosol optical properties, such as the single scattering albedo (SSA), asymmetry parameter (g), fraction of backscattered light (Bs) and lidar ratio (LR).

In addition to the two extreme dust events, we have performed an analysis of several moderate dust

events that reached the UGR station during the year 2022. Results show differences between the optical properties during moderate and extreme dust events, especially in terms of SSA and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$, probably due to the higher predominance of absorbing particles during moderate dust events, as evidenced by the higher equivalent black carbon concentration (EBC). Figure 1 shows F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ during the more intense period of the extreme dust events in March 2022 as well as the seasonal average (average of F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ for moderate dust events) during 2022. While F_{11} only shows some differences in the backward scattering region, $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ differs substantially, especially for 405 nm.

Figure 1. F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ for the different dust events.

This study provides the first multiwavelength measurements of F_{11} and $-F_{12}/F_{11}$ for transported mineral dust aerosol, for events of varying intensity, as well as other derived optical properties. Measurements of EBC indicate that differences between moderate and extreme dust events might be due to influence of local pollution with the transported mineral dust. Further chemical analysis is needed to support this hypothesis.

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Growth and global persistence of stratospheric sulphate aerosols from the 2022 Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai volcanic eruption

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Keywords: Aerosol size distribution, Volcanic Eruptions, Climate, AERONET, Photometry, Satellite
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Stratospheric sulphate aerosols play a key role on atmospheric chemistry and Earth's radiation budget, but their size distribution, a critical parameter in climate models, is generally poorly-known. We address such gap for the 2022 Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai (HT-HH) volcanic eruption by exhaustively analyzing a set of satellite observations (TROPOMI, IASI, AHI, CALIOP) together with photometric ground observations from the worldwide open-access AERONET network, including data from several ACTRIS stations (Boichu *et al.*, 2023). The synergistic analysis of satellite and ground-based observations, as well as multi-station data analysis, was performed using the AERIS [VOLCLUME web portal](#) (Boichu and Mathurin, 2022). This interactive portal, dedicated to the tracking and analysis of the 4D physico-chemical properties of volcanic plumes in the atmosphere, from source to global scales, was used in crisis time to deliver information on HT-HH aerosol properties.

We document a rapid growth of HT-HH sulphate aerosols in the days following eruption, faster than observed for 1991 Pinatubo eruption and likely due to the exceptional hydration of the stratosphere by this phreatomagmatic eruption. On longer term, we provide, with improved spatial and temporal resolutions, the size distribution of HT-HH sulfate aerosols, which is characterised by an unusual aerosol fine mode (peak radius in 0.3-0.5 μm) that is identified at 20 stations of the southern hemisphere until May 2023 (time of writing). Nevertheless, 1.4 years after eruption, HT-HH sulfate aerosols remain smaller than Pinatubo particles. Smaller aerosols backscatter more efficiently visible light and sediment more slowly than larger particles, implying stronger and longer-lasting negative radiative forcing.

Figure 1. Stack of the time-series of Hunga Tonga aerosol peak radius at the 20 AERONET stations of the southern hemisphere represented in the top panel. HT-HH eruption is indicated by vertical dashed line.

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VOLCLUME, an interactive web portal dedicated to the multiscale monitoring of volcanic emissions and their impacts on the atmosphere

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Keywords: Volcanic Emissions/Plumes, Gas, Particles, Web Portal, Satellite/Ground Remote Sensing, LEO/GEO Satellites, Photometry, LIDAR, Air Quality, Climate, Aviation Hazards, Volcano Monitoring
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The [VOLCLUME web portal](#) is dedicated to the near-real time and retrospective tracking and analysis of the 4D physico-chemical properties of volcanic plumes in the atmosphere (Boichu and Mathurin 2022). The portal allows for jointly analysing a broad panel of satellite and ground-based active/passive remote sensing observations of both volcanic gas and particles, including Low Earth and Geostationary Orbit imagery, spaceborne or ground-based lidar, and photometric measurements. The portal also gives access to in-situ ground-level air quality monitoring networks. This synergy enables users to detect and isolate a volcanic plume signature down to the ground, from source to regional or global scales. Interactivity and flexibility of the portal aims at facilitating assessment of the multiscale atmospheric impacts of volcanic plumes that include – depending on the type and magnitude of the eruption – modifications of the atmospheric chemistry, degradation of air quality, aviation hazards, and climate impacts.

Figure 1. VOLCLUME web portal dashboard illustrating the 3D tracking of SO₂- and sulphate aerosol rich plume from Cumbre Vieja eruption (La Palma, Canary Islands).

An additional feature of the portal is its ability to quantify temporal variations of gas and particle emissions, over daily to annual timescales, from any active volcano in the world. To this end, a companion

interactive web application, named « SO₂ Flux Calculator », has also been developed to automate the estimation of daily SO₂ gas flux emissions from TROPOMI observations with a robust noise estimation (Grandin *et al.* 2023). Knowledge of the volcanic source, often highly variable with time, is indeed crucial for accurately initialising models of volcanic plume dispersion and robustly assessing atmospheric hazards. Regarding local volcanological hazards, this focus on emissions is also essential as it allows to remotely track changes in the degassing or eruptive activities of any isolated or non-instrumented volcano.

VOLCLUME is an interdisciplinary portal relevant for atmospheric scientists and institutions in charge of air quality or aviations hazards, but also to the earth science community, in particular volcanologists and volcanological observatories. For illustration, we present different case-studies including the eruptions of Cumbre Vieja (La Palma, Canary Islands), Piton de La Fournaise (La Réunion), Soufrière Saint-Vincent (Lesser Antilles) and Hunga Tonga.

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A Saharan dust intrusion in Potenza characterized through lidar linear depolarization ratio at three wavelengths (355, 532 and 1064 nm)

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Introduction

A Saharan dust intrusion was observed at CNR-IMAA Atmospheric Observatory CIAO (Potenza, Italy), on 6 November 2023 and characterized using lidar measurements of linear depolarization ratio at three wavelengths (355, 532 and 1064 nm).

The observed layer was below 2 km and therefore the dust particles are contaminated with the background continental aerosol present in the region. The study shows the potential of modern lidars at high time and space resolutions, able to provide with depolarization measurements at the three wavelengths typically used in lidar systems.

Systems overview

The measurements reported in this case study were performed with the fixed lidar of the CNR-IMAA. The system is based on two laser sources. One laser emits only at 1064 nm, allowing to optimize the aerosol depolarization measurements at this wavelength. The second laser emits radiation at 532 and 355 nm. The system includes two Cassegrain telescopes, one with a larger diameter (400mm), for the far range measurements, and one with a diameter of 200 mm for near range measurements, allowing a full overlap altitude down to 200 m. This lidar system has technical characteristics better than those required by ACTRIS for being a National Facility (NF). It is able to provide continuous and unattended measurements of aerosol backscattering at 355, 532 and 1064, aerosol extinction at 355 and 532 nm, volume and particle depolarization ratio at 355, 532 and 1064 nm, and water vapour mixing ratio in the planetary boundary layer region and in the free troposphere. The performances of the instrument were checked during a one-month direct intercomparison campaign, held in September 2023. The system is one of the reference lidars of the CARS topical centre in ACTRIS.

Case study: 6 November 2023

The HYSPLIT backward trajectory analysis in Fig. 1 shows the path of the mineral dust originated in western Saharan regions around 3-4 November 2016. After crossing the Tyrrhenian Sea, the dust plumes reached Potenza on 6 November 2016. Similar to the majority of autumn cases (Mona et al. 2006), the intrusion occurs at low altitude and consequentially the dust is

contaminated by continental background aerosols. In these conditions, the analyses show great uncertainty and only high resolution lidars allow to characterize the different layers.

Figure 1. Four-days backward trajectory analysis for the air masses reaching Potenza at altitudes of 2300 m a.s.l. on 6 November 2023.

Fig. 2 shows the time evolution of the lidar cross polarized signal at 532 nm, measured from 23:05 to 02:16 UTC on 6 November 2023. In this case, we find very stable layers throughout the whole measurement, with the highest aerosol load at 1.9km.

Figure 2. Lidar cross polarized signal at 532 nm, measured from 23:05 to 02:16 UTC on 6 November 2023 at CIAO atmospheric observatory in Potenza.

Results in terms of aerosol optical and microphysical properties will be presented, showing the potential of the lidar advanced systems in studying these events.

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Canadian smoke entrainment in the Granada Atmospheric Boundary Layer: synergistic approach of remote sensing and in-situ techniques

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The presence of atmospheric aerosols plays an important role in influencing the Earth's radiation budget, as they interact with solar radiation and impact cloud properties. In biomass burning events, smoke particles can be released and lifted from the surface to the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL), the free troposphere, or even the lowermost stratosphere, influencing regional circulation and cloud dynamics (Baars, 2019). Once out of the ABL, aerosol particles can be transported over long horizontal distances. These long-range transported aerosols may descend and back again to ABL levels far away from its source. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze not only the outbreak itself, but the ABL entrainment of long-range transported aerosols (Bravo-Aranda, 2015, Hu, 2019 and Sicard, 2019).

The main aim of this work consists of analyzing the unprecedented outbreak of Canadian wildfire smoke which was observed over Granada through satellite and ground based remote sensing along with in situ techniques between 27 and 30 June 2023. Smoke plumes up to 13 km high were detected at the ACTRIS National Facility AGORA, Andalusian Global Observatory of the Atmosphere.

Identification and monitorization of Canadian smoke plume from space was made using Aerosol Absorbing Index (AAI) product, also called Ultraviolet Aerosol Index (UVAI) from Sentinel-5P. Fig 1. shows the initial stages of the smoke outbreak on 22/06/2023 and the arrival to Granada on 27/06/2023.

Atmospheric column characterization was carried out with a Cimel sun-photometer, reflecting a high concentration of fine mode particles. Aerosol typing and particle vertical distribution were performed by the state-of-the-art Raman lidar ALHAMBRA. It includes elastic, Raman and water vapor detection, depolarization and fluorescence capabilities. These advanced features enabled to gather information about location, type, and particle shape. The results were combined with a Doppler lidar system. It provided us with 3D-wind field, turbulence kinetic energy dissipation rate and attenuated backscatter profiles which allowed to study the ABL dynamic throughout the biomass burning event.

High equivalent black carbon mass concentrations and an increase in concentrations of UV-absorbing fine

particles were obtained using an aethalometer included within the in-situ equipment located at the Sierra Nevada remote station (2610 m above sea level (asl)). Both indicated the unusual presence of smoke particles during the study period. In contrast, no significant change was detected at the Granada urban station (680 m a.s.l.), which usually has high levels of urban background. Hence, it is fair to highlight the importance of monitoring at remote locations set at high altitude for detecting long- and medium-range aerosol transport episodes.

Figure 1. Sentinel-5P AAI map for days 22 and 27 of June 2023.

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Pollen observation in Athens detected by Burkard pollen trap using space-based data from CALIPSO

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Pollen concentration and type are routinely monitored at ground level using aero-biological collectors that capture pollen particles. While these measurements provide valuable information on the local abundance and diversity of pollen, the understanding of the vertical distribution and transport of pollen is still limited, so new techniques and technologies are needed. CALIPSO data products generated by the CALIOP satellite can be used to study atmospheric particles such as aerosols and clouds, but they have not yet been utilized to characterize pollen grains. This collaborative study will provide new insights into pollen optical characteristics.

Methodology

In this study selected pollination events in the area of Athens are analysed. The Burkard collector, located on the rooftop of Physics building (lat 37.97°, lon 23.78°), records pollen particles concentrations with a 2-hour time resolution. On the 12th of March 2021, pollen concentration during CALIPSO overpass (11:36-12:28 UTC) exceeded 400 grains m⁻³, with the dominant pollen types belonging to *Pinaceae* and *Cupressaceae* at a rate of 69% and 24% respectively.

In this study, we utilized the CALIPSO Aerosol Layer Product, the Aerosol Profile Product and the Aerosol Feature Mask Product, Kim et al (2018).

Results and Conclusions

In this case study, CALIPSO characterized the occurring aerosols as marine and dusty marine. The layer extended from 0.08 km up to 1.37 km and the mean optical properties are presented in Table 1.

Initially the origin of the air masses was being investigated using the **NOAA HYSPLIT** model. Four-day backward trajectories arriving at 12 UTC in Athens for 0.5, 1, 1.5, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 km indicated no transportation of Saharan dust. Mass concentration profiles performed with the **RAMS/ICLAMS** and **DREAM/BSC** models confirmed the absence of marine aerosol and dust particles up to 5 km. **MERRA-2** dust and mass concentrations were simulated lower than 5 µg and 2.5 µg respectively. This was also indicative of the CALIPSO aerosol type being unrelated to marine or/and dust particles.

Table 1. CALIPSO Layer Products

Attenuated Backscatter statistics 532nm (km ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹)	0.003±0.001
Attenuated Backscatter statistics 1064nm (km ⁻¹ sr ⁻¹)	0.001±0.001
Feature Optical Depth 532nm	0.047±0.012
Feature Optical Depth 1064nm	0.034±0.014
Particulate Depolarization Ratio Statistics (%)	4.2±17.1
Particulate Color ratio Statistics	0.695±0.575
Final 532 Lidar ratio (sr)	23.0±5.06
Final 1064 Lidar ratio (sr)	23.0±5.06

Small color ratio values are indicative of large particles which according to our simulations are not dusty marine nor pure marine aerosols. The identification of CALIPSO aerosol type leads to low lidar ratios, probably due to marine aerosol contribution. However, the low depolarization ratio is not indicative of pollen particles, especially for *Pinus*. This reduction is likely due to the mixing of *Cupressaceae* pollen grains with both pine and anthropogenic aerosol particles, Shang et al (2020). It is highly probable that the presence of pollen particles in the atmosphere acts as a confounding factor for the CALIPSO feature mask classification algorithm.

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Dust aerosol radiative effects during a dust event and heatwave in summer 2019 simulated with a regional climate model over Spain

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The Mediterranean region is one of the regions with the highest aerosol load due to air masses carrying many different aerosol types. One of the most common aerosols is mineral dust because of its proximity to the North African deserts (Prospero et al., 2002). During periods of mineral dust outbreaks, the effect on human health is associated with the biological matter and microorganisms transported by the dust plume that can be harmful to humans (Griffin, 2007) and/or with the increase in the particulate matter load at ground level when dust is present (Tobías et al., 2011). When dust intrusion occurs simultaneously with a heatwave event, its effect on human health gets even worse. In this context, the dust radiative properties and forcings combined with the heatwave are examined with the ALADIN regional climate model during an event that occurred between 20th June and 5th July, 2019 (see Figure 1).

First, some key variables of the dust intrusion calculated by ALADIN (aerosol and dust optical depth, dust mean-layer height, etc.) are compared against observations from either local sun-photometers and lidars or satellite. The thermodynamics of ALADIN reflecting the heatwave is checked against local radiosoundings.

Second, the dust direct radiative effect of ALADIN is then compared to the results in the shortwave of (Cordoba et al., 2021) and in the longwave of (Sicard et al., 2022) obtained for the same event.

Third, an estimation of the aerosol semi-direct effect of this dust and heatwave event is carried out with radiative products from Aladin-Climate model. This aerosol semi-direct effect of dust particles is compared with the direct radiative forcings to quantify the effect of the dust intrusion on the profile of temperature.

Fourth, an attempt is made to unravel the heatwave impact from the dust event, as the effect of the synergy of both events remains a quite unknown topic.

Figure 1. Anomalies of aerosol optical depth from Aladin-Climate model with MODIS satellite and AERONET stations (circles) over southwest of Europe at 26th June 2019.

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Physical properties of aerosols at Izaña Observatory during the recent extreme dust events impacting the subtropical North Atlantic

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In this study we focus on the extreme Saharan dust events that affected the subtropical North Atlantic during the winters of 2020-2022. We used the aerosol data set recorded at the Izaña GAW/ACTRIS observatory (2367 m a.s.l., Tenerife, Canary Islands) and the data provided by the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) program of the ENA (Eastern North Atlantic) station (30 m a.s.l., Graciosa, Azores Islands) to characterize the physical properties of aerosols during the extreme events that impacted Izaña of 23-24 February 2020, 16-17 February 2021 and 14-17 January 2022.

Izaña dataset used here comprises measurements of aerosols scattering and back-scattering coefficients (TSI™ - nephelometer), absorption coefficients (Magee™ - aethalometer and Thermo™ - MAAP), size distribution from 10nm to 20 μm (TSI™ SMPS + APS) and PM₁₀ concentrations (Thermo™ beta radiation attenuation monitor). These information is complemented with measurements of aerosol optical depth (AOD) from Cimel sun-photometers of the AERONET network (<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov>) and vertical distribution of aerosols from MPL micropulse Lidars from the MPLNET (<https://mplnet.gsfc.nasa.gov>) at Izaña and Graciosa, and a CL31 Vaisala ceilometer at Graciosa.

During the 2020 dust event, 24-h mean PM₁₀ concentrations reached up to 1300 μg/m³ (1-h mean of 3500 μg/m³). These concentrations are nearly 10 times higher than the 24-h maxima recorded between 2002 and 2008 at Izaña (150 μg/m³; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2011). In the events of 2021 and 2022, 1-h mean PM₁₀ concentrations up to 800 and 1000 μg/m³ were recorded. These results dramatically contrast with the PM₁₀ concentrations typically measured at Izaña under dust-free conditions (1-5 μg/m³, García *et al.*, 2017).

The AOD at 500 nm reached a value of 3 during the 2020 event, and a value of 2 during the other two episodes at Izaña. The MPL micropulse Lidar signal at Izaña revealed dense dust layers extending up to 5 km in

height during the dust super event of 2020, and lower altitudes up to 3 km, during the 2021 and 2022 super dust events. A higher linear volume depolarization ratio of 0.32 at 532nm was also measured, for a more extended period during the first episode, suggesting a high concentration of large particles with significant depolarization. A the lower Angstrom Exponent (AE) 440-870 nm of 0.5 was registered in the first event, while AE of 1.1 was observed in the second and third events.

The size distribution measured in-situ with the APS agrees with that retrieved volume size distribution of aerosols obtained with the sun photometer (Dubovick *et al.*, 2000). Some of these events were extensive enough to affect the Azores region. The dust cloud from the 2020 event was detected at ENA on Feb. 26, 2020. The AOD reached a maximum of 0.7 and the MPL showed a layer with a strong signal between 2000 and 3000 m a.s.l. The 2022 episode was also detected at ENA on Jan. 20, with an AOD of 0.25 and a maximum signal in the MPL between 2000 and 3000 m a.s.l. Our results on optical and physical properties of dust aerosols include a complete comparison of physical properties of dust during these extreme dust events compared to regular dust events.

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Recording-breaking Canadian wildfire in 2023: properties and variabilities of long-range transported biomass burning aerosol derived from lidar measurements at ATOLL observatory

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Keywords: aerosol, lidar, wildfire, properties, variability

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The Canadian wildfire in 2023 was marked by its unusually early onset and prolonged duration of fire activities, as well as the record-setting burning area. According to the estimate of the Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS), the Canadian wildfire in 2023 accounted for about 23% of total global wildfire carbon (brown carbon and black carbon) emissions for 2023 (Copernicus 2023). Brown carbon and black carbon, two important components of Biomass Burning Aerosol (BBA), play an important role in the climate because their high absorption could warm the atmosphere, and influence the temperature pattern and cloud formation. During the transport, the optical and microphysical properties as well as the chemical compositions of the BBA particles change with the particle age and aging conditions. However, this complex process remains inadequately characterized, introducing significant uncertainties in the representation of BBA in the climate models.

The lidar system LILAS, operated at ATOLL observatory, national facility of ACTRIS, has detected long-range transported BBA layers since May 2023 and up to October 2023. LILAS emits laser radiation at 3 wavelengths-- 355, 532 and 1064 nm and is able to derive the profiles of $2\alpha+3\beta+3\delta+\phi+\omega$ dataset, i.e., two extinction and three backscattering coefficients, three particle linear depolarization ratios (PLDR), one fluorescence backscattering coefficient or capacity and one water vapor mixing ratio (WVMR) or relative humidity (RH). From the observations of LILAS and a spectrum fluorescence lidar in Moscow, more than 30 BBA layers observed from May to September 2023, were selected and analysed.

This study investigates, for the first time, optical and microphysical properties of BBA particles, their variation with the layer height, transport time and WVMR/RH. The results show BBA particles in the upper troposphere have different properties compared to those in the lower troposphere, regarding particle size, shape and chemical composition (inferred from fluorescence spectrum). Figure 1 show the vertically dependent particles effective radius and Figure 2 shows the correlation between fluorescence capacity and WVMR on 28-29 May 2023. BBA particles are mostly with effective radius of 0.2 μm in the lower troposphere

and 0.3 μm in the upper troposphere. The BBA plumes with lower fluorescence capacity and depolarization, usually appear in the lower troposphere and come with RH of 20-40%, while those of higher depolarization and fluorescence capacity, and red-shifted fluorescence spectrum, are usually drier (RH<=10%). More results will be shown in the final presentation.

Figure 1. The retrieved effective radius of BBA particles observed from May to September 2023 at ATOLL observatory.

Figure 2. 2D histogram of the fluorescence capacity and water vapor mixing ratio (in g/kg) in the transported BBA plumes in the night of 28-29 May 2023.

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Long range transport of smoke over Switzerland: aerosol properties and spectral features

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Wildfire smoke transport from N. America to Europe is not a rare event (e.g. Ansmann et al., 2018). Especially during 2023 the northern hemisphere has been impacted as a result of 2023's record-setting Canadian wildfires. Unprecedented quantities of air pollutants and greenhouse gases were released into the atmosphere: observed maximum daily mean PM_{2.5} concentration in New York City reaching 148.3 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, (50-year record). Also, Europe and China were affected, the later increasing daily mean PM_{2.5} concentration in northwestern China by up to 2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Wang et al., 2023). In September 30th aerosol measurements at Jungfraujoch (JFJ) (46.5N, 8E, 3400m a.s.l.) (picture 1) and October 1st, 2023 at Davos (DAV) (46.8N, 9.8E, 1580m a.s.l.), Switzerland, showed a greatly increased aerosol load. Air mass back trajectories showed that the aerosol sources for central Europe was Eastern Canada, where several wildfires were present.

Picture 1. Photo of the Jungfraujoch area in Swiss Alps for 30th of September (left) and 29th of September (right) (photo: Jungfraubahn; roundshot.ch)

Aerosol Optical depth and aerosol extinction coefficient measurements at October 1st were 5-6 times higher from the long-term average for both DAV and JFJ. (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Spectral AOD measurements at DAV (Oct. 1) with 5 sun-photometers and spectroradiometers. Sub-plotted: JFJ spectral extinction coefficient at the peak concentration time (Sep. 30th) simulated using size distribution data measured at JFJ and optical material properties constrained with in situ and remote sensing observations.

This size distribution was quite unusual with a modal diameter at ~ 800 nm and a tail extending to around 1.5 μm . Mass concentration we measured based on APS is as high as 55 $\mu\text{g/m}^3$.

Moreover, as shown in figure 1 an interesting spectral dependence of both AOD/DAV and Extinction coefficient at JFJ have been observed. Showing a pronounced change/decrease of the AOD from around 500nm towards the UV spectral range.

A likely explanation for this spectral feature is that in this case the particles grew exactly to a “medium” diameter at which the drop in the UV is more pronounced. Looking at simulations of mass specific extinction cross sections for well-defined particle diameters, shows that the drop appears at a diameter of ~ 500 nm and is also evident at ~ 800 nm. At 1069 nm the spectral dependence flattens out and essentially vanishes at longer (2500 and 4900 nm) wavelengths (Figure 2). This feature has been also investigated with remote sensing and in situ measurements at Payerne station (46.8N, 6.9E, 490m a.s.l.).

Figure 2: Particle size dependence of spectral mass specific extinction cross sections simulated with optical material properties constrained with in situ and remote sensing observations on September 30th, 2023 at JFJ.

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Impact of extreme wildfires on stratospheric aerosol and gaseous composition

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The severity of wildfires has remarkably increased over the last years in both Northern and Southern hemispheres and there is an emerging realization of their effect on climate and ozone layer. Intense wildfires release tremendous amounts of heat into the atmosphere, which gives rise to extreme thunderstorms termed Pyrocumulonimbus (PyroCb). These storms, augmented by the energy of combustion, can generate vigorous convective updrafts injecting smoke and other combustion products into the stratosphere, where the residence time of aerosols is not limited by cloud scavenging and precipitation. A number of recent studies have put in evidence that the effects of strong PyroCb events on the global stratosphere rival those of moderate volcanic eruptions in terms of magnitude and duration whilst exceeding them in terms of radiative forcing (e.g. Khaykin et al., 2020). Furthermore, the PyroCb injections into the stratosphere were shown to generate persistent synoptic-scale anticyclones (SCV – Smoke-Charged Vortex), lofting confined bubbles of combustion products and moisture deep into the stratosphere due to solar heating of carbonaceous aerosols, which prolongs their atmospheric residence time and radiative effects.

Here we use ground-based lidar records in France (ATOLL, SIRTa, OHP) and New Zealand (Lauder) together with global observations by MLS, OMPS, CALIPSO satellite missions to characterize and quantify the planetary-scale impact of wildfires on stratospheric gaseous composition and aerosol burden as follows. First, we identify the wildfire events during the last two decades with a measurable stratospheric impact and classify them into four categories ranging from 1 (e.g. Alberta 2023) to 4 (Australian Black Summer 2019/20) based on the magnitude and longevity of their stratospheric impact. Using a combination of nadir and limb observations along with ERA5 analysis, we explore the spatiotemporal evolution and dynamics of the smoke plumes. Then, we quantify the aerosol and gas mass fluxes into the stratosphere for each event.

We show evidence for the geographical and seasonal extension of wildfire events. By using long-term ground-

based and satellite lidar observations of depolarization, we point out the longevity of fine smoke particles in the stratosphere.

Finally, a particular focus is made on the anomalous 2023 Boreal wildfire season and its impact on the lowermost stratosphere. Using multiwavelength fluorescence lidar observations (Veselovskii et al., 2023), we point out contrasting properties of smoke aerosols in the free troposphere and upper troposphere/lower stratosphere.

Figure 1. Primary source regions of wildfire smoke in the UTLS as inferred from OMPS-NM Aerosol Index: North America, Australia and Siberia.

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Dust aerosols, a challenge for agriculture

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Keywords: ACTRIS, aerosol particle, dust, agriculture, topsoil, pesticides, health effects

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Agriculture is associated with a number of problems and threats; greenhouse gas emissions, water and wind erosion loss of fertile topsoil, animal health, climate change vulnerability, pollination and biodiversity loss, greater susceptibility of soil degradation and crop loss at monocultures, food toxins, eutrophication, increasing demand for water and food, and more. These can all have serious implications for climate and food security.

However, agriculture is affected by several other factors that can be both beneficial or a threat, which stem from short-lived gases and aerosol particles, where some of the effects are not as well known; Crop damage by ozone, release of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs) that affect chemistry and aerosol formation, ammonia emissions which lead to secondary aerosol formation, pollen emissions, pesticides emissions, agricultural dust emissions from arid soils, or during tilling and harvest operations, jeopardized air quality for workers at farms or with livestock, bioaerosol emissions from livestock, and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) spread over long distances. Hence, there can be a significant effect on human health through inhalation, on climate via a variety of processes, and on crop damage.

It is basically unknown how dust emissions contribute to loss of fertile topsoil, negative health effects among workers and the general population from long-range transport, pesticides spread, and how it contributes to climate effects. A study by Kristensson et al. (2020), shows that dust can account for half of the PM10 mass concentration in spring-time in northern rural Europe (Figure 1). However, it is not known where this dust comes from: agriculture, road dust, various long-range transported dust sources such as desert dust and high-latitude dust, or others. The agricultural dust can contain pesticides, which amplifies the hazardous health effects. Also, dust could have a larger oxidative potential than other PM10 sources. Dust contributes to ice nuclei formation and thereby to cloud formation.

There could however be a remedy for this uncertainty. We will demonstrate how the ACTRIS network can provide a unique opportunity to investigate aerosols from agriculture more closely. Namely, several existing measurements of organic aerosols, dust tracers, and other aerosol properties can be helpful to quantify dust aerosol and help to identify sources in Europe due

to the dense network of stations. Pesticides can be traced by filter measurements and existing pesticide networks in France and Sweden.

Figure 1. Source/receptor modelling of the dust contribution (dashed line) to measured PM10 mass concentrations (solid line) at Vavihill rural field site in southern Sweden during 2000.

In combination with remote sensing from the ceilometer network and satellite data, we show how dust transport from deserts or high-latitude dust in free troposphere can be separated from near-local sources. Measurements can be combined with Lagrangian modelling to quantify source contribution of various sources. This however, requires also improved emission measurements of several dust sources.

ACTRIS provides a foundation for this research. By combining different agricultural problems in a holistic manner in a multi-disciplinary approach, we hope to find synergies between many solutions to make agricultural practices more sustainable in a changing climate.

This work was funded by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Environmental Research (MISTRA) as part of the Swedish air pollution research program ASTA (International and National Abatement Strategies for Transboundary Air Pollution), and the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency. Also ACTRIS Sweden contributed to the work, which is a National Research Infrastructure funded jointly by the Swedish Research Council (Grant 2021-00177) and the six Swedish Research Performing Organizations involved.

Kristensson et al., 2020. Abstract, EAC symposium, 2019.

Seasonal, regional and vertical characteristics of high carbon monoxide plumes along with their associated ozone anomalies as seen by IAGOS between 2002 and 2019

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Keywords: Atmospheric chemistry, fires.

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IAGOS is a European research infrastructure using passenger aircraft to sample the atmospheric composition along aircraft trajectories. In-situ measurements from IAGOS are used here to characterise extreme values of carbon monoxide (CO) in the troposphere between 2002 and 2019. In addition, we use the SOFT-IO model, combining the FLEXPART lagrangian dispersion model with emission inventories over the footprint region to identify the origins of the CO in the sampled plumes. The impact of biomass burning and anthropogenic emissions on such CO plumes measured at different altitudes and in different regions of the world are characterised through CO mixing ratios and simultaneously recorded ozone ones.

The lower troposphere (LT) reaches its maximum values of CO during the Northern Hemisphere (NH) winter because of the higher anthropogenic emissions during this season and the low convective activity. These high CO values are therefore essentially due to anthropogenic emissions and the ozone associated with these plumes is low during the winter months (DJF).

In contrast, CO plumes in the upper troposphere (UT) are the result of high emissions from the ground and efficient vertical transport, which enables CO to be transported from the LT to the UT. These vertical movements are favoured during the months of JJA in the NH. As a result, CO plumes in the UT very often originate from few well-identified regions benefiting from important pollution export pathways. Thus, of the many anomalies observed in the UT which are due to anthropogenic plumes, a large proportion come from East Asia and North America. The large fires which can occur during this season in the boreal regions are also responsible for important CO anomalies in the UT in JJA. These plumes are often associated with ozone values higher than average.

The middle troposphere (MT) is a mix between the two previous vertical levels: the origin of the plumes is partly local and partly comes from long-range transport; the maximum emissions during the boreal winter are counterbalanced by the increase in

vertical transport and boreal fires during the summer. This layer has the highest proportion of episodes linked to fires originating from the boreal zones of Asia and America.

The Indian region has a strong signal linked to its own anthropogenic emissions in the lower troposphere. However, at higher altitudes, in addition to local anthropogenic plumes, we can observe plumes originating from fires from North Africa during the months of DJF and MAM and from fires from Equatorial Asia during the months of SON.

The emission regimes and meteorological conditions are fundamentally different within the troposphere over Africa. Convection is no longer the limiting factor and the transport of the CO plumes is driven by the ITCZ shift, trade winds and the upper branch of the Hadley cell redistributing the polluted air masses to higher latitudes. In addition, biomass fires constantly occur on the African continent and, depending on the season, the fires will take place in the northern or southern hemisphere, following the hemisphere of the strongest Hadley cell. These fires have a major impact on the CO anomalies of their respective hemisphere.

Temporal evolution and vertical impact of the fresh volcanic aerosols during the Cumbre Vieja volcano eruptive activity at La Palma (Canary Islands)

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Keywords: mass conversion factors, polarized Micro-Pulse Lidar, volcanic ash.

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For the first time in fifty years, the Cumbre Vieja volcanic area (La Palma, Canary Islands, Spain) erupted on 19 September 2021, giving birth to a new volcano. Fresh volcanic aerosols were continuously injected into the troposphere at different height levels, decreasing with time until the end of December 2021 (15 weeks duration). A wide set of different instrumentation was deployed all over the Island in order to evaluate the effects of the volcanic plumes on the atmosphere and the air quality. For the first time, a long-term study of the relative mass contribution and vertical impact of the volcanic components, ash and non-ash particles separately, was carried out during the eruptive activity. In particular, a polarized Micro-Pulse Lidar (P-MPL) was deployed at Tazacorte (at around 8 km west from the volcano) from 17 October 2021 until the end of the volcano activity (11 weeks) for vertical 24/7 monitoring of the volcanic particles. Results of this work have been published in Córdoba-Jabonero *et al.* (2023), showing here the main conclusions.

First, a statistical study of the mass conversion factors for mass concentration estimation of the volcanic (ash and non-ash) particles was performed by using the AERONET sun/sky-photometer dataset at Fuencaliente (at around 18 km south from the volcano). A representative mass conversion factor was obtained for ash and non-ash particles: 1.89 ± 0.53 and 0.31 ± 0.06 g m⁻², respectively, with no dependence on time and optical depth. Second, these factors were used to calculate the ash and non-ash mass concentrations from P-MPL observations. Ash particles dominated 11% of the time and mostly until week 3 (i.e. week 7 from the volcanic eruption). Their mass concentration decreased by one order of magnitude: the relative ash mass contribution was $73 \pm 18\%$ with a total mass loading of 566 ± 281 mg m⁻² at week 1, reducing gradually down to $38 \pm 32\%$ and 120 ± 49 mg m⁻², respectively, at week 11. Layer-to-layer, it decreased with increasing layer-height;

no ash was detected above 4 km at the end of the volcanic period. Third, in order to analyse the potential AERONET underestimation of the coarse mass conversion factor due to the 15 µm cut-off effect in the AERONET retrieval, two worst-case-scenarios (WCS) were examined, representing aged-like ash particles (WCS1, 4-µm radius) and fresh-like (WCS2, 10-µm radius). For both scenarios, the mass concentration of the volcanic plumes exceeded the first contamination level (> 200 µg m⁻³, as defined by the UK Meteorological Office) up to 5-6 km height mostly during week 1 and up to 1-2 km until week 9. The extreme contamination level (> 2000 µg m⁻³, aircraft flight limitations) was only exceeded from week 1 to week 6 under WCS2 conditions.

This work infers a new long-term insight on the volcanic matter injected in the atmosphere with relevance for Air Quality issues and air traffic safety policies.

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Characterization of the Earth-atmosphere system conditions during a dust-induced heatwave in summertime 2022 over the SW Iberian Peninsula

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Extreme events (heatwaves, droughts, intense aerosol outbreaks, etc.) are linked to high perturbations in the radiative balance of the atmosphere by modifying the thermal equilibrium of the Earth-atmosphere system, hence affecting the climate. In particular, the aerosol-induced climatological implications cannot be unambiguously determined due to the uncertainties associated with the aerosol direct and indirect radiative effects. Among both, the indirect one remains more unclarified due to the lack of information on aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI) (Myhre et al., 2013). ACI represent one of the major mechanisms involved in the formation of clouds, with implications in their evolution, lifetime and precipitation, since their microphysical properties might be affected.

In this context, mineral dust is one of the most important aerosol types, by efficiently acting as either Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN) (Karydis et al., 2011) or Ice Nucleating Particles (INP) (DeMott et al., 2003). The potential occurrence of dust-induced CCNs or INPs can be differentiated by investigating the vertical temperature and relative humidity fields, which yield additional ingredients relevant for the cloud formation. Information on those cloud-relevant parameters is necessary for their implementation in climatic/weather modelling. Saharan air masses, which are warm and with (extremely) low water vapour content in summertime, can be transported over long distances. A frequently dust-influenced region is the Southern Iberian Peninsula (IP), relatively close to the Saharan desert sources, and prone to heatwave incidence. Active and passive remote sensing observations were performed during a summertime dust-induced heatwave at two close SW IP stations, Évora in Portugal (38.6°N 7.9°W, 293 m asl) and El Arenosillo/Huelva in Spain (37.1°N 6.7°W, 52 m asl). The purpose of this work is to vertically assess the potential impact of the dust particles in the likely production of CCNs (and/or INPs). In addition, associated changes in the temperature/humidity profiles under

those dusty conditions were analysed; both Copernicus land surface temperature (LST) and ECMWF temperature and relative humidity profiling databases were used; nucleation parametrization-based procedures were applied to obtain the CCN/INP concentrations (Mamouri and Ansmann, 2016).

The aim of this work is to present the variability of the Earth-atmosphere system conditions and potential/predicted occurrence of CCNs/INPs during a dust-induced heatwave as observed in June 2022 over IP from a holistic point of view. Results obtained from the characterization of that intense dust intrusion under heatwave conditions are examined for that purpose.

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Assessment of the vertically-resolved aerosol radiative effect during an intense dust outbreak over the Iberian Peninsula

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At this moment, humanity is confronted with a climate emergency. Focusing on radiative forcing, mineral dust plays a crucial role because of its direct impact when interacting with radiation. Since pre-industrial times, the dust mass that has lifted into the atmosphere from North African regions has increased by 46%. In this context, and according to the latest IPCC technical report, the frequency, intensity and duration of some extreme events are rising. Furthermore, not only there is an increased occurrence of Saharan dust outbreaks over the Iberian Peninsula (IP) in comparison to long-term records, but there is also a growing frame of research documenting extreme and intense episodes in that area.

This study focuses on the analysis of the vertically-resolved aerosol radiative effect during a long-lasting and intense Saharan dust outbreak over the IP. This event extended from the southwest to the northeast IP, and temporally from 25 March to 7 April 2021. The characterization of this dust outbreak was conducted across five Iberian lidar stations (see Fig. 1): Barcelona (BCN), Torrejón/Madrid (TRJ), Granada (GRA) and El Arenosillo/Huelva (ARN) in Spain, and Évora (EVO) in Portugal. The use of polarized lidar measurements, together with the two-step POLIPHON algorithm (Mamouri and Ansmann, 2014), allowed to distinguish fine (Df) and coarse (Dc) dust particles. This fact is significant, given that the potential impact of Df particles in the radiative budget has been mostly neglected, owing to dust intrusions are typically dominated by Dc particles.

Considering that the optical and mass properties of the extended event were well characterized in López-Cayuela *et al.* (2023), this work focuses on quantifying its dust direct radiative effect (DRE) in both shortwave (SW) and longwave (LW) ranges by using the radiative transfer model GAME (Dubuisson *et al.*, 1996), and carrying out a vertical DRE assessment, focused on the net effect and

heating rate. Moreover, this study introduces a novelty as compared to previous works: a comparative analysis of the dust DRE (DRE^{dust}) is performed, either considering each Df and Dc contribution to DRE separately (i.e. $DRE^{dust}=DRE^{Df}+DRE^{Dc}$), or only taking into account the DRE contribution of the total component ($DD=Df+Dc$), i.e. $DRE^{dust}=DRE^{DD}$, which is the usual procedure in other works. This work is particularly related to the upcoming ESA/JAXA EarthCARE mission to be launched in 2024.

Figure 1. MODIS reflectance over the Iberian Peninsula on 31 March 2021 (lidar stations marked in red).

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IAGOS in-situ profiling of air quality indicators above densely populated areas during the European heatwave 2022

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Nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), and aerosol particles are important air quality indicators which have anthropogenic and natural sources at ground (e.g.: transportation sector emissions, industry, agriculture, biomass burning) and within the troposphere (e.g.: lightning, aircraft emissions). Furthermore, their concentrations in the atmosphere are strongly affected by photochemistry.

The European Research Infrastructure IAGOS (Petzold *et al*, 2015; Thouret *et al*, 2022; www.iagos.org) monitors the vertical profiles of climate and air quality relevant trace gases like CO, O₃, (Nédélec *et al*, 2015), NO, NO₂ and NO_x (Berkes *et al*, 2018) near airports in highly populated urban areas (e.g.: Frankfurt (Main), Germany) during take-off and landing. These profiles provide essential information about the chemical composition of the lower troposphere, which is not available from surface-based stations or remote sensing instrumentation.

IAGOS can also detect layers of enhanced pollution level that were advected from distant source regions and have the potential to affect the urban air quality at the receptor site due to downmixing. Thus, IAGOS data provide valuable information complementary to the surface-based air quality network stations, facilitating the link to high-resolution models and satellite observations, such as the vertical profile of the NO to NO₂ ratio. The latter being difficult to retrieve from remote sensing measurements.

In our contribution, we characterize the variability and the vertical structure of these trace gases in the background atmosphere of the lower free troposphere that interacts with the urban boundary layer. During the European heatwave in 2022, IAGOS observed enhanced mixing ratios of boundary layer ozone up to altitudes of 2.5 km above Frankfurt (Main), see Figure 1. These observations will be put in relation to background profile measurements during periods without extreme heat load.

Figure 1. Afternoon profile over Frankfurt (Main) on 3 Aug 2022.

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Benefit of ground-based microwave radiometers for a better understanding of urban heat waves

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In order to better understand the impact of surface heterogeneities and mesoscale atmospheric conditions on urban heat islands, a network of three ground-based microwave radiometers (MWR) was deployed in the Paris region during summers 2022 and 2023. Providing continuous measurements of temperature profiles at a high temporal and vertical resolutions in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) as well as integrated water vapor and liquid water path, MWRs are key instruments to document the spatio-temporal variability of the ABL between the MWR urban site in the centre of Paris and two sub-urban sites approximately 30 km away from the city centre.

In this work, challenges to compare the measurements provided by several MWRs from different instrument generations with different data processing will be discussed. To that end, temperature and humidity retrievals performed in real time either with multi-variate regressions or neural networks trained from a climatology of radiosoundings will be evaluated against radiosoundings launched during Intensive Observation Periods (IOPs). We will show how temperature profiles with root-mean-square errors below 1.5 K can be retrieved and have comparable accuracy within the ABL while higher biases are observed in the free troposphere. A bias correction based on the continuous monitoring of brightness temperatures (BT) differences between MWR observations and simulated BT spectra from the AROME model will be proposed. Finally, an homogeneization of the retrievals of temperature and humidity profiles as well as LWP will be proposed thanks to the use of new retrieval algorithms.

After this first step of evaluation of MWR products, the temperature evolution between the MWR located in the centre of Paris and the two other MWR units located in sub-urban areas will be compared, focussing on several heat waves documented during the field experiments (Fig.1). First results have already highlighted significant differences in the ABL temporal evolution with a temperature increase starting up to 2 hours earlier

in the city centre compared to the sub-urban sites. The nocturnal cooling can also be delayed by several hours between the centre of Paris and sub-urban sites during major heat waves. Differences in the vertical structure of the ABL and more specifically on the thickness of the warm layer will also be documented and linked to the ABL dynamics. To that end, atmospheric stability provided by MWRs will be used as indicators of the ABL mixing and compared to information provided by Doppler Wind Lidars and Automatic Lidars Ceilometers. The link between atmospheric stability and both mechanical mixing and thermal stratification will be discussed.

Finally, first comparisons with the numerical weather prediction model AROME and fine scale modelling from the Meso-NH model will be presented to evaluate the capability of current NWP models as well as hectometre scale modelling to correctly represent the ABL spatio-temporal variability during urban heat waves.

Figure 1. Time series of temperature on 17 June 2022 observed in the centre of Paris (top panel) and the sub-urban site at SIRTA (bottom panel).

This work is conducted as part of the PANAME initiative and was supported by the WMO Research Demonstrator Project and ANR H2C.

Effect of wildfires on aerosol optical and microphysical properties, transport and ageing

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Keywords: aerosol optical depth, smoke, ageing.

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The historic heatwave and the outbreak of wildfires in 2021 in Greece led to significantly high aerosol optical depths (AOD) and Ångström exponent (AE) values in Athens during the month of August (Founda *et al* (2022), Masoom *et al* (2023)). On August 7, smoke plumes, that were transferred from the mainland, were detected over the island of Antikythera (PANGEA) in altitudes between 0.5–3.0 km above the surface (Figure 1).

The smoke over Athens and the transported smoke to PANhellenic GEophysical observatory of Antikythera (PANGEA) can be considered as fresh and aged smoke, respectively. The spectral aerosol absorption (single scattering albedo (SSA)) of smoke differs in magnitude (Figure 2), the median SSA decreases monotonically with wavelength at both sites, with the spectral decrease of SSA being more drastic at Athens.

Figure 1. (a) Polly^{XT} Lidar attenuation backscatter coefficient and (b) Hysplit 24-h backward trajectories at PANGEA, (c-d) Aeronet total, fine and coarse AOD, fine mode fraction (FMF) at 500 nm and AE at Athens and PANGEA on August 07, 2021.

The aging of the smoke plume leads to aerosol removal due to dispersion, coagulation, or sedimentation with distance and time leading to a shift from accumulation mode towards coarse mode.

Figure 2. (a) Normalised mean volume size distribution, (b) mean spectral single scattering albedo, (c) fine mode volume median radius and (d) mean spectral real and imaginary refractive indices at Athens and PANGEA on August 07, 2021.

This study aims to explain the changes in optical properties changes during smoke transport from Athens to PANGEA and their attribution to possible physical and chemical processes for these changes.

This work was supported by the ACTRIS-CH (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure – Swiss contribution) funded by the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, Switzerland.

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Characteristics of biomass burning-derived aerosols during the traditional “Burning of the Witches” in the Czech Republic

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Open biomass burning (OBB) is a major source of air pollutants, with global, regional, and local impacts on air quality, public health, and climate (Chen et al., 2017). This study focuses on the impact of open combustion of biomass during the traditional “burning of the witches” (BoW) on the physicochemical properties and evolution of aerosols collected at the ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) site National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice (NAOK), in the Czech Republic (49°35'N, 15°05'E).

The BoW is an old pagan tradition celebrated in the Czech Republic during the night from April 30 to May 1 by lighting bonfires made of woodpiles with fake witches. Several chemical (carbonaceous and inorganic components) and physical (particle size distribution, light absorption, and scattering) properties of atmospheric aerosol were measured 5 days before (pre-) and after (post-) the BoW in 2023 (Table 1).

Table 1. Aerosol measurements at the NAOK during April 25 - May 5, 2023.

Measured parameters	Instruments
Elemental (EC) and organic carbon (OC)	OCEC analyzer, Sunset Laboratory Inc., USA
Equivalent black carbon (eBC) and light absorption (δ_{ab})	AE33, Magee Scientific
Total light scattering (δ_{sc}) and backscattering (δ_{bsc})	Aurora 3000, Ecotech
Size-resolved NR-PM ₁ (organics, SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , NH ₄ ⁺ , Cl ⁻ , and PAHs)	C-ToF-AMS, Aerodyne
Particle number size distribution	MPSS, TROPOS-Leipzig
Elemental composition	Xact® 625i, Cooper Environmental
PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀ mass	MP101M, Environnement SA

The OBB emissions during the BoW led to a significant change in the aerosol chemical composition

and optical properties, and chemical aging and fast size growth were observed over the BoW-night. The concentrations of the aerosol chemical components and aerosol absorption and scattering coefficients measured during the BoW were significantly higher than the values observed before and after the BoW (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The BoW to pre- and post- BoW ratios measured for different aerosol chemical species and optical properties.

During the BoW, eBC consisted mainly of eBC_{BB} (>90%). The particle number concentration sharply increased during the BoW, with a distinct peak in the 10-20 nm mode due to the fresh OBB emissions and a rapid size growth over the night (shift towards larger sizes). The freshest BB emissions identified by the AMS method (Cubison et al., 2011) were dominated by the organics, accompanied by NO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ (shift towards smaller size, unlike SO₄²⁻).

The research leading to these results was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic within the Large Research Infrastructure Support Project - ACTRIS Participation of the Czech Republic (ACTRIS-CZ LM2023030), and within the CzeCOS program, grant number LM2023048.

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Extreme wildfires over northern Greece during summer 2023: Investigating the effects on aerosol optical properties and solar radiation

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Keywords: Remote Sensing, aerosols, wildfires

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The Mediterranean region witnesses frequent summer smoke incidents, favoured by stable weather conditions due to the absence of precipitation. During the second half of August 2023, Greece has suffered a series of wildfires that have burned a large swath of the Dadia forest in Alexandroupoli (Evros; 41.11°E, 26.22°N). During this event, air quality in the Greek mainland was substantially affected, and the emitted smoke stretched hundreds of miles toward Italy and Northern parts of Africa. In this work, the impact of these fires on the air quality and surface radiation levels of Thessaloniki are examined.

Figure 1. Time series of spectral AOD measured by LAP-AUTH AERONET sun photometer during August 2023.

Aerosol observations were performed by the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics, Thessaloniki, Greece (LAP-AUTH; <https://lapweb.physics.auth.gr/>; 40.6°N, 22.95°W, 60 m asl) during the biomass burning event. LAP-AUTH, as a member of many monitoring networks, is one of the best equipped atmospheric observatories in southern Europe, and a key site for ACTRIS, the European Research Infrastructure for aerosol, clouds, and trace gases investigation (www.actris.eu). LAP-AUTH is equipped with several remote sensing instruments for aerosol and radiation monitoring such as the ones used in this work, a Raman-depolarization lidar system (Michailidis et al., 2023), a MAX-DOAS system (Karagiozidis et al., 2023), two Brewer spectrophotometers (Bais et al., 1996) and a Cimel Sun-photometer operating in the framework of Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET; Holben et al., 1998). The operational LAP-AUTH measurements allowed the monitoring of the fresh smoke aerosol evolution, as well

as the analysis of its optical and geometrical properties in horizontal and vertical extents. Sunphotometric measurements showed extreme aerosol optical depth values (AOD), reaching nearly 3.5 in the UV wavelength range (Fig. 1), extremely above the climatological mean (~0.45 in August), which was accompanied by a strong reduction in solar irradiance at ground level. Elevated smoke plumes were detected at altitudes of 3.5–6.5 km by lidar measurements and HYSPLIT trajectories confirmed that the detected air masses passed over the burning areas before reaching LAP-AUTH.

The presented wildfire event allowed the in-depth investigation of the atmospheric composition and its impact on solar radiation using synergistically active and passive remote sensing instruments. Wildfires are part of the wider problem for Mediterranean countries, and the frequency of summer wildfires is predicted to increase in view of the projected increasing occurrence of summer heatwaves (Zittis et al., 2022).

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Estimation of the radiative impact of smoke aerosols from forest-fires, using two different algorithms to retrieve aerosol properties from CALIPSO

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Keywords: radiative effects, forest-fire aerosols, CALIOP, libRadtran, POLIPHON, ASSA

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We present the local radiative impact of aerosols emitted by the forest-fires in Greece, on the 8th of August 2021 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Wildfires in Greece on 8 August 2021 (by NASA Earth Observatory, <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/148682/fire-consumes-large-swaths-of-greece>, public domain).

This event is only one out of many similar events occurring in the eastern Mediterranean region in August 2021, due to a powerful heat dome, nicknamed “Lucifer” (Eberle and Higuera Roa, 2022). On this particular day, the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation (CALIPSO, https://www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov/resources/calipso_users_guide/data_summaries/index.php#lidar) passed over central Greece, which was greatly affected by the forest-fires on that day (Massom *et al.*, 2023). In this study, we use the aerosol optical properties of the layers emitted by these forest-fires, as provided by the Cloud-Aerosol Lidar with Orthogonal Polarization (CALIOP) on board the CALIPSO satellite and the libRadtran radiative model (Emde *et al.*, 2016; Mayer and Kylling, 2005) to estimate their local radiative effects.

Towards this goal, we use two different methods to derive the aerosol properties required as input to the radiative transfer simulations: The 1st is the Polarization Lidar Photometer Networking (POLIPHON) method (Mamouri and Ansmann, 2014) which permits the retrieval of aerosol-type-dependent microphysical properties including the volume concentration. The 2nd method is the Aerosol Species Separation Algorithm (ASSA) (Siomos *et al.*, 2021) which permits the retrieval of the vertical concentration profiles of individual aerosol species similar to the Optical Properties of Aerosols and Clouds (OPAC) (Koepke *et al.*, 2015), which can then be directly used in libRadtran. The results are then compared to evaluate the different simulation techniques.

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Lidar and sun-photometer observations of Saharan dust loads above Sofia, Bulgaria, during the July 2023 extreme heat waves over Europe

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Keywords: heat wave, aerosol, dust, lidar, sun photometer.

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In July 2023, Europe was affected by a series of heat waves caused by a high anticyclone centered over the Central Mediterranean and North Africa. In Bulgaria, in the period 9-26 July, near-surface temperatures were in the range of 35-40 °C, reaching locally 40-43 °C, being well above climatic norms throughout the country. The extreme heat waves were accompanied by a massive transport of Saharan dust over the Mediterranean and South Europe, including the Balkan Peninsula.

The Sofia EARLINET/ACTRIS station conducted systematic monitoring of desert dust loads throughout the heat wave period. Lidar measurements were performed using a Raymetrics 8-channel Depolarization Raman lidar LR332-D300 ($3\beta-2\alpha-2\delta$), whereas solar irradiance measurements are conducted by a collocated 9-channel Cimel CE318-TS9 sun/sky/lunar photometer.

Modelling/forecasting data from online available web-resources were also used for characterization of aerosol/dust transport (by MONARCH, SKIRON, NOAA HYSPLIT models and MODIS satellite imagery), as well as those for (re)analysis of related climatic and climatological conditions and factors (by NOAA-PSL NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis, Meteorological profiles and data). Air transport data show strong direct transfer of dust-containing air masses from Northwest Africa northeastward to the Sofia region. The dust plume reached Bulgaria on 12 July and remained until 26 July with dust load values of near 1000 mg/m².

Daytime and nighttime lidar measurements were carried out throughout the period noted above. Presented here are results obtained on 13 July, at the height of the initial dust intrusion. Quicklooks for this date show the presence of a main aerosol/dust layer extending up to 5-5.3 km asl, dominated by the densest dust sublayer in the 2.3-4 km range, as well as overlying weak dust layers up to about 7 km asl.

Vertical profiles of the aerosol/dust backscatter (at 1064, 532 and 355 nm) were retrieved from both the daytime and nighttime lidar measurements. Profiles of aerosol extinction and lidar ratio at 355 nm and 532 nm were retrieved from measurements conducted with the nighttime lidar configuration with Raman channels at 387 and 607 nm. Results from the nighttime measurements carried out on 13 July are shown in Figure 1. The obtained mean range-resolved values of the aerosol extinction (α), backscatter (β), and lidar ratio (S) are: $\alpha(532) = 39.87 \pm 4.62 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$, $\alpha(355) = 51.37 \pm 13.48 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$; $\beta(1064) =$

$0.77 \pm 0.2 \text{ Mm}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$, $\beta(532) = 1.13 \pm 0.39 \text{ Mm}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$, $\beta(355) = 2.14 \pm 0.44 \text{ Mm}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$; $S(532) = 39.89 \pm 4.62 \text{ sr}$, $S(355) = 25.06 \pm 3.11 \text{ sr}$. The extinction-related Ångström exponent varies from about 1 near the surface to about 0.1-0.2 up into the dust layer, indicating a dominance of coarse dust fractions.

Figure 1. Vertical profiles of the aerosol backscatter (a), extinction (b), and lidar ratio (c).

A set of AERONET columnar aerosol parameters such as total and fractional aerosol optical depth (AOD), Ångström exponent (AE), volume size distribution (VSD), lidar ratio (LR) and linear depolarization ratio (LDR) were also obtained and analyzed. Their daily means and standard deviations for 13 July are as follows: AOD: 0.15 ± 0.02 (1640 nm) - 0.37 ± 0.04 (340 nm); LR: 71.28 ± 8.91 (440 nm) - 46.71 ± 4.98 (1020 nm); LDR: 0.13 ± 0.02 (440 nm) - 0.23 ± 0.01 (1020 nm); AE: 0.55 ± 0.07 (500/870 nm) - 0.70 ± 0.08 (380/500 nm); $\text{AOD}(\text{Coarse})/\text{AOD}(\text{Fine}) = 1.64$ (500 nm), with coarse mode peak being near 2 μm . These columnar aerosol parameters are typical of aerosols dominated by coarse mode desert dust, being in agreement with the results obtained from the lidar measurements.

Conclusions are drawn about the impacts of the extremely warm air masses rich in desert dust on the structure and composition of the troposphere over Sofia, as well as on the local weather, ecosystem and human health in the considered heat-wave period.

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Lidar observations of wildfire smoke in Cyprus during 2021-2023

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Increased heat and extended drought, parameters inextricably connected with climate change, have been the key drivers in amplifying the wildfire risk worldwide. Studies indicate escalating wildfire threats in Southern Europe due to climate warming (Dupuy et al., 2020), and the US already experiences extended wildfire seasons and heightened frequency (Markon et al., 2018; Westerling, 2016). It is well-known that smoke particles play an important role in the climate system and affect the air quality in many regions of the world. Therefore, it is of great importance to investigate the properties of smoke particles with focus on their optical and microphysical properties.

In this presentation, we focus on the statistical analysis of particle optical and microphysical properties observed in the atmosphere of Cyprus during wildfire smoke events in the summer of the period 2021-2023. Emphasis is given to the intense activity of wildfires in Turkey's Mediterranean Region in July and August 2021 as well as in Greece during the summer of 2023 that caused tragic human losses and devastating ecological, environmental, and economic disasters. These events motivated us to study the optical properties of smoke at different aging levels (or duration of the long-range transport). Backward trajectories, generated with the HYSPLIT model, helped us determine the origin of the air masses and the time at which they arrived at Limassol site.

Observations were made with a multiwavelength polarization Raman lidar, Polly (POrtable Lidar sYstem) (Engelmann et al., 2016), which is operated at the Cyprus Atmospheric Remote Sensing Observatory (CARO) of the Eratosthenes Centre of Excellence at Limassol (34.677° N, 33.0375° E). The Polly instrument used, allows the measurement of height profiles of the particle backscatter coefficient β at 355, 532, and 1064 nm, the particle extinction coefficient α at 355 and 532 nm, the corresponding lidar ratios L , as well as the volume and particle linear depolarization ratios at 355 and 532 nm. In this study, we present a statistical analysis of the selective cases with respect to the geometrical and optical properties. To achieve this, we made use of 60-90 minutes nighttime observations (20:00-21:00 UTC and 01:00-02:30 UTC) for which Raman lidar method (Ansmann et al., 1992) was applied.

In addition, the polarization-lidar photometer networking (POLIPHON) method (Mamouri and Ansmann, 2014) was applied for the estimation of the smoke mass concentration. Conversion factors needed for the conversion of the smoke particle extinction coefficients into respective particle microphysical properties were determined from the sunphotometer observations in Limassol, Cyprus, belonging to AERONET.

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Properties of heavy precipitation events during the CyCARE campaign

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Keywords: distribution, clouds, Cyprus.

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One of the direct effects of climate change in some parts of the World is the change in the precipitation intensity and frequency. While total precipitation is likely to decrease, it is expected that the intensity and frequency of the heavy precipitation events will increase. Such intense events can cause landslides, and floods can have an immediate short-term impact on everyday activities, but can also produce damages with long-term effects.

Cyprus and the rest of the East-Mediterranean and Middle-East is a region of the World where climate change impacts will be quite adverse (Zittis, 2022). However, research infrastructure in this region is relatively sparse compared with other regions (e.g., Europe). Until recently, observations on atmospheric chemistry and physics processes were done using data collected during campaigns or intensive observation periods, lasting from a couple of weeks to several months. It is worth mentioning here the PreTect, A-LiFE or CyCARE experiments. Only recently, research infrastructure that samples in situ or remote sensing are made permanently available in the region (e.g., Cyprus).

CyCARE was conducted from October 2016 and March 2018, when the TROPOS-LACROS setup was deployed in Limassol, Cyprus (Radenz, 2021). The setup consisted of a 35 GHz cloud radar, ceilometer, microwave radiometer and a disdrometer of type OTT Parsivel². A multiwavelength Raman lidar and a Doppler wind lidar also allowed measurements to observe aerosol-cloud-dynamics interaction. A sun-photometer measuring since 2010 in Limassol was used to provide complementary column-integrated aerosol information.

In this paper, we present the properties of the vertical structure of the atmosphere during strong precipitation events observed in the CyCARE campaign.

Strong precipitation events were selected from the disdrometer data. The original data, with sampling at every 30 seconds, were resampled at 10 minutes, and from this the 95-percentile was selected as the threshold ($p_{95} = 115\text{mm/h}$ for total precipitation during 10 minutes). It resulted in a total of 75 events, occurring during 41 different days out of the total 515 days of the CyCARE campaign. These events are distributed from October to March, and for each month the number of events is presented in Table 1.

For the selected events the ice and liquid water content were investigated (Hogan, 2006), and from the

cloud-radar observations the rain rate, Doppler velocity and reflectivity factor were selected. Figure 1 presents the distribution of the numbers of particles per diameter class of the events where the 10-minute average precipitation rate is above the 95-percentile threshold.

Table 1 Number of events with accumulated rain in 10 minutes higher than the 95 percentile.

2016		2017					2018		
Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb
2	20	9	1	9	3	7	6	11	7

CyCARE dataset is used as a reference because as from spring 2024, Limassol will become a permanent ACTRIS Cloud Remote Sensing station, with a similar setup of instruments as deployed during the campaign. The efforts of building an aerosol and cloud remote sensing station in Limassol are supported by the H2020 Excelsior project.

Figure 1 Number of particles per diameter class during the heavy precipitation events.

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An Intensive Biomass Burning Aerosol Observation in 2022, over Skukuza, South Africa: Preliminary Results

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Keywords: Aerosol, Biomass burning, Southern Africa, river of smoke.

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The Southern Hemisphere is known to have significant main sources of carbonaceous aerosols from both Southern Africa (SA) and South America (SAM). These regions are known to have seasonal Biomass Burning (BB) activity, from June to November, which has the potential to emit pollutants, such as carbon monoxide (CO) and aerosols, both of which are harmful to the environment and human health.

During the 2022 BB season, the Biomass Burning Aerosols Campaign (BiBAC) has been conducted in the Kruger National Park (KNP), at Skukuza in South Africa. BiBAC aimed to quantify the optical properties of aerosols over SA and the Southwestern Indian Ocean (SWIO) basin, as well as the transport of plumes at several scales. During the Intensive Observational Phase (IOP) of BiBAC, a panel of instruments were deployed at KNP: a mobile lidar, ground-based and in-situ optical particles counter (LOAC, Light Optical Aerosols Counter), and a mobile monitoring station.

Measurements of the KNP's sun photometer during the IOP were compared with the whole data set (1998–2011 and 2016–2021). Multiyear monthly average of aerosol optical depth (AOD) and Angström Exponent show values from 0.2 to 0.3 and 1.2 to 1.5, respectively. These values are similar to those reported by Ranaivombola *et al* (2023) during the BB season. Daily measurements through the IOP were in line with multiyear average values, except for two periods: mid-September and mid-October. These two periods were chosen statistically according to quartile 3 (Q3) of the relative difference (RD) between the daily observations during the IOP and the whole data set. We considered each AOD value for which the RD value was above Q3 and considered a day before and after each period. This approach allows to define two events: September 18 to 23 and October 9 to 17, called here after event 1 and event 2, respectively. Using aerosol classification from sun photometer measurements, both events reveal a prevalence of BB and urban industrial aerosols, with a predominance of BB and moderately absorbing aerosols, based on the method used by Kumar *et al* (2020) and Ranaivombola *et al* (2023).

By combining satellite observations (Total column of CO from IASI and AOD from MODIS-Aqua) and CAMS reanalysis (AOD and mean sea level pressure), the southward and eastward transport of AOD and CO

plumes from BB areas in SA and toward the SWIO basin is highlighted.

During event 1, the plume was driven by two high-pressure cells in the Atlantic Ocean and SWIO basin, leading to the formation of the so-called “river of smoke” (Swap *et al* 2003, and Flamant *et al* 2022). As reported in both works, the meteorological conditions were influenced by westerly waves associated with a cut-off low (COL) that favored the eastern transport pathway. However, in our event 1 the westerly wave was not converted into a COL.

During event 2, two high-pressure systems moved from the Atlantic Ocean to the SWIO basin, crossing over the southern part of the continent. Unlike event 1, the presence of these two high-pressure cells may have limited the spread of the plume over the continent and its breakout into the SWIO Basin. Our study also examines the large-scale transport of BB plumes from SAM across the Atlantic Ocean. Since the BB activity is coincident in SA and SAM, the impact of Amazonian BB activity should be considered.

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Mineral dust intensive study within the aerosol and cloud remote sensing infrastructure at Cape Verde

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Keywords: AOT, Mineral dust, Aerosol

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Within the framework of ACTRIS-D, we implemented instruments for an aerosol and a cloud remote sensing facility in Mindelo (Sao Vicente, Cape Verde). Permanent measurements of aerosol components began in 2021 with a Multiwavelength-Raman-polarization-lidar, PollyXT (a new EARLINET and PollyNET station, Baars et al., 2016), and a CIMEL-318 Sun photometer (AERONET station). Cloud components were added in 2023, including a HATPRO-G5 microwave radiometer, a Streamline Doppler wind lidar, and a 94-GHz RPG cloud radar (Cloudnet station).

This permanent station in the tropical North Atlantic provides detailed information on the unique atmospheric aerosol and cloud conditions above Cape Verde. The location is crucial for investigating the transport of dust and biomass-burning aerosols from Africa towards South and Central America. Additionally, it serves as an optimal site for satellite validation. Together with our ARS stations in Dushanbe (Tajikistan) and Limassol (Cyprus), we observe the optical properties of atmospheric aerosols, with a primary focus on mineral dust in the so-called dust belt.

Our lidar measurements in Cape Verde indicate that the atmosphere above the station is nearly constantly influenced by Saharan mineral dust, either as pure dust or as dust mixture (e.g., biomass-burning aerosol). We will present a statistical analysis of the obtained optical and resulting microphysical properties of the atmospheric aerosol, leveraging nearly two years of continuous lidar measurements (particle backscatter coefficient at 3 wavelengths - 355 nm, 532 nm, and 1064 nm -, the extinction coefficient at 355 nm, 532 nm, and the depolarization ratio at 3 wavelengths). We will showcase the resulting microphysical properties for some highlighted cases.

The detected aerosol layers with the lidar indicate that, usually, in the northern hemispheric winter season, the aerosol layer (a mixture with Saharan dust) is located below approximately 3 km height and occasionally is mixed down to the ground, while in the northern hemispheric summer season, the relatively pure Saharan dust layer extends up to 6 km height. Below approximately 1 km height is a layer of marine aerosol.

In Figure 1, we present an overview of the Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT) from our AERONET Sun photometer measurements at the station since 2021 (start of the measurements in July). On average, the AOT

is lower during winter times and higher during summer. We observe some cases of exceptionally high AOT within the two-year period.

On the 21st of August in 2021 the measured AOT at 500 nm was 1.95. The lidar measurements show a strong dust layer. An analysis with POLYPHON (Polarization Lidar Photometer Networking) reveals a dust-related backscatter coefficient (532 nm) of $\sim 20 \text{ Mm}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1}$. The quasi particle depolarisation ratio at 532 nm is 0.25 – 0.3 in the dust layer.

Figure 1. AERONET Aerosol optical thickness at 500 nm from the years 2021 - 2023. The level 2 data points are measured with a CIMEL Sun photometer and have been reprocessed.

Our presentation will provide a thorough analysis of aerosol conditions above Mindelo, Cape Verde, emphasizing significant findings from two years of continuous lidar measurements. Furthermore, we will present recent cloud measurements, providing insights into cloud composition.

We thank our local partners at Cape Verde (Instituto Nacional de Meteorologia e Geofisica, INMG) and the authorities, as well as national and international partners working at CVAO, CVOO, and OSCM (York University, UK; MPI for Biogeochemistry, Jena; GEOMAR, Kiel).

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Volatile organic compound characterization and reactivity at a mixed forest site in the Belgian Ardennes during the July 2022 heat wave over Europe

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Keywords: volatile organic compounds, OH reactivity, source attribution

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Reactive volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are significant precursors of gaseous pollutants (such as ozone) and secondary organic aerosol (SOA), thus affecting both air quality and climate. Because of their high reactivity, they strongly contribute to the atmospheric oxidation capacity.

In July 2022, Europe was hit with a large heat wave and an intensive EMEP/ACTRIS O₃ and VOC campaign (12-19/07/2022) was organised, aiming at a better prediction of high O₃ episodes. As part of this campaign, ambient air was sampled on canisters, DNPH cartridges and TENAX/Carbopack sorbent tubes once a day during a fixed sampling period at the EMEP station in the vicinity of the mixed forest ICOS ecosystem site at Vielsalm (50°18'18.2"N, 5°59'53.0"E, 450 m.a.s.l.). Samples were analysed for (oxygenated) VOCs by HPLC-MS and GC-MS by reference laboratories. These offline measurements were complemented by online above-canopy PTR-TOF-MS VOC concentration measurements (PTR-TOF-4000, Ionicon Analytik GmbH) performed at the 52-m high tower located at the ICOS ecosystem site in Vielsalm.

The 2022 PTR-TOF-MS dataset (covering April to November) has been used for preliminary source characterization of reactive carbon in the mixed forest ecosystem with the aim to (i) identify and localize VOC sources, and (ii) investigate their contribution to OH reactivity. As shown in Fig. 1, seven factors which contribute to OH-reactivity in different manners were identified by non-negative matrix factorization (NMF). These factors were labelled according to the major VOC contributor per factor. As expected in a mixed forest environment, OH-reactivity is dominated by the isoprene and the monoterpenes factors. Peaks in OH-reactivity owing to high contribution of the monoterpenes source factor were linked to the sawmill emissions located southwest of the site and are restricted mostly to nighttime occurrences.

Simultaneous offline chromatographic (available around noon, sampling periods represented by vertical lines in Fig. 1) and online PTR-TOF-MS measurements allow for intercomparison between measurement techniques. Results of the intercomparison for some specific compounds will be shown, and potential reasons

for differences in concentrations will be discussed. Furthermore, the availability of multiple VOC analysis techniques allows maximizing the number of measured compounds for calculation of OH-reactivity at the site. We will compare calculated OH-reactivity from each individual technique to the combination of data to discuss the representativeness of different instruments. Deviations between PTR-TOF-MS and chromatography based OH-reactivity calculations will be investigated in function of different source factors.

Fig. 1. (top) Hourly average VOC-related OH-reactivity as determined from calibrated PTR-TOF-MS measurements (black dots) and from NMF source factors (colours).

Error bars represent the standard deviation of OH-reactivity determined on minute resolution. Dashed red and solid green vertical lines correspond with sampling periods for offline quantification of VOCs by reference laboratories. (bottom) Ratio of OH-reactivity calculated using NMF source factors relative to those calculated directly with PTR-TOF-MS measurements.

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Immersion ice-nucleating particle detection within wildfire plumes in Payerne, Switzerland

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Keywords: ice-nucleating particle, mixed-phase cloud, wildfire plume, biomass burning aerosol

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Ice crystals occurring in mixed-phase clouds (MPCs) play a vital role in global precipitation and energy balance. The unstable equilibrium between coexisting liquid droplets and ice crystals in MPCs affects cloud lifetime and radiative properties, as well as precipitation formation. As such, aerosol-cloud-climate interactions have been a persistent source of uncertainty in determining anthropogenic forcing, climate sensitivity and the climate effects of aerosols (IPCC, 2021).

Field observation of atmospheric INP number concentration (N_{INP}) could provide first-hand data, allowing for parameterization in models and lay the foundation of accurately quantifying the indirect climate effect of aerosols. As part of the Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) cloud in-situ (CIS) measurement, two automated horizontal ice nucleation chambers (HINC-Auto; Brunner and Kanji, 2021) have been collecting immersion N_{INP} data ($-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH}_w = 104\%$) at Jungfraujoch (3580 m a.s.l., $46^{\circ}33'\text{ N}$, $7^{\circ}59'\text{ E}$) and Payerne (491 m a.s.l., $46^{\circ}48'\text{ N}$, $6^{\circ}56'\text{ E}$) for over 18 and 4 months, respectively.

In this work, we present preliminary results from the PERICLES Campaign in Payerne performed from May to June 2023, during which the biomass burning aerosols (BBAs) within wildfire plumes from N. America and S. Germany (as indicated by back trajectory analysis) have been observed to affect the local aerosol concentration. Several online instruments provide aerosol physico-chemical properties including total number concentration (N_{total} ; CPC 3757, TSI), size distribution (MPSS, TROPOS; Fidas 200, Palas), chemical composition (ACSM, Aerodyne), black carbon mass concentration (m_{BC} ; MAAAP, Thermo Scientific), fluorescent aerosol number concentration (Rapid-E, Plair SA), as well as vertical aerosol profiles (RALMO UV Raman lidar, MeteoSuisse; Elastic-fluorescence lidar, EPFL).

Overall, N_{INP} does not show a clear diurnal pattern and there is no clear correlation between N_{INP} and m_{BC} (Figure 1a, Pearson correlation coefficient $r = 0$), as well as between N_{INP} and N_{total} . An absence of correlation in a region heavily affected by traffic emissions is in

agreement with previous studies that aerosols from anthropogenic emissions are not effective immersion INP (e.g., Zhang et al., 2022). There are two periods between May 9 and 17, as well as between May 27 and June 2, when average N_{INP} is higher ($6.9 \pm 7.0\ \text{\#}/\text{stdL}$) than campaign average ($2.5 \pm 5.6\ \text{\#}/\text{stdL}$). During these two periods, N_{INP} shows a higher positive correlation with m_{BC} (Figure 1b and 1c). After minimizing the impact of anthropogenic emission during daytime (8:00 – 21:00), the correlation between nighttime (21:00 – 8:00) N_{INP} and m_{BC} during these two periods becomes stronger ($r = 0.4$). The spikes of m_{BC} during nighttime are most likely linked to BBA within wildfire plume, suggesting the potential of aged and fresh BBA to contribute to atmospheric immersion freezing at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The contribution of pollen and Saharan dust to N_{INP} remains to be explored.

Figure 1. Ice-nucleating particle number concentration N_{INP} ($-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) shows a higher correlation (as indicated by the Pearson correlation coefficient r) with black carbon mass concentration m_{BC} during biomass burning aerosol plume events during night-time (21:00-8:00 local time).

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THEME 4 - INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODOLOGIES FOR ATMOSPHERIC PROBING, INCLUDING CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION OF SATELLITE ATMOSPHERIC MISSIONS

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Machine Learning-Based Global Calibration Models for Air Quality Low-Cost Sensors

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Keywords: Low-cost Sensors, Air quality, Machine learning.

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Deploying high-density sensor networks would enhance the analysis of air quality and lead to the development of effective mitigation strategies. Even though low-cost sensor networks can achieve high spatial resolution, concerns about their accuracy and reliability have been raised. Therefore, researchers are exploring the integration of machine learning techniques into sensor calibration to reduce costs and efforts associated with traditional methods and to improve sensor performance.

In this study, we examined the transferability of machine-learning-based calibration models among low-cost sensor units targeting NO₂ and NO. A global model is expected to reduce calibration costs by eliminating the need for individual calibrations in a network of tens or hundreds of low-cost sensors. This study utilized data obtained from four low-cost sensor units located in three different sites within Switzerland. The global models were evaluated under similar and different emission conditions, referred to as Case A and Case B, respectively. The study proposed integrating O₃ measurements from nearby reference stations (Fig. 1) to counter cross-sensitivity.

Figure 1. Map view of low-cost sensors co-location sites (ZUE and LAU) featuring nearby monitoring stations, in both Zurich and Lausanne (© Google Earth 2023).

The results of this study (Fig. 2) showed excellent calibration transferability between sensor units of similar emission conditions (Case A), with the average model performance being $R^2 = 0.90 \pm 0.05$ and $RMSE = 3.4 \pm 0.9$ ppb for NO₂ and $R^2 = 0.97 \pm 0.02$ and $RMSE = 3.1 \pm 0.8$ ppb for NO. There is also relatively good

transferability between sensor units with different emission conditions (Case B), with the average performance for NO₂ being $R^2 = 0.65 \pm 0.08$ and $RMSE = 5.5 \pm 0.4$ ppb, and $R^2 = 0.82 \pm 0.05$ and $RMSE = 5.8 \pm 0.8$ ppb for NO. Interestingly, the results illustrate a substantial improvement in the calibration models when integrating O₃ measurements (i.e. higher R^2 and lower RMSE), which is more pronounced when sensors are situated in regions with elevated O₃ concentrations. The proposed methodology is adaptable to various low-cost sensors targeting different pollutants. Finally, the study underscores the significance of leveraging publicly available data to enhance the reliability of low-cost air quality sensors.

Figure 2. Average performance of global machine-learning-based calibration models (MLR, SVR and RF) for NO and NO₂, in both cases A and B. O₃ measurements were obtained from "Station Z1" in Zurich and "Station L1" in Lausanne.

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First ACTRIS intercomparison for nitrogen oxides (NO_x) at Research Centre Jülich

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ACTRIS (Aerosol, Cloud and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) is a pan-European research infrastructure which aims to build a network of observation stations that provide high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric components and make them openly accessible to users around the world. Within ACTRIS, the Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas) is responsible for the quality assurance (QA), measurement guidelines and calibration protocols for reactive trace gases such as nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), also referred to as NO_x. These two compounds play a key role in atmospheric chemistry, contributing to the formation of tropospheric ozone, smog and acid rain. However, the quantification of NO_x remains challenging on account of the short lifetime and large spatiotemporal variation.

A total of 38 instruments were intercompared in summer 2023 as part of the intercomparison campaign at the CiGas unit, the Research Center Jülich, Germany. Participants from 18 institutions in Europe from present and future national facilities, both observational and exploratory, took part in the campaign. The NO_x measurement techniques comprised of Chemiluminescence Detectors (CLD), Tunable Diode Quantum Cascade Lasers (TDQCL), Iterative CAvity-enhanced Differential optical absorption spectrometers (ICAD), Cavity Attenuated Phase Shift instruments (CAPS), IBBCEAS (Incoherent BroadBand Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy), Cavity Ring-Down Spectrometers (CRDS), photoacoustic sensors (PAS), and a Long Path Absorption Photometer (LOPAP).

Trace gases, dry and humid air were introduced into a common sampling PFA line using a custom-built Controlled Evaporation Mixing (CEM) system. Daily calibrations were performed using a reference gas standard for NO and gas phase titration from NO and ozone for NO₂ to evaluate sensitivity drifts of the instruments. The participants calibrated their instruments prior to and after the campaign with their own calibration procedures.

The addition of humidity and ozone impacted the quantification of NO_x in CLD and CAPS instruments. However, these effects can be corrected for. In addition, we investigated the interference effects of nitrous acid (HONO), glyoxal (CHOCHO), formaldehyde (HCHO) and alkyl nitrates and alkyl nitrites on the instruments. CLD equipped with photolytic converters photolyzed glyoxal resulting in a negative interference whereas CAPS instruments exhibited a positive glyoxal interference.

CLDs equipped with molybdenum converters were showing a HONO interference. Alkyl nitrates also caused interferences in some instruments, while isobutyl nitrite was found to be photolyzed by photolytic converters. Furthermore, measurements in ambient air from the JULIAC tower at a height of 50m were compared. The results of the intercomparison campaign will be presented.

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Results from a 2-months rehearsal campaign as part of the preparation activities for the validation of the upcoming EarthCARE mission

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Keywords: Cal/Val, EarthCARE, remote sensing, ATMO ACCESS, ACTRIS.

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In the framework of the ATMO ACCESS pilot activities for internal stakeholders, a project has been initiated to support the validation of the European Space Agency's (ESA) EarthCARE mission.

EarthCARE is an Earth Explorer Mission scheduled for launch in May 2024 that will perform observations of the atmosphere using a high spectral resolution lidar, a Doppler cloud radar, a multi-spectral imager and a broadband radiometer. It can thus be considered as a space-based ACTRIS aerosol and cloud remote sensing observatory.

To meet the extensive validation needs of these novel spaceborne observations, the ATMO ACCESS pilot was utilized for a dedicated project, resulting in a consortium of 46 participating observatories plus the ACTRIS central facilities, i.e., the ACTRIS Topic Centres CARS & CCRES and the ACTRIS Data Centres CLU & ARES. A sketch of the planned 16-month activity is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Timeline of the pilot activity for the EarthCARE validation.

The main goal of the initiative was to establish a near-real-time work and data flow to be ready at EarthCARE launch for immediate validation activities. This involves carrying out measurements at the National Facilities and other associated stations, performing quality assurance tests that are analysed and approved by the TCs, and implementing a data flow in near-real time from the observatories to the centralized data processing units and from there, with a preliminary but ad hoc quality

control, to the ACTRIS data portal. From there, ESA's Validation Data Centre (EVDC) will be able to harvest the metadata of the observations collocated with satellite overpasses to provide them to ESA experts who can then use the data for validation analysis.

A rehearsal campaign was conducted from October to November 2023 to test the established workflow and identify potential improvements.

During the 2-month rehearsal campaign, the ACTRIS aerosol and cloud remote sensing facilities and some associated stations performed observations according to a specific schedule defined by simulated overpasses. Most of the cloud remote sensing (cloud profiling) data were already delivered to EVDC in near-real-time during the whole rehearsal period. The complex QA/QC and central processing for lidars (ARS) delayed the process at the beginning of the rehearsal, but preliminary data were delivered to EVDC. On the EVDC side, it was demonstrated that the ACTRIS harvester system mentioned above was successfully set up and operated according to plan, which proves the concept of the established workflow.

In conclusion, ACTRIS and its collaborators could show within this ATMO-ACCESS-pilot-activity already its potential as an operational research infrastructure for satellite validation applications. After the rehearsal campaign, an intensive analysis will take place, including a reprocessing of the campaign data set with optimised settings, with the final goal to be ready for the EarthCARE launch, currently scheduled for the beginning of May 2024. The validation activities will start about 3 weeks after launch and will additionally include the deployment of mobile facilities directly under the EarthCARE orbit and limited validation data analysis. However, the pilot activity will end in 2024, so that the continuation of these efforts is not yet secured.

In this contribution, we will present the status of the preparatory activities focussing on the results and lessons learnt from the rehearsal campaign.

Development and validation of on-line auto-GC-FID systems for the continuous monitoring of trace level VOCs, OVOCs and BVOCs

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Keywords: on-line monitoring, gas chromatography, OVOCs.

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Atmospheric air pollution stands as a main environmental concern, exerting important impacts on air quality, climate dynamics and human health. Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) are particularly important atmospheric gaseous pollutants, which are released into the atmosphere from both anthropogenic and natural sources. Among these molecules, Biogenic Volatile Organic Compounds (BVOCs) and Oxygenated Volatile Organic Compounds (OVOCs) play a significant role in the overall VOC emissions, posing a challenge for accurate measurement through conventional gas chromatography methods. The ISO 16000-3 method is the reference standard method for measurement of aldehydes and ketones, using DNPH cartridges for sample preconcentration. This method is very sensitive and allows identification and quantification from low ppt to high ppb levels depending on flow and sampling time (Uchiyama et al., 2004). Nevertheless, this technique is time consuming as the sample must be manually eluted from DNPH cartridge before analysis with HPLC-UV. Other techniques allow specific quantification of specific OVOCs such as formaldehyde but cannot quantify all OVOCs (Mascles et al., 2022). In response to these challenges, there is a growing need for an automated and continuous monitoring system for the characterization of aldehydes, ketones and alcohols, as well as VOCs and BVOCs. Such kind of systems are already quite used for the characterization of VOCs in ambient air. Nevertheless, quantifying light OVOCs is frequently challenging due to potential interference and often requires the use of a mass spectrometer (Bachelier et al., 2022). This study aims to present a comprehensive analysis of the system's performances under both controlled laboratory conditions and field environments. By studying its capabilities and limitations, this research seeks to contribute valuable insights toward enhancing our ability to monitor atmospheric pollutants.

A specific automated gas chromatograph equipped with a Flame Ionization Detector (FID) has been design for the monitoring of methanol, acetaldehyde, acetone and ethanol. The system uses a combination of three columns combined with a backflush method to separate and analyse OVOCs in ambient air. Linearity curves on OVOCs compounds were obtained by analysing various concentrations of a TO-15 cylinder. The linearity

range was set between 2,5 ppb and 10 ppb. Figure 1 shows the linearity obtained on ethanol:

Figure 1. Linearity curve obtained for ethanol between 2.5 ppb and 10 ppb

The system shows a very good linearity with a $R^2 = 0.9988$. Moreover, this system is used to continuously monitor ambient air. The variations of methanol, acetone and ethanol in indoor air are shown in Figure 2. In addition to this system, another GC was used to perform quantification of heavier OVOCs (from C3-C12).

Figure 2. 24h trend for the monitoring of some light OVOCs in ambient air

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Presenting GRAINS: INP spectrometer at the AGORA Observatory

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Keywords: ice nucleating particles, droplet freezing assay, high-mountain station.

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Atmospheric aerosol particles can act as ice nucleating particles (INP) by heterogeneous freezing, forming ice crystals in clouds. These ice crystals have a very important impact in the cloud microphysical and optical properties, affecting the Earth's radiative budget and the hydrological cycle through precipitation. However, cloud processes caused by changes in the concentration, morphology or type of aerosol particles that act as INP are not well understood (Forster et al., 2021). In this sense, aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI) show large uncertainties in climate change estimations, mainly due to a lack of broad knowledge of particle sources and how particles evolve to become effective INP. For this reason, it is crucial to study the INP ability of different aerosol types and under different atmospheric conditions.

The AGORA (Andalusian Global ObseRvatory of the Atmosphere) Infrastructure, included in ACTRIS (Aerosols, Clouds and Trace gases Research Infrastructure) and located in Southeastern Spain, counts with two different stations located 20 km away from each other (horizontal distance): an urban background station (UGR; 37.2°N, 3.6°W, 680 m a.s.l.) and a high mountain station (SNS; 37.1°N, 3.4°W, 2610 m a.s.l.). The main sources of anthropogenic particles at UGR station are road traffic and biomass burning (Titos et al., 2017). On the other hand, the SNS station is located in a pristine environment where local natural aerosol predominates (i.e., soil dust and biogenic particles), but it can also be affected by transported anthropogenic particles from the metropolitan area of Granada due to upslope winds. Transported Saharan dust is the main source of natural particles in the area, affecting both observatories (Cazorla et al., 2017). These features make the AGORA observatories a unique infrastructure for the study of INP under different atmospheric scenarios.

In this study, we present the GRAnada Ice Nucleating particle Spectrometer (GRAINS), recently developed at the AGORA Observatory. GRAINS is an offline immersion freezing device, that allows to characterize INP in a broad temperature range. The instrument's design is based on INSEKT (Schiebel, 2017) from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). GRAINS consists of one aluminium block with 2 sets of wells that fit two 96-well (0.2 ml volume) polymerase chain reaction (PCR) plates (Fig. 1a). The block is connected to a thermostat (LAUDA RP 250 E) using ethanol as working fluid. The temperature is regulated with a Pt100 sensor placed inside the block, between both PCR plates. The

aluminium block ensures an efficient heat transfer to the PCR plates, where the aerosol is suspended in ultrapure water.

For the determination of the INP concentration, the samples are cooled down to temperatures of -25°C, at a programmable cooling rate (Fig. 1b). GRAINS has a camera (ELP USB8MP02G-SFV (5-50)) that takes frames every 5 seconds, in which frozen aliquots can be optically detected by a difference of brightness between frozen and unfrozen wells. Background correction is applied considering the freezing ability of the ultrapure water used to create the solution. The INP concentration is calculated with the equation from Vali (1971).

In this study we present the validation of the GRAINS instrument, including temperature validation of the sensors and quality control based on the freezing spectra of well-known INPs, such as Arizona test Dust (ATD) or Snowmax. GRAINS will be used to perform INP laboratory measurements and to study the freezing ability of particles sampled in AGORA, following ACTRIS Cloud In-Situ (CIS) standard operation procedures.

Figure 1. (a) Overview of the GRAINS instrument. (b) Cooling rate applied to the samples.

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Multiply HSRL instrument for the Cal/Val of satellite missions - Update

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Keywords: HSRL, LIDAR.

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MULTIPLY is a airborne High Spectral Resolution Lidar (HSRL) currently under development by a consortium of European institutions from Romania, Germany, Greece, and Poland under the umbrella of ESA-ESTEC.

MULTIPLY will be one of ESA's reference instruments build to contribute to the calibration and validation activities (Cal/Val) of the upcoming ESA aerosol sensing missions like ADM-Aeolus, EarthCARE and the Sentinel-3/-4/-5/-5p.

The MULTIPLY lidar will deliver a full set of optical products for the calibration of ESA satellite instruments: the aerosol extinction and backscatter coefficient profiles, depolarization profiles (at three wavelengths: 355nm, 532nm, 1064nm), as well as aerosol intensive parameters like Ångström exponents, extinction- to-backscatter ratios, and linear particle depolarization ratios. The instrument will act as one of reference instruments for presently active and future Earth Observation Missions of the European Space Agency.

Fabry-Pérot interferometers (FPI) are considered for spectral filtering in UV and IR, while iodine filtering technique is selected for VIS. Narrow field-of-view detection is foreseen to augment the FPI throughput. Laser source with low pulse energy is designed to allow eye-safe operation at narrow beam divergence. The receiving unit incorporates one near field and one far field telescope. The instrument also incorporates three depolarization telescope modules for the retrieval of depolarization products in UV, VIS and IR.

Current status

The development and manufacturing of the MULTIPLY HSRL system is currently progressing well. We currently have the first UV HSRL ready and by the beginning of 2024 we will be able to perform the first measurement tests.

At this stage, the instrument will possess the capability to perform night-time measurements in the HSRL UV channels, enabling the characterization of aerosols and clouds during night-time. Furthermore, the instrument will be able to perform calibrated depolarization measurements, both during daytime and night-time, across all three channels: UV, VIS, and IR.

Figure 1. The HSRL instrument at MPI-M, Hamburg. Laboratory tests.

The High Spectral Resolution Lidar instrument developed within MULTIPLY will become one of the European Space Agency's reference instruments, contributing significantly to the calibration and validation activities of upcoming aerosol sensing missions such as ADM-Aeolus, EarthCARE, and the Sentinel -3, -4, -5, and -5p. Its integration into the Cal/Val activities of current and upcoming ESA missions highlights the instrument's significance in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of remote sensing data, facilitating robust scientific analyses and informed policy decisions.

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Comparison of cloud cover measurement techniques

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Clouds play a crucial role in Earth's radiative balance and impact industrial applications such as solar energy production, airport operations or ground-to-space optical communication. Uncertainties in their measurement persist: cloud cover is traditionally observed subjectively, leading to inconsistencies. Several methods using instruments like pyrgeometer and ceilometers offer improved accuracy (Utrillas et al. 2022). Infrared all-sky cameras such as the Sky InSight™ can provide more granular descriptions of the cloud cover. We propose to compare the cloud cover retrieved from those varied methods and suggest means to explain and mitigate any discrepancies.

Cloud cover timeseries obtained at the NOAA Surfrad Radiation Budget Network (SURFRAD) Table Mountain site in Boulder, Colorado, USA over 2023 are investigated. Measurements are retrieved from a pyrgeometer (Eppley's PIR), a ceilometer (Vaisala's CL51) and an infrared all-sky camera (Reuniwatt's Sky InSight™). Specific approaches are used to derive the cloud cover, depending on the instrument. For the pyrgeometer, we used the existing NOAA RadFlux product (Riihimaki et al. 2019). For the ceilometer, we compute a weighted average of low cloud occurrences over the last 30 minutes following the approach proposed by Wagner et al. (2015). For the Sky InSight™, we use the provided cloud mask image and compute the ratio of cloudy pixels over the total number of pixels with a zenith angle below 70°. The calculation is performed either directly on the image (*Hemispherical cloud cover*) or on a ground projection of the hemispherical image (*Ground projected cloud cover*).

Clear-skies (0 and 1 octa) or overcast (7 or 8 octas) readings are prevalent, representing 65.0% of cases for the pyrgeometer measured cloud cover, 85.0% for ceilometer readings, and respectively 82.7% and 84.7% for the Sky InSight hemispherical and ground cloud covers. Overall, cross instrument accuracy within one octa across all methods range between 70% and 75%. This accuracy needs to be contrasted by the high number of occurrences of clear and overcast skies at the site of interest. For partial cloud cover cases (octas 2-6), cross-instrument accuracies drop to 25%-34%. The ceilometer diverges most, while the camera and pyrgeometer tend to agree more often.

Figure 1: Distributions of cloud cover (in octas) for the different methods.

Analysis of several study cases indicate that ceilometer cloud cover measurements tend to miss edge clouds or holes in the cloud cover because of their narrow spatial constraints – making partial cloud cover readings less likely. They are also sensitive to optically thin clouds, contrary to the other instruments.

Alternatively, while both camera and pyrgeometer measurements are sensitive to the whole sky dome, the latter under-estimates cloud cover for thin overcast skies (altostratus), while the former may miss some high-altitude thin clouds

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The Finnish Meteorological Institute Airborne Mobile Platform for ACTRIS Aerosol and Cloud Interaction Studies

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Keywords: UAV, aerosols, clouds.

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The interaction between aerosols and clouds is a very complex and active area of research. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly recognized as a significant tool that can fly under, in and above clouds to collect data on aerosol and cloud particle concentrations, cloud microphysical properties, and other atmospheric state variables. Direct airborne UAV in-situ measurements allow more detailed, accurate, high resolution and affordable data collection in comparison with the traditional ground-based, satellite-based or manned aircraft methods.

An airborne mobile vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) platform was developed at the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) to study aerosol and cloud interactions (ACI) as part of the European Union - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) – exploratory platform initiative. The pilot campaigns took place in the FMI reserved airspace (TEMPO D area Pallas) with a side length of 7 km and ceiling of 2 km AGL in April and September 2023. The Sammaltunturi station (565 m MSL) served as a reference point for the vertical profiling measurements during the pilot campaigns.

Figure 1. The FMI VTOL platform during the flight.

The VTOL frame is made of Kevlar and carbon fiber (model Great Shark, Foxtech Ltd.), it has a wingspan of 3.2 m and total flight weight of 23 kg, see Fig. 1. It provides generous inner space for the installation of the scientific payload. During these campaigns the following instruments were utilized: a pair of CPCs with different cut-off diameter (model 3007, TSI Inc.) and POPS (Handix Ltd) were located inside the VTOL fuselage and a pair of meteorological sensors were attached outside the VTOL fuselage. During 11 campaign days a total of 34 flights

were conducted, each consisting of three vertical profiles, with a maximum reached altitude of 2 km MSL.

Figure 2. Three vertical profiles presented as timeseries for atmospheric state variables. total aerosol number concentration measured with CPCs and aerosol size distribution with POPS.

In the next step the implementation of in-situ cloud instrumentation is expected to FMI VTOL platform. The first test campaigns were already conducted in the autumns of 2022 and 2023. Open path UCASS cloud probe (~300 g, Girdwood et al., 2022), holographic μ CEMET (~700 g, Tiitta et al., 2022) and mCDA (<1 kg, Palas GmbH) are promising candidates.

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New instrument developments for use on commercial aircraft: IAGOS in-situ instrumentation

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Keywords: IAGOS, Aircraft based measurements, Aerosol, Air-Quality, NOx, NO₂, In-Situ

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In addition to high measurement accuracy, reliability and long-term stability, a key aspect in the development of scientific instruments for use on commercial aircraft is the safety of the instrumentation during operation. As the safety requirements for the certification of these instruments become more stringent, it is necessary to find alternatives for commonly used, potentially hazardous working fluids and gases, and to optimize the instruments for the use of these alternatives. For the Package 2 NO_x instrument (P2b), we have already succeeded in obtaining the Supplemental Type Certificate STC from EASA and CAA by substituting pure Oxygen with a 80/20 Helium Oxygen mixture to produce Ozone, required for the chemiluminescence method used. Since August 2023 we have regular measurements on CAL aircraft now probing the area of southeast Asia for NO and NO₂.

This presentation will further focus on an update on the new P2 packages under certification.

A) The Air-Quality instrument P2e has been designed to avoid all certification critical parts such as gas cylinders and alcohols, which has been the biggest obstacle so far. This instrument has passed all qualification tests and is expected to get the minor change approval this year. This is the basis for the first (test) deployment onboard Lufthansa aircraft. The

instrument has been fully characterized in the laboratory. The results will be presented here.

B) After the Aerosol package P2c has been successfully operated on board the IAGOS-CARIBIC Flying Lab for two years. Certification for IAGOS-CORE and the new A350 IAGOS- CARIBIC platform had to be postponed due to changing safety regulations. The obstacle was the working fluid Butanol which is commonly used in a Condensation Particle Counter (CPC). Butanol is an alcohol that is toxic and highly flammable.

With dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), we have found a naturally abundant, non-hazardous, and sustainable substitute for Butanol, that can be used with only minor modifications (replacement of seals) of currently available and already used alcohol-based CPCs, as implemented in the IAGOS P2c aerosol package. The scientific characterization of DMSO as a new working fluid in alcohol-based CPCs (see Figure 1) has been described by Weber et al. (2023) (Patent pending). Key results are presented in Weber et al. (2023).

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Weber, P. et al., Aerosol Research, 1, 1–12, DIO: 10.5194/ar-1-1-2023

Figure 1 (a) Comparison of the concentration linearity of two Sky-CPC 5.411 units to the electrometer reference at different pressure levels for ammonium sulfate and (b) comparison of the correlation between B-CPC and D-CPC on ambient air (Weber et al 2023).

Quantifying energy budgets in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer over western Germany

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Keywords: synergy, mixing diagrams, bulk Richardson number, advection.

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The processes involved in land-atmosphere interaction are crucial for weather and climate prediction. Their influence in extreme events, such as heat waves, can be better understood utilizing measurements. Quantifying energy budgets in the daytime boundary layer is challenging but necessary to better parametrize them in models (Milovac et al. 2016). The increasing availability of high-quality measurements of the driving variables in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) provides an excellent starting point for performing this task.

Instrument synergy

We utilized measurements at the Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution (JOYCE, ACTRIS National Facility), in particular, temperature and humidity profiles from an azimuth-scanning MicroWave Radiometer (MWR) and 3D wind vector from a Doppler Wind Lidar (DWL). Synergistic variables are obtained: Richardson bulk number for ABL height determination, as well as local temperature and humidity advection. In turn, these variables are utilized to then quantify energy budgets with the mixing diagram approach.

Richardson bulk number Ri_B

Ri_B is a measure of instability in the ABL that can be estimated combining thermodynamic (MWR) and dynamical (DWL) measurements, which are available from most ACTRIS cloud remote sensing stations.

$$Ri_B = \frac{g}{\theta_0} \frac{(\theta_z - \theta_0)z}{u^2 + v^2}$$

In the present work, Ri_B is plotted (Fig. 1) and qualitative differences are clearly seen for two summer days (with and without heat wave). Furthermore an applied threshold in Ri_B provides an estimate of ABL height, which considers turbulent mixing processes associated to both shear and buoyancy.

Figure 1. Daytime Ri_B evolution for days without heat wave (left) and with heat wave (right). Black contours are the ABL heights via threshold Ri_B .

Advection estimations

A novel approach for estimating advection is implemented. Horizontal inhomogeneities of temperature and humidity are estimated from the MWR azimuth-scans at 30° elevation and horizontal velocities from DWL are employed. Appropriate weighting and averaging is applied to derive local values of temperature and humidity advection within the ABL.

Mixing diagrams

Within the mixing diagram (Fig. 2), we show the temporal co-evolution of the vertically-averaged ABL sensible and latent heat over a defined time interval. Over this time interval, these energies transferred into the ABL must be balanced by surface fluxes, advection, and entrainment fluxes. These diagrams are built up as follows:

1. $C_p \theta$ vs Lq Evolution: obtained from MWR from surface up to ABL height (from Ri_B).
2. Surface sensitive and latent heat fluxes: obtained from a close-by Eddy-Covariance station (ICOS).
3. Advection: estimated from MWR horizontal inhomogeneities and velocities from DWL.
4. Entrainment: estimated as a residual vector as in Santanello et al. (2009).

With the vector representation as given in Fig. 2, we can characterize the contributions to the ABL energy budget and thus identify dominant process for different situations.

Figure 2. Mixing diagrams obtained for a non heat wave and a heat wave day from 0900 to 1600 h.

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Assessing the quality of the Sentinel-5p TROPOMI cloud products and their reprocessing using ground-based Cloudnet data

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Keywords: TROPOMI, Cloudnet, cloud, atmospheric composition.

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The retrieval of atmospheric composition by Sentinel-5P TROPOMI is strongly affected by radiative interferences with clouds. Therefore, cloud data products, containing parameters like cloud fraction and cloud height are essential to filter and/or correct atmospheric data products like columns of nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde, sulphur dioxide and ozone. The three main TROPOMI cloud retrieval algorithms are: (i) L2_CLOUD OCRA/ROCINN CAL, (ii) L2_CLOUD OCRA/ROCINN CRB, and (iii) the S5P support product FRESKO-S.

The ESA/Copernicus Atmospheric Mission Performance Cluster (ATM-MPC) validation service routinely assesses the quality of the trace gas and cloud products. Consolidated validation reports are published each three months at <https://mpc-vdaf.tropomi.eu/>. A major part of the operational ground-based correlative data streams is obtained from the ESA Validation Data Center (EVDC). Comparison results are available at the ATM-MPC automated validation server (AVS, <https://mpc-vdaf-server.tropomi.eu/>).

The TROPOMI-retrieved cloud height is compared with that of the ground-based Cloudnet network available at the ACTRIS-Cloudnet data portal, following the protocol of Compernelle et al. (2021). Currently measurements from 28 Cloudnet and US ARM stations of are used, 15 with near real time data. Stations like Cabauw are especially interesting as also ground-based measurements from trace gases are available, enabling a combined validation of more TROPOMI products.

Version upgrades have had a significant impact on the S5P cloud data characteristics. The change of the wavelength window in the FRESKO product is clearly visible in the comparison with Cloudnet cloud height, and in NO₂ column validation results regarding the tropospheric and total NO₂ column. The first upgrades of the ROCINN products led to an improvement in correlation with Cloudnet cloud height, but to a more negative bias for the low clouds, which is however not clearly visible in the HCHO validation results.

To resolve the discontinuities due to the processor version jumps, a full mission reprocessing was performed. The reprocessed ROCINN data have a lower dispersion and higher correlation with respect to the Cloudnet cloud heights. The bias of OCRA/ROCINN CAL cloud top height becomes more negative, but that of OCRA/ROCINN CRB cloud height bias improves. The reprocessed FRESKO data have a bias low on average but with a high seasonal cycle.

A topic of research is how to optimally compare the intrinsically different satellite and Cloudnet measurements. E.g., ROCINN CAL cloud *top* heights appear negatively biased compared to Cloudnet. Comparing cloud *mid* heights improves this bias significantly.

Figure 1. Monthly median cloud mid height difference between S5P OCRA\ROCINN_CAL and Cloudnet.

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Validation of satellite NO₂, HCHO, and SO₂ products with ground-based DOAS: the impact of different assumptions in stratospheric correction, cloud correction and prior profile

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Keywords: GOME-2A, OMI, MAX-DOAS, zenith-sky DOAS, NO₂, HCHO, SO₂.

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It is the goal of the ESA CCI+precursor project to produce harmonized multi-sensor climate data records for precursors of ozone and aerosol. The impact of different settings and/or products for the same geophysical variable and sensor were explored during the round-robin phase of this project. Here we report on the impact on validation results for (1) GOME-2A stratospheric NO₂ columns vs NDACC zenith-sky DOAS, (2) GOME-2A HCHO columns vs MAX-DOAS, and (3) OMI SO₂ columns vs MAX-DOAS.

Stratospheric NO₂: GOME-2A versus zenith-sky DOAS

Stratospheric columns of the following satellite products were analyzed: (i) QA4ECV with default TM5 data assimilation (DA) for the stratospheric correction, (ii) an alternative QA4ECV product using STREAM, based on weighted convolution, and (iii) a prototype AC SAF product also using STREAM. The validation results are similar for the three products, except for a positive bias at polar latitudes for QA4ECV TM5.

Figure 1. Left: comparison of GOME-2A QA4ECV strat NO₂ using TM5 DA with zenith-sky DOAS. Right: same but for GOME-2A QA4ECV NO₂ using STREAM.

HCHO: GOME-2A versus MAX-DOAS

Columns of the satellite products QA4ECV HCHO and operational AC SAF HCHO were analyzed, each with and without cloud correction applied, and employing different models for the prior profile. The ROCINN-based cloud correction has a very minor impact on the validation results for the AC SAF product. The FRESCO-based cloud correction leads to a more negative bias and lower correlation for the QA4ECV product. The choice of model for the prior profile is relatively less important.

SO₂: OMI versus MAX-DOAS

OMI COBRA SO₂ columns were compared with MAX-DOAS measurements at Xianghe, switching on/off the cloud correction and testing different priors. Differences in validation results are relatively minor; the best slope is obtained when using a cloud correction and the CAMS-reanalysis as prior. When switching off the cloud correction, the impact of prior choice is marginal.

Figure 2. OMI COBRA SO₂ vs MAX-DOAS at Xianghe, using cloud correction and CAMS-reanalysis as prior.

This work has received funding from ESA, Contract No 4000138243, project "CCI+ Phase-New ECVs: Precursors for Aerosol and Ozone ECV". We thank the EUMETSAT AC SAF project for providing the HCHO data product.

Two Wavelengths Compact LIDAR for Aerosol and Water Vapor

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Keywords: lidar, aerosol, optical properties.

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The Naples observation station is one of the National Facilities (NF) of ACTRIS. A new innovative lidar system, called TWCA (Two Wavelengths Compact LIDAR for Aerosol), has been recently developed in the framework of the PER-ACTRIS-IT project and is part of the transportable atmospheric analysis equipment operative at the ACTRIS site of the University of Naples “Federico II” located at CeSMA (Advanced Metrological and Technological Services Center). TWCA is a lidar for atmospheric aerosol analysis.

TWCA is a compact, transportable, two-wavelengths lidar that acquires both elastic and Raman backscattered light equipped with depolarization analysis of the detected signals. The emitter is an OEM, high repetition rate (2 kHz), solid state Nd:YAG laser source (Bright Solutions srl). The second (532nm) and third harmonic (355nm) of the fundamental wavelength (1064nm) are sent in the atmosphere. The receiver is based on a Ritchey-Chretien telescope with a diameter of 20 cm and a focal length of 50 cm; the system operates in a monostatic configuration.

The collected light is split in six different channels equipped with the corresponding PMT. Data are acquired both in analog and photon-counting modes by two CLASS acquisition boards, specifically developed by ALA (Advanced Lidar Applications). The elastic signals are both divided into parallel and cross polarized components with respect to the laser polarization, while the other two signals correspond to the Raman echoes of the 355 nm wavelength from N₂ (386nm) and H₂O (407 nm). The depolarization calibration is carried out by inserting a halfwave plate with a servo motor; moreover, neutral density filters are used to avoid PMT saturation, when appropriate. The TWCA system is also provided with a tool to perform the telecover calibration test.

The TWCA lidar is managed by a LARA controller board (Advanced Lidar Applications), that allows to control every lidar component (servo, laser, PMT power, acquisition board, etc.). The system is designed to probe the atmosphere in the range 0.15 - 20 km of altitude. Besides very low weight and size, TWCA exploits a scanning system allowing measurements with a zenith angle between 0 and 90°. The main characteristics of the system are summarized in Table 1.

The instrument is operative since 2023. In this communication, exemplificative ACTRIS compliant measurements (see Figure 1, e.g.) as well as all the

ACTRIS standard quality assurance procedures (Freudenthaler et al., 2018) for lidars (Rayleigh fit, overlap correction, telecover test, depolarization calibration) will be presented addressing TWCA capabilities.

Table 1. TWCA lidar main characteristics

Laser source	
Output wavelengths	355nm; 532nm
Repetition frequency	2kHz
Beam Divergence	< 0.3mrad@355 nm < 0.2mrad@532 nm
Receiver	
Telescope configuration	Ritchey-Chretien
Primary mirror diameter	200mm
Pinhole	1mm
Channels	
Elastic	355P; 355S; 532P; 532S
Raman	386nm; 407nm
Acquisition	
Acquisition data	(0.15-20) km
Minimal spatial resolution	15m
Minimal time resolution	30s

Figure 1. Backscattering coefficient (a) and false colour map (b) retrieved by TWCA on 20 June 2023 for the 532 nm parallel polarized wavelength.

Freudenthaler, V.; Linné, H.; Chaikovski, A.; Rabus, D.; Groß, S. *EARLINET Lidar Quality Assurance Tools*, Atmospheric Measurement Techniques Discussions 2018, 1–35.

Validation of Aerosol Layer Height product from space-borne instruments using ACTRIS' Aerosol Remote Sensing facilities

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Keywords: aerosol layer height, satellite, validation, lidar

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As reinforced by the latest synthesis report (IPCC, 2023: Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report), aerosols have a total effect on the radiative forcing in the atmosphere of -0.9 w m^{-1} and a significant effect on human health.

Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) is a new operational Level-2 product retrieved from space-borne instruments including ESA's TROPOMI and Copernicus Sentinel 3. The algorithm is based on hyperspectral measurements of the oxygen A band, assuming that the aerosols are confined to a single layer with a fixed pressure difference between top and bottom of the layer, and constant aerosol volume extinction coefficient. The algorithm features a spectral fit estimation of reflectance across O₂ A band using neural networks and the retrieval method is Optimal Estimation.

This study presents the validation methodology and results of the space-borne Level 2, version 2.2 (ALH ATBD, KNMI, ESA, 2022) product of TROPOMI against ACTRIS' Aerosol Remote Sensing Lidar and Ceilometers.

Satellite data from 2018 until 2024 are firstly filtered for quality assurance (qa) values below 0.5 and then spatially averaged around the ground-based stations. Ground-based Range Corrected Signals (RCS) have been used to determine the aerosol layer heights using a modified gradient method with a continuous wavelet function.

Fig 1. (a) shows a representation of daily RCS of the ceilometer station in Magurele, Romania and, with black dots, the retrieved aerosol layer mid height. Fig. 1 (b) shows the RCS profile for which the algorithm for layer height retrieval was applied.

Experiments over selected lidar stations have been conducted and NATALI (Nicolae, et. al, 2018) software has been used to determine the aerosol mid height and the aerosol optical properties. In depth analysis of aerosol optical properties have been made also for cases of long-range transported aerosol cases.

Furthermore, for selected locations, sensitivity studies have been conducted, pearson coefficient has been calculated using different combinations of qa, spatial, and temporal averaging of satellite-borne and ground-based retrievals.

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The AOTF-based NO₂ camera: Urban applications

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Keywords: NO₂, air quality, spectral imaging.

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So far, most attempts to map the distribution of NO₂ from the ground have been made with visible-light scanning grating spectrometers (e.g. MAX-DOAS, Pandora). Benefiting from a high retrieval accuracy, they only achieve a relatively low spatiotemporal resolution that hampers the detection of dynamic features, or strong spatial gradients.

Over the last years, a new type of passive remote sensing instrument has been developed (Dekemper, 2016). The main goal is the measurement of the 2-D distributions of NO₂ slant column densities (SCDs) with a high spatiotemporal resolution above extended areas, or in point source plumes. The key element of this instrument is its acousto-optical tuneable filter (AOTF) which not only delivers sufficient spectral resolution for resolving the structures of the absorption cross section of the NO₂ molecule (~0.7nm) but is also tuneable over a wide spectral domain.

The measurement concept is based on sequential acquisitions of monochromatic images of a scene. By tuning the AOTF to selected wavelengths in the range 440-450nm, one can build a hypercube: a 3D array made of two spatial dimensions, and a spectral axis. The light spectrum acquired in the field of view of each pixel can be processed by conventional methods (e.g., DOAS) in order to retrieve the NO₂ SCD. The typical product is an array of 512x512 NO₂ SCD values derived from an hypercube containing ~50 wavelengths acquired in ~1 minute. The spatial sampling is <1m at a distance of 1km.

Figure 1 illustrates the measurement principle in urban conditions: one spectral image of the hypercube is displayed to show the scene, and the spectrum recorded by one pixel is processed by the DOAS method.

Figure 1: Left: A spectral image acquired by the NO₂ camera in the European district in Brussels. Right: DOAS

fit and residuals of the spectrum recorded by the pixel indicated by a red cross.

Figure 2 illustrates the advantage of the NO₂ camera: thanks to its high spatial resolution, a selection of the pixels to process can be carefully made. Here, only the pixels "seeing" the sky were processed, allowing to look between the tall buildings.

Figure 2: Example of the selective processing of "sky" pixels. The color indicates the NO₂ SCD in molecule/cm².

In 2023, the NO₂ camera has been selected as a work package of the QA4EO IDEAS+ framework (Instrument Data quality Evaluation and Assessment Service - Quality Assurance for Earth Observation). The concept has been improved to allow automated operations from the rooftop of the Sapienza University, in Rome. From there, the instrument can map the NO₂ SCD field above the city skyline.

In this paper, we will present the concept of this innovative instrument, and show results obtained in urban conditions (Brussels, Rome). We will address its performance (error budget, spectral/spatial/temporal resolution), and highlight its key advantages over more traditional systems for NO₂ pollution monitoring.

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Dekemper, E., et al. (2016) *The AOTF-based NO₂ camera*, Atmos. Meas. Tech. **9**(12), 6025–6034.

Dust aerosol mineralogy retrieved from its infrared optical signature: a laboratory study highlights the potential of infrared remote sensing for aerosol climate studies

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Keywords: mineral dust, mineralogy, aerosol remote sensing

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The mineralogy of dust aerosols (i.e. the abundance, relative proportions and state of mixing of the different minerals composing the aerosols, including mainly silicates in the form of clays, quartz, and feldspars, carbonates, sulfates, and iron and titanium oxides) is of key relevance in driving its climatic and environmental effects. Ground-based and airborne observations support the evidence that the dust mineralogy is heterogeneous in the atmosphere, varying from local to global scale due to changes in the mineralogical composition of the emitting source soils and atmospheric processing. However, the capability to get regional and global mapping of airborne dust mineralogy is still missing to date. This gap represents a fundamental limitation for properly developing and validating the representation of dust in Earth System Models and constraining its regional and global climate forcing.

Because the different minerals composing the fine and the coarse fractions of dust show different spectral absorption signatures, remote sensing spectral and hyperspectral observations can be used to fill this gap by detecting the presence of diverse minerals and reconstructing their relative proportions in the dust aerosols. Based on this idea, recent efforts move into this direction, including the EMIT mission (Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation) started in 2022.

In this study we demonstrate, starting from exemplary data acquired in the CESAM simulation chamber on dust aerosols from global sources (Di Biagio et al., 2023; <https://cesam.cnrs.fr/>), that the extinction signature of suspended dust aerosols in the 740–1475 cm^{-1} infrared spectral range (6.8–13.5 μm) can be used to derive dust mineralogy in terms of its infrared-active and coarse-sized minerals: quartz, clays, feldspars and calcite. We show that diverse spectral infrared signatures allow to distinguish dust aerosols from different sources worldwide with variable composition, and that following the changes of the dust extinction spectra with time informs on particles size-selective mineralogy changes during atmospheric transport. Results from the present study confirm the major advance that hyperspectral

infrared remote sensing observations, as those by IASI (Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer), IASI-NG (Next Generation) and FORUM (Far-infrared Outgoing Radiation Understanding and Monitoring) instruments, can provide to dust science and open unique perspectives for their application to aerosol remote sensing and climate studies.

Figure 1: Temporal evolution of the total mass concentration of dust aerosols and minerals contributions obtained from analysis of infrared spectra and comparison with the total mass concentration of dust from online size distribution data.

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Di Biagio, C., et al., Infrared optical signature reveals the source-dependency and along-transport evolution of dust mineralogy as shown by laboratory study, *Sci. Rep.*, 13, 13252, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39336-7>, 2023.

Evaluation of the performance of nine cloud spectrometers during the ACTRIS intercomparison campaign at Sonnblick Observatory

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Keywords: cloud spectrometers, intercomparison, ACTRIS.

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The primary cloud microphysical parameters for studying aerosol-cloud interactions include the total number aerosol and cloud droplets concentration, the effective radius of cloud droplets and the cloud liquid water content (Doulgeris *et al.*, 2022). The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS) Intercomparison Campaign was facilitated by the European Centre for Cloud Ambient Intercomparison (ECCINT), at the Sonnblick Observatory (3.106 m asl) in Austria in 2022. Our main motivation was to evaluate the performance of a variety of cloud spectrometers under varying conditions.

From November 21st to December 5th, we evaluated the performance of nine cloud spectrometers: three Fog Monitors 120 (FM-120, DMT), two cloud droplet analyzers (CDA, Palas GmpH), one mini cloud droplet analyzer (mCDA, Palas GmpH), two ground-based fog and aerosol spectrometers (GFAS, DMT) and one holographic image system (ICEMET, University of Oulu). The spectrometers were variously positioned based on their design. One FM120 was installed horizontally and fixed to one wind direction, while the other two were installed vertically. The GFAS and the ICEMET were positioned horizontally and consistently aligned to face the wind direction. CDA's inlet had a vertical orientation.

Cloud presence was determined by comparing cloud droplet counts from the cloud spectrometers against the visibility and the relative humidity. The station was considered within a cloud when the visibility was below 500 meters, and the relative humidity was close to 100%.

Optimal performance was observed in cloud spectrometers positioned horizontally and aligned with the wind direction. Sub-zero conditions posed challenges, leading to ice rimming that impacted FM-120 due to blockage and freezing of its rotating inlet. Conversely, the CDA exhibited resilience but encountered operational losses due to its inlets' vertical orientation. Despite these challenges, the determination of Effective Diameter (ED) and Mean Volume Diameter (MVD) remained feasible. Liquid Water Content (LWC) emerged as the most sensitive parameter for the cloud's spectrometers. This sensitivity was primarily induced by variations in cloud droplet number concentrations and the sampling efficiency of large cloud droplets.

This work emphasized ECCINT's crucial role in optimizing cloud spectrometer performance across varied environments, ensuring high-quality datasets vital for advancing cloud research.

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Recommendations for reporting equivalent Black Carbon (eBC) concentration based on long-term pan-European in-situ observations

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Keywords: equivalent black carbon; Filter absorption photometers, Elemental carbon, Site specific MAC

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INTRODUCTION

Equivalent Black Carbon (eBC) has become one of the key targets for current research on air quality (AQ). To incorporate eBC as a new variable in AQ guidelines and to develop effective mitigation strategies, it is crucial to estimate its mass concentration in a consistent way throughout the AQ monitoring networks (AQMNs) with minimal uncertainties (Savadkoohi et al. 2023). A reliable determination of eBC mass concentrations derived from filter absorption photometers (FAPs) measurements depends on the appropriate quantification of the mass absorption cross-section (MAC) for converting the absorption coefficient (b_{abs}) determined from FAPs measurements to eBC. Several studies have shown a substantial variability in MAC due to local and regional variability in e.g., eBC sources, burning conditions, and eBC internal mixing among other. This MAC variability may lead to considerable uncertainty in eBC estimation.

METHODS

This study investigates the spatial-temporal variability of the MAC obtained from simultaneous elemental carbon (EC) measurements and b_{abs} determination performed following the ACTRIS procedures at 22 sites. We compared different methodologies for retrieving eBC integrating different options for calculating MAC, including: locally derived MAC, median MAC value calculated from 22 sites, and site-specific rolling regression MAC. The eBC concentrations that underwent corrections using these methods were identified as MeBC (median MAC), LeBC (local MAC), and ReBC (Rolling MAC) respectively. These corrected eBC concentrations were compared with eBC as directly provided by FAPs (NeBC; nominal instrumental MAC).

RESULTS

The median MAC values were $7.8 \pm 3.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ from 12 aethalometers at 880 nm, and $10.6 \pm 4.7 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ from 10 MAAPs at 637 nm. Combining datasets obtained from these two types of FAPs resulted in a median value of about $10.7 \pm 4.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ at 637 nm. However, the experimental MAC values showed significant site and seasonal dependencies, with heterogeneous patterns

between summer and winter in different regions. Pronounced differences (up to more than 50%) were observed between NeBC from FAPs and ReBC due to the differences observed between the experimental and nominal MAC values. Moreover, long-term trend analysis spanning 9-12 years revealed a statistically significant (s.s.) decreasing trends in EC mass concentrations at 4 out of 5 sites used for the analysis. Interestingly, we show that the corresponding corrected eBC trends are not independent on the way eBC is calculated, due to the variability of MAC. NeBC and EC decreasing trends were consistent at sites with no significant trend in experimental MAC. Conversely, where MAC showed a s.s. trend, the NeBC and EC trends were not consistent while ReBC concentration followed the same pattern as EC.

CONCLUSIONS

These results underscore the importance of accounting for MAC variations when deriving eBC measurements from FAPs and emphasizes the necessity of incorporating EC observations to constrain the uncertainty associated with eBC. Thus, this study recommends the use of co-located measurements of b_{abs} and EC mass concentrations by expanding monitoring networks to include regular EC sampling. However, in situations where EC observations are unavailable, we recommend applying the default MAC value of around $10 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ recommended by ACTRIS when b_{abs} is provided by MAAP at 637 nm (Zanatta et al. 2016) and the MAC value of $7.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ when b_{abs} is provided by aethalometers at 880 nm.

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Identification and Analysis of Multimodal ACTRIS-CCRES Cloud-radar Doppler Spectra for Comprehensive Insights of Mixed Phase Clouds

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Keywords: Clouds, Remote sensing, Mixed-Phase, Hydrometeor.

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Clouds, composed of hydrometeors such as supercooled liquid droplets, ice crystals and snowflakes, play a critical role in the Earth's climate system. Clouds have a fundamental effect, influencing the water cycle, solar radiation distribution, and broader climatological processes. They pose challenges in their representation within climate models and lack a comprehensive theoretical framework (IPCC, 2023). Specifically, the study of mixed-phase clouds, characterized by the coexistence of multiple hydrometeors is still challenging due to its complexity (Shupe et al., 2004). Regarding remote sensing, Doppler cloud radar allows for deriving the Doppler velocity spectrum from which information on the motion of atmospheric targets can be analyzed (Kalesse et al., 2016). This work presents an aliasing detection method and an innovative algorithm to determine the number of modes in the Doppler velocity spectra, which enables a more comprehensive analysis of the mixed-phase clouds.

Figure 1. Number of modes detected in the Doppler spectrum on September 13th 2021 on 11:00-12:00 UTC.

Figure 1 shows the number of modes determined during a rain event that occurred on 11:00-12:00 UTC on September 13th 2021. As can be seen, the cloud is mainly characterized by monomodal spectra from

range of 100 to 300 (i.e., 4 to 10 km asl). Multimode spectra mainly appear on the top of the cloud around range #300 (i.e., around 10 km agl) likely linked to different sizes of ice crystals. Additionally, precipitation (range #100, i.e., 4 km asl) shows a variety of multimodes spectra with up to four modes (orange color), allowing to test the algorithm under different circumstances. The multimode detection may help on the hydrometeor classification and to identify where microphysical inversions based on monomodal distribution can be applied.

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ALHAMBRA: a new state-of-the-art Raman lidar at Granada ACTRIS NF with $3\beta+3\alpha+2\delta+\omega+2\phi$ configuration

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Keywords: lidar, spectral fluorescence, aerosol typing.

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Aerosol particles significantly influence the atmospheric energy balance, playing a pivotal role in cloud formation and evolution. The challenge lies in obtaining precise measurements due to the vast variability in aerosol type, concentration, size, and chemical composition. This variability significantly contributes to the primary uncertainty in estimating total radiative forcing (Quaas, 2022).

The ALHAMBRA system, operational at the UGR urban station in Granada, Spain, as part of the AGORA (Andalusian Global Observatory of the Atmosphere), consists of two sub-systems. The near-field sub-system focuses on the planetary boundary layer (PBL) and includes elastic detection at 1064 (1064.2 nm), 532 (532.1 nm), and 355 (354.7 nm), along with N₂ vibrational Raman (VR) detection at 532 (607.4 nm) and 355 (386.7 nm). The far-field sub-system extends to the low stratosphere, covering elastic detection at 1064 (1064.2 nm), 532 (532.1 nm), and 355 (354.7 nm), as well as N₂ rotational Raman (RR) detection at 1064 (1058 nm), 532 (530.2 nm), and 355 (353.9 nm). Each subsystem includes water vapor detection (ω) at 355 (407.5 nm).

The linear particle depolarization ratio (δ) can be determined at 532 and 355 nm, is proven to be valuable for studying atmospheric aerosol and aerosol-cloud interactions. It provides information about the shape and thermodynamic phase of scatters (Bravo-Aranda, 2013; Granados-Muñoz, 2015; Ansmann, 2019).

Detecting pure rotational energy states of molecules (RR) extends independent extinction (α) and backscattering (β) profiles to nearly the entire day, overcoming VR limitations and reliably improving signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) (Ortiz-Amezcuca, 2020).

The system also integrates fluorescence capabilities (ϕ) for both subsystems through two approaches: integrated signal detection in the 420-520 nm range using a broadband interferential filter (Veselovskii, 2022) or spectral signal detection via optical fiber to a HORIBA 1250M imaging spectrometer (Tatarov, 2021; Reichardt, 2023). Two exchangeable gratings of 1200 and 300 g/mm enable observation of different spectral ranges and resolutions.

By having the near-field subsystem, the total overlap height can be significantly reduced to

approximately 150 metres above ground level, improving characterisation at lower layers, where the highest concentration of primary biological aerosol particles, such as pollen grains, are found.

The $3\beta+3\alpha+2\delta+\omega+2\phi$ synergistic combination within the vertical column from the lowermost layers is expected to be a great opportunity to take a step forward in atmospheric monitoring and deepen the knowledge of atmospheric processes.

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COSMIC-2 satellite mission for atmospheric boundary layer worldwide monitoring: calibration by ground-based remote sensors and radiosondes

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The atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is the lowest part of the troposphere, where direct interactions with the Earth's surface take place. A deep understanding of the processes involved in ABL would entail a positive impact on a wide range of applications, included both scientific and social, economic and health ones. However, up until now, quantitative knowledge about spatial and temporal variations in ABL dynamics is still limited.

Satellite data are particularly useful for global scale analysis because of their spatial coverage. The COSMIC-2 mission makes use of the radio-occultation technique to monitor the atmosphere, covering low and mid-latitudes regions. Since October 2019, COSMIC-2 provides more than 4000 high-quality profiles of meteorological variables such as temperature, pressure, humidity, and refractivity, which could lead to better monitoring of atmospheric boundary layer height (ABLH). The aim of this work is to develop, validate, and tune new methods to retrieve ABLH from refractivity data collected by the COSMIC-2 mission.

The determination of the most suitable algorithm lied in intercomparisons with different methods involving different variables (refractivity, temperature, range-corrected signal (RCS)) and both physical and empirical background. The validation methods considered were the minimum refractivity gradient, parcel method, Liu and Liang method, and RCS gradient method. These approaches were applied to the available data from microwave radiometer, lidar, ceilometer, and radiosondes at two ACTRIS stations (Granada and Évora). Also, radiosondes launched over Graciosa (Azores) were considered. The resulting ABLHs were then compared via robust linear regressions to the ABLHs computed from COSMIC-2 refractivity profiles. The search of the optimum algorithm consisted of determining a percent value (τ) which indicates the minimum magnitude (with respect to the magnitude of the refractivity gradient absolute minimum) of a negative peak in the refractivity gradient profile to be attributed as the ABLH. Hence, the algorithm assigned the ABLH to the lowest negative peak

in the refractivity gradient profile whose magnitude was, at least, $\tau/100$ times that of the absolute minimum. The decision of the best τ value was made by means of a goodness of fit function (GF) that took into account the determination coefficient, the slope and the number of observations assessed in the linear regressions.

Given that ABL behaves differently along the day on land areas, three values of τ were computed for daytime, nighttime, and transition periods (sunrise and sunset), respectively, in order to take into account the ABL daily evolution. Over oceans, that daily cycle is more subtle, therefore only one value of τ was retrieved. This was determined by radiosounding data in close-to-sea zones.

The obtained τ values for land regions were 82, 68 and 97% for daytime, nighttime, and transition periods, respectively. Regarding oceanic zones, the resulting τ was 99%, which is extremely close to the traditional method (minimum refractivity gradient, that is equivalent to using $\tau = 100\%$). Moreover, the comparative analysis for land regions revealed that the best agreements occurred when the ABLHs computed from COSMIC-2 data were compared with those computed from RCS data (lidar and ceilometer). This could be explained if we bear in mind that methodologies based on MWR data tend to accumulate more errors related to data retrieval (inversion algorithms), as well as the involvement of more variables.

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Multi-scheme chemical ionization inlet, MION2, for fast reagent ion switching in atmospheric pressure chemical ionization mass spectrometry (CIMS)

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Keywords: mass spectrometry, filter, HOM

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Chemical Ionization Mass Spectrometry is a powerful technique for the rapid and sensitive detection of atmospheric trace gases relevant to particle formation, air quality and climate. The comprehensive detection and quantification of different species with different volatilities, degree of oxygenation, and functional groups – often originating from the same chemical process – generally requires using more than one ion scheme. To facilitate multiple ion schemes with only one mass spectrometer, the Multi-Scheme Chemical Ionization Inlet (MION2) has been developed (Rissanen *et al* (2019), He *et al* (2023)).

The MION2 inlet uses electric fields to inject reagent ions produced from the irradiation of a precursor gas radially into the ion-molecule mixing region (IMR). The injection of ions can be turned off quasi-instantaneously by controlling the electrode voltages (Fig. 1). This is different to inlets that achieve reagent switching by turning the ionization source on or off while maintaining the flow of precursor gas into the IMR. MION2 achieves excellent detection limits as (1) reagent precursor gas is not mixed into the IMR, the sample gas, and (2) because of the ambient pressure preventing dilution and allowing well-controlled laminar flows.

Figure 1. Example of rapid reagent and polarity switching with MION2.

The radial design of MION2 allows to mount multiple ion sources in front of a single mass spectrometer, differing regarding the reagent ion or alternatively employing the same ion but with different reaction time. The reaction time can be controlled from

as little as 60 ms by introducing drift tubes between the mass spectrometer and ion injection point. If all inlets are

turned off (by turning off voltages), the MION2 inlet allows the sampling of ambient ions.

The MION2 inlet can in principle be coupled to any mass spectrometer (e.g., time-of-flight (TOF)) and integrated into any type of setup. Recently, a new thermal desorption unit has been developed. We have successfully used the new inlet in instrumentation and a measurement strategy that (1) maximizes the retention of ambient trace gases to tenax filters, (2) thermally desorbs the collected filter deposit, (3) prepares the analyte for mass-spectrometric detection using the MION2 inlet, and (4) unambiguously analyses the composition filter deposit using an ultra-high-resolution Orbitrap mass spectrometer, without further chromatographic separation (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Rich ambient filter mass spectrum determined with thermal desorption MION2 Orbitrap.

In conclusion, the ability of MION2 to rapidly switch between reagent ion chemistries (including polarities), in combination with achieving excellent detection limits, expands the analytical capabilities of CIMS instruments and facilitates the comprehensive analysis of a broader range of compounds.

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Towards the development of an XRF setup for the Near-Real-Time measurement of low-Z elements in atmospheric aerosol samples

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Elemental composition of atmospheric aerosol is included in the set of variables measured by ACTRIS-ERIC observational platforms and provides useful information about aerosol sources, thus being often included in source apportionment studies.

In recent years, instrumentation capable of measuring aerosol elemental composition in Near-Real-Time (NRT) with fairly good precision and low Minimum Detection Limits (MDLs) was produced. One of those instruments is the Xact 625i (Furger et al. 2017), which measures more than 30 elements with MDLs ranging from about 0.1 to 800 ng/m³ (at 1- σ confidence level) and sampling/analysis times ranging from 15 to 240 minutes. These characteristics make it suitable for both field campaigns and long term monitoring, so that its use is currently growing.

Nevertheless, pretty high MDLs are present for elements with low atomic number Z, especially Aluminium and Silicon. Moreover, low-Z elements like Sodium and Magnesium are not detected at all by the instrument. These elements are well known to be characteristic tracers of natural aerosols like desert dust and sea spray (Rodríguez et al. 2020). Thus, the low accuracy of Xact 625i on low Z elements can potentially prevent the proper identification of natural aerosol sources by using Xact 625i measurements.

With the aim of overcoming this limitation, a compact setup to perform measurements on aerosol filters is under development at the Laboratory of Nuclear Techniques for Environment and Cultural Heritage (LABEC) of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) in collaboration with the Cultural Heritage Network (INFN-CHNet). INFN-LABEC is also designed as the Elemental Mass Calibration Centre (EMC2) within ACTRIS CAIS-ECAC. This setup consists of an X-ray tube with Rhodium anode (Moxtek©, 40 kV, 0.1 mA, 4 mm beam spot size on the sample). The tube is coupled with fast-SDD X-ray detectors (Amptek©). The setup compactness (about 20x20x20 cm³) makes it possible to implement it into an hourly aerosol sampler to measure aerosol elemental composition in NRT.

Both daily 47 mm teflon filters collected with the Gemini sequential sampler (Dadolab©) and hourly nuclepore filters collected with the STRAS (Size and Time Resolved Aerosol Sampler) developed by INFN were analysed with the XRF setup. In order to improve the XRF measurements, different solutions were tested.

These are the use of (i) different detectors, (ii) different metal filters placed in front of the X-ray tube and (iii) Helium flux on the samples during the measurement to reduce the attenuation of low energy X-rays. In order to provide a robust reference for the validation of the XRF setup, PIXE measurements at the LABEC 3 MV tandem accelerator were carried out. Moreover, a comparison between the XRF setup and Xact 625i was accomplished by comparing their typical MDLs.

For what concerns elemental concentrations measured with XRF and PIXE, a good agreement was found for most of the analysed elements, with exceptions for Zn, Cu, Pb and Ti. By looking at the comparison between MDLs (Figure 1), Xact 625i shows significantly higher performances for elements with Z > 16, but lower MDLs than the ones of Xact 625i are achievable for Al and Si. Moreover, fairly good MDLs are achieved also for Na and Mg, which are not measured by Xact 625i. To sum up, the detection of low-Z elements like Na and Mg is achievable, under proper optimisation, by using our compact XRF setup. Moreover, actual MDLs for Al and Si could be further reduced by a proper optimization of the Xact 625i setup.

Figure 1. Comparison between typical (1h analysis time) Xact 625i and XRF MDLs at 3- σ confidence level.

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Green, broadband coherent Doppler-lidar for aerosol-cloud-dynamics-interaction studies

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Keywords: Heterodyne high-spectral-resolution Doppler-lidar, Mie-Rayleigh-Brillouin signal, multiple peaks

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Introduction

Disentangling aerosol-cloud-dynamics interaction can only be done with a combined remote-sensing instrument approach (Bühl, 2019). In the scope of the ACTRIS-project, a heterodyne high-spectral-resolution Doppler-lidar at 532 nm wavelength and with a 6.4 GHz broadband data acquisition is developed to enable the observation of aerosol and cloud particles and atmospheric dynamics with high temporal and velocity resolution. The high backscatter signal level, Doppler resolution, and the ability to detect the molecular backscatter signal enables observations of aerosol and cloud particles at the same time at higher temporal, spatial, and velocity resolution. This work presents the current technical setup and the state of the data processing chain.

Technical setup

A scheme of the optical setup is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of Doppler-lidar. AOM...Acusto-optic modulator, SHG...second harmonic generation, FC...fibre coupler

Characteristic for the transceiver setup is the four-stage pulse amplifier, a separate SHG for local oscillator and pulsed signal and the separation of outgoing and atmospheric pulses by a dichroic mirror after the SHG-crystal. The interference of reference and atmospheric signal takes place in the FC and causes a beat signal that is analysed by a time-resolved Fourier transform.

The wavelength of 532 nm causes a resolution of $3.76 \text{ MHz m}^{-1} \text{ s}$. The data acquisition bandwidth of 6.4 GHz enables the detection of both aerosol and cloud particle (Mie) and molecular (Rayleigh-Brillouin) signal in one spectrum.

Measurement and discussion

A measurement case is shown in Figure 2. Plot (a) shows an around 3.5 km thick aerosol layer with some clouds above 5 km around 06:00 UTC. Plot (b) reveals some gravity waves around 05:30 UTC and precipitation at the end. The integrated Rayleigh-Brillouin in plot (c) reaches up to around 2.5 km with only 10s integration time (20000 shots). Plot (d) indicates that especially in the precipitation more than one peak in the spectra is found.

Figure 2. Measurement case from 5th July 2023 over Leipzig, Germany.

The separation of these multiple peaks, their attribution to a specific particle type with the help of other Doppler techniques and the differentiation of the dynamic processes is one important next step as well as the improvement of the optical setup to reach higher signal strengths.

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Retrieval of ozone number density profiles from limb scattering measurements by machine learning techniques

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We present a general approach for the inversion of limb radiances scattered by the Earth atmosphere illuminated by solar radiation in the UV-VIS-NIR range.

Atmospheric remote sensing typically requires the definition of a “forward” model, which represents the radiative transfer (RTM) within the atmosphere towards the detector. The forward model converts an atmospheric state vector into a corresponding observed radiance.

The retrieval of atmospheric absorbers from observations is the inverse problem, often ill posed and constrained by the instrumental performance factors (mostly SNR, vertical and spectral resolution, etc.).

A substantial body of literature exists regarding algorithmic methods to address this challenge (Rodgers, 2000), broadly categorized into Bayesian and non-Bayesian interpretations. However, in cases where the RTM is non-trivial and strongly non-linear, no closed-form inverse formula exists. In such instances, all methods aim to converge towards an optimal solution through an iterative scheme, necessitating numerous expensive evaluations of the forward model, which are often not recorded.

When dealing with a large number of observations and recognizing that the inverse problem entails a reverse mapping, from the radiances to the state vector, an alternative strategy can be considered. This involves running the RTM for a very large training set (LTS) comprising various possible realizations of the atmosphere/radiances cases, thereby shifting the computational load to LTS generation. The resulting extensive look-up table (LUT) inputs/outputs are then swapped to feed an artificial neural network (ANN). The recently demonstrated capabilities of ANNs in performing non-linear regression make them a viable solution.

This research has been conducted in parallel with the development of the data processor for the ALTIUS Earth Watch mission where operational ozone number density profiles are the main target. ALTIUS will be operated mostly in limb scattering geometry.

The Ozone Neural Network Inversion (ONNI) contains:

- The generation of the LTS including ozone, aerosol, air and albedo.

- The radiance computations at all relevant wavelengths, tangent altitudes and solar angles by using the Monte Carlo RTM SmartG (Ramon, 2019).
- The statistical description of the LTS limb spectral radiance profiles with a Principal Component Analysis (PCA).
- The building and optimisation of the ANN for reverse mapping of the radiances into the LTS.

The proposed methodology was tested against self-consistency and can be generalized.

Amongst the very few limb sounders operating today, the OMPS instrument on board SUOMI-NPP is a sensor rather similar to ALTIUS, for both vertical and spectral ranges. Recently, Aroso *et al.* (2018) have inter-compared two ozone retrieval algorithms applied to the OMPS radiances. It was therefore a unique chance of testing our ONNI method on the same data, taking into account that no instrumental fine-tuning nor special corrections (like cloud screening) would be applied.

The results are very encouraging when considering a full month of OMPS observations (Mar 2016) and they will be presented at the conference.

Figure 1: NASA/BREMEN/ONNI retrieved ozone profiles and the associated standard deviations

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Fluorescence lidar improves the detection of (thin) aerosol layers

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Keywords: fluorescence lidar, aerosol detection, smoke-cirrus interaction.

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Climate change is the biggest global challenge of today's world, and to predict its future development, a deeper understanding of aerosol particles is essential. Multiwavelength polarization lidars are very powerful tools to detect and determine aerosol type (Floutsi et al., 2023; Groß et al., 2013). Since the air density and atmospheric transmission decrease with altitude, the lidar signal shows a wide dynamic range from the ground up to high altitudes. Usually, neutral-density filters are used to avoid saturation of the detectors at lower heights. However, this reduces the sensitivity at high altitudes, which limits the reliable detection of aerosol layers to a certain height.

Recent studies showed that the fluorescence lidar technique has great potential to improve aerosol classification (Reichardt et al., 2018; Veselovskii et al., 2020; Veselovskii et al., 2022). Our present study demonstrates that fluorescence measurements extend the potential of a lidar system beyond classification. The fact that fluorescence backscattering is only induced by aerosol particles improves the detection of aerosol layers, especially in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) region, where often thin layers are present and go unnoticed when looking at the traditional elastic channels only.

In 2022, a new detection channel to measure fluorescence backscattering in the spectral range from 444 to 488 nm was added to the Multiwavelength Atmospheric Raman Lidar for Temperature, Humidity, and Aerosol Profiling (MARTHA) at TROPOS, Leipzig. In several measurement cases, the vertical profile of the aerosol fluorescence revealed the presence of aerosol layers that were not or only barely visible with the elastic detection channels. One exemplary case on 21 September 2022 is shown in Fig. 1. Judging from the elastic backscatter signal in Fig. 1(a), the upper troposphere would appear rather clean. Above the polluted boundary layer, only some thin layers up to 4 km height and a thin cloud at around 4 km height are visible. Instead, the enhanced fluorescence backscattering coefficient in Fig. 1(b) clearly reveals the presence of two smoke layers at around 9 and 9.75 km height, likely from North American wildfires, as suggested by back trajectories. In the mean backscattering-coefficient profiles, these smoke layers were barely noticeable from the molecular background, even when carefully choosing an optimal averaging period. Thus, it is unlikely that these two higher aerosol layers would have been detected without the additional fluorescence information.

Figure 1. (a) Range-corrected lidar signal at 1064 nm and (b) fluorescence backscattering coefficient measured at Leipzig on 21 September 2022.

The same issues have been observed for several nights in the 2023 summer wildfire season. Smoke layers were sometimes missed by the elastic channels, but they were clearly present in the fluorescence signal. This was particularly true for optically thin layers that were at high altitudes or present above cirrus clouds. This enhanced detection sensitivity for thin smoke layers has revealed that those layers are not so rare in the upper troposphere, especially during the burning season. This new feature can potentially bring some clarity to the discussion of what mechanisms predominate in the formation of cirrus clouds (homogeneous or heterogeneous ice nucleation). Those thin layers might not have a relevant radiative effect, but they could be relevant INP sources in otherwise relatively clean air.

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First data from the novel LIDAR at Atmospheric Rome joint supersite (ARTE)

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Keywords: ACTRIS, Aerosol Remote Sensing, LIDAR

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The Italian Atmospheric Rome joint supersite (ARTE) National Facilities includes two experimental ground-based sites located in the metropolitan area of Rome: one in the semi-rural area of Tor Vergata, the other in the urban site located at “Sapienza” University. The former site hosts a multi-wavelength multi-telescope Rayleigh-Mie-Raman (RMR) system at the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) research area of Rome-Tor Vergata. Such high-power system was designed and developed in the mid-90s by Congeduti *et al* (1999) with primary objective of monitoring several geophysical variables in the mid/upper atmosphere (e.g. Dionisi *et al* 2010, 2013a, b). Since 2016 the RMR system is part of the European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (EARLINET). The use of separate 11 Newtonian telescopes, with diameters of 15 cm, 30 cm and an array of nine 50 cm with f-number of 3, offers the possibility to sample the altitude range into smaller partially overlapping intervals. This allows for inter-normalization and reconstruction of profiles extending from approximately 0.3 up to 40 km altitude, depending on the geophysical variables.

To meet ACTRIS’s technical specifications, specific upgrades and tests based on the characteristics of the system were recently carried out on the 15 and 30 cm telescopes channels. The RMR performance in the near range was characterized by controlling the orientation of the 355 nm and 532 nm laser beams as well as the XYZ position of the receiving optical system placed in the focal point of the telescopes through computer-controlled servomotors (resolution and repeatability better than 5 μm). A semi-automated mapping procedure was developed to characterize the dependency of the acquired signal from the relative transmitter-receiver geometry by moving the diaphragm across the focal plane of the telescope, as described by Di Paolantonio *et al* (2022).

Figure 1. Schematic of the ACTRIS configuration for the 15 and 30 cm telescopes.

The system upgrades included the installation of a new high-energy Nd:YAG laser, as well as new modular multi-wavelength separation units equipped with remotely operated electrical shutters to perform dark measurements for each telescope. Each separation unit can be rotated to perform polarisation calibration measurements. The upgraded design of the optical system for the 15 and 30 cm telescopes is shown in Figure 1. This new configuration allows for an increase in the number of acquisition channels from five to twelve (summarized in Table 1) to meet the requirements of $1\beta + 1\alpha + 1\delta$ at 355 nm.

$$2\beta + 1\alpha + wv + T \rightarrow 2\beta + 2\alpha + 1\delta + wv + T$$

Current CH#	New CH#	Tele ϕ (cm)	λ (nm)	Type	IF FWHM (nm)
N/A	1	15	354,7	Elastic transmitted	0,5
N/A	2		354,7	Elastic reflected	0,5
N/A	3		386,7	N ₂ Raman	0,3
N/A	4		407,5	H ₂ O Raman	0,3
1	5		532,1	Elastic	0,5
N/A	6		607,6	N ₂ Raman	1,0
8	7	30	354,7	Elastic transmitted	0,5
N/A	8		354,7	Elastic reflected	0,5
4	9		386,7	N ₂ Raman	0,3
5	10		407,5	H ₂ O Raman	0,3
2	11		532,1	Elastic	0,5
N/A	12		607,6	N ₂ Raman	1,0

Table 1. Specifications for the upgraded channels. The new acquisition channels are highlighted.

Finally, we implemented roof automation with an ethernet relay and visual inspection via webcam for redundancy, an developed a custom software for remote power on and shut down, remote instrument control, measurement scheduling, data acquisition and real-time data visualization. In this work we present the first data obtained with the novel upgraded lidar system described above.

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Two and a Half Years of Aerosol Measurements Using an Automated Photometer on the First long-term AERONET Ship Site

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Keywords: ship-borne photometer, aerosol retrieval, MAP-IO program

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The Earth's oceans play a crucial role in regulating the planet's climate and atmospheric processes. An integral component of this system is the presence of aerosols, which significantly impact weather patterns, air quality, and the overall climate. While extensive efforts have been made to study aerosols over land with, e.g., the well-established AERONET network, a critical gap exists in our understanding of oceanic aerosol dynamics, impeding accurate global climate predictions.

Efforts to bridge this gap involve enhancing monitoring infrastructure, advancing satellite technologies, and innovating approaches to remote oceanic aerosol study. In this context, our work focuses on surface ship-based aerosol observation using a ship version of the automatic CIMEL 318-T photometer (fulfilling AERONET protocols/standard requirements) which has been in development since 2017. This innovation brings ocean-based photometry to the precision and automation standards of ground-based AERONET sites. In 2021, a significant milestone was achieved with the establishment of the first permanent and operational ship-site on the Research Vessel Marion Dufresne in the Indian Ocean (MAP-IO program, www.mapio.re).

The primary analysis of this work will present the first two and a half years of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) data from this inaugural ship-based site with automatic photometer measurements. Beyond temporal AOD analysis, we present the first microphysical and optical aerosol retrieval meeting AERONET level 2 requirements (figure 1). While measurements in the Indian Ocean region typically reflect pristine conditions, the week of October 12-18, 2023, marked by a biomass burning event, yielded several days with $AOD(440) > 0.4$, meeting AERONET level 2 criteria for aerosol retrievals using sky/sun measurements. Additionally, we use AOD

measurements from this new ship-based automatic photometer to validate AOD data coming from satellite sensors (in particular, S3-OLCI).

Moreover, we share findings from tests and proposed technical enhancements conducted during the TRANSAMA-AMARYLLIS campaign aboard the Marion Dufresne, highlighting advancements in data collection techniques. Notably, during this campaign, two photometers were deployed on the ship, facilitating tests and improvements.

Figure 1. Total column volume size distributions coming from the first retrievals meeting AERONET level 2 requirements from a ship-borne sun-photometer (Indian Ocean 16-17th October 2023). The size distributions retrieved from the closest (time and space) ground-based AERONET site (St Denis, La Reunion, 19th October) are also represented.

This work was supported by the ESA funded project QA4EO (Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation), and also by the European Union, H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015 (ACTRIS-2 (grant no. 654109)). MAP-IO was funded by the European Union through the ERDF programme, the University of La Réunion, the SGAR-

Réunion, the Région Réunion, the CNRS, IFREMER, and the Flotte Océanographique Française.

Accurate retrieval of pure black carbon aerosol properties including light absorption from in situ measurements of light scattering phase function

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Keywords: polarimetry, aerosol property retrieval, black carbon

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Remote sensing of aerosol physical and optical properties such as volume size distribution or single scattering albedo typically builds on probing the light scattering phase function combined with polarimetric retrievals. However, the inverse problem often is ill-posed due to the complexity of atmospheric aerosol. In particular, accurate retrieval of light absorption and single scattering albedo poses a main challenge, as demonstrated by Schuster *et al.* (2019) in controlled laboratory experiments, partly due to simplified aerosol representation in standard inversion algorithms. Here we demonstrate that considering non-spherical shape reduces uncertainty and bias of aerosol property retrievals for BC particles.

We used PSL size standards (spherical, non-absorbing), nigrosin (spherical, absorbing) and surrogates of black carbon particles (aggregate, absorbing) as test aerosols. An Aerodynamic Aerosol Classifier was used to select different particle sizes and to produce unimodal size distributions. Phase function and polarized phase function were measured using a laser imaging type nephelometer (uNeph; Moallemi *et al.*, 2023). Aerosol properties were independently measured using a condensation particle counter, scanning mobility particle sizer, aerosol particle mass analyzer, and photo-acoustic absorption photometer.

Optical forward calculations were either done using Mie theory for spheres or using Multi-Sphere T-Matrix (MSTM) calculations applied to aggregates as described in Romshoo *et al.* (2021). Property retrievals were done by implementing least-square minimization optical forward calculations to measured phase function data with aerosol properties as fit parameters.

PSL spheres and nigrosin were used to test feasibility of unbiased retrieval using a Mie kernel for spherical homogeneous particles. Indeed, agreement of individual retrievals with independent data was excellent with very small mean bias and high precision. The RMSE was 3% for retrieved volume equivalent diameter and 8% for number concentration. For PSL's the RMSE of retrieved real and imaginary refractive index was 0.008 and 0.002, respectively. For nigrosin, the RMSE compared with the mean value of the literature data was 0.026 and 0.058. This is small given a standard deviation of 0.03 for the literature data. A mean bias of 6% and an RMSE of 9% achieved for the absorption coefficient also falls within uncertainty of the independent measurement.

Using the Mie kernel does not provide a good fit to phase functions measured for non-spherical BC

aggregates (blue line in Fig. 1) and retrieved aerosol parameters were systematically biased. By contrast, using the MSTM kernel provided a good fit (red line in Fig. 1), and retrieved aerosol properties including absorption are unbiased within uncertainty.

The results demonstrate that using a simple aggregate model (perfect and monodisperse primary spheres) is sufficient for accurate BC property retrieval given simple BC aerosol samples and polarization resolved measurements. Future work will focus on coated BC and on ambient measurements, to assess the potential of reducing retrieval uncertainty for atmospheric aerosol by including a BC particle component in the aerosol model and optical forward kernel.

Figure 1. Measured and fitted phase functions for size-selected pure BC with an aggregate shape. TEM measurement, assumption for Mie inversion, and MSTM retrieval result for particle shape are also shown.

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The Swiss remote sensing network EMET-MET

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Keywords: Remote sensing, radiometer, doppler lidar

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EMER-Met is the new meteorological forecasting system for the protection of the population in Switzerland. It provides the meteorological basis for coping with all types of emergencies, especially in case of nuclear and chemical accidents. EMER-Met consists of a dedicated upper air measurement network and a high-resolution numerical weather prediction model.

The measurement network is composed of state-of-the-art remote sensing instruments to measure accurate wind and temperature profiles in the boundary layer. At three sites, a radar wind profiler PCL1300, a Doppler lidar Windcube-200s and a microwave radiometer Hatpro-G5 are installed. The synergy between the radar wind profilers and the doppler lidars allowed to reach an availability of 99% in 2022. Compared to the radiosounding, the RMS of the vector difference was below 2m/s for both the lidar and the radar, reaching the "breakthrough" WMO/OSCAR requirement for NWP forecasting in the boundary layer.

The data from the measurement network are assimilated into the operational 1-km ensemble numerical weather prediction (NWP) system. In the case of the microwave radiometers, we assimilate the brightness temperatures using an adapted version of the RTTOV observation operator. To ensure best impact on the NWP results, the data quality of the measurements is of high importance and is monitored closely on a

daily and monthly basis against radiosondes and the NWP model itself. EMER-Met is operational since 2022 and to our best knowledge, it is the first time that the brightness temperatures measured by surface-based microwave radiometers are assimilated operationally.

Instruments used in EMER-Met are also used in ACTRIS and one of the stations, Payerne is part of ACTRIS and is sensing data to the network.

This presentation will focus on the synergies between ACTRIS and the EMER-Met network and on the upper air network performance and standard operation procedures used.

Figure 1. illustration of the EMER-Met network

BLAnCA: a new broadband light absorption analyser for complex aerosol

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Keywords: optical absorption, innovative techniques, carbonaceous aerosol

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Atmospheric particulate matter (PM), and especially carbonaceous aerosol, plays a fundamental role in the Earth's energy balance and climate due to its light absorption and scattering properties. It is crucial to be able to study these properties in detail to obtain meaningful insights on its climate impact and – as they are related to aerosol sources and composition – to develop efficient abatement strategies.

In this context, a new instrument for light absorption measurements has been developed at the Physics department of the University of Genoa, within the ISPIRA project of the Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics (I.N.F.N.), and PNRR ITINERIS and RETURN grants. BLAnCA (Broadband Light Analyzer of Complex Aerosol) [1] is equipped with a wide spectrum light source and a high-resolution spectrometer. It can perform measurements of the light absorption coefficient (b_{abs}) of aerosol collected on a filter, on the spectral range [350, 900] nm with a resolution of 5 nm. At each wavelength, the phase-function of the light scattered by the sample is measured by placing the detector element on a movable arm that spans the scattering half-plane with an angular resolution up to 0.1°. This resolution allows absorption measurements of aerosol collected on several filtering supports, from quartz to Teflon fiber filters, to thin membrane filter such as Nuclepore. To determine the wavelength-resolved absorption coefficient of the sample from the measured phase functions, a modified version of the Multi-Angle Absorption Photometer scheme [2] is used.

The figure shows the λ -resolved optical absorption measured on different types of aerosol, loaded on quartz fiber filters. Synthetic and real-world aerosol samples are included. The synthetic aerosol was produced at ChAMBRe (Chamber for Aerosol Modeling and Bioaerosol Research), the atmospheric simulation chamber managed by INFN at the Department of Physics, University of Genoa [3], using a Mini Inverted Soot Generator [4]. The plot shows the differences in the optical behavior. In particular, the real aerosol has a marked peak around 550 nm, and the dust sample shows a steep rise in the UV region followed by a likewise steep abatement in the short-visible band. The absorbance of the wood-burning sample features three distinct regions of decreasing steepness, whereas the synthetic soot sample has a much flatter behavior, compatible with the

assumption that the absorption coefficient for Black Carbon has a λ^{-1} dependence on the wavelength.

Existing devices can only measure light absorption at a limited number of wavelengths (<10), whereas BLAnCA makes it possible to distinguish finer features in the absorption spectra that could be missed without this high spectral resolution. This data allows to obtain crucial information about the aerosol type, composition, ageing-induced optical modifications and source apportionment, and will also be fundamental for the optical characterization of particulate that will be generated in ChAMBRe in future experiments.

Figure 1. Absorbance spectra for four different aerosol samples. Black: synthetic soot, used as proxy for pure Black Carbon. Blue: resuspended desert dust. Red: real aerosol sampled in an urban background location. Brown: aerosol from smouldering wood combustion.

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Real-time bioaerosol and coarse particle cytometry in the atmosphere

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Keywords: bioaerosol, coarse particles, cytometry, monitoring, machine learning.

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The present study focuses on real-time monitoring of bioaerosols and coarse particles in the atmosphere, employing state-of-the-art Swisens Poleno air-flow cytometers. These automated systems, comprising both hardware and classification algorithms, have been deployed at two key locations: the rooftop of the Finnish Meteorological Institute in Helsinki and atop Sammaltunturi in Pallas Atmosphere-Ecosystem Supersite. They enable in-depth measurements of particle properties like shape, size, fluorescence, scattering, and polarization in real-time. The measurements span optical and aerodynamic diameters from 1 to 100 μm , processing approximately 500 measurement events per minute with an airflow of 40 litres per minute. This setup effectively handles coarse particle concentrations up to 12500 particles per m^3 , with higher concentrations managed by adjusting the triggering probability.

The working principle of Swisens Poleno is as follows: laser light scattering triggers the measurement, providing an initial estimate of particle size, velocity, and alignment by combining information from two trigger lasers. Following the trigger, two focused images, 90° apart, are reconstructed using digital holography, and UV-induced fluorescence provides information about the particle composition. Finally, optical polarization characteristics of the particle are measured in a time-resolved manner before it exits the device. The

classification algorithm employed a supervised machine-learning methodology, leveraging a convolutional neural network architecture proposed by Sauvageat et al., 2020. At the moment, our algorithm focuses on the typical pollen found in Southern Finland, playing a key role in establishing the Finnish bioaerosol monitoring network. However, it's highly flexible and has the capability to be expanded to include spores, algae, and non-organic aerosols.

Our algorithm demonstrated remarkable performance, achieving an overall accuracy of nearly 90%. It was assessed in the EUMETNET AutoPollen Intercomparison Campaign, where its performance was found to be on par with two other top-performing algorithms (Maya-Manzano et al., 2023). Finnish monitoring results were compared to Hirst-type pollen trap data (see Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Time series of observed pollen concentrations by Swisens Poleno (top panel) and by Hirst-type pollen trap (bottom panel).

Determination of low-level temperature profiles from microwave radiometer observations during rain events

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Keywords: microwave radiometer, temperature profiling, rain

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The continuous development and improvement of weather and climate models poses a great challenge to atmospheric remote sensing. For the evaluation of the models, increasingly better-resolved measurements and retrieval methods are needed, e.g. regarding air temperature profiles. Conventional observational approaches mainly fail as they are limited to provide continuous observations of temperature profiles under all weather conditions and especially during rain.

A microwave radiometer (MWR) can provide temporally highly resolved profiles of temperature and humidity, as well as integrated water vapor and liquid water path (Westwater et al., 2005), however, state-of-the-art retrievals are generally only possible during non-raining conditions (Ware et al., 2004). During rain the atmosphere becomes opaque to microwave radiation and thus no reliable information can be retrieved from higher atmospheric layers. Additionally, the radome of the instrument might get wet and the received signal is dominated by the liquid water accumulated on the instrument.

Here we show that the rain impact can be reduced by using only off-zenith elevation scans, i.e., observations at lower elevation angles, because liquid water usually accumulates at the top of the MWR. Furthermore, the influence of rain can be reduced by using only the higher frequencies of

the oxygen absorption complex which are almost saturated anyway and will thus not be influenced as strongly by liquid water.

A cross comparison with retrievals for certain angles and certain frequencies gives information about how accurate the rain retrieval is under different conditions, i.e., cloud free or during rain (Fig. 1). The retrieval performance is shown on simulations as well as on real measurements. First results show a good performance within the atmospheric boundary layer which is of high interest for precipitation studies. These promising results can help to directly observe the cooling due to precipitation evaporation and better quantify the according cooling rates within the atmospheric boundary layer.

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Figure 1: Panels a, b, and c show a comparison of four temperature retrievals and ECMWF output with radio-soundings launched at 4:45, 10:45, and 22:45 UTC on AUG 1, 2023. Retrieval name nomenclature: $Xv[z]Y\phi$. X : number of frequencies with elevation scanning; Y : number of elevation angles. The index z indicates that, additionally, three zenith observations for 51.26–53.86 GHz have been included in retrieval.

One-year continuous non-methane organic gas measurements with a PTR-TOF-MS at the Meteorological Observatory Hohenpeißenberg (HPB)

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Keywords: NMOG, HPB, ACTRIS, GAW.

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Non-methane organic gases (NMOG) are important constituents of the Earth's atmosphere. They play a crucial role in the oxidation capacity of the atmosphere and tropospheric ozone formation and take part in particle formation and growth via condensation.

Most routine observations of NMOG in the troposphere were so far performed with gas chromatography (GC/FID or GC/MS) techniques. While having a good chemical characterization, and being very accurate these techniques have some limitations. These comprise limited time resolution due to usually longer analysis times and the preconcentration step usually required for gas chromatography has a large potential for losses and artefact formation during the sampling process.

Proton transfer time-of-flight mass spectrometry (PTR-TOF-MS) is a comprehensive measurement technique so far mostly used for measurement campaigns. It can measure all compounds with a proton affinity higher than water (thus excluding smaller alkanes and alkenes) simultaneously without preconcentration and with a time resolution of one second or better. However, it is susceptible to fragmentation (especially for alkanes and alcohols) and cannot distinguish between isomers. Since both techniques complement each other, PTR-TOF-MS and GC/FID and GC/MS measurements are operated at the ACTRIS NF station Hohenpeissenberg side by side.

We will present the implementation of a PTR-TOF-MS instrument at our station and first ambient air observations data from the first year of continuous measurements.

Continuous measurements of anthropogenic and biogenic VOCs at the GAW Global station and ACTRIS-NF candidate Hohenpeissenberg (HPB) have been performed twice a day with on-line GC/FID (Plass-Duelmer et al., 2002) and GC/MS techniques since 1998 and 2000, respectively. Starting from May 2023, a VOCUS S PTR-TOF-MS (Krechmer et al., 2018) is applied to monitor a broad range of NMOG with a time resolution of one minute and detection limits for most compounds below 1 ppt.

We will detail the implementation of the instrument, including the characterization procedure to achieve high quality data. These are valuable information

for other stations planning to set up a PTR-TOF for continuous measurements at their site.

Figure 1. Three weeks times series of the compounds with the molecular formula C₈H₁₀ (xylenes and ethylbenzene) retrieved from the PTR-TOF-MS (red line) and the GC/MS (blue crosses) measurements at the Meteorological Observatory Hohenpeissenberg during October 2023. Error bars (GC) and shaded area (PTR) depict total uncertainty. Data shown is preliminary and not quality assured.

We will further present a first time series of PTR-TOF-MS measurements of various NMOG (e.g. aromatics, terpenes, aldehydes, terpenoids) with a time resolution of one minute. Characterisation experiments, instrument performance and set up will be discussed and PTR data will be compared to the GC/FID and GC/MS measurements.

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First deployment of the novel Particle Size Magnifier 2.0 for measuring the aerosol size distribution between 1 – 12 nm in atmospheric and laboratory conditions

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For studying aerosol formation and growth processes it is essential to directly detect the forming particles and to measure the particle size distribution down to the size of the nucleating clusters (~1 nm) with good time and size resolution. Recent studies have shown that the initial cluster formation and subsequent growth might be two different processes, controlled by partly different vapors, and especially the growth over the critical size range between ca. 2 to 4 nm is still poorly understood (Stolzenburg et al., 2023). Moreover, ultrafine particles often dominate the aerosol number concentration, especially in urban environments, but data on their properties and variation is still lacking.

Measuring the smallest particles is challenging due to their high diffusivity and low charging probability. Standard methods for aerosol size distribution measurements, such as mobility particle size spectrometers (MPSSs) exhibit large uncertainties in the sub-10 nm range (Wiedensohler et al. 2012). Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop better instrumentation and methods for determining the sub-10 nm particle concentration and size distribution.

The novel Airmodus Particle Size Magnifier 2.0 (PSM2.0) allows to resolve the size distribution between ca. 1-12 nm with time resolution of 2 min, without needing to charge the particles before size analysis (Sulo et al. 2023). Additionally, due to the re-design of the saturator flow system, flow mixing and internal liquid handling, PSM2.0 is significantly more stable than the earlier PSM version (A10 PSM), which improves its applicability in field conditions.

To test the performance of prototype PSM2.0 in field conditions and to compare it to other instruments, we performed measurements at the SMEAR III station in Helsinki during May 2023. SMEAR III is an urban background station located at the Kumpula Campus area ca. 4 km from the Helsinki city center. The instrument was measuring side-by-side with a Differential Mobility Particle Sizer (DMPS), an A10 PSM and a Neutral Cluster and Air Ion Spectrometer (NAIS). Further testing of the instrument was done at the CLOUD chamber at CERN during fall 2023 and during the ACTRIS intercomparison workshop for nanoparticle instruments in Helsinki in

November 2023. Results from these experiments will be presented in this contribution.

The initial data shows that the PSM2.0 compares well to the A10 PSM and NAIS ion mode in sizes below 2 nm, and to NAIS particle mode at the intermediate size range (2-7 nm), while MPSSs tend to show lower concentrations in this size range (Fig 1). Importantly, the instrument sizing range has been extended and time resolution improved (compared to earlier PSM version), without losing accuracy or detection efficiency of the smallest particles. This improved capability to detect both the cluster mode and lower end of nucleation mode provides an overlap between the activation size distribution measurements with the PSM and mobility size distribution measurements with conventional MPSSs, and thus significantly improves our capabilities to study particle formation and growth processes.

Figure 1. Comparison of the size distributions measured with different instruments at SMEAR III station (adapted from Sulo et al. 2023). PSM2.0 data in blue color.

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Characterization and application of an ultrahigh sensitivity PTR-MS instrument with a well-defined ion chemistry for air monitoring

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We present a novel instrument for detecting organic compounds on a molecular composition level in real-time based on proton-transfer-reaction mass spectrometry (PTR-MS). This FUSION PTR-TOF 10k combines several improvements compared to state-of-the-art PTR-MS technology:

An optimized Fast-SRI (selective reagent ion) ion source is capable of switching between four ionization modes with H_3O^+ , NH_4^+ , NO^+ , and O_2^+ primary reagent ions within sub-seconds to seconds. In addition, this new ion source improves the decoupling from the reaction chamber providing lowest interferences with neutral radicals (e.g. $\text{OH} < 0.1\%$) and parasitic reagent ions ($< 2\%$ for all ionization modes). Table 1 summarizes the primary reagent ion purity for all ionization modes.

Table 1. Overview of the impurities of the primary reagent ions (PI; H_3O^+ , NH_4^+ , NO^+ , and O_2^+) in percent.

PI-Mode	H_3O^+	NO^+	O_2^+	NH_4^+
H_3O^+ -Mode	98.64	0.49	0.83	0.03
NO^+ -Mode	0.63	99.20	0.17	0.00
O_2^+ -Mode	0.25	1.50	98.25	0.00
NH_4^+ -Mode	1.44	0.37	0.12	98.07

Ion-molecule reactions with organics occur in a fully controlled environment of a novel reaction chamber called FUSION where a traditional DC drift field can be superimposed by RF voltage. FUSION provides the needed clean ion chemistry with ion-molecule reactions at predictable reaction energies and reaction rates that are crucial for quantitative operation of a PTR-MS (Reinecke, 2022).

This FUSION RF reactor is coupled to a high duty-cycle PTR-TOF mass spectrometer with a rated mass resolution $m/\Delta m > 10\,000$. This allows for a good separation of isobaric signals and an unbiased assignment of most chemical compositions of interest.

With these enhancements, FUSION PTR-TOF 10k achieves lowest limits of detection (< 1 pptV in 1 s) and sensitivities up to $80\,000$ cps ppbV^{-1} while conserving the clean ion chemistry, linear response, and soft ionization settings of a traditional PTR-MS.

To demonstrate the unique capabilities of FUSION PTR-TOF 10k two experiments were performed: (a) the gas phase measurement of ambient air in Innsbruck, Austria, to demonstrate the linear response to clear sub-

pptV levels of VOC and (b) a CHARON particle inlet is coupled to the instrument to measure non-refractive sub- μm organic aerosol during summertime in Innsbruck (Eichler, 2015).

In both gas and particle phase, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), a class of toxic and persistent compounds formed through incomplete combustion of organic materials, have been observed among many others and will exemplarily be presented (Kim, 2013). Figure 1 illustrates the high resolving power of the employed TOF mass analyser enabling clear molecular identification of PAHs as well as the achieved detection limits in the low pg m^{-3} range at high-time resolution for these condensed organics.

Figure 1. Quantitative detection of ultra-low concentrations of PAHs condensed on particles in ambient air in Innsbruck, Austria.

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PM2.5 Retrievals by Integrated-Nephelometer using GRASP algorithm from SPARTAN Network

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PM2.5 monitoring is crucial as it provides insights into fine particulate matter, enabling analysis of air quality and understanding its impact on human health. The SPARTAN network deploys AirPhoton IN100 nephelometers and sampling stations as well as other instruments at sites around the world. The 3-wavelengths nephelometers measure total and back scatter at 450, 532 and 632nm at PM2.5 and PM10 size-cutoffs with high temporal resolution. By combining gravimetric measurements from sampling station filters and nephelometer measurements, SPARTAN has provided hourly PM2.5 which have been validated against TEOM measurements and shown reasonable agreement with correlation of 0.79 (Snider et al., 2015).

GRASP is a next generation open-source algorithm developed for aerosol retrievals which has been applied in diverse in-situ and airborne instruments such as sun-radiometer, lidar, satellite sensors etc (Dubovik et al, 2011, Lopatin 2021, Torres 2014). In recent developments, GRASP has also been applied various nephelometers, such as PI-Neph, IMAP as well as Integrated-Nephelometer to obtain aerosol properties.

In this study, GRASP has been utilized to retrieve PM2.5 from SPARTAN nephelometer measurements. In the IN-Neph/GRASP retrievals, the aerosol size distribution and refractive indices have been obtained and by integrating size distribution, the PM2.5 can be calculated assuming aerosol density is unity. Then, the aerosol density is determined for each site by comparing the PM2.5 retrievals from test datasets and the SPARTAN PM2.5 hourly estimates and these densities have been applied on the nephelometer PM2.5 retrievals for each site.

Figs.1 and 2 show the comparison between GRASP retrieved PM2.5 and SPARTAN PM2.5 hourly estimate, as it's seen that at Downsview, Canada site, the two PM2.5 datasets have very strong consistency and the retrieved PM2.5 captured the temporal variation of PM2.5 very well even during the low pollution episodes. Fig.3 has shown the result for Beijing, China site, which exhibits good retrievals from 23-April to 17-July 2023, however

the retrieval performance for the later half month became worse, which might be due to the change of aerosol type thus the density estimate was not suitable anymore. Based on current results, the investigation and development on determining the correction factor is ongoing, and it's expected to get PM2.5 retrieval from nephelometer alone instead of relying on other instrumentation, which would in the future facilitate the PM2.5 monitoring in a wider coverage.

Figure 1. Scatterplots of GRASP retrieved PM2.5 and SPARTAN hourly estimated PM2.5 at Downsview, Canada.

Figure 2. Time series of GRASP retrieved PM2.5 and SPARTAN hourly estimated PM2.5 at Downsview, Canada.

Figure 3. Time series of GRASP retrieved PM2.5 and SPARTAN hourly estimated PM2.5 at Beijing, China.

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Fiducial Reference Measurement in Support for Operational Meteorological Satellite Missions.

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Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM) are tailored and fully characterized measurements and therefore key elements of the EUMETSAT Calibration and Validation (Cal/Val) activities. Consequently, it is important for EUMETSAT, as an operational agency, to ensure a gapless provision of ground-based measurements during the mission lifetime.

For this purpose, EUMETSAT is continuously performing gap analysis towards existing ground-based measurements in order to identify the needed consolidation in term of Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM). The quality, the timeliness, the access, long-term availability and special FRM needs (e.g. global coverage, better overpass time match) should be considered for the network consolidation.

EUMETSAT's assessment is performed per product as identified in the mission requirements and the Cal/Val plans. This allows EUMETSAT to find commonalities and synergies between the instruments to be highlighted, therefore making the gap analysis more complete. In general, the availability of in-situ measurements and FRMs will be evaluated through a dedicated roadmap and in close coordination with the EUMETSAT member states and the European Commission. Targeted effort through EUMETSAT interactions with entrusted entities (e.g. ACTRIS, EEA, EUMETNET) will help to further coordinate the availability of needed Cal/Val parameters.

This abstract is presenting the example of the atmospheric composition and air quality products (table 1) that illustrate well the complementarity and challenges of the actual and future EUMETSAT operated missions. This is highlighting the ACTRIS efforts producing high-quality aerosol, cloud and trace gas data with centralised access and quality assessment. Availability of European infrastructure is essential for the long term sustained provision of adequate FRMs for calibration and validation of operational meteorological satellite missions.

Table 1. EUMETSAT Operational Missions related to Air Quality.

Products	Satellites Missions	Metop GOME-2	IASI	S3 SLSTR	OLCI	MTG S4	IRS	Metop-SG S5	3MI	IASI-NG	CO2M
GASES											
O ₃ total column											
O ₃ tropospheric column											
O ₃ profile											
NO ₂ total column											
NO ₂ tropospheric column											
NO total column											
HCHO total column											
SO ₂ total column											
SO ₂ layer height											
CH ₃ CO total column											
CO total/partial column											
CO profile											
CO ₂ total column											
CH ₄ total/partial column											
Nitric acid partial column											
Water vapour total column											
Water vapour profile											
AEROSOLS											
Aerosol optical depth		(1)									
Aerosol effective radius											
Aerosol layer height											
Aerosol refractive index											
Aerosol single scattering albedo											
Aerosol Model or Type		(1) class									
Aerosol absorbing index		(1) flag							(2)		
Volcanic ash		(1) flag							(2)		
Desert Dust		(1) flag							(2)		
Fine mode fraction											
Angstrom coefficient											
CLOUDS											
Cloud detection and fraction											
Cloud top phase											
Cloud top height											
Cloud droop effective radius											
Cloud optical thickness											

(1) PMap aerosol product (assimilated by CAMS) combining of Metop instruments GOME2/AVHRR/IASI
 (2) MAP aerosol product combining Metop-SG instruments 3MI/Metimage/S5/IASI-SG

Cal/val of European spaceborne lidars leveraging the ACTRIS National Facility in Cyprus

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A large amount of development has occurred in the last few years around the launch of two spaceborne lidar missions by the European Space Agency (ESA). Aeolus, active from 2018 to 2023, was the first satellite capable of observing winds from the surface to the stratosphere, and has led to significant progress in atmospheric dynamics research and operational weather forecasting. EarthCARE, expected to be launched in the first half of 2024, aims to significantly improve our understanding of how clouds and aerosols affect the Earth radiative budget, with observations at unprecedented levels of accuracy.

The Cyprus Institute deploys its national facilities in an effort to contribute to the calibration and validation of both satellites. During June 2022, the Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory (USRL), an ACTRIS national facility and mobile exploratory platform, took part in the ESA-ASKOS experiment in Mindelo, Cape Verde, and operated several Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), fitted with a number of unique in-situ aerosol instruments able to profile the Saharan Air Layer between the surface and an altitude as high as 5,300 m ASL. The ATMO-ACCESS TransNational Access (TNA) project “Diurnal vAriation of the vertically resolved siZe distribution in the Saharan Air Layer” (DAZSAL) was also conducted at the same time. The campaign aimed to validate the Aeolus L2A product in the presence of dust and marine aerosols, estimate the influence on Aeolus products of non-spherical particles, evaluate the impact of particle orientation, and study the diurnal cycle of the dust size-distribution at high altitudes.

The instruments deployed on-board the UAVs permitted evaluation of the vertically-resolved particle size-distribution between 0.1 and 40 μm diameter, investigation of the particle orientation, and complementing observations of ground-based remote sensing set out by NOAA and TROPOS. Moreover, high-altitude dust samples were collected on impactors, for further analysis by Scanning Electron Microscopy. Weather was a determining factor for both the ground-based remote sensing operations and the UAV operation, and airport traffic was another constraint that needed to be accounted for.

In addition to USRL, the Cyprus Institute operates the Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory (CAO), which provides long-term in-situ and remote sensing observations over the island, and which is another valuable validation infrastructure, and also an ACTRIS national facility. Moreover, a great potential for the exploitation of synergies is available through the collaboration and memorandum of understanding with the nearby ERATOSTHENES centre of excellence, home of another national facility, the Cyprus Atmospheric Remote Sensing Observatory (CARO).

In this presentation we will discuss the potential and complementarity of these three infrastructures for the cal/val of Aeolus and EarthCARE, the knowledge acquired during the ASKOS campaign in Cape Verde, the opportunities stemming from the strategic location of Cyprus for the cal/val of EarthCARE, the existing plans, the room for further development, the funding opportunities, and the challenges.

Figure 1. UAV-derived aerosol concentration profile (left) and ground-based lidar-derived aerosol extinction coefficient (right) in Cyprus, 25 October 2023.

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The potential of EARLINET for the validation of aerosol height products from passive satellite sensors: An overview for TROPOMI/S5P and GOME-2/ MetOp sensors

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The knowledge of vertical distribution of aerosol is a key parameter in climate modelling and remote sensing. Large uncertainties in magnitude and sign of radiative effect originate from unknown or imprecise knowledge of aerosol height (ALH). Aerosol height information is an important parameter for aviation safety, can provide value to the modelling communities by improving air quality forecasting studies and helps in understanding atmospheric transport mechanisms. Polar satellites such as the Meteorological Operational (MetOp) and Sentinel-5 Precursor (S5P) satellite programme series offer the advantage of global and daily coverage and instruments like Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2 (GOME-2) and Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument have been used successfully for the retrieval of aerosol height during the last decade. This kind of product focuses on the retrieval of vertically localised aerosol layers in the free troposphere, such as desert dust, biomass burning aerosol or volcanic ash plumes.

Figure 1. (Left) TROPOMI/S5P ALH and (Right) lidar backscatter profile at 1064nm on 24 April 2022 over Limassol station.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the ability of TROPOMI and GOME-2 satellite instruments, to deliver accurate geometrical features of lofted aerosol plumes over Europe. Comparisons with ground-based correlative measurements constitute a key component in the validation of passive and active satellite aerosol products. For this purpose, we use ground-based observations from quality-controlled lidar stations reporting to the European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (EARLINET; Pappalardo et al., 2014). An optimal methodology for validation purposes (Michailidis et al., 2021; 2023) has been developed and applied using the EARLINET optical profiles and satellite aerosol products, aiming at the continuous and in-depth evaluation of the

GOME-2 (Tilstra et al. 2019) and TROPOMI (Nanda et al., 2018) ALH product since 2007 and 2018, respectively. The quantitative validation at pixels over selected EARLINET stations illustrates that the TROPOMI and GOME-2 ALH products are consistent with the EARLINET lidar products, with mean biases of -0.18 ± 1.68 km and -0.51 ± 0.77 km respectively. A dust case event originating from Saudi Arabia, is presented in Fig.1, on the 24th of April 2022, over Cyprus. This dust event was well-captured by TROPOMI/S5P and compared against lidar measurements obtained by Limassol EARLINET station (CUT-TEPAK) regarding the ALH retrievals.

This study highlights the importance of the synergistic use of active and satellite passive observations suggesting a promising usage of ALH from passive satellites for understanding the details of the presence and transport of aerosol layers. Furthermore, it is planned to implement the mentioned methodology for the evaluation process of the dust profile product from IASI/ MetOp using the EARLINET database. The increased availability of high-quality-assured profiling data from EARLINET will also form a scientific background to improve performance of future (e.g. Sentinel-4,-5) passive satellite sensors leading to a better understanding of the role of the aerosol height regarding air quality and climate.

We acknowledge EARLINET stations for providing aerosol lidar profiles. This work was funded by the ESA-Quality Assurance for Earth Observation (IDEAS-QA4EO) and EUMETSAT-ACSAF projects.

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Detection of Saharan Dusts Events at Jungfraujoch, Switzerland using Hidden Markov Models applied to in situ aerosol measurements

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Saharan Dust Events (SDEs) have important impacts on air quality, climate, weather and photovoltaic energy forecasts. SDEs can be identified using in situ measurements of aerosol optical properties (Collaud Coen et al., 2004) and size distributions (Duchi et al., 2016). However, these existing methods are limited by their overreliance on single instruments/datasets and their classification results do not always agree. The goal of the present study is to explore new statistical modelling and machine learning methods for SDE detection that take as input a broader range of measurements. As a first step, we restrict our inputs to multivariate, in situ aerosol measurements that will be routinely recorded at ACTRIS Observational Platforms such as the Jungfraujoch National Facility in the Swiss Alps.

We focus primarily on statistical models known as Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). HMMs can be used to compute a sequence of hidden states corresponding to a time series of measurements. The hidden states can then be associated with physical phenomena such as the occurrence of SDEs. HMMs have several advantages in this problem context, including unsupervised training, flexibility, and the potential to be extended to other applications (e.g., detection of wildfire plumes, free tropospheric conditions, etc.). We consider standard HMMs as well as two variants: autoregressive HMMs (AR-HMMs) and hidden semi-Markov models (HSMMs).

As proof of concept, we used 5 years of measurements (2016-2021) of aerosol optical properties and size distributions from the Jungfraujoch observatory. Two years (2017, 2020) were arbitrarily chosen for manual labelling of SDE events by expert judgement based on multiple inputs (in situ measurements, air mass back trajectories, CAMS dust forecasts). These labels represent a quasi-ground-truth since their accuracy cannot be fully validated. The HMM-based classification results were compared with those from two baseline methods: the traditional method based on the single scattering albedo exponent (SSA exponent; Collaud Coen et al., 2004) and a random forest model (supervised machine learning method).

Figure 1 provides a sample of the overall results. It displays the positive (SDE identified), negative (non-

SDE identified), and balanced (average of the classes) accuracies for the various methods for the labelled year 2017, where the other labelled year 2020 was used for training the random forest model and assigning HMM states to SDEs. The baseline models were generally very good at classifying non-events (higher negative accuracy), but this came at the expense of missing actual SDEs (lower positive accuracy). A better balance between the event classes was found for the HSMM model, which was good at detecting both SDEs and non-SDEs. Overall, the performance of the HMM models was comparable to the baseline models, demonstrating successful proof of concept. Furthermore, the HMMs could also be used to detect an entirely different phenomenon – the occurrence of free tropospheric conditions – with good accuracy. These are promising results considering the inherent advantages of the HMM approach (e.g., unsupervised training).

In the presentation, we will provide a deeper overview of the HMM modelling framework as well as the obtained results. In addition, we will present an outlook on how the approach could be further developed and utilized with ACTRIS observations in the future.

Figure 1. Accuracy metrics (%) for the labelled year 2017

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Estimation of rain induced attenuation in cloud radar observations

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Figure 1: Ice water content retrieval status from the Cloudnet categorize product (Moisseev et al, 2023). No retrieval of ice cloud properties is carried out above rain (grey colour).

The cloud remote sensing observations carried out at ACTRIS stations provide a unique dataset of cloud properties that spans across different climatic zones. These observations can be used to evaluate the representation of clouds by numerical weather prediction models (Illingworth et al, 2007). Currently, no retrieval of ice cloud properties above the melting layer of precipitation is carried out as a part of ACTRIS cloud remote sensing data analysis, see Fig. 1 for an example of the ice water content retrieval status from the Cloudnet categorize product (Moisseev et al, 2023). The uncorrected attenuation caused by a wet radar radome, path attenuation in rain, and attenuation in the melting layer introduce significant errors that make the retrieval of ice cloud properties highly inaccurate. In such cases there is no retrieval of ice cloud microphysical properties, making the observed statistics of ice clouds only representative of non-raining cloud systems. To obtain observations of ice cloud properties representative of all cloud systems, the attenuation should be estimated and compensated for.

The standard equipment of ACTRIS Cloudnet stations consist of a cloud radar, ceilometer, microwave radiometer, disdrometer, precipitation gauge, and weather station. In this study, we show how observations from the disdrometer in combination with a precipitation gauge and cloud radar can be used to estimate rain-induced attenuation in radar measurements. The data used in this study is collected at the University of Helsinki SMEARII ACTRIS cloud remote sensing station, located in Hyttiälä, Southern Finland during the years 2022 and 2023. Measurements are taken by a Parsivel disdrometer, Pluvio precipitation gauge, and a vertically pointing W-band Doppler cloud radar.

Disdrometer observations of raindrop size distributions (DSD's) have been used to derive radar-

based rain retrievals, and radar calibration offsets in many studies (Myagkov et al, 2020). The challenge in this type of analysis is the inherent uncertainty of computed radar variables from disdrometer observations, arising from the relatively small sampling volume. The objective of this study is to estimate the attenuation at temporal scales of a minute, and therefore the uncertainties of such estimates should also be computed. The proposed method is to use disdrometer observations to calculate the radar reflectivity factor to estimate radome attenuation, and specific rain attenuation to derive rain path attenuation of the radar signal. To assess the uncertainty of these estimates, DSD observations are forward modelled (Moisseev & Chandrasekar, 2007).

Rain evaporation and an increase in precipitation intensity due to embedded clouds, will limit the applicability of the disdrometer derived specific attenuation for compensation of rain path attenuation. A method for diagnosing such cases is derived by comparing the observed radar reflectivity profile and the expected profile that is computed from a combination of disdrometer and radar observations.

Overall, we show that in many cases the previously unknown attenuation can be estimated and therefore the statistics of ice cloud properties can be extended by including ice over rain cases.

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Validation of aerosol backscatter profiles from ceilometer through balloon-borne measurements

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Remote sensing techniques are essential to monitor and characterise atmospheric aerosol. Ceilometers have been proved to be a good tool to detect and monitor not only clouds, but also aerosol. In the last years, the developments of automatic lidars and ceilometers with profiling capabilities as well as advances in the calibration techniques related to such devices offer the capacity of characterizing optical properties such as aerosol backscatter coefficient. In the present study, we have evaluated the vertical profiles of the aerosol backscattering coefficient (β_{aer}) measured by the commercial CHM15K ceilometer (Lufft, Germany) by means of co-located balloon-borne measurements using COBALD (Compact Optical Backscatter Aerosol Detector) sondes. These sondes operate at two wavelengths (455 and 940 nm) and provide high precision in situ measurements of β_{aer} . A total of 30 COBALD sondes have been used for this validation launched at the aerological station of MeteoSwiss at Payerne (Switzerland) and the Richard Assmann Observatorium (DWD, MOL-RAO), in Lindenberg, Germany.

A wavelength conversion to account for spectral dependence and to correct for vertical and temporal resolution differences is required for a proper comparison (Brunamonti et al., 2021). This conversion is performed using the Angstrom law, and its derived Angstrom exponent obtained from the COBALD profiles. COBALD sondes show a vertical resolution of ≈ 5 m and are averaged in height bins of 30 m, corresponding to the vertical resolution of the E-PROFILE Level 2 data from the ceilometer. The ceilometer signal is also averaged in 30-minute bins, roughly corresponding to 10 km of balloon ascent time. Once all the corrections have been made, a statistical study is carried out to validate the profiles.

In addition to different retrieval techniques (forward and backward retrieval) for the ceilometer measurements, synergetic products from ceilometer and sun-

photometers measurements using GRASP (General Retrieval of Aerosol and Surface Properties) algorithm have been evaluated (Román et al., 2018). The use of the synergetic approach allows to improve the spectral information of the aerosol from the ceilometer and to obtain vertically resolved microphysical parameters. Figure 1 shows a statistical comparison between the ceilometer and the COBALD profiles.

Figure 1. Absolute backscatter differences between ceilometer inversions (Klett forward and backward inversions) and COBALD measurements.

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Improving elastic/Raman lidar near range measurements by estimation of the overlap function

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Keywords: Raman lidar, near range, overlap retrieval

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At near ranges, lidar signals suffer from a varying overlap between the emitted laser beam and the field of view of the receiving optical assembly. The overlap function of a lidar system can be defined as the ratio between the power scattered by a scattering volume at a given range that reaches the photodetector (excluding transmission losses) and the power scattered by the same scattering volume that reaches the telescope aperture (Wandinger, 2005;Comeron et al., 2011).

Wide-field near-range channels can be a solution for this issue as proposed by ACTRIS guidelines. Unfortunately, extra channels increase the cost of the lidar instrument.

The authors published an explicit method for retrieving the overlap function of an aerosol lidar with either pure- or vibro- rotational Raman channels in (Comerón et al., 2023). The method is based in the property of Raman backscatter inversion algorithm, which is independent of the overlap function, as long as it is the same for both elastic and Raman channels, as proposed initially by (Wandinger and Ansmann, 2002). The novelty is that it does not require any explicit lidar inversion and no iterations have to be performed.

Figure 1. Example of overlap function retrieved for different lidar ratio values (Comerón et al., 2023)

In this presentation, the authors will present the overlap functions retrieved for the present co-axial configuration of Barcelona lidar. The effect of applying the correction of the overlap to raw signals and its effect on elastic and Raman inversions will be presented as well.

Single calculus chain (SCC) ELPP module output will be used to calculate both the overlap-corrected and non-corrected raw signals. ELDA module output will be used for retrieving backscatter and extinction profiles.

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Intercomparison between MPL and ACTRIS Barcelona lidars in the framework of ATMO ACCES pilot TNA project for EarthCARE calibration/validation

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EarthCARE, ESA's and JAXA's Earth Cloud, Aerosol and Radiation Explorer mission, is scheduled to be launched in spring 2024. The objective of the ATMO ACCESS pilot TNA project is to calibrate/validate (Cal/Val) EarthCARE instruments/products against reference ground-based and airborne measurements provided by different networks of advanced instrumentation. In the frame of the project, intercalibrations between ACTRIS instruments and other systems and networks have been programmed in order to ensure a homogenization of the global validation dataset.

Among them, an intercomparison exercise between the Barcelona MPL (Micropulse Lidar) and the co-located Barcelona ACTRIS lidar is being performed in cooperation with NASA. MPLs are standardized lidars, globally distributed in the MPLNET network (<https://mplnet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>) (Welton et al, 2001). They operate and automatically upload data to a dedicated database in 24/7 regime. The objective of this exercise is to provide an in-depth characterization of both MPL and ACTRIS instruments through a co-validation of their respective products, identifying eventual sources of bias and quality issues.

Barcelona MPL is a backscatter lidar operating at 532 nm with depolarization measuring capabilities and automatic processing performed by MPLNET (Welton et al, 2002). Barcelona ACTRIS lidar is a multiwavelength (1064, 532 and 355 nm) Raman lidar with depolarization capabilities at 355 and 532 nm that uses automatic processing provided by ACTRIS' Single Calculus Chain (SCC) (D'Amico et al, 2015). Analysis is focused, on the one hand, on instrumental features such as limitations in both the near range (overlap) and the far range (alignment), interferences and noise. For this analysis, range-corrected signals are compared. On the other hand, the eventual effect of the different processing algorithms is also assessed by means of products comparison (backscatter, extinction and depolarization coefficients). Comparisons are performed following the

procedures and quantifying parameters stated in (Sicard et al, 2009). In this presentation, we will show the results of this comparative analysis.

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Figure 1. Barcelona ACTRIS (left) and MPL (right) lidars.

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New online services such as the “Homeless Data Portal” and “FLEXPART trajectories and footprint” provided through ATMO-ACCESS

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Keywords: Homeless Data Portal, FLEXPART, ATMO-ACCESS.

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The ATMO-ACCESS (Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities) EU-project is an ongoing project with the objective to provide coordinated open physical, remote and virtual access to state-of-the-art facilities and services in atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI)s. The ATMO-ACCESS online services for science are building on the expertise of ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS. The new virtual access portal aims to offer online cross-atmospheric research infrastructure services, address the archiving and curation of data, integrated data products for analysis and interpretation, footprints and virtual tools for training.

This presentation will focus on virtual access and demonstrate new services, such as the “Homeless Data Portal” and “FLEXPART products for ground based aerosol and trace gas observations”, developed through ATMO-ACCESS.

Homeless Data Portal

The “Homeless Data Portal” is a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up for submission of atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and trans-national access activities that are not normally included in any data management of data curation system. These data sets are considered “homeless data” and will be handled according to the FAIR principles as far as possible. All users can request data curation services for their atmospheric measurement data. The service also includes DOI minting for the data sets if requested by the user, either for individual data sets, or a collection DOI for a large set of data, e.g., full campaigns. This will make more data available for the end-users, as well as providing benefits for data collectors in terms of storage, usage tracking and access to RI (Research Infrastructure) specific tools for curation and data access.

FLEXPART products

FLEXPART products for ground based aerosol and trace gas observations. This service include products for BC, dust and microplastics measurements and more.

Figure 1. Source contribution to BC concentrations at Zeppelin mountain Jan 2022.

Figure 2. Footprint emission sensitivity for BC at Zeppelin mountain 1. Jan 2022.

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Condensation particle counter for unattended long term measurement use

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Keywords: condensation particle counter, monitoring, indoor air

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Here we present results of a new, propylene glycol, from two condensation particle counters (Airmodus A30 and A20). Propylene glycol (PG) is an odorless, non-harmful liquid, with low flammability (ECHA, 2023). A condensation particle counter (CPC) using PG can run for more than 10 times longer than a butanol CPC with a given amount of working fluid, without compromising the data quality, due to its much lower consumption.

PG has seen commercial use in e.g. vape-pens and in airplane de-icing. As a working fluid in particle counters PG was tested by Iida et al. (2009) in as a “booster” for activating sub-2 nm particles, but it has not been used previously in a stand-alone CPC as the working fluid. PG has considerably lower vapor pressure (10.6 Pa @ 20 °C) compared to butanol (639.6 Pa @ 20 °C), resulting in considerably lower PG consumptions, enabling much longer continuous operation for a given amount of working fluid.

Due to the lower vapor pressure, the CPC needs to be operated at higher ΔT between the condenser and the saturator. Despite this, the formed droplets remain smaller than in butanol CPCs, requiring the optical units to be fitted with a higher-powered laser to convert the butanol CPCs to a PG CPCs.

Figure 1. Activation efficiency curves for Airmodus A20 and A30 CPCs using NaCl and Ag as the seed material.

Compositional effects on particle activation are a well-known property of all CPCs for all working fluids. Water, Butanol and DEG for instance activate organics, silver, and sodium chloride, respectively, more poorly than ammonium sulfate (Wlasits et al., 2020). PG, likewise, has a compositional effect, but based on preliminary testing it appears to be smaller than for butanol CPCs (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Counting efficiency calibrations for the PG A30 and A20 CPCs. The N/Q/t values indicate raw data without dead-time correction.

Conclusions

We have presented an CPC with an alternative for butanol as the working fluid. The well-known drawbacks of butanol including toxicity, strong odor, high consumption, and flammability are avoided with PG. Our preliminary work shows that the cut-off (Figure 1.) or the concentration response (Figure 2.) of the CPC has not been affected by the change of the working fluid. The benefits of PG would appear suitable for long-term monitoring stations, and remote location where the butanol consumption and refilling are problematic, as well as for indoor air studies.

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Sensitivity study using ATLID lidar simulator and upcoming plans for the EarthCARE validation

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Keywords: ATLID Level 1 simulator, EarthCARE cal/val, eVe lidar.

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The Earth Clouds, Aerosol and Radiation Explorer (EarthCARE) is a joint mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) and the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) which will be launched in May 2024 (Illingworth et al., 2015; Wehr et al., 2023). Onboard EarthCARE, a High Spectral Resolution Lidar (HSRL) operating at 355 nm will be deployed, the Atmospheric Lidar (ATLID), which will provide profiles of the optical properties of aerosols and optically thin clouds (e.g. backscatter and extinction coefficients, depolarization ratio).

During the pre-launch phase of EarthCARE a lidar simulator tool has been developed aiming to provide realistic simulations of the space-based ATLID lidar signals (Donovan et al., 2023). The simulated lidar signals are used to produce the ATLID level 1 (L1) products of the attenuated particulate (Mie) backscatter, the attenuated molecular (Rayleigh) backscatter, and the attenuated cross-polar backscatter. Upon EarthCARE launch, the simulator is foreseen to be used from the Cal/Val teams for the optimum assessment and validation of the ATLID L1 products. In this study, we compare the the ATLID Level 2A (L2A) aerosol products derived from the simulated signals against the eVe lidar profiles targeting to investigate the sensitivity of the ATLID design on real aerosol layers. To this end, ground-based measurements of aerosol properties from eVe lidar are used as an input in the ATLID L1 simulator tool. Then, the simulated ATLID L1 products are used in the ATLID processing chain for obtaining realistic profiles of the L2A aerosol products that are eventually compared against the eVe lidar "ground-truth". The eVe lidar measurements used have been acquired during the ASKOS campaign that was held in Cabo Verde during 2021 and 2022.

The eVe lidar is a combined linear/circular polarization and Raman lidar for aerosol profiling that consists ESA's ground reference system for calibration and validation of the ESA Aeolus and EarthCARE mission (Paschou et al., 2022). The system will undergo upgrade to enhance its capabilities for the calibration and validation activities of EarthCARE mission, retaining its combined linear/circular configuration while incorporating state-of-the-art equipment tailored for

measurements on multiple scattering effects and automations to enhance the measurement procedures.

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AERIS data and services for cal/val activities

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The AERIS atmosphere Data Centre (<https://www.aeris-data.fr>), part of the French Data Terra Research Infrastructure (<https://www.data-terra.org>), has the objective to facilitate and enhance the use of atmospheric data, whether from satellite, aircraft, balloon, or ground observations, or from laboratory experiments. It generates advanced products and provides services to facilitate data use, to prepare campaigns, and to interface with modelling activities. It consists of four Data and Service Centres (DSC) with strong expertise in data curation, storage, preservation and dissemination: ICARE (Lille), ESPRI (Paris), SATMOS (Lanion) and SEDOO (Toulouse). AERIS has close relationships with different laboratories for transferring prototype products and expertise on data. Most of these data centres are involved in European initiatives and projects promoting the FAIR data principles and participating in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). AERIS hosts and manages data from many European projects and Research Infrastructures (ACTRIS, IAGOS, HEMERA...) and is involved in several satellite missions (IASI, CALIPSO, Megha-Tropiques, MicroCarb...).

AERIS is therefore used to provide and update atmospheric observation data provided by organizations or researchers offering today a vast archive of data enriched over time. If AERIS archives the measurement data of a wide range of atmospheric parameters, it also offers access to data, or databases, which can help in the analysis of the measurements (e.g. spectroscopy), or the understanding of observations (emission inventories, chemical kinetics). It offers sites and databases dedicated to experiments or instruments, campaigns, structuring projects.

This presentation of AERIS will be focused on calibration/validation activities with a zoom on space data. We will show tools and services where ACTRIS data serves objectives of space mission to provide the

scientific community with information e.g. atmospheric composition and state. AERIS is involved in the development of several space mission (e.g. METOP, MicroCarb, MTG, ...) in coordination with CNES and Eumetsat. On the other hand, AERIS lead or is involved in several Topical Centre of ACTRIS, providing data to the ACTRIS datacentre.

AERIS has implemented a data catalogue in order to make all the AERIS datasets discoverable and accessible. For this purpose, all the metadata describing the datasets are the most complete as possible and made compliant with standard formats and protocols. To allow interoperability with other data portals, standard services are being implemented and a vocabulary linked to the ones used in the French and International Environmental Community has been setup. In the next years an emphasis will be made to the use of semantics in order to improve the data discovery and advanced services such as online data comparison and processing.

Figure 1 Overview of the AERIS/ICARE DataViz with different visualization tools

We will describe and present example of tools and data services provided by AERIS for calibration or validation support, cal/val services, visualization tools, and dashboard.

First O₃ and NO₂ observations over the Indian Ocean by mobile Mini-SAOZ

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Keywords: ozone, NO₂, Indian Ocean, TROPOMI.

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In the frame of the MAP-IO (Marion Dufresne Atmospheric Program - Indian Ocean) project a Mini-SAOZ (Système d'Analyse par Observation Zénithale) UV-Visible spectrometer was installed onboard Marion Dufresne vessel to provide simultaneous measurements of total ozone (O₃) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) columns. The analysis is done by DOAS (Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy) method following the NDACC (Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change) recommendations. Zenith sky measurements are performed from sunrise to sunset until a Solar Zenith Angle (SZA) of 94°. The exposure time is adjusted automatically between 0.01s to 60s in order to optimize the signal and the spectra are co-added in memory during a 60s duty cycle. The data from a GPS device is used for SZA, location and time calculation. The dark current of the detector is subtracted from each spectrum. O₃ and NO₂ morning and evening vertical columns are averaged between 86 and 91 SZA.

Figure 1. Left: GPS antenna and optical head installed outdoor at 30 m above the instrument. Right: Mini-SAOZ in Meteo room.

The Mini-SAOZ is working in an operational way since the beginning of the project in January 2021. It was considered as a pilot mobile platform for the Central processing of SAOZ UVVIS Unit in the frame of CREGARS (Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing) of ACTRIS.

In this presentation, three years of continuous measurements are shown and various studies are presented.

An example: Satellite comparisons

Observations at ground are usually used as reference dataset for the validation of satellite observations in order to detect a systematic error or a drift or also to ensure a continuity and coherence between different spatial missions. The last satellite

mission monitoring O₃ and NO₂ columns with a very high-resolution is Sentinel 5 Precursor (S5P) mission (Veefkind et al., 2012) carrying onboard the TROPOMI (TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument) instrument. The observations of TROPOMI were already compared to the measurements of SAOZ/NDACC instruments, for O₃ see Garane et al. (2019) and for NO₂ Verhoelst et al (2021).

The Mini-SAOZ of Marion Dufresne is also compared to the SAOZ instruments of Réunion (20.9°S, 55.5°E) and Kerguelen (49.3°S, 70.3°E) NDACC stations. The Mini-SAOZ was already compared to other UVVIS instruments in the frame of CINDI 2 campaign at Cabauw, The Netherlands. Its performances are within the expected UVVIS WG recommendations (Kreher et al., 2020). Figure 2 shows the intercomparison of ozone total columns between Mini-SAOZ observations at Marion Dufresne, TROPOMI co-located data.. The columns observed by SAOZ/Mini-SAOZ instruments are superimposed to the figure when the ship is close to both NDACC stations at $\pm 0.2^\circ$ in latitude and longitude. A very good agreement is observed between the different measurements with a mean bias within $\pm 1\%$.

Figure 2. Evolution of the total ozone column observed by the Mini-SAOZ of Marion Dufresne, TROPOMI and NDACC SAOZ of Reunion and Kerguelen.

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A new CPC for ultrafine particle measurement

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Ultrafine particles (UFPs), defined as particles <100 nm in size have attracted considerable interest in recent years due to their potential harmful effects on human health. As a result, WHO (World Health Organization) has stressed the danger of UFPs and recommended to expand the measurement range of air quality monitoring stations to ultrafine particles. Adding the concentration of UFPs as a standard to air quality measurement stations would help to build up a solid global data basis (WHO, 2021).

Condensation Particle Counters (CPC) have been shown to be most suited for the determination of the number concentration of UFP. The CEN16976/2016 standard therefore defined CPC as the method of choice for determination of particle number concentration (CEN/TS, 2016).

AVL List GmbH, with headquarters based in Graz, Austria, is one of the world's leading manufacturers of CPCs. Originally, these devices have been developed for the automotive industry. Within this scope, the instruments are widely used for the determination of the particle number concentration for engine research & development and for the homologation of the vehicles.

Figure 1. AVL UFPM

The recently developed AVL UltraFine Particle Monitor (UFPMTM) is a laminar flow, butanol-based CPC. The instrument was calibrated at the World Calibration

Centre for Aerosol Physics (WCCAP, TROPOS Institute in Leipzig, Germany) using Silver nanoparticles. As shown in Figure 2, the AVL UFPMTM can be set to a cut-off diameter of either 7 or 10 nm). Additionally, to comply with ACTRIS standards, it has been equipped with a pulse out option.

Figure 2. Calibration performance of AVL UFPMTM

The AVL UFPMTM was used in a measurement campaign in an urban background station in Graz. The city of Graz is located in a mountain basin at 353 m a.s.l.. Due to the fact that Graz is located in a basin, surrounded by mountains, the airmasses carry higher loadings with fine dust compared to most other European cities. The campaign started in November 2022 for a period of 6 months. In addition to the AVL UFPMTM another butanol-based CPC was measuring side-by-side. The station also provides gas measurements (e.g. NO_x, CO, SO₂, O₃), PM and wind direction/wind speed/other meteorological data.

Results from this campaign will be shown. This includes a comparison to the other butanol-based CPC, which is part of the station and the long-term stability and low maintenance of the AVL UFPMTM.

WHO global air quality guidelines. Particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2021

Ambient air - Determination of the particle number concentration of atmospheric aerosol; German version CEN/TS 16976:2016

Thessaloniki's Lidar System upgrade with water vapor and fluorescence channels.

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Keywords: lidar, fluorescence, water vapor.

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Thessaloniki's lidar system (THELISYS) is part of the multitype ground-based instruments that belong to the Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics (LAP), located in the Physics Department of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece (40.63°N, 22.96°E; 60m a.s.l.) and is part of the European Aerosol Research Lidar Network (EARLINET; <https://www.earlinet.org/>), providing quality assured aerosol products since 2001 (Siomos et al., 2018). THELISYS through the last two decades has been gradually upgraded regarding its mechanical and optical parts. In the frame of the project "Panhellenic infrastructure for Atmospheric Composition and climate change" (PANACEA; <https://panacea-ri.gr>, MIS 5021516) THELISYS lidar has been gradually upgraded since 2021, to be fully automated, providing continuous measurements of aerosol and cloud properties.

On June 2023, THELISYS multiwavelength Raman depolarization system ($3b+2a+1\delta$) was upgraded and further equipped with two additional channels for calculating the vertical distribution of aerosol fluorescence (466nm) and the water vapor (408nm) using the appropriate interference filters. The two new channels are resided in a single PMT (Photomultiplier Tube) with a shutter, which inserts a filter whenever we intend to acquire dark, water vapor, or fluorescence measurements (Figure 1). THELISYS new products are the fluorescence backscatter coefficient, the fluorescence capacity and the water vapor mixing ratio.

In general, fluorescence lidar offers an opportunity for monitoring atmospheric biological particles and pollen grains (Veselovskii, 2020), which efficiently produce wide band fluorescence emissions when exposed to UV radiation. Thus, a growing interest in pollen studies is made in recent years as they can affect human health by causing allergy-related diseases. Additionally, the application of fluorescence lidar technique was intensively considered during the last decades to study aerosol particles and these measurements are proven to provide independent information about aerosol composition, which can be further used for classification (Saito, 2018).

Furthermore, over the past few decades, Raman lidars have become a potent instrument for supplying intricate water vapor profiles with remarkable vertical and temporal precision (Whiteman, 1992). The water vapor calibration is made by normalizing the lidar profile to a measured value obtained from meteorological

radiosondes that are launched daily at Thessaloniki Airport.

Thus, with the current THELISYS setup, we aim to further improve the aerosol characterization and typing procedures over Thessaloniki. The retrieved fluorescence backscattering and the particle depolarization ratio can be used to track pollen grains in the atmosphere especially from plants, i.e., quercus and birch, which are frequently observed during the period February to October in Thessaloniki area. Given that few lidar based studies, that combine fluorescence and water vapor, exist in literature for aerosol characterization, THELISYS dataset will provide a valuable dataset of aerosol properties towards an improved aerosol cluster analysis. The initial outcomes from the conducted THELISYS measurements are scheduled to be unveiled in March 2024.

Figure 1. Thessaloniki's Lidar System design.

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Airborne flux measurements for validation of VOC emission inventories and source attribution

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Keywords: volatile organic compounds (VOC), urban, agricultural, emission, inventory, airborne.

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For accurate prediction and modelling of air quality and climate, it is necessary to understand the emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from the potpourri of sources that they are emitted from: traffic, industry, households, plants, agriculture, etc. In the past, efforts to understand the magnitude and composition of VOC emissions have often relied on indirect methods – either using bottom-up emission models, or inferring emissions top-down from concentration measurements via chemical transport models. Both approaches rely on a number of assumptions regarding chemical reactions and transport - and thus are subject to large uncertainties.

Airborne flux observations provide direct emission and deposition information at landscape scale with a resolution of a few km. We performed airborne eddy covariance measurements of a large range of VOCs on board a Twin Otter aircraft in Los Angeles [1] and the agricultural San Joaquin Valley [2] in California using PTR-ToF-MS. Combining these observations with a footprint model, we matched them with gridded inventories in space and time. The comparison with the inventories showed a good representation of typical traffic VOCs but a significant underestimation of oxygenated VOCs (likely from volatile chemical products and cooking) and terpenoids by the inventories. Using airborne flux footprints in combination with landcover information of the San Joaquin Valley, we disaggregated the observed VOC emissions by multivariate linear regression and attributed them to their sources. This way, we obtained typical VOC emission rates and composition for dairy farms, citrus crops, citrus processing facilities, oak forests, oil and gas wells, and urban areas.

Figure 1. Schematic of the approach comparing airborne VOC flux measurements with gridded emission inventories as done for Los Angeles in Pfannerstill et al., 2023a. Figure under creative commons license (CC-BY 4.0) from Pfannerstill et al., 2023a.

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Real-time Monitoring of semi-volatile Emerging Contaminants via Chemical Ionisation Mass Spectrometry: Calibration for Comprehensive Atmospheric Analysis and Source Identification

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Keywords: CIMS, PFAS, emerging contaminants

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Emerging contaminants encompass an omnipresent, diverse range of chemicals associated with potential risks for human health and the environment. Their measurement in the gas phase traditionally relies on offline sampling technologies providing crucial data for policy makers concerning local or global trends. (Barber et al., 2007). However, these methods, due to their extended sampling times and thus low time resolution, prove inadequate in pinpointing the atmospheric sources and biggest contributors. Time-of-flight chemical ionization mass spectrometry (ToF-CIMS) offers high time resolution measurements with sub-pptv detection limits, allowing direct measurement of trace compounds in the air or headspace. It has been demonstrated as a viable method for real time detection of some of the emerging volatile organic molecules such as PFAS or pesticides. (Riedel et al., 2019, Murschell et al.)

In this study, we present measurements of selected emerging contaminants, including PFAS, utilizing our recently developed AIM chemical ionization reactor. Operating at medium pressure (50 mbar), AIM is optimized for adduct-ion chemistry and the measurement of complex, less volatile molecules, which typically undergo fragmentation in other real-time CI techniques like PTR. Additionally, AIM employs a VUV lamp as an ionization source, simplifying safety concerns associated with commonly used radioactive ion sources. We demonstrate the reactor's ability to achieve extremely sensitive detection for emerging contaminants on the order of sub part-per-trillion range.

To obtain accurate measurement and determine air concentrations, one must carefully evaluate general steps such as: sample collection, preparation, and calibration. As CIMS involves direct introduction of sample, our focus was on establishing a reliable calibration approach. When dealing with molecules not readily available in standard gas cylinders, calibration involves evaporating a specific volume of a diluted standard solution in a predetermined volume of clean air. We present calibration results that involve comparison of two approaches for standard introduction into the system.

We report sensitivities to selected compounds and the instrument's response to changing sample conditions, used solvent and temperature along with an approach that mitigates sensitivity variations based on ambient humidity. Furthermore, we explore the implementation of various reagent ions.

Figure 1: CIMS calibration curves for selected FTOHs and PFCAs with the corresponding calibration factors.

Our study emphasizes the reactor's capability to achieve highly sensitive detection for emerging contaminants at sub ppt levels. The Aim reactor can be used as a versatile tool for ambient measurements, covering various emerging contaminants in addition to the typically measured VOCs and inorganic acids typically monitored by this technique. We will emphasize its potential applications in environmental monitoring.

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Simultaneous observations of vertical profiles of aerosol properties in Garmisch-Partenkirchen and on Mount Zugspitze

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Keywords: aerosols, lidars, photometers, size distribution.

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The development of the remote sensing facilities at KIT Campus Alpin (Germany) is presented. The remote sensing equipment is located in the mountainous area of Zugspitze (2962 m a.s.l.) and in the valley of Garmisch-Partenkirchen (734 m a.s.l.).

Optical remote sensing of aerosol is, amongst others, one of the essential methods when it comes to the investigation of aerosol concentrations and their composition. Photometers and lidars, working simultaneously at several wavelengths, are nowadays widely used for such observations.

A new lidar system is currently implemented at the KIT Campus Alpin. It is based on a diode pumped Nd:YAG laser, operating at 3 wavelengths. The usage of a 300 mm diameter mirror resulted in an overlap near 250 m making this device suitable for observations of aerosols in the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) and the free troposphere. Energies of light pulses are 90, 90, and 50 mJ respectively while the repetition rate is 100 Hz. The receiving part has 7 channels (3β , 2α , 2δ). A new laboratory has been built in order to host this newly installed lidar system.

After a technical break, connected with building renovations at the summit, the photometer on Mount Zugspitze is now back in operation. This atmospheric observation facility can be seen as representative for the atmospheric conditions at high altitudes over central Europe. Moreover, in Garmisch-Partenkirchen, in the vicinity of the new lidar, a second CIMEL photometer is currently starting its operation. Both devices are sun, lunar and sky photometers.

The placement of a photometer near the lidar is a great opportunity to retrieve vertical profiles of optical and microphysical properties of aerosol. Using such software like GRASP (Dubovik et al 2021) allows for providing not only the detailed retrieval of columnar aerosol optical and microphysical properties but also the information about aerosol vertical distribution. The synergy of radiometer and lidar data provides information that is not available if only radiometer or lidar data would be used. This special setup allows for the retrieval of concentration profiles of fine and coarse modes of aerosol particles. (Lopatin et al 2021).

Mounting two photometers on different altitudes allows for distinguishing of aerosol optical and microphysical properties in two layers: PBL (typically <3 km a.s.l.) and the free troposphere (Posyniak et al 2020). Moreover, this will contribute to a better understanding of the properties of aerosol which is trapped in mountain valleys.

We will present the application of another approach with a software resolving aerosol particle size distribution (APSD) at different altitude levels for this particular instrumental setup. In this method, a predefined APSD function with few free parameters is directly substituted into the lidar equations (Sitarek et al 2016). The minimization technique allows for finding the parameters which provide the best fit of APSD, comparing theoretically generated signals with the experimental ones. The method does not require former knowledge of the lidar ratio (Makuch et al 2021). The results will be compared with findings produced with GRASP.

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Discriminating between "Drizzle or rain" and sea salt aerosols in Cloudnet for measurements over the Barbados Cloud Observatory

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Keywords: trade wind clouds, virga, sea salt aerosols

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The highly sensitive Ka-band cloud radar of the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO) frequently reveals radar reflectivities below -50 dBZ (haze echoes) within the updrafts and below the cloud base of shallow cumulus clouds. Haze echoes over the BCO are signals from hygroscopically grown sea salt aerosols (Klingebiel et al., 2019).

Synergistic retrievals like Cloudnet provide the potential to identify different hydrometeors by applying state-of-the-art routines on a complex combination of ground-based remote sensing instruments (Illingworth et al., 2007). Cloudnet offers a range of products, including the target classification scheme, designed to identify the thermodynamic phase of hydrometeors. Based on relying on radar reflectivities, haze echoes are classified as precipitation ("Drizzle or rain") within the Cloudnet target classification scheme for the measurements over the BCO.

We present a technique to discriminate between "Drizzle or rain" and sea salt aerosols in Cloudnet that will be applicable for marine Cloudnet sites. The method is based on deriving heuristic probability functions utilizing a combination of radar reflectivity factor, radar Doppler velocity, and ceilometer attenuated backscatter coefficient. The method is crucial for investigating the occurrence of precipitation and significantly improves the Cloudnet target classification scheme for the measurements over the BCO. The results are validated against the amount of precipitation detected by the Virga-sniffer tool developed by Kalesse-Los and Witthuhn *et al* (2023) over a two year period and during the EUciding the RoI of Cloud-Circulation Coupling in ClimAte (EUREC⁴A; Stevens *et al* (2021)) field experiment in Jan–Feb 2020 for the measurements in the vicinity of the BCO.

In the atmospheric column above the the BCO, "Drizzle or rain" is on average more frequent during the dry season compared to the wet season, due to the higher occurrence of warm clouds contributing to the amount of precipitation. Supported by the Cloudnet statistics and the results obtained from the Virga-Sniffer tool, 50 % of detected warm clouds in the dry and the wet season precipitate. The proportion of precipitation

evaporating before reaching the ground (virga) is higher during the dry season, and similar when reaching the ground compared to the wet season. During EUREC⁴A, a higher proportion of precipitation that is reaching the ground is detected over the RV-Meteor compared to the BCO.

Figure 1. Cloudnet target classification (including the new haze echo classification) and Virga-sniffer results for Dec 2, 2021 based on BCO observations.

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Airborne imaging of Arctic low-level clouds in the thermal-infrared – Application and testing of satellite cloud retrieval

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Keywords: airborne imaging, thermal-infrared, satellite retrieval validation.

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Arctic low-level clouds are a key uncertainty in understanding the feedback mechanisms causing enhanced Arctic warming, also known as Arctic amplification (Wendisch et al., 2023). These clouds were intensively studied during an airborne measurement campaign in March-April 2022 over the Fram Strait close to the sea ice edge. The observations were performed with the High Altitude and Long Range Research Aircraft (HALO), which carries the thermal-infrared (TIR) imager VELOX (Video airborne Longwave Observations within six channels; Schäfer et al., 2022). VELOX provides 2D images of brightness temperature in two broadband (both 7.7-12.0 μm) and four narrow-band channels centred at 8.65 μm , 10.74 μm , 11.66 μm and 12.0 μm . For a target distance of 10 km, a VELOX image covers an area of 6.4 km x 5.1 km with a spatial resolution of 10 m that allows to resolve fine cloud and sea ice structures. An example is given in Figure 1 showing sea ice surfaces and cloud streets covering the open ocean.

Airborne measurements in the TIR spectral range deliver information on cloud top temperature and cloud emissivity, which can be used to retrieve micro- and macrophysical cloud properties. Respective retrieval methods are available, e.g., for spaceborne measurements (Hünenbein et al., 2023a,b). The new satellite EarthCARE (Earth Clouds, Aerosols and Radiation Explorer; Wehr et al., 2023), which is expected to launch in May 2024, will carry the Multi-Spectral Imager (MSI). This push-broom sensor will measure radiances in seven spectral channels covering the visible to TIR spectral range. The three TIR MSI channels centred at 8.8 μm , 10.8 μm and 12.0 μm are similar to the VELOX channels. For the prospective MSI measurements a cloud product processor (M-CLD) has been developed comprising a cloud mask (M-CM; Hünenbein et al., 2023a) and cloud optical and physical products (M-COP, Hünenbein et al., 2023b). The M-CLD retrieval was adapted to the VELOX

measurements to determine cloud properties. These airborne measurements in the Arctic represent a testbed for the M-CLD processor as clouds are observed above contrasting surfaces, i.e., sea ice and open ocean. As an MSI pixel has a size of 500 m, the high spatial resolution of the VELOX data enables a sub-pixel validation. On these spatial scales, we expect inhomogeneities of cloud microphysical properties and emissivity, which may cause biases in the M-CLD cloud products.

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Figure 1. VELOX 2D brightness temperature T_B fields at 11.66 μm merged into a push-broom image along the HALO flight track.

Assessment of the Liquid Cloud Calibration for Atmospheric LiDAR Ceilometers

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Keywords: ceilometer, ceilometer calibration, liquid-cloud calibration.

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The calibration of Atmospheric LiDAR Ceilometers (ALC) is crucial for ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and stability of the LiDAR signal (Kotthaus et al., 2016). This process becomes particularly important when studying aerosols as it involves correcting the electronic background factors. A notable method for ALC calibration is the liquid cloud technique, which was first introduced by O'Connor et al. (2004). This method relies on the fact that the LiDAR ratio of liquid water clouds is a known constant.

In this study, we aim to assess the liquid-cloud technique by applying it to multiple ceilometer types (Vaisala CL31, CL51, and CL61, Lufft CHM8k and CHM15k, and Campbell Scientific SkyVUEPRO CS135) which are located at a single location in Munich. This approach is useful for the comparison between different ceilometers, an advantage offered by the ACTRIS CARS ALC testbed. In this regard, we have built upon the code of Hopkin et al. (2019) by changing the signal integration over bins to integration over height, and extensive error debugging necessary to apply the code for all different ceilometer types and facilitating a more effective comparison between ceilometers. In addition, a minimum signal threshold has been added to avoid low backscatter features that are not liquid water droplets (e.g. hydrated aerosols).

Figure 1. Time-height cross section of the attenuated backscatter (log-scale, manufacturer calibration) at 910 nm from ceilometer CL31 in Munich, 18-05-2023. Red circle marks an ice cloud as determined by the Cloudnet classification.

Figure 2. Calibration values (C_1) results for CL31, 18-05-2023 in Munich. Red circle marks an ice cloud as determined by the Cloudnet classification.

To test the algorithm, we used the Cloudnet classification product for the Munich station to select suitable days characterized by stratiform water droplet clouds, excluding those with ice clouds, drizzle, or high aerosol load. The calibration from multiple ceilometers was calculated for May 18th and 19th (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2), and the whole May 2023 period of a CL31 (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Vaisala CL31 calibration coefficient (C) results for May 2023.

The calibration proved to be consistent and robust, producing similar calibration values for the data analysed. However, some outliers were identified, corresponding to profiles that may contain other meteors than water droplets, such as ice crystals. These outliers were found across all ceilometers and could potentially be corrected by implementing additional and/or stricter filters. Regarding the monthly analysis many days exhibited profiles that passed all the calibration filters, even when the conditions were not ideal.

We plan to extend this work by making the code compatible with all the ceilometer types mentioned, and adding more filters to avoid the identified outliers, such as ice clouds. Furthermore, we will evaluate a long-term database of approximately 14 years for a ceilometer CL31 located at Girona (Spain, NE Iberian Peninsula).

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The Irish Atmospheric Simulation Chamber: a national facility for atmospheric sciences

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Keywords: atmospheric simulation chamber, radical chemistry, cavity enhanced trace gas detection.

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The Irish Atmospheric Simulation Chamber (IASC) was established in the Centre for Research into Atmospheric Chemistry at University College Cork (UCC), Ireland to enable the study of fundamental atmospheric processes and to quantify parameters needed in air quality and climate models. This national research infrastructure consists of a custom-built chamber (~27 m³) made of Teflon FEP foil, supported in an aluminium frame, and surrounded by a temperature-controlled enclosure containing 140 UV lamps for experiments on light-driven reactions. Standard parameters such as temperature, pressure (absolute and differential), relative humidity, and CO₂ mixing ratios are continuously monitored. The facility is also equipped with a range of commercial instruments for continuous, online measurements of atmospheric constituents including NO_x (chemiluminescence detector), O₃ (photometer) and particulate matter (scanning mobility particle sizer, SMPS). A time-of-flight chemical ionization mass spectrometer (ToF-CIMS), typically operated using I⁻ or C₆H₆⁺ as the reagent ion, is used for detecting trace gases and particle phase species, especially organic compounds.

At the core of the facility, however, is a selection of ultra-sensitive optical detector systems, which are based on cavity-enhanced absorption methodologies developed in UCC. The methodologies comprise cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) and incoherent broadband cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy (IBBCEAS) in conjunction with dispersive and high resolution Fourier transform detection schemes. Target species that can be detected are NO₂, NO₃ radicals, HONO, glyoxal (CHOCHO), methylglyoxal (CH₃COCHO), H₂O, and CO₂. With this suite of instrumentation, the IASC can derive much needed information and parameters to constrain predictive atmospheric models and improve forecasts. It enables detailed investigations of a wide range of atmospheric processes including chemical reactions of radicals, volatile organic compound (VOC) oxidation, secondary pollutant formation, as well as secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation and ageing in day and night cycles.

The current capabilities of IASC will be presented at the ACTRIS meeting and typical characterization experiments like the reaction of NO + O₃ (Figure 1) will be outlined to demonstrate some of its performance. In Figure 1, NO₂ measurements from 3 different instruments, CRDS

(green, extractive), IBBCEAS (black, open path) and chemiluminescence (blue, extractive) are compared with a kinetic model (AtChem, red). The mixing ratios measured by extractive and open path instruments converge in time between 13:30 and 14:45 hr.

Figure 1. NO₂ mixing ratio as a function of time in the reaction NO + O₃. Red: AtChem simulation model, black: IBBCEAS (355-390 nm), blue: chemiluminescence (Teledyne), green: CRDS (405 nm). Chamber operated in air-conditioned experimental (dilution) mode (grey = dark area, white area = UV illuminated). Vertical dashed lines: 13:00 addition NO & fan on, 13:04 addition O₃, 13:07 addition O₃, 13:22 fan off, 14:12 fan on, 14:15 fan off, 14:45 UV lights on, 15:34 flushing started.

The IASC is an internationally recognized facility with involvement in European research and training networks such as EUROCHAMP-2020 and ATMO-ACCESS. The technological potential of IASC makes it attractive to the international research community as well as private sector users. The versatile and highly instrumented nature make the IASC an ideal test bed for the development, testing and benchmarking of new atmospheric monitoring technologies and sensors under controlled (not field) conditions. Collaborations with industry and high profile international atmospheric scientists have been established and are further envisaged.

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Comparison of ToF ACSM and C-ToF-AMS running in parallel

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Keywords: ToF ACSM, C-ToF-AMS, m/z.

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Over the last two decades, various types of aerosol mass spectrometers have been developed and used in atmospheric aerosol research. C-ToF-AMS (Compact Time of Flight Aerosol Mass Spectrometer, Drewnick et al., 2005) and ToF-ACSM (Time of Flight Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor, Fröhlich et al. 2013) are two examples of these devices that were compared in our study.

There are several differences between the instruments, but both have a time-of-flight mass detector, but in contrast to Fröhlich et al. 2013 with a lower mass resolution in the case of the ToF-ACSM. Another important difference is the higher pressure in the measurement chamber, which means that the difference between air + aerosol and air-only signals must be measured in the case of ToF-ACSM. This leads to not so low detection limits and a lower mass range in the case of this simpler instrument. Nevertheless, the data from both instruments are used in a similar way to distinguish different types of organic aerosol with the PMF method. However, in order to obtain comparable results, the temporal evolution of each m/z should be comparable for both instruments. Here we show how this exercise works for our instruments.

The two instruments ran back-to-back in several comparison campaigns at NAOK (National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice) from September 16, 2019, when ToF ACSM was brand new and C-ToF AMS was about 10 years old. Each campaign lasted 2-4 weeks and was conducted at different times of the year. The data were CE corrected and the main species showed reasonable agreement within the time periods. However, when individual m/z were considered, differences were evident in both the average m/z and the temporal evolution of individual m/z within a campaign. Efforts to find the reasons for the differences in temporal development based on the parameters recorded in the device did not yield any results. An example of the mean, standard deviation and median ratios of individual m/z values between ToF-ACSM and C-ToF-AMS data for data above the measured median value is shown in Figure 1. Up to m/z 120 a considerable variability of the ratios around one can be seen, thereafter a systematic increase for higher m/z up to m/z 200 can be observed.

The temporal development of m/z 43 and m/z 44, which are used as the main components for distinguishing between oxidized and fresh aerosols, is shown in Fig. 2. The graph shows periods with the same

or different behavior of the two m/z shown as well as with the same behavior of one m/z and different behavior of the other m/z within a relatively short campaign.

Figure 1. ACSM to AMS m/z ratios, data lower than median value not used for ratios calculation.

Figure 2. ToF-ACSM and C-ToF-AMS m/z 43 and m/z 44 time evolution during the first comparison.

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Revisiting the needs of UAV-based observations in ACTRIS: New Technologies & Opportunities

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In-situ data can provide a great deal of information about the atmospheric environment that affects almost all aspects of human life. Despite the wealth of data emanating from in-situ atmospheric observations, there is a clear lack of cost-effective measurements conducted within the first kilometres of the troposphere. Height-resolved observations can provide essential input for validating remote-sensing retrieval algorithms and evaluating atmospheric models by giving unique information relevant to air quality, long-range transport of pollutants, radiative forcing, cloud formation, etc.

The Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory (USRL; Kezoudi et al., 2021) of the Cyprus Institute is a recently upgraded research infrastructure dedicated to Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based atmospheric research, development, testing, innovation, and training. USRL is currently the only mobile platform of the EU Research Infrastructure Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS), offering UAV-sensor solutions that can be used everywhere in Europe for intensive field experiments through a transnational access scheme and compliance with the drone regulation set by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA).

Figure 1. The mobile GCS and aerial views of the UAV runway and hangar.

The USRL infrastructure in Cyprus consists of a private paved UAV runway (Fig. 1) with private overhead aerospace granted permanently by the Cyprus Civil Aviation Authorities, a fully-equipped electromechanical workshop dedicated to the development of UAVs and atmospheric sensor integration, and a mobile ground control station for real-time control and monitoring of the unmanned flights. The USRL airfield resides at a rural background site of Cyprus, close to the Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory (CAO), which is another national facility of the ACTRIS network.

The USRL fleet vehicles vary in type, size and mass, depending on the payload and specific application (Fig.2). The USRL UAVs are equipped with a range of

Figure 2. The UAV fleet of USRL.

robust in-situ sensors used to provide both trace gases and aerosols observations. These UAV-sensor systems have the capacity to provide dense profiling of the lowest atmospheric layers (0-6km altitude) and to perform 3D mapping of plumes close to emission point (e.g., characterization of stack emissions). In addition to this, the newly state-of-the-art development of the UAV-balloon-sensor system from the USRL allows for the extension of these observations up to the stratosphere.

Since 2009, the USRL is participating in national and international research projects dedicated to: (i) the better understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions, (ii) the profiling of aerosol absorption properties in contrasted atmospheric environments, (iii) the vertical distribution of air pollutants below and above the planetary boundary layer over Cyprus, (iv) the aerosol size distribution over the Mediterranean Sea / Red Sea, and Arabian Gulf, (v) the validation of Aeolus satellite (dust) products, (vi) the characterization of ship emissions, and (vii) the provision of transnational access for research, development, and training.

Herewith, we present a brief overview of the major scientific and technical achievements of USRL, highlighting its great potential for future field experiments.

Kezoudi et al. The Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory (USRL): A New Facility for UAV-Based Atmospheric Observations. Atmosphere 2021, 12, 1042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos12081042>

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Investigating the application of narrow-band Rotational Raman filters for the detection of polarizing effects in a lidar transceiver

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Narrow-band interference filters (IF) are commonly used to isolate part of the pure Rotational Raman (RR) spectrum in modern Raman lidar systems. Such systems are usually focusing on measuring the extinction coefficient with an improved signal-to-noise-ratio compared to the simpler vibrational Raman technique. In this study we will examine whether they can be applied in polarization lidar system for the detection of unwanted polarizing effects coming from the receiving optics, the emitting optics, or the laser.

The concept behind this technique is based on the fact that the RR lines are highly depolarized with a depolarization ratio of exactly 0.75 for linear molecules such as N₂ and O₂ (She, 2001). Typical polarization Raman systems rely on narrow-band IFs to isolate the Cabannes line. Despite that, a small part of the RR is always transmitted to the co- and cross-polarized channels. As a result, the observed volume linear depolarization ratio (VLDR) in aerosol free regions can range between approximately 0.0035 and 0.015. The exact value depends on the IF transmission, the emitted laser wavelength, and the atmospheric temperature (e. g. Behrendt and Nakamura, 2002). This molecular value is often used as a reference point in quality assurance checks of lidar systems to detect changes between the expected emitted state of polarization and the one recorded. The small Cabannes depolarization ratio is excellent for the detection of depolarization effects coming from the optics or the laser itself. A single reference value, however, is not enough to express all potential sources of cross-talks in sophisticated lidar systems. For example diattenuative effects tend to introduce cross-talks that are proportional to the atmospheric VLDR (e.g. Freudenthaler, 2016). The much higher RR depolarization ratio is a far better candidate for the detection of such effects.

One could go one step further and attempt to cover the space between the Cabannes depolarization ratio and the pure RR depolarization ratio by taking advantage of the temperature dependence of the RR spectrum (see Behrendt and Nakamura, 2002). A special IF with well determined transmission can be applied for this purpose. This IF should partly attenuate the Cabannes line, making it comparable

with the RR lines in terms of intensity, and also attenuate the higher J RR lines whose cross section is stronger for higher air temperatures (see She, 2001). The resulting depolarization ratio varies with height. Lower values appear for higher temperatures and vice versa. As long as the filter transmission and the air temperature profile is known, the molecular depolarization ratio profile is also known, offering more reference points for polarization calibration measurements.

In this study, we show simulations of the optimum transmission shape that these RR calibration filters should have in order to achieve the widest range of reference depolarization ratio values. We assume commercially available IF shapes such as Gaussian, Lorentzian, and multiple-cavity IFs. We also take into account realistic tolerances in the transmission function. Moreover, we present the first lidar measurement performed with pure RR filters installed on the polarization channels of PollyXT lidar system installed in Mindelo, Cape Verde. We investigate the extent of information one can get for the lidar transceiver (total and cross-polarized) when using both the Cabannes and the pure RR depolarization ratio in a particle-free range in a lidar system which measures the total and cross-polarized component of the backscattered beam.

Acknowledgments

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Developing European infrastructure for real-time bioaerosol monitoring

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Keywords: real-time, bioaerosol, pollen, fungal spores.

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Despite their importance for human health, ecosystems, and climate, knowledge about bioaerosols in the environment is poor (Fröhlich-Nowoisky *et al*, 2016). Air quality, including particulate matter, is extensively monitored across Europe but its biological components are either reported as organic carbon (<10 µm particles) or ignored (coarser particles). To radically improve this situation, the SYLVA Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) aims to fill gaps in temporal resolution, timeliness, and availability of information about bioaerosols in Europe.

SYLVA develops infrastructure, technologies, and methods to expand and continue the European automatic monitoring of bioaerosol in the long-term. This includes establishing IT-infrastructure to host and process raw data from the monitors, identify the observed particles, and make their concentrations publicly available (Figure 1). SYLVA is also developing a platform to design, test, and run particle identification algorithms. Importantly, the infrastructure will be able to accept data from all devices from the main European bioaerosol manufacturers.

Figure 1. Infrastructure being developed as part of SYLVA for data hosting, transfer, and access.

An integral part of the project will focus on testing and developing instruments and methods in a range of extreme environments across Europe (Figure 2). To date, most automatic bioaerosol monitors have been run in central Europe, with particle identification algorithms optimised for these conditions. To fill a large knowledge gap, the instruments as well as these algorithms will be pushed to the limits under difficult environmental conditions and to identify other bioaerosols (particularly other pollen and fungal spores). Furthermore, to complete the aerobiological profile across Europe, SYLVA will carry out eDNA analyses using third generation sequencing techniques (Sofiev *et al.*, 2022) at several of

the SYLVA sites. All data and algorithms developed by the project will be made publicly available through the SYLVA infrastructure.

Figure 2. Map of SYLVA pilots where instruments and techniques will be tested under extreme environmental conditions (north: cold and wet, altitude: windy and high altitude, south: hot and dusty).

To ensure that the technology, methods, and results from SYLVA meet the needs of end-users, SYLVA is working actively with a range of stakeholders through a dedicated stakeholder forum. It includes representatives from different groups, such as public health, agriculture, policy making, and research. The various products and services developed through SYLVA, such as an API for data access and improved pollen forecasts, will be tested by this user group. The impact of the real-time information will also be assessed within the pilot studies. For example, real-time pollen forecasts will be provided to schools during the main exam periods and their use evaluated.

The infrastructure and technology developed through SYLVA can also serve the ACTRIS community. To find out more about the project, please visit SYLVA website: <https://sylva.bioaerosol.eu>

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A new generation of turbulence-resolving water vapor lidars: Implications on the understanding of short-term variability and fluxes

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Keywords: Water vapor, Boundary Layer, Lidar.

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Water vapor, unarguably, is one of the most important atmospheric trace gases as it has high impact on multiple processes - ranging from weather to climate scales. Especially in the planetary boundary layer (PBL), precise measurements with high spatio-temporal resolution are needed in order to improve, amongst others, numerical weather forecast and the calculation of latent heat fluxes (e.g. Wulfmeyer et al., 2015). Only recently, several mobile instruments that fulfill the tempo-spatial requirements for the requested data have been developed (e.g. Lange, Behrendt and Wulfmeyer, 2019; Vogelmann et al., 2022, Speidel et al., 2024).

When it comes to the ability of resolving turbulent processes within the PBL, the measuring instruments have to proof their eligibility of delivering high-resolution data at sufficient quality. This can be shown through the calculation of turbulence spectra, which have to be in accordance to Kolmogorov's “-5/3-law” (A.N. Kolmogorov, 1991). Here, we present such spectra for different instruments in order to give an answer to the question if it is possible to retrieve vertical fluxes of latent heat with the described lidar systems - even under daytime conditions.

Furthermore, the calculated water vapor mixing ratios on a temporal scale of up to 10s raise the opportunity of revealing unprecedented insights into the simultaneous short-term variability of humidity in a broad range of altitudes (Fig. 1). The reliability of these measurements is questioned both by calculated uncertainties and extensive cross-comparisons between several different water vapor lidar systems and simultaneous radiosonde ascents. As we know, radiosondes are capable of delivering data at high quality and resolution, however, not at one specific geographical location. Therefore, the herein presented, high-resolution, lidar data provides insight to the currently concealed potential which the future application of such lidar systems might have. This information is of general interest for insitutional weather services but also for the large eddy simulation community which, up to now, largely relies on radiosonde data for their modeling activities.

Albeit the fact that the presented data helps to increase our general knowledge, solitary information on humidity profiles is not sufficient. Therefore, in order to come towards a comprehensive understanding of the described issues and processes, the introduced humidity measurements are supplemented by measurements of aerosol concentrations, temperature profiles and vertical wind information on at least equally high resolutions.

All presented findings result out of three major field campaigns in which the instruments have been operated in combination with many other, complementary, sensors.

Figure 1: A snapshot of water vapor mixing ratios at a temporal resolution of 10s, showing detailed structures and changes in the PBL and above.

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Use of ACTRIS/Cloudnet products within the EUMETSAT validation facility for Level 2 Cloud products

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The EUMETSAT Central Facility is entrusted to retrieve and disseminate high resolution cloud products (down to a few hundred of meters) based on combined visible to thermal infrared measurements from the new generation satellites such as the Copernicus Sentinel-3 (S3) and Carbon Dioxide Monitoring (CO2M), the Meteosat Third Generation (MTG), and the EUMETSAT Polar System Second Generation (EPS-SG).

EUMETSAT cloud products are validated and continuously quality monitored against independent reference data to ensure: i) state-of-the-art algorithm performance and product quality/accuracy to satisfy user and operational service requirements; ii) stability and continuity/consistency over time (i.e., coping with instrument degradation and swaps, algorithm evolutions, updated calibration results, etc.). Lidar/radar instruments have established themselves as a trustworthy source for the detection of cloud layers and superior to any other validation data source when it comes to estimate the cloud height and the particle microphysical and optical properties. For almost two decades (since 2006), the CloudSat and CALIPSO observations have been the prime reference source for the validation of EUMETSAT cloud products, with focus on vertical structure. EarthCARE will provide the natural continuation to the observations provided by these two instruments, which met their end of life in 2023. However, EarthCARE is a time-limited mission (expected lifetime ~3yrs) and its cloud products will not be available for the commissioning of MTG FCI L2 retrievals. Thus, EUMETSAT will rely on ground-based active measurements from the ACTRIS network for the long-term monitoring (>20yrs) of its cloud products over Europe.

In this contribution we present the use of the cloud products generated by the ACTRIS-Cloudnet processing facility maintained by the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), as envisaged within the Cal/Val infrastructure for the new EUMETSAT missions. These

activities involve the development of dedicated and automated tools to handle the validation of products from geostationary and polar-orbiting satellites, including data download and organization, matchups with the ACTRIS stations and the development of comparison metrics. Furthermore, the different sensitivity of ACTRIS measurements with respect to CALIPSO and CloudSat will require careful investigations to transfer the current experience in the use of A-Train products as a validation reference to the ACTRIS-Cloudnet products.

The overall validation strategy is herewith demonstrated via validation exercises (Figure 1) performed using EUMETSAT current operational cloud products from the Meteosat Second Generation Spinning Enhanced Visible Infra-Red Imager (MSG/SEVIRI) and preliminary products from MTG/FCI.

Figure 1. Example of the daily comparison plot between the EUMETSAT SEVIRI (top-panel) and FCI (bottom-panel) Optimal Cloud Analysis (OCA) products and the ACTRIS/Cloudnet cloud profiling products over Lindenberg station on the 27 June 2023. OCA cloud phase, top and base heights overplotted on the ACTRIS classification profile (symbols and colour code are as per legend).

Superconductor detectors (SNSPDs) for infrared lidar measurements

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Infrared wavelengths are particularly suitable for studying pollutants and greenhouse gases (GHG), e.g., carbon dioxide, which play an important role in global warming and display absorption lines in the IR spectral region. These atmospheric trace gases can be studied by infrared LiDAR systems. However, one of the main challenges is the poor detection efficiency and the significant noise of detectors operating in the IR spectral range. A promising solution to such issues is represented by Superconducting Nanostrip Single Photon Detectors (SNSPDs). These devices offer near unity detection efficiency in the infrared spectral range and less than 1 cps dark count rate, in addition to few nanoseconds dead time and picosecond time resolution (Peng, 2020), (Ejrnaes, 2009).

The ability to detect single photons with high efficiency and low noise, constitutes one of the main benefits of using a SNSPD for infrared LiDAR applications.

Here, we report a comparative analysis of the performances of two SNSPDs and of an APD, using them as detectors in the MALIA LiDAR (Multiwavelength Aerosol Lidar Apparatus) operative at the National Facility of the ACTRIS Research Infrastructure (Pappalardo, 2018), at the University of Naples Federico II. Laser pulses provided by a Nd:YAG system 1064 nm with a power of 2 W and a pulse duration less than 10 ns were sent into the atmosphere at a repetition rate of 1 kHz and the backscattered photons collected by a Newtonian telescope were sent to the spectral selection box and filtered using dichroic filters.

The collected backscatter signal was split into two channels by a beam splitter. The reflected signal was coupled to the APD through a focusing lens, whereas the transmitted one was coupled to a fiber and sent to the SNSPDs.

LiDAR measurements were carried out by registering two separate series of measurements over 30 and 15 minutes comparing, separately, the signals registered by the APD with those of the two SNSPDs. One SNSPD is coupled with a monomodal fiber, and the other with a multimodal fiber. As an example, Figure 1 reports the signals registered by the APD (left) and the SNSPD with a multimodal fiber (right). One can observe that the LiDAR signals of the two detectors evidence the same atmospheric structures. However, it is worth noting that

the level of the SNSPDs signal is lower than that of the APD. This behaviour is due to the photon losses in the signal optical propagation line from LiDAR receiver to the SNSPD. In fact, the collected light is focused on a fiber with a diameter of 600 μm . Then a series of fibers with consecutive smaller diameters are used to couple the light to the multimode 50 μm diameter fiber of the SNSPD. Due to the mismatches between the various core diameters of the fibers, a geometric attenuation factor of almost 3 orders of magnitude is expected, which explains the much lower SNSPD signal. This attenuation problem will be overcome by using an appropriate fiber to couple the light to the SNSPDs in the final setup, and further measurements will be carried out to address the final performances of the SNSPDs for LiDAR applications.

The good agreement of the two profiles reported in Figure 1 confirms the correct operation of SNSPDs and demonstrate that such detectors can provide a feasible route towards LiDAR operation in the infrared.

Figure 1. Comparison between the APD (red) and SNSPD multimode (blue) detectors at 1064 nm

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Airborne Measurements of OH Reactivity over Urban Megacities

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The production of organic peroxy radicals from the reactions of the hydroxy radical (OH) and organic compounds is frequently a rate-limiting step in the formation of ground-level ozone. One of the foci in current air quality research is therefore to quantify all of the reactive trace gases in the atmosphere that can generate these peroxy radicals from the reaction with OH. As a constraint on the sum of these compounds, we developed a custom instrument that can directly measure the total OH reactivity, the inverse of the atmospheric lifetime of OH, at the Forschungszentrum Jülich. This instrument was employed on the AEROMMA measurement campaign, organized by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration in the summer of 2023. The measurement campaign utilized a variety of aircraft and an array of advanced instrumentation to investigate the chemical composition of urban pollution outflows. It is expected that the importance of vehicle emissions is decreasing and that of other emissions, like volatile chemical products, are increasing. OH reactivity was measured over major urban areas, including New York City, Los Angeles, Chicago, and Toronto.

A suite of instrumentation measured the OH reactants, such as inorganics, nitrogen oxides, alkanes/alkenes, aromatics, and biogenic organic compounds. In the presentation, the sum of OH reactivity from these species is compared to the measured reactivity, to explore the closure of reactivity budget.

From the measurement campaign, the relative contributions of different emission sources to the total OH reactivity including sources for VCPs are analyzed.

Figure 1. Example flight over Chicago: airborne OH reactivity measurements overlaid on a map. Map data Google ©2023.

Aerosol optical depth in the UV with Pandora and Cimel

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Aerosol particles influence the radiation budget of the atmosphere and air quality, making them crucial in climate change research and for addressing public health concerns. Especially in the UV range, measurements of aerosols become tricky, as the signal of the incoming solar radiation decreases with decreasing wavelength (Silva 2023).

The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) provides standardized measurements of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) with interferential filters at specific wavelengths measured with a sun photometer of the company Cimel (Holben *et al* 1998). The lowest available wavelength of these measurements is 340 nm. To investigate aerosol behaviour at shorter UV wavelengths, we use data from the Pandora spectrometer. This provides standardized measurements of trace gases within the Pandora Global Network (PGN) (Herman *et al* 2009). For that, the Pandora measures radiance and irradiance data at a high spectral resolution starting at 300 nm in the UV.

These direct sun measurements provide the possibility of calculating Pandora AOD using the Lambert-Beer law, which describes the irradiance V_λ as a function of the wavelength λ as:

$$V_\lambda = V_0 \exp(-m \tau_{\lambda, total}) \quad (1)$$

In this equation V_0 is an instrument specific calibration constant, which represents the hypothetical measurement signal at the top of the atmosphere. The term m represents the air mass factor and $\tau_{\lambda, total}$ represents the total trace gas optical depth, with ozone being the main contributor in the UV range. For this study, we obtain trace gas information from the PGN. V_0 is determined using AOD data from a co-located AERONET sun photometer. We extrapolate the calibration to wavelengths further in the UV, where AERONET data is not available.

To quantify possible uncertainties of the UV AOD product, we consider the factors of measurement uncertainties of ozone, the uncertainty of the calibration constant V_0 , and spectral and spatial straylight. Furthermore, we examine AOD variations for different aerosol types measured in Innsbruck in June 2023 focusing on the 310 nm to 380 nm range. During this month, our observations include AOD measurements during a Sahara dust event and biomass burning aerosols from forest fires.

For the wavelengths where both instruments provide data, we found that the Pandora AOD typically falls within a maximum deviation of 0.015, divided by the air mass, from the AERONET AOD over a one-day period (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Difference of AOD product of Pandora and Cimel photometer at the wavelengths 340, 380, 440 and 500 nm in Innsbruck for 14th of June 2023.

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CAECENET: Automatic and continuous columnar and vertical aerosol properties from photometer and ceilometer measurements

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This study presents CAECENET, a novel system designed to automatically retrieve columnar and vertically resolved aerosol properties. The system employs the GRASP algorithm (Generalized Retrieval of Atmosphere and Surface Properties; Dubovik et al., 2014), utilizing as input aerosol optical depth (AOD) and sky radiance measurements from sun-sky photometers, as well as range-corrected signal (RCS) measurements from ceilometers. The implementation of this approach, known as GRASP_{pac} (Román et al., 2018), is integrated into CAECENET system. This system assimilates AERONET (Aerosol Robotic Network) sun-sky photometer data from the CÆLIS database (Fuertes et al., 2018) and ceilometer data from the ICENET database (Iberian Ceilometer Network; Cazorla et al., 2017). This is achieved in a user-friendly manner, eliminating the need for manual inversion calculations for each observation.

Figure 1. Vertical profiles of volume concentration (A), extinction (B), scattering (C), absorption (D) and backscattering (E) for the 27th of June 2023 at Valladolid. Shadowband represents the uncertainty of the retrieved values.

CAECENET allows for continuous and near real-time monitoring of both vertical and columnar aerosol properties, which is very useful for analysing regional events. The arrangement of measurement stations, for now across the Iberian Peninsula, allows the near-real-time aerosol 3D monitoring. This approach allows for the collection of data regarding the speed of event dissemination, variations in aerosol altitude, potential

impediments or external factors influencing its concentration, and the resulting impacts on aerosol optical properties. This information is valuable for both scientific research on aerosols and for the general public due to its contribution to monitor events that can impact aviation traffic or public health. Figure 1 shows an example of CAECENET's data for the volume concentration, extinction, scattering, absorption and backscattering vertical profiles at Valladolid (Spain), the 27th of June 2023, when a biomass burning aerosol, originated in Canada wildfires, reached the Iberian Peninsula.

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Application in an Antarctic site of a neural network for cloud cover retrieval from all-sky cameras

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Keywords: Cloud cover, All-sky camera, Convolutional neural network, Antarctic, AI, Image identification.

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Cloud cover (CC) is an important weather indicator that represents the fraction of sky by covered all visible clouds according to the World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2017). Cloud cover ranges between 60% to 90% above 60°S into southern latitudes (Warren et al., 2015) and some works show that Antarctic clouds play a big role in the climate system, both directly at south latitudes and indirectly on global scale, highlighting the need for further research on them (Lachlan-Cope, 2010).

This work presents a new model based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) to estimate daytime cloud cover from sky images captured by all-sky cameras; this model has been named as CNN-CC. A total of 49016 daytime sky images, recorded at different Spanish locations (Valladolid, La Palma and Izaña) from two different all-sky camera types, have been manually classified into different CC (in oktas) values by trained researchers and randomly split into a training set and a test set to validate the model. The CC values predicted by the CNN-CC model are compared with the images on the test set, which serve as reference. The predicted CC values closely match the reference values within ± 1 oktas in 99% of the cloud-free and overcast cases. Moreover, this percentage is above 93% for the rest of partially cloudy cases. The mean (MBE) and standard deviation (SD) of the differences between the predicted and the reference CC values are 0.01 oktas and 0.67 oktas, respectively, pointing out a good accuracy but also a precision below 1 okta, which is within the assumed uncertainty.

Once the model is validated, the CC has been calculated for a set of images captured every 5 minutes, from January 2018 to March 2022 at the Antarctic station of Marambio (Argentina). These CC values have been compared against direct field observations of CC measured at this location, which is not used in the training process. As result, the model slightly underestimates the observations with an MBE of -0.3 oktas, while the precision is given by an SD of 1.4 oktas. The monthly and annually cloud cover values have also been calculated. Overcast conditions are the most frequent in Marambio, accounting for 47.5% of all observations throughout the year, rising to 65% in

January, as shown in Figure 1. The annual mean cloud cover value at this location is 5.6 oktas, with a standard deviation of approximately 3.0 oktas. A similar analysis has been performed, separating data by hours, but no significant diurnal cycles have been observed except for some isolated months.

In general, we can conclude that the developed model for the prediction of CC provides realistic results that fits well with independent measurements. As a future prospect, a set of night-time images will be classified to train the model not only for predicting cloud cover during daytime but also during night-time.

Figure 1. Color map of cloud cover (CC) frequency at Marambio for each month and cloud cover value using the cloud cover data retrieved with the sky images.

Adapted from González-Fernández et al., 2023.

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The Lunar Irradiance Model of ESA (LIME)

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Keywords: Moon, satellite, calibration-validation, remote sensing, lunar radiometry

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The Moon is an ideal calibration source for Earth Observation satellites, as it provides a stable source, within the range of the Earth radiometric levels and free from atmospheric effects. However, using the Moon as reference requires the use of a model that can account for the variation of the Moon's disk-integrated irradiance that results from changes in Sun-Earth-Moon geometry.

In this work we present a novel application of ground-based photometer observations from the Aerosols, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS). A new lunar irradiance model, the Lunar Irradiance Model of the European Space Agency (LIME, Toledano et al., 2023) has been developed from ground-based observations acquired using a lunar photometer that is operated at the Izaña Atmospheric Observatory and Teide Peak Observatory (Tenerife, Spain), managed by the State Meteorological Agency of Spain (AEMET). The top-of-atmosphere Moon irradiance was obtained from the application of the Langley plot technique over 5 years, with 590 lunar observations acquired between March 2018 and December 2022 (figure 1). These data cover a Moon phase angle range from -90° to 90° (first to third quarter). The data are traceable to the international system of units thanks to the photometer absolute calibration performed at the National Physical Laboratory. A fitting procedure to the lunar reflectance was made following the equation provided by Kieffer and Stone (2005) for the Robotic Lunar Observatory (ROLO) lunar model.

Figure 1. Top-of-atmosphere lunar irradiance measurements used to derive the LIME model.

Lunar irradiance measurements within the AERONET network, to which ACTRIS contributes with ground-based radiometric observations in the aerosol

remote sensing stations, are routinely performed for the retrieval of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) at night-time, using Cimel 318T Sun/Moon radiometers. The need of top-of-atmosphere irradiance for the AOD retrieval revealed inaccuracy of the existing models about 5%-10%, thus correction schemes had to be developed (Román et al. 2020).

For a lunar model to be useful for satellite calibration/validation purposes, the uncertainty estimation is a key aspect. In LIME, a metrologically and statistically rigorous uncertainty analysis has been made, and a set of comparisons to satellite sensors has been performed to validate the model outputs: PROBA-V, Pleiades, Sentinel 3B as well as to the Global Space-based Inter-Calibration System (GSICS) implementation of the ROLO. The LIME model output has an expanded ($k = 2$) radiometric uncertainty of $\sim 2\%$ at the lunar radiometer wavelengths (440, 500, 675, 870, 1020, 1640 nm), selected with narrow-band interference filters. Interpolated values in the range 400-2500 nm are provided using the reflectance spectrum measured with rock samples from the Apollo missions.

It is planned to provide a software tool (the LIME-Toolbox) for the LIME model to be publicly available for scientific purposes. It is also expected that Moon observations at the high-altitude locations will continue until at least 2024, in order to further constrain the model parameters in subsequent updates, that will be incorporated into the LIME-Toolbox. Further information about the LIME model and related database is available at <https://calvalportal.ceos.org/lime-documents>.

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Harmonized Ultrafine Particle (UFP) Number Measurements in Europe: Achievements and Challenges

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The need to expand the common air quality monitoring networks by including the continuous measurement of particle number (PN) concentration and particle size distributions (PSD) in the sub-micrometer size range was emphasized for the first time in the Global Air Quality Guidelines by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2021. Harmonization of ultrafine particle (UFP) measurements across Europe has been the focus of two technical specifications, namely CEN/TS 16976:2016 for measurements of PN and CEN/TS 17434:2019 for measurements of PSD. In addition, it is a common goal of standardization efforts made within the ACTRIS research infrastructure. While CEN/TS 16976:2016 for Condensation Particle Counter (CPC) is in the final stage of being converted into a full standard (prEN16976:2023), the revision of CEN/TS 17434:2019 is anticipated to begin in 2024.

This study presents achievements made during the revision of CEN/TS 16976 for the calibration of CPCs and will review the shift in their 50% detection efficiency (D_{50}) to 10 nm, from 7 nm previously. The new D_{50} of 10 nm has implications for the use of CPCs as part of a Mobility Particle Size Spectrometer (MPSS, which is often called Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)) according to CEN/TS 17434:2019 and the closure between the total integrated number concentration measured in parallel by a SMPS/MPSS and a standalone CPC.

The quality of this closure does not only depend on the selected lower cut-off size of the CPCs used but also on the general stability of the analyzed aerosol. While the development of CEN/TS 17434:2019 was driven much by rural/urban background monitoring, the new EU-directive for clean air (EU, 2022) also puts some focus on hotspot measurements close to UFP sources (e.g. roads, airports, harbors). Different technological approaches might be needed in such scenarios since both the concentrations and the timescales greatly vary close to a source. In addition, PSDs from such sources tend to show a significant contribution of nucleation mode particles. As a consequence, a lower detection limit of 10 nm might not be sufficient to fully characterize and understand such sources.

We show a full closure of total PN concentration from data gathered with a CEN-SMPS (Model 3938W50-CEN10, TSI Inc., Shoreview, USA) as well as a standalone

CEN-CPC (Model 3750-CEN10, TSI Inc.). The measurement site was next to a major bus depot and a highway, which greatly impacted the aerosol population during the measurement. In addition, we will show data of a side-by-side comparison of a CPC with D_{50} of 7 nm and of 10 nm (Models 3750-CEN7 and 3750-CEN10, TSI Inc.) next to a highway. These data demonstrate that a significant fraction of PN is present in the sub-10 nm size range which has to be considered when characterizing such UFP sources.

Based on these results we strongly recommend to continue working on the overlap between sub-10 nm and super-10 nm efforts at UFP measurement stations. Furthermore, we suggest to consider specific aspects important for close-to-source-measurements when revising CEN/TS 17434 for PSD.

Figure 1: Time series of a side-by-side comparison of CPCs with a 10 nm (green) and a 7 nm (blue) lower cut-off diameter D_{50} next to a highway in the Netherlands.

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From gaseous precursors to aerosol particles: Enhancing the understanding of secondary organic aerosol using state-of-the-art mass spectrometers

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Keywords: Mass spectrometry, secondary organic aerosol, volatile organic compounds.

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ACTRIS has successfully developed a network of monitoring aerosol physical properties and bulk chemical composition as well as trace gases such as NO/NO₂, SO₂, and O₃. However, there remains room to improve volatile organic compound (VOC) monitoring, including their oxidation products at high time resolution. These products can participate in the particle phase, contributing to secondary organic aerosol (SOA). SOA represents a large fraction of atmospheric aerosol.

The detection of VOC oxidation products requires the use of state-of-the-art mass spectrometry (MS), including ionization techniques that are adapted to covering the wide volatility range from VOC precursors to extremely low volatility products. Special aerosol inlets can be utilized to provide molecular information from these products in both gas and particle phases.

ACTRIS-Sweden is developing a mobile exploratory platform equipped with state-of-the-art mass spectrometers for on-line aerosol and trace gas observations. The platform will consist of multiple mass spectrometers; one measuring VOCs, one detecting oxidation products in both gas and particle phases and a third aimed at measuring aerosol bulk chemical composition. The initial goal is to support and supplement the permanent, fixed ACTRIS-Sweden stations. The instruments will provide complementary insight into secondary particle composition and sources, as well as unique information on particle formation pathways from different precursors.

In proof of concept test campaigns we have operated a Vocus proton transfer reaction time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Vocus-PTR-ToF-MS) in parallel to a chemical ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometer coupled to a filter inlet for gases and aerosols (FIGAERO-CIMS) at the Norunda ACTRIS station for two summers (2022 & 2023). These campaigns have illuminated design

strategies for MS implementation and operation in the mobile platform. Moreover, these initial studies will allow for maximum data utility and integration with ACTRIS aerosol in situ and other ACTRIS and co-located ICOS measurements during the mobile measurement platform implementation phase. Herein, we primarily present gas and particle phase measurements from FIGAERO-CIMS as well as other complementary station measurements from the summer campaigns. The challenges and limitations of developing a mobile ACTRIS-compliant platform are discussed.

The MAP-IO program, a pilot experiment to study the feasibility of a permanent shipborn ACTRIS mobile platform

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Due to its remoteness, the Southern Ocean (south of 35°S) is probably one of the less studied oceans in the world. In the context of climate change, the evolution of the ocean CO₂ sink remains uncertain. This uncertainty is particularly strong in the Indian and Southern Ocean due to the lack of seasonal and intra-seasonal observations. From an atmospheric point of view, the lack of atmospheric observation over the Southern Ocean poses several problems as well for numerical weather forecasts (data assimilation), for climate models (long term observation) and for calibration/validation of spaceborne sensors. Recently, the WMO has emphasized this need to address operational and scientific issues.

The MAP-IO (Marion Dufresne Atmospheric Program - Indian Ocean; Tulet et al., submitted) program aims to overcome the lack of observation in this region of the Earth by equipping the Marion Dufresne vessel with a set of 18 in-situ and remote sensing instruments for atmosphere and marine studies.

MAP-IO takes advantage of the regular rotations around the French Austral islands by documenting the atmosphere and the ocean surface states over a wide variability of seas and latitude conditions. These multi-year observations of the Indian and Southern Oceans make it possible to uniquely document the trends, the mechanisms of ocean-atmosphere exchanges and the atmospheric composition on a seasonal and interannual basis.

The MAP-IO program is designed in an observatory scheme with three main objectives: (i) integration into international atmospheric and oceanic networks by providing high quality data on a region devoid of permanent observation, (ii) validating and calibrating space sensors and numerical weather forecasting models, and (iii) monitoring global changes and interannual variability by continuous observation of atmospheric and phytoplankton over the Indian and Southern Oceans. Launched at the beginning of 2021, MAP-IO has already recorded in

July 2023 nearly 700 of measuring days on sea (~ 75 % of the time).

The first climatological studies based on the database show significant intra-seasonal and latitudinal variabilities of greenhouse gases concentration and aerosol optical depth. The total number, the size distribution and the CCN properties of aerosols observed on ship vary considerably upon the air masses sampled (from a hundred to thousand particles per cm⁻³). The phytoplankton community structure has been studied by resolving several size classes and the collected data sets can be considered as one of the most important dataset of surface phytoplankton abundances collected so far in such a short time and in this remote area.

Several innovations have been developed. The development of fast GNSS zenith delay inversion algorithms for integrated water vapor content restitution, integrating the specificities of ship movements. Adaptations to make the CE318T lunar/solar photometer autonomous and adapted to heavy swells and icing. A Mini-SAOZ, successfully tested for the first time on a ship, enabled continuous acquisition of integrated water vapor and ozone columns over the ocean. Test campaigns for onboard instruments, such as the CE370 micro-lidar during the AMARYLLIS-AMAGAS campaign, demonstrated the potential for the permanent deployment of active remote sensing instruments on ships.

MAP-IO was funded by the European Union through the ERDF programme, the University of La Réunion, the SGAR-Réunion, the Région Réunion, the CNRS, IFREMER, and the Flotte Océanographique Française.

Tulet, P., et al. (submitted to ESSD), MAP-IO, an atmospheric and marine observatory program onboard Marion Dufresne over the Southern Ocean.

Characterization of the BTS array spectroradiometer for trace gas and aerosol retrievals

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Keywords: BTS, characterization, calibration, UV, array-spectroradiometer.

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A detailed characterization of the BTS2048-UV-S-WP (further BTS) array spectroradiometer by Gigahertz-Optik GmbH is presented. Building on the characterization of the BTS for total ozone column measurements presented in Zuber *et al* (2018) we extend our focus to include NO₂, SO₂ and aerosol optical depth (AOD) retrievals in the UV range.

The appeal of the BTS lies in its improved optical stray-light correction mechanism compared to other commercially available array spectroradiometers whose performance falter below 310 nm (Egli *et al*, 2016). Gonzalez *et al* (2022) found that in the 305-360 nm region the BTS performance with its default calibration is comparable to that of a double monochromator Brewer spectrophotometer. We want to perform further characterization of the BTS in the laboratory to assess its potential for trace gas retrievals, particularly O₃, SO₂ and NO₂, using the same spectral fitting algorithm as applied within the Pandonia Global Network (PGN).

To evaluate the quality of our absolute calibration, the BTS is placed on a sun tracker on the roof of a university building in Innsbruck. From the acquired direct sun spectra we derive AOD at 340 and 380 nm and compare it to the results of a collocated Cimel sun photometer from The Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET).

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Validating Copernicus trace gas satellite constellation data: State of the art and remaining needs

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Keywords: Satellite validation, FRM, maturity, networks, gap analysis

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The validation means and methods for satellite trace gas products have evolved significantly in the past decade: (1) New ground-based instruments have been developed and networks have expanded both in geographical coverage and in capabilities, (2) traceability to metrological standards and uncertainty characterization of the (Fiducial) Reference Measurements (FRM) has improved considerably (3) rapid provision (<1 week) of FRM through efficient data distribution services is becoming commonplace, (4) the advantage of new advanced comparison methods has been demonstrated, and (5) all of this has facilitated the development of comprehensive, operational, near-real-time validation systems such as the Validation Data Analysis Facility Automated Validation Server (VDAF AVS) of ESA's Atmosphere Mission Performance Cluster (ATM-MPC) for the Sentinel-5 Precursor (S5P) mission (Fig. 1).

On the other hand, several networks experience increased difficulty to fund their activities, station-to-station differences in validation results suggest (poorly understood) intra-network and inter-network inhomogeneity, the network coverage (in terms of probing the full range of the measurand and of the influence quantities impacting the retrieval) is usually not yet complete, timeliness is still poor for several products, comparability between ground-based and satellite measurements requires further methodological advances, and the accuracy and breadth of scope of the latest generation of satellite sounders puts correspondingly tight and difficult-to-meet requirements on the FRM data quality.

In this contribution, we report on the comprehensive maturity assessment performed on the current (European) satellite trace gas validation infrastructure which was carried out as one part of the Horizon 2020 project "Copernicus Cal/Val Solution" (CCVS.eu), which built on earlier work in FP7 and H2020 projects "Quality Assurance for Essential Climate Variables" (QA4ECV) and "Gap Analysis for Integrated Atmospheric ECV Climate Monitoring" (GAIA-CLIM). We detail the state of the art in trace gas validation along the lines described above and discuss the remaining needs,

including an identification of potential actors. This assessment synthesizes lessons learned in the operational validation for ESA's ATM-MPC and Climate Change Initiative (CCI) projects, for EC/ECMWF's Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), for EUMETSAT's Atmospheric Composition Satellite Application Facility (AC SAF), and in various smaller programmes. As such, this contribution is meant to provide the ACTRIS community with a broad "end user perspective" on the essential measurements it provides for satellite validation.

Figure 1. Illustration (at one station) of the fully automated, operational validation of S5P-TROPOMI total ozone columns in the ATM-MPC VDAF-AVS, with comparisons up to a couple of days before the writing of this abstract. TROPOMI data in blue, the Pandora data in red.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101004242 (Project title: "Copernicus Cal/Val Solution").

Lidar observations of aerosol, water vapor and temperature in the boundary layer during pre TEAMx 2022 and Swabian MOSES 2023 and its potential for a quantitative analysis of turbulent mixing at the upper edge of the planetary boundary layer

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Keywords: lidar, profiling, turbulent mixing, aerosol, water vapor.

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Atmospheric transport and mixing under turbulent conditions are still a major source of short-term atmospheric variability and, thus a major source uncertainty in numerical weather prediction on small spatial scales. For a better parametrization a better understanding and an improved quantitative description of the atmospheric dynamics on the timescale of turbulence is required. One approach is the acquisition of the atmospheric state with a high resolution in space and time which was the major motivation in several recent experiments, such as CHEESEHEAD (Butterworth et al, 2021), FESSTVal (Hohenegger et al, 2023) and Swabian MOSES.

With the recent development of powerful and accurate laser transmitters (e.g., Vogelmann et al, 2022), the development of a new generation of lidars capable for boundary layer profiling of water vapor, temperature, and aerosols on the time scale of 10s has become real (Wulfmeyer et al, 2021).

A new developed Raman Lidar (Purple Pulse Lidar Systems), profiling aerosol, water vapor and temperature with a 10 s temporal resolution was applied during the pre-TEAMx-Campaign in Summer 2022 at Innsbruck and during Swabian MOSES in summer 2023. While TEAMx is aiming at the complex atmospheric dynamics in alpine mountainous surroundings, Swabian MOSES is focussed on the development of thunder cells in the region of the black forest. An almost identical system will be implemented as part of the **ACTRIS** National Facility Aerosol Remote Sensing at Garmisch-Partenkirchen.

Table 1. Technical Specifications of the Raman-Lidar

Laser	Innolas DPSS Evo 2, 355mJ, 200Hz, 70mJ, seeded.
Receiver	40cm, 1 x elastic, 2 x rotational Raman, 1 x vibrational Raman, Licel
Vertical range [km]	aerosol: > 10 / 7 km
day / night	water vapor: 2.5 / 7 km
Temperature	3.5 / 10 km

Figure 1. Distribution of aerosol and water vapor at Innsbruck measured during 24h of the pre-TEAMx-Campaign with the Raman-Lidar. The high temporal resolution allows for a detailed examination of the short-term boundary layer dynamics.

We will present first results obtained with the new Lidar System and how the high spatio-temporal resolution supports the examination of turbulent fluxes, mixing and the uptake of aerosol into to the air stream of the free troposphere.

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EarthCARE aerosol products and their validation needs

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Keywords: EarthCARE, ACTRIS, aerosol remote sensing.

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The Earth Cloud Aerosol and Radiation Explorer (EarthCARE) is ready to be launched in May 2024. The joint satellite of the European Space Agency (ESA) and the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) carries four instruments: a cloud-profiling radar (CPR), a high-spectral-resolution lidar (ATLID), a multi-spectral imager (MSI), and a three-view broad-band radiometer (BBR). The instruments will provide synergistic observations of aerosol, clouds, radiation, and their interactions with unprecedented accuracy. One of the objectives of the mission is to obtain closure of measured and calculated top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation fluxes for a 100 km² snapshot view of the atmosphere with an accuracy of 10 W m⁻², which would substantially improve our knowledge of global radiative forcing (Wehr *et al*, 2023).

For aerosol-related studies, profiles and layer-mean values of particle extinction and backscatter coefficients, lidar ratio, and linear depolarization ratio at 355 nm along the track of the satellite are available from ATLID. This information is further used for aerosol typing. The aerosol optical thickness (AOT) at 355 nm from ATLID is complemented by the AOT at 670 nm (over land and ocean) and 865 nm (over ocean) derived across a 150-km wide swath from MSI observations, i.e., columnar Ångström exponents along track and across-track scene information are available as well.

The EarthCARE products are calculated in near real-time (NRT) by using a sophisticated data production chain (Eisinger *et al*, 2023). Level 1 (L1) data contain the calibrated, geolocated, and fully corrected signals measured by each instrument. In the case of ATLID, L1 data consist of the attenuated co-polar Mie and Rayleigh signals and the total cross-polar backscatter signal at a vertical resolution of about 100 m and a horizontal resolution of 285 m. MSI L1 data used for the AOT retrieval are the normalized TOA radiances at the four visible to shortwave-infrared bands (670, 865, 1650, and 2200 nm) available with a horizontal resolution of 500 m.

Level 2 (L2) processing starts with a feature-mask algorithm for ATLID (van Zadelhoff *et al*, 2023) and a cloud-mask algorithm for MSI (Hünnerbein *et al*, 2023), followed by the ATLID profile (Donovan *et al*, 2023), ATLID layer (Wandinger *et al*, 2023b), and MSI AOT (Docter *et al*, 2023) product generation. Furthermore, a synergistic ATLID-MSI aerosol column product is provided, which transfers along-track ATLID aerosol

information to the MSI swath (Haarig *et al*, 2023). Aerosol classification is based on the Hybrid End-to-End Aerosol Classification (HETEAC) model in all EarthCARE algorithms (Wandinger *et al*, 2023a; Floutsi *et al*, 2023).

A careful validation of the L1 and L2 products is required to reach the ambitious scientific goals of the EarthCARE mission. ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing facilities are optimally conditioned for this purpose. The standard equipment comprising a high-power Raman polarization lidar and a sun/sky photometer, together with the rigorous quality assurance concept of ACTRIS, allows for a detailed validation of all EarthCARE aerosol products. Workflows for observation, data processing, and NRT data provision have already been implemented thanks to a pilot activity organized in the framework of the ATMO-ACCESS project. Furthermore, L1 tools for the conversion between ground-based and space-based observation geometries have been developed by the EarthCARE science team.

In the presentation, we will give an overview of the status of EarthCARE aerosol product development and validation preparation at the time of the EarthCARE launch.

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Versatile and advanced mass spectrometers for improved molecular-level characterization of atmospheric organics

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Keywords: Mass Spectrometry, Organic, Aerosol.

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The wide range of organic species in the atmosphere reflects the many sources and processes from which they originate. Gas phase organics in the atmosphere can be directly emitted or formed by oxidation in the atmosphere. Particle phase organics can be primary or secondary, arising from the condensation of oxidized gas phase compounds or condensed phase chemistry. While real time chemical ionization mass spectrometric methods have greatly improved our capability to characterize individual organic molecules in the atmosphere, they have been limited by the chemical selectivity of the reagent ions and the fact that molecular formulas obtained from mass spectrometry do not differentiate between structural isomers. In this work new mass spectrometers designed to address these limitations are described.

reagent ions, including those that form positive and negative ions. The B-TOF was deployed in a field campaign in Antarctica, during the AEROMMA campaign in New York City, and in several laboratory measurement intensives. The near-simultaneous use of multiple chemical ionization schemes enables measurements of a wide range of gas phase organic species including precursors, photochemical products, organic nitrates, and reduced nitrogen species. Combining the B-TOF with a particle inlet further extends the power of these measurements to organics in the condensed phase.

The need for identifying and separating structural isomers within a complex mix of organic species is addressed by coupling a sensitive gas chromatograph (GC) with chemical ionization such as proton transfer reaction (PTR). Switching between chemical ionization with and without GC pre-separation enables improved identification and quantification of volatile organic species observed in chemical ionization mass spectra. The utility of this technique is demonstrated using laboratory and field measurements of hazardous air pollutants, volatile chemical products and other ozone and secondary organic aerosol precursors.

Figure 1. Schematic of fast-switching bipolar time-of-flight mass spectrometer (B-TOF)

First, the need to simultaneously detect a broader range of species with a single instrument is addressed by utilizing a fast-switching bipolar time-of-flight mass spectrometer (B-TOF) together with a chemical ionization inlet that enables switching between multiple

Spectral lines for identifying chemical components of mineral dust via Raman Lidar

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Keywords: Chemical composition, Raman spectroscopy, Raman Lidar.

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Understanding the chemical composition of atmospheric dust is crucial for assessing their interactions with radiation, clouds, and trace gases in the atmosphere and consequently their effects on air quality and the regional climate. At present, the chemical characterization of atmospheric dust relies on laboratory experiments. While Lidar can estimate the aerosol types, microphysical properties, and their vertical distribution but fails to achieve the spectral specificity to infer the chemical composition of atmospheric dust. In this work, we propose a two-step process for remotely determining the chemical composition of atmospheric dust. In the first step of the work, we investigated the Raman spectra of various components of mineral dust, such as corundum, quartz, carbonates, sulphates, etc., and their mixtures under controlled **laboratory** measurements. In the course of this process, we have pinpointed specific spectral lines determined by vibrational frequencies that can function as distinctive markers for a particular dust composition. These identified spectral markers pave the way for the identification of such dust compositions in atmospheric pollution, constituting a crucial aspect of the subsequent stages of our work. The dust compositions and their corresponding spectral signatures investigated in this study are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Dust compositions and their spectral signatures

Chemical composition	Raman shift (cm ⁻¹)	Vibrational modes
Quartz	462-464	Si-O stretching
Corundum	417.3	Al-O-Al stretch
Carbonate	1080-1100	C-O stretching
Calcite	280.3	External mode
Aragonite	204	External mode
Dolomite	302	External mode
Magnesite	330.2	External mode
Sulphate	1000	S-O stretching
Barite	458	Bending (ν_4)
Anhydrite	496.7	Bending (ν_2)
Apatite	970.3	Stretching (ν_1)
Olivine	825.4, 859.3	Si-O stretching
Garnet	916.2, 347.4	ν_1 , Ext mode
Zircon	992.5, 347.4	ν_1 , Ext mode
Feldspar	511	Si-O-Si stretch
Kaolinite	635	Al-O-Si vibration

One noteworthy finding from this research is the presence of luminescence features alongside Raman lines in one of the samples. This adds to the spectral signature database and holds the potential for utilization in Lidar remote sensing applications for chemical mapping. The subsequent phase of our research integrates Lidar technology with optical spectroscopy to form spectroscopic Lidar. This approach allows for the collection of both elastic and inelastic scattered light, enabling the exploration of the chemical composition of dust particles by leveraging spectral signatures identified during laboratory investigations. The overall approach of this work is depicted as a flow chart in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the approach to determine the chemical composition of atmospheric dust.

In conclusion, this study marks a noteworthy progression in the chemical characterization of atmospheric dust, achieved through an innovative remote sensing technique. The primary objective of this methodology is to enhance the detection and analysis of dust particles remotely. Moving into the next phase of our research, where Lidar measurements obtained through this novel approach will be analyzed, we anticipate a more nuanced understanding of atmospheric dust composition. This refined knowledge holds promise for broader applications in environmental and health-related considerations.

**THEME 5 - ATMOSPHERE,
POLLUTION AND HEALTH,
INCLUDING URBAN STUDIES**

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Tuukka Petäjä and Stephane Sauvage

Ozone vertical profiles in the Paris city center during summer 2022 ACROSS campaign.

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Keywords: ozone, lidar, polluted boundary layer.

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Understanding the ozone diurnal cycle at the surface in a Western European city like Paris is still a major issue during summer pollution episodes. Differential absorption lidar (DIAL) O₃ profiles were measured during the 2022 ACROSS summer campaign using the ALTO instrument (Klein et al., 2018). Ozone time evolution from early morning to sunset has been monitored on 26 days from June 13 to July 19, 2022 in order to study the mixing of the nocturnal residual layer with the convective boundary layer during the day.

Such DIAL measurements have been analysed in conjunction with surface O₃ concentrations of the AIRPARIF air quality network, namely the Paris 13 ground station and the Eiffel tower top (320m ASL), of the QUALAIR station at the top of the Sorbonne Université tower (120 m ASL) and with two daily IAGOS aircraft vertical profiles during take off and landing from CDG Paris Airport.

Three measurement periods have been identified when surface O₃ concentrations exceeded 100 µg/m³: case (A) from June 14 to 18 with the largest ozone concentrations recorded during the ACROSS campaign in a well mixed PBL and with advection of a dust layer aloft of the Paris PBL, case (B) with persistent positive vertical O₃ gradient during the day, case (C) corresponding to the O₃ during the onset of a heat wave event in the Paris area.

Figure 1. Surface O₃ time evolution at Paris 13 ground station and at the top of two towers, red arrows show the days analyzed with DIAL observations

Two examples of the daily temporal evolution of the ozone profile measured by DIAL are shown in Fig.2 (left-hand column) with in-situ observations (coloured pixel with black cross) at the surface and top of the 2 towers. The regional context of ozone distribution was described using the CAMS model ensemble mean to track the position of the ozone plume around Paris and its recirculation around the city center. The vertical ozone profile from the CAMS simulation (in red) is shown in Fig.2 (right-hand column) for June 16 and 17 during Case A, with the lidar profiles in blue and the IAGOS flight in green.

Fig.2: (left) DIAL and in situ (pixel with black cross) O₃ daily time evolution in µg/m³ on June 16 and 17 (right) comparison of O₃ profiles (red) from CAMS simulations for 5 levels at 6UT (□), 12UT (○) and 18UT (▽) with DIAL (blue) and IAGOS (green) O₃ profiles.

Analysis of the three cases show the respective role of regional transport and urban layer dynamical development.

This work was supported by OSU Ecce Terra (<https://www.sorbonne-universite.fr/plateformes-techniques/plateforme-qualair>) and the ACROSS LEFE-INSU project (<https://across.aeris-data.fr/>)

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Operational aerosol monitoring through remote sensing in support to air quality networks

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Keywords: aerosol, air quality, remote sensing

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Air Quality Monitoring Networks (AQMNs) in Europe are progressively extending their measurement capabilities for the in situ characterization of aerosol particles physical and chemical properties, but generally lack information along the vertical dimension, which is conversely essential for a comprehensive understanding of surface-level pollution. This vertical perspective can be provided by Automated Lidar-Ceilometers (ALC), remote sensing instruments able to operate unattended 24/7, profiling the aerosol load in the troposphere.

The ALC ability to disclose the particulate matter vertical stratification becomes particularly useful when evaluating the atmospheric dispersion capability of locally emitted particles, or when dealing with potential non-local sources of pollutants, such as those transported over medium to long distances (e.g., fires or desert dust plumes). Recently available polarization-sensitive ALC systems (PLC) are also enhancing the ability to discriminate aerosol types.

In Europe, most Member States run extended networks of ALC/PLC systems, and are contributing to the EUMETNET initiative E-Profile (<https://e-profile.eu/>). The ACTRIS community (www.actris.eu) is also progressively employing ALCs.

In Italy, the national ALC network (ALICENET, www.alice-net.eu) currently includes 20 systems operating from north to south along the peninsula, covering, among others, several urban areas (as Milan, Genova, Torino, Rome, Messina, Catania). The network, coordinated by CNR-ISAC, is a joint effort with several Italian EPAs and Research Institutions. The data processing chain is developed, maintained and centralized at CNR-ISAC, allowing homogeneous quantitative retrievals of aerosol products (e.g., Dionisi *et al*, 2018; Bellini *et al*, 2024). These include aerosol optical and physical properties (e.g. particulate matter mass concentration profiles) and automatic identification of local and advected aerosol layers, these being of particular interest for discounting transboundary contributions in the framework of the EC Air Quality Directive.

In the framework of the ongoing H2020 RI-URBANS project, aimed at the implementation of new service tools to monitor AQ in European cities,

the ALICENET retrievals are being validated and tested over Italian and other pilot EU urban sites to evaluate the possibility to upscale the existing ALC data processing tools. Figure 1 shows an example of the application of the ALICENET PM retrieval based on ALC data collected in Paris (France, 11-19 June 2022). Figure 1 shows local aerosol within the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) and elevated desert dust plumes descending and entraining into it. On June 18, this leads to a marked increase in surface PM10 concentrations.

Figure 1. Vertical profiles of depolarisation (top) and PM (centre) collected in Paris by PLC and ALC on 11-19 July 2022. The bottom panel shows the PM10 as estimated by the ALC (lowermost level) and measured at the surface (Airparif AQMN data).

The presentation will describe current capabilities, advantages, limits and potential of the use of ALC/PLC systems as benefit to AQMNs.

This work received support by the EC H2020 Project RI-URBANS (GA N. 101036245). We also acknowledge the Italian partners collaborating to ALICENET, ACTRIS, ATMO-ACCESS, the PROBE Cost Action, Vaisala, QUALAIR-SU, and the PANAME initiative.

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A hybrid approach for estimation of PM_{2.5} concentrations in an urban neighbourhood using low-cost sensors and machine learning algorithms

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Keywords: Low-cost sensors, PM_{2.5}, Random forests

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PM (Particulate Matter) air pollution has a considerable negative influence on the human cardiovascular and pulmonary systems. According to the European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2020), an estimated 417,000 premature deaths in Europe occurred in 2018 as a result of chronic exposure to PM_{2.5} (PM < 2.5 µm in diameter).

Various types of models are employed to predict PM levels. Some are based on atmospheric processes and emissions, e.g., Chemical Transport Models (CTMs) or Lagrangian particle dispersion models. Others use a statistical approach based on meteorological variables and emission proxies. Among the latter, Machine Learning (ML) tools show a better performance compared to linear models due to the highly non-linear response of atmospheric species to environmental conditions and emissions. Moreover, at very fine temporal and spatial scales, ML algorithms, particularly tree-based models, exhibit a better prediction accuracy compared to CTMs or statistical models.

Our research aims to provide a novel methodology to predict PM_{2.5} levels at fine spatial and temporal scales based on ML tools. The overarching goal is to demonstrate that this methodology can estimate missing PM_{2.5} measurements in urban areas where no direct observations are available. To this goal a hybrid dataset was prepared from inputs of an intensive aerosol campaign (15th April - 20th June, 2023) that was carried out in the Selly Oak neighbourhood of Birmingham, UK, with a focus on a 1×1 km² block housing about 10,000 university students. 4 low-cost Optical Particle Counters (OPC-N3, Alphasense, UK) measuring particle number size distribution (PNSD) in 24 bins from 0.35 – 40 µm, as well as PM₁, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ mass concentrations, were installed at four different fixed locations in the study area. 4 additional OPC-N3 devices were used for aerosol mapping using a mobile backpack-based arrangement. Local businesses and schools helped to collect data from the static sensors while university students helped collect data from the mobile sensors.

All sensors were then calibrated by collocating with the research grade instruments at the Birmingham Air Quality Supersite (BAQS) both before and after the campaign, for approximately 4 days each.

To enable a fine-grained analysis of the distribution of PM_{2.5} along different sections of the road, the network was divided into 30-meter segments and the centroid was computed for each segment. Other spatially resolved proxy variables of atmospheric emissions were assigned to each centroid: the population data, the average traffic count by vehicle, the rank of the road, the average frequency distribution of vehicle speed with a 2-hour time resolution across the week. Finally, the hybrid dataset included meteorological parameters from the Birmingham Air Quality Supersite (BAQS) (wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, atmospheric temperature) and aerosol properties from reference instruments at BAQS.

Three different calibration approaches were used: 1) Standard Random Forest Regression (RF) with an 80-20 train-test split to predict PM_{2.5} levels based on the provided input features ($R^2 = 0.85$, MAE = 1.60 µg m⁻³). 2) Sensor Transferability Evaluation: Calibrating the RF on a specific OPC unit and evaluating its performance on an independent OPC (best performance $R^2 = 0.65$, MAE = 2.76 µg m⁻³). This approach assesses the model's generalization across different sensors. 3) Road Transferability Evaluation: Calibrating the model on one road and evaluating its performance on a different new road ($R^2 = 0.71$, MAE = 2.46 µg m⁻³). This approach explores the model's ability to generalize across different road types.

This methodology has a great potential for enhancing spatial resolution beyond the regulatory monitoring infrastructure, refining air quality predictions and improving exposure assessments, essential for investigating health impacts.

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Health Risk of the Tajogaite volcanic eruption in La Palma: disentangling urban and natural contributions from long term air quality monitoring network

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Keywords: air pollution; desert dust outbreak; health impact assessment, chronic exposure

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Volcanic eruptions produce a vast amount of fine particulate matter and gases (ie. SO₂), degrading air quality locally and over wide areas. The quality of the air we breathe is a major public health concern, as demonstrated by the 3 million deaths per year caused by fine particle pollution worldwide¹. The continuous eruption of the Tajogaite volcano from September to December 2021 in the Island of La Palma, Canary Islands archipelago (Spain), raised the question of the exposure of the local population potentially affected by this activity. However, exposure to volcanic emissions rarely occurs in clean atmospheres, bringing concerns about co-exposures of volcanic emissions and existing air pollution, particularly in urban areas like the ones located on La Palma Island. The eruption directly releases airborne particulate matter and gas, and indirectly due to the lava flows vaporizing seawater when entering the sea, and burning vegetation, crops, asphalt and buildings (production of organic compounds). These volcanic emissions are complex cocktails rich in various compounds potentially toxic for humans. The *La Palma Health Impact Project* was designed to assess the health effect of the Tajogaite activity on local population through a holistic approach combining air quality monitoring data, physico-chemical analysis of gases and ashes (atmospheric and deposited), toxicological, epidemiological and psycho-social risk studies.

Here, we have carried out a Health Assessment Impact (HIA) for PM through a Relative Risk assessment following Wheida et al. (2018) and Muller et al. (2021). For that purpose, we went through a spatial and temporal analysis of the long-term air quality data over one decade to characterize the regional air quality conditions before, during and after the eruption event. Atmospheric data include PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO_x, ozone and CO, as well as meteorological data to support interpretation.

Our study first reveals the poor air quality of La Palma urban areas with frequent exceedances of the WHO guidelines, usually associated to Saharan Dust Outbreaks for PM₁₀. Figure 1 reports the time series of PM₁₀ collected during the eruption and the two months following the eruption. During the eruption, the PM₁₀ atmospheric loadings (up to 1750 µg.m⁻³) on the western part are clearly affected by the volcanic plume compared to the eastern part even the temporal pattern. However, during the two Saharan dust outbreaks of January and February 2022, the PM₁₀ show a similar temporal

pattern at all stations with atmospheric levels as significant or even higher (Eastern part) than the ones observed during the eruption. This multi-source feature is also confirmed by the physico-chemical analysis of the volcanic ashes, obtained by scanning electron microscope, as well as the presence of persisting biomass burning Volatile Organic Compound markers close to burned forest trees.

Given the multi-source nature of the volcanic environment, we defined three scenarii to implement the HIA (Global, Urban and Volcanic). We isolated the dust outbreak events impacting the island over the last decade by combining air quality statistical criteria, backward air mass trajectory analysis and satellite images (MODIS and aerosol index OMI/OMPS). More than 80 Dust Outbreak Events have been identified over the last decade. We estimated the health risk attributed to volcanic emissions through a side-by-side comparison of the different scenarii. The Volcanic Emissions from the Tajogaite is responsible of an excess of 2 premature deaths per year on average (+4 deaths for 100 000 inhbt). The uncertainties of the HIA approach will be discussed and put in perspectives with the entire project.

Figure 1: Time series of PM₁₀ during the eruption (September to December 2021) and two months after during a Saharan Dust Outbreak from both western and eastern stations (yellow shaded area).

This work is supported by the I-site CAP2025 of University of Clermont Auvergne and the CIR4 Research International Centre on Natural Disasters.

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Long-term measurements of greenhouse and reactive gases, and aerosols, at Saclay/SIRTA observatory in the Ile de France Region as part of ICOS and ACTRIS

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Keywords: CO₂, Pollutants, Atmosphere.

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Today, around 7 million deaths a year worldwide are linked to air pollution. Moreover, urban planning projections show that by 2050, there will be 2 billion more people in cities, further increasing the contribution of cities to rising CO₂ emissions. In addition, this could lead to health problems linked to deteriorating air quality.

Our study focuses on the city of Paris and the Ile de France region, where the main pollutant and CO₂ emission sectors are road traffic and the residential sector. (AirParif, 2018). Depending on the emission sector, there is co-emission between pollutants and greenhouse gases (GHG) which can be used to link atmospheric observations of those components to a particular sector. This so-called multi-component atmospheric approach can therefore complement the information provided by sectorial inventories. This study uses data measured on the Saclay peri-urban site to analyze long-term time series of CO₂ and pollutants with meteorological conditions and surface emissions.

At Saclay, the ACTRIS SIRTA station measures reactive gases, and aerosol while the ICOS tall tower measures greenhouse gases. The two stations are not co-located but are only 2 km apart. The compounds chosen for this study are CO₂, CO, CH₄, from the ICOS tower, and NO_x, O₃, and black carbon (BC) from the SIRTA site. The BC has been separated into wood burning (BC_{wb}) and fossil fuel (BC_{ff}) contributions (Petit, 2015). The data from the two stations cover more than ten years of measurements for all the compounds mentioned. Since Saclay is located about 20km from southwest Paris, it was necessary to distinguish between two geographical sectors. An urban sector with the main contribution from Paris and a rural sector for comparison with concentrations close to background levels. The two sectors account for more than 44% of total data (Figure 1).

The diurnal cycles of the studied compounds show similar patterns in the urban and rural sectors but with very contrasted amplitudes. The NO₂, BC_{ff}, and CO cycles in the urban sector are strongly driven by the traffic with morning and evening peaks corresponding to the rush hours (Figure 2). On the other hand, BC_{wb} diurnal cycle peaks mainly in the evening as expected with the timing of the residential heating, and contrary to other species the amplitudes of the maximum are higher in the rural sector (Figure 2). This can be explained by the larger use

of wood burning in the rural areas, whereas it is strictly regulated in Paris.

The diurnal cycle of CO₂ peaks in the morning mainly due to photosynthesis, but a share comes from emissions from transport or the tertiary sector (Figure 2). Species ratios, such as CO/CO₂ and NO₂/CO₂, are calculated for further study and comparison with emission inventories.

The study will also include analysis of seasonal cycles and long-term trends for the two geographical sectors.

Figure 1. Wind rose of Saclay data

Figure 2. Normalised diurnal cycle for NO₂, CO, BC_{ff}, BC_{wb} and CO₂ in the urban sector

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SwissPollen: Real-time monitoring of bioaerosols across Switzerland

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Between 20-30% of the European population suffers from pollen and fungal spore allergies, resulting in direct and indirect costs ranging from €50-150 billion per year (Zuberbier *et al*, 2014). For decades, pollen and fungal spores have been monitored using manual methods with counting being done by hand under the microscope and results reported as daily average values from 3-9 days after the measurement.

New technologies developed over the past years are revolutionising the field of pollen and fungal spore monitoring. Combining artificial intelligence with advanced measurement methods, several devices are now available on the market that provide real-time observations of pollen as well as the potential to detect and identify a range of other airborne particles, including fungal spores and other aerosol larger than ~5 microns.

The SwissPollen monitoring network has been using one such automatic device since the beginning of 2020, reaching operational level for a number of pollen taxa in 2023. This instrument, the Swisens Poleno, takes holographic images as well as fluorescence spectra and lifetimes of individual airborne particles in real-time. Using deep learning algorithms, particles can be identified down to the species level (Figure 2), which is critical in particular in the case of allergenic pollen and fungal spores. To date, only the holographic images have been used but recent developments are proving that the inclusion of fluorescence measurements significantly improves particle identification.

Figure 2. Left: in-flight detection of single particles using digital holography and fluorescence, and Right: illustration of the deep learning algorithm applied to the holographic images to identify particles in the Swisens Poleno instrument.

The SwissPollen network, operated by MeteoSwiss, comprises 15 monitoring stations and since the beginning of 2023 provides hourly information in real-time through its website and smartphone app (figure 2). Furthermore, the real-time observations are integrated into the COSMO-ART model to provide forecasts to end-users (Adamov and Pauling, 2023). The Swiss network is the first national network worldwide to provide such information – both real-time measurements and forecasts based upon them.

Figure 2. Example of data provided in real-time to the public through the MeteoSwiss website: hourly Alder concentrations at the Basel measurement site. The strong peak towards the end of the time series, related to the passage of a cold front, would not have been detectable with the daily mean data available from manual monitors.

There is considerable potential to identify a wide range of other particles using the technology run as part of the SwissPollen network. Erb *et al* (2023) showed that *Alternaria sp.* fungal spores, which are an important plant pathogen in agriculture, could be identified while iberulites have also been identified during Saharan dust events over Switzerland. Further research is ongoing to establish whether other large particles such as microplastics can be identified.

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Atmospheric dynamics on new particle formation (NPF) in Lille

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Lampilahti et al., (2021, 2020) have shown the impact of local vertical dynamics such as the effect of the boundary layer dynamics and roll vortices. Over ATOLL (Atmospheric Observation at LILLE), results from Crumeyrolle et al. (2023) suggested a possible effect of atmospheric dynamics on NPF event occurrence and evolution. To confirm this result, an UltraSonic Anemometer (USA) has been installed in the close vicinity of a SMPS and a CPC in order to calculate aerosol fluxes and study the impact of the atmospheric turbulence using Eddy covariance.

Figure 1 highlights a study case (22/08/2023) showing the influence of turbulence on the onset of the NPF and on the Particle Number Size Distribution (PNSD) evolution. During this study case, two NPF events have been detected starting at 10:45 and 19:35. These events have been disrupted by the dynamics of the atmosphere, leading to shrink effects. The first shrink effect occurred after a short period (around 1h) corresponding to the inclusion, at 12:00, of a Northerly air mass conducting to high negative particle flux (figure 1.b) and a decrease of the heat flux (not shown here). However, this shrink effect is well observed, between 13:00 and 18:00, which is related to the convergence period of the Northerly and the South-westerly front, associated with relatively high TKE values of this day (figures 1c). This front can contribute to a more rapid dispersion of atmospheric precursors and can reduce the concentration of precursors in a single location, thus limiting opportunities for nucleation and particle growth and can reduce their residence time over the site. A shorter residence time means that the chemical reactions necessary for particle

formation have less time to occur. The second NPF event (between 19:35-23:00) is probably influenced by the NorthWesterly Nocturnal Low Level Jet (NLLJ), detected by a relative increase of the TKE, which can transport secondary particles freshly formed, during the day, to the ATOLL site. At the end of the LLJ period, the wind direction changed and the shrink effect occurred again.

Figure 1. Temporal evolutions of PNSD (a, from 10nm to 800nm), Particle flux (b), TKE (c) and vertical wind speed(d).

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Aerosol spectral complex refractive index and single scattering albedo in the Paris urban area and its suburban and forested surroundings during the ACROSS field campaign: variability and constraint for direct radiative effect estimation in regional models

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Keywords: Complex refractive index, urban, rural, aerosol

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The complex refractive index (CRI) and single scattering albedo (SSA) are key parameters driving aerosol spectral optical properties and direct radiative effects (DRE). Their value and spectral variation under different influences, such as anthropogenic- and biogenic-dominated environments and anthropogenic-biogenic mixing situations, remain not fully understood. As a consequence, oversimplified representations of aerosol optical properties are generally used in climate models. The CRI and SSA retrievals represent therefore useful tools to validate and constraint the model configurations.

Field observations from the ACROSS campaign (Cantrell and Michoud, 2022), performed in June-July 2022 in the Ile de France region, are used in this study to deepen the knowledge of aerosol optical properties, aiming to improve the aerosol representation in the CHIMERE model and provide the best constraint for DRE simulations. Measurements obtained at the Paris city center (PRG), at the SIRTa observatory and at the Rambouillet rural forest (RambForest) sites during ACROSS are considered, in order to explore the CRI variability from anthropogenic- to biogenic-dominated environments, including anthropogenic-biogenic mixing situations.

The CRI retrievals at seven different wavelengths, performed by combining the Mie theory with optical and size distribution measurements, as well as the SSA data, are representative of different atmospheric conditions, aerosol loadings as well as type and chemical compositions. In fact, the June-July 2022 period was characterized by highly diversified weather conditions: 1) two strong heatwaves, promoting SOA build-up and favoring the export of the Paris pollution plume towards the forest site; 2) Saharan dust events transported from the upper atmosphere to the ground; 3) biomass burning episode; 4) periods with reduced anthropogenic influence.

The ACROSS CRI and SSA averages ($\pm\sigma$) at 520 nm show values of $1.41(\pm 0.06)$ - $0.037(\pm 0.020)$ i, $0.73(\pm 0.10)$;

$1.52(\pm 0.07)$ - $0.038(\pm 0.017)$ j, $0.80 (\pm 0.08)$; and $1.51(\pm 0.05)$ - $0.025(\pm 0.07)$, $0.86(\pm 0.05)$ at the PRG, SIRTa and RambForest sites, respectively, over the whole period, showing an urban-to-rural gradient. The CRI and SSA retrievals under these different conditions and their link to meteorology and particle chemical composition are investigated.

Hence, the CRI and SSA presented here constitutes unique datasets from which models can benefit to validate and constrain simulations and DRE estimations, under both urban and biogenic emission influences. These data are used to initialize and perform sensitivity studies on the aerosol DRE, using the WRF-CHIMERE coupled model and the Rapid Radiative Transfer Model for GCMs (RRTMG).

This work has been supported by the ACROSS and the RI-URBANS projects. The ACROSS project has received funding from the French National Research Agency (ANR) under the investment program integrated into France 2030, with the reference ANR-17-MPGA-0002, and it was supported by the French National program LEFE (Les Enveloppes Fluides et l'Environnement) of the CNRS/INSU (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique/Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers). The RI-URBANS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101036245. PEGASUS is a national facility of the CNRS-INSU as part of the French ACTRIS research infrastructure. IMT Nord Europe's group has been supported by Labex CaPPA (ANR-11-LABX-0005-01). L. N. Hawkins and D. O. De Haan were supported by NSF-IRES 1825094.

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Source Identification and Temporal Variation of Nitrogenous Gases in Urban (Abidjan, Korhogo) and Rural (Lamto) Environments of Côte d'Ivoire.

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As part of INDAAF and PASMU projects, this study aims to characterise nitrogen gas pollution in urban (Abidjan, Korhogo) and rural (Lamto) areas of Côte d'Ivoire (Kassamba-Diaby et al (2023)). This work focused on identifying pollution sources and monitoring monthly and seasonal variations in concentrations.

Gaseous nitrogen pollutants (NO_2 , NH_3 , and HNO_3) were monthly sampled from April 2018 to December 2020 using INDAAF gas passive samplers (Bahino, 2018). Ground-based data were compared with satellite data: CrIS Fast Physical Retrieval (CFPR)- NH_3 and Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI)- NO_2 , with a resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Pearson correlation coefficients allowed the identification of gaseous compound sources.

Source identification reveals that nitric acid (HNO_3) is linked to photochemical pollution across all sites. In urban areas such as Abidjan and Korhogo, NO_2 is primarily associated with vehicular traffic, while NH_3 stems from household fire combustion. In the rural Lamto site, both NO_2 and NH_3 are tied to biomass burning sources.

Ground-based monthly mean concentrations of NO_2 range from 2.6 to 25.5 ppb in Abidjan, 0.3 to 1.5 ppb in Lamto, and 0.6 to 29.3 ppb in Korhogo. For NH_3 , monthly means range from 1.1 to 12 ppb in Abidjan, 1.2 to 7.2 ppb in Lamto, and 1.7 to 7.6 ppb in Korhogo. HNO_3 monthly concentrations vary from 0.6 to 2.7 ppb in Abidjan, 0.1 to 0.6 ppb in Lamto, and 0.6 to 29.3 ppb in Korhogo (Figure 1).

Results emphasise the prevalence of nitrogenous gas concentrations in urban areas compared to the rural area of Lamto. Furthermore, the analysis highlights the significance of NH_3 gas sources in Lamto, whereas NO_2 is predominant in urban areas. Seasonal variabilities of the three nitrogenous gases revealed that periods of high concentration occur during dry season periods with low rainfall at all sites. The annual mean ground-based concentrations of NO_2 are 10.8 ppb, 0.7 ppb, and 3.8 ppb in Abidjan, Lamto, and Korhogo, respectively. Considering the air quality thresholds set by the World Health Organization (WHO), results showed that the city of Abidjan surpasses the threshold, particularly during the dry season. Consequently, these elevated levels of air pollution pose a risk to human health.

Figure 1: Monthly and seasonal variation of nitrogenous gases concentration (NO_2 , NH_3 , HNO_3)

Satellite data's analysis reveals that the highest monthly vertical column densities (VCDs) of NH_3 and NO_2 are linked to the driest months and peak burnt surface fractions, particularly in Lamto's rural area. Lamto's monthly averages VCDs range from 2.42×10^{16} to 4.53×10^{17} molecules of NH_3 per square centimetre, from 1.32 to 12.91×10^{15} molecules of NO_2 per square centimetre, with burnt surface percentages from 0.75% to 35.91%. The findings strongly suggest that biomass burning is the primary source of elevated nitrogen compounds during the dry season in Lamto.

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Unveiling the urban complexity: integrating aerosol chemistry, oxidative potential, and epidemiological insights through long-term observations

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Urban areas act as dynamic hubs, where aerosol particles play a pivotal role in shaping air quality and public health outcomes. Integrating long-term detailed observations of particle matter, both for their detailed chemistry and oxidative potential, brings unique challenges in understanding the complex interactions among emission sources and health impacts.

Les Frenes station is situated in an urban background area in Grenoble, where a long-term partnership between the regional air quality monitoring network, the national reference laboratory and research institutions is driven by a shared commitment to observe and understand the complex dynamics of air quality in this urban area and its impacts on the population. About 15 years of detailed observations of air quality data are nowadays available for this site. Aerosol chemistry and oxidative potential characterization give access to the emission sources and the atmospheric reactivity underlying health-relevant impacts. These long-term observations, associated with other specific studies, also reveal pollutant trends, offering an insight into how these atmospheric constituents and their emission sources evolve over time and space. It is also further interconnected with epidemiological insights, establishing links between air pollution and public health outcomes.

This work presents the main scientific results¹⁻⁵ obtained from these long-term observations

and partnerships, identifying trends, sources of pollution, and potential ways for targeted intervention to reduce air pollution impacts. This overall sustained effort at *Les Frenes* station, and the forthcoming developments, brings an example of the potential power of urban supersites for in situ measurements since by pooling resources, expertise, and high-quality data, allow improving the knowledge on aerosol health impact and shaping local political initiatives for improved air quality.

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Chemical compositions and sources contribution of urban aerosols during winter in Wrocław, Poland.

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Keywords: particulate matter, chemical composition, OC, Poland

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Introduction

Atmospheric aerosols are the main constituents of the atmosphere due to their effect on human health (WHO, 2021, Manisalidis et al., 2020) and atmospheric chemistry. Aerosols originate from different natural and anthropogenic sources, both as primary emission and secondary aerosols formed through gas-to-particle conversion processes. This diversity of emission sources and atmospheric processes contributes to the varied chemical composition, optical and physical properties of atmospheric aerosols. Identifying the chemical compositions and sources of aerosols is required to assess the climate and health risks, and to optimize pollution control strategies establishing effective PM reduction measures (Fuzzi et al., 2015, UNEP, 2014).

In Poland, some mitigation strategies have been implemented to improve air quality during the last few years, but the concentration of PM_x is still higher than in most European countries. This is mainly due to the common use of fossil fuels and biomass for heating purposes. The study aims to describe the chemical composition of PM during the winter period in Wrocław, and the relations between weather factors and PM properties.

Data and sampling site

An intensive aerosol field campaign was carried out at an urban location in Wrocław (670000 inhabitants) (51°06'N; 17°05'E; 116 m a.s.l.) during the winter period (from 15 November to 5 December 2022). The online analysis of the chemical composition of aerosols was made using AMS (Aerodyne) belonging to CEH from Edinburgh. The gravimetric sampler was used to collect filters for off-line analysis. The sample collection was conducted in approximately 24-hour intervals, and the filters were exchanged at 6:30 UTC. Supporting meteorological (in situ and remote sensing) and air quality data were obtained from the Meteorological Observatory of the University of Wrocław.

Results

The average daily mass concentration of PM_x during the field experiment ranged from 14.6 to 65.3 μg m⁻³. There

was substantial variation in chemical composition (Figure 1), mainly due to weather conditions. A large share of OC and a diurnal pattern of organic particles with elevated concentration from evening hours to morning confirms the household emission as a main source of PM in an urban atmosphere. Moreover, the significant contribution of chloride may indicate the burning of waste in the local heating system.

Figure 1. The chemical composition of PM during Wrocław winter campaign

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Meteorological influences on Black Carbon concentration in Wrocław, Poland.

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Introduction

Particulate pollution is a critical issue in Poland, which has serious environmental impacts both on air quality and thus human health, as well as regional and global climate. This is primarily due to the widespread use of fossil fuels and biomass burning for home heating. Therefore, the highest concentrations of particulate matter occur in the winter season. During high-pressure weather, with low temperatures and low wind speed, PM concentration increases, leading to deterioration of air quality, reduced visibility, and an increased risk of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. One of the most important components of PM is black carbon, it originates from the incomplete combustion of fuels, such as diesel, gasoline, coal, and biomass (Bond et al., 2013). Black carbon (BC) is one of the most important, so-called short-lived climate pollutants, contributing to radiative forcing on the climate system (IPCC, 2022). Epidemiological studies confirm, that BC exposure increases the risk of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases (Kirrane et al., 2019). However, despite this, the observation of BC in Poland is inadequate, but there is a need to assess urban black carbon to better understand the dynamics of BC concentration and optimized reduction strategies. The main aim of the study is to analyse the variability of BC concentration in relation to meteorological conditions.

Data and sampling site

The measurements of BC and particulate matter have been carried out at an urban location in Wrocław (670000 inhabitants) (51°06'N; 17°05'E; 116 m a.s.l.) since December 2022. The eBC mass concentrations were measured using a multi-wavelength (370, 470, 520, 590, 660, 880 and 950 nm) aethalometer (Model AE43, Magee Scientific, Berkeley, CA, USA). The PM_{2.5} concentration was obtained by TEOM analyser. The data were gathered in 1-minute resolution. Supporting meteorological (in situ and remote sensing) and air quality data (UFP size distribution) were obtained from the Meteorological Observatory of the University of Wrocław.

Results

The average daily mass concentration of PM_{2.5} during the period analysed ranged from 3.6 to 33.9 µg m⁻³. The mean BC concentration during the period was found to be 2.09 µg m⁻³, varied from 1.02 µg m⁻³ in May up to 3.42 µg m⁻³ in December, and the daily concentration of BC ranged from 0.22 up to 12.8 µg m⁻³.

Figure 1. Descriptive statistics (min, max, 1st, and 3rd quartile and median values) of hourly BC concentration.

Burning of biomass fuels comprised nearly 30% of the total amount of BC. The concentration of BC and PM_{2.5} was highly correlated ($r^2=0.69$). The average contribution of soot to PM_{2.5} was almost 30%, which falls within the range of a few percent to above 50% for individual PM_{2.5} samples. During haze episodes the average concentrations of equivalent BC on haze days were much higher than those on the non-haze day, especially during the first part of the episode due to direct primary emissions from household sector and stagnant, cold meteorological conditions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The hourly course of PM_{2.5}, BC and BB during January 2023

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From Urban Haze to Alpine Gaze: Tracing the Linkages Between Black Carbon and PAH in UFP

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Keywords: Ultrafine Particles, Black Carbon, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

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Ultrafine particles (UFP) have diameters of 100 nm and less. The composition UFP is an important factor for human and environmental health, particularly, when containing constituents such as black carbon (BC) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH).

BC is emitted from incomplete combustion and known for its strong light-absorbing properties. PAH are a group of organic compounds, which are mostly classified as carcinogenic or mutagenic, and formed in the process of incomplete combustion, as well. Thus, understanding the interplay between UFP and the content of BC and PAH, is key of assessing both the underlying processes of sources, airborne transport and transformation as well as its potential impact on air quality, weather and climate.

Therefore, we developed a novel unit for separation and collection of UFP. UFP were efficiently separated from larger atmospheric particles using a three-stage cascade impactor. Below the final stage, with a previously characterized cut-off of 100 nm, UFP were collected on quartz fiber filters. An automated filter change was programmed at 24-hour intervals to achieve favorable temporal resolution while collecting a total air volume of 43.2 m³, sufficient for mass-based chemical offline analysis. Additionally, ozone was removed from the sample air using an ozone denuder, to prevent reactions with the already collected particles. This step was crucial in obtaining untainted results concerning the composition of PAH in UFP. The UFP samples were subsequently extracted via a soft, optimized solvent-based method. The offline-analysis for investigation of chemical PAH fingerprints was performed with standard high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) – fluorescence detection (FLD). The method was characterized through the calculation of recovery rates using standard reference material, and by determining its limit of detection (LOD). This LOD, defined by a noise-to-peak ratio of 3 and validated through standard deviation analysis (3 σ) along with consistent calibrations, was adapted for the specific sampled air. Consequently, this approach enabled the detection of individual PAHs in UFP, with LOD values ranging from 1.1 pg/m³ to

4.6 pg/m³, reflecting the method's' capability to detect even low concentrations of PAH in UFP from environmental samples.

Additionally, the novel unit included an in-built Micro-Aethalometer for concurrent BC observations. The Micro-Aethalometer MA 200 operated throughout the entire UFP collection period. Measurements were conducted at a flow rate of 150 ml/min and a time resolution of 5 minutes using the single-spot sampling mode on PTFE material with a resolution of 1 ng/m³ and a LOD of 30 ng/m³. Analysis was performed using five wavelengths: IR (880 nm), Red (625 nm), Green (528 nm), Blue (470 nm), and UV (375 nm). The Micro-Aethalometer was repeatedly evaluated against reference instrumentation with side-by-side observations.

We deployed the unit, for the combined analysis of PAH in UFP and BC, across various urban and rural settings in Bavaria, Germany, such as the Alpine Zugspitze and Munich Airport. Preliminary results indicated that the concentration of equivalent black carbon (eBC), measured through absorption at 880 nm, varied significantly by location, ranging from 18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to over 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. We analysed the observed variations in order to emphasize the intricate interplay between BC, PAH and other components in UFP, highlighting the multifaceted interactions within the atmospheric environment.

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Chemical and size fractionation of particulate matter near a ferromanganese plant to assess its oxidative potential

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Keywords: oxidative potential, particulate matter, trace elements, manganese.

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Particulate matter (PM) oxidative potential (OP) has recently been considered a better health-based metric of PM exposure than PM mass concentration (Bates et al., 2019). However, there is no clear consensus on the sensitivity of different OP assays to PM properties (such as size fraction and chemical composition) and emission sources. Manganese (Mn) is a major contributor to OP (Gao et al., 2020). However, to our knowledge, the sensitivity of OP assays to Mn in PM in areas with high Mn levels has not been studied so far.

This study analyzes three different acellular OP assays (ascorbic acid (AA), dithiothreitol (DTT) and 2,7-dichlorofluorescein (DCFH)) and their sensitivity to the chemical composition of PM samples of different sizes (PM_{2.5}, PM_{10-2.5}) collected in an industrial-urban area. Urban samples from a nearby area were also collected for comparison purposes. High concentrations of Mn in PM mainly characterize the industrial area, due to the proximity of a ferromanganese alloy plant. The filters of the two size fractions were subjected to a chemical fractionation procedure and analyzed for soluble (in a phosphate buffer solution) and insoluble concentrations of 39 elements by ICP-MS. This approach allowed us to assess the bioaccessibility of the elements and to increase their selectivity as source tracers (Canepari et al., 2019). Data on the ferromanganese plant production rate during sampling were also available. Spearman correlations and principal component analysis (PCA) were performed on the data obtained in the different size and solubility fractions of PM to identify the main tracers of the ferromanganese plant and other sources that contribute to local PM levels and OP values near the industrial source of Mn.

Table 1. Spearman correlation coefficients between OP, PM, and soluble Mn according to the particle size.

	PM _{10-2.5}			PM _{2.5}		
	OP ^{DTT} _v	OP ^{AA} _v	OP ^{DCFH} _v	OP ^{DTT} _v	OP ^{AA} _v	OP ^{DCFH} _v
Mass concentration (µg/m ³)	0.12	0.34	0.05	0.29	-0.02	0.21
Mn soluble concentration (ng/m ³)	0.93	0.47	0.85	0.80	0.18	0.54
OP ^{DCFH} _v (nmol H ₂ O ₂ /m ³)	0.76	0.18		0.57	0.50	
OP ^{AA} _v (nmol/min/m ³)	0.54			0.53		

The correlation coefficients between the OP values determined by the three assays, the mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM_{10-2.5}, and the concentration of soluble Mn in the studied industrial-urban area are shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficients change with the size fraction; the highest

values were found between soluble Mn and OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} in the coarse fraction, and soluble Mn and OP^{DTT} in the fine fraction. In the coarse fraction, OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} were found to be well correlated, while OP^{AA} seems to be poorly correlated with the other assays.

PCA revealed that the largest variance in the dataset (PC1, 41.2%) is explained by the higher content of all elements in PM_{2.5}. However, from Figure 1, we can observe that a smaller portion of the variance (PC2/PC3, 25.6%) is explained by the different element concentrations in the two size and solubility fractions of PM due to different contributions of three main emission sources: industrial emissions (group A) releasing Mn and other elements in soluble PM; traffic (group b) emitting elements from abrasion of vehicle brakes; soil dust (group c) releasing crustal elements. OP^{DTT} and OP^{DCFH} assays predominantly respond to PM emitted from the ferromanganese plant. In particular, they are particularly sensitive to soluble Mn. The emission of these elements in PM depends on the ferromanganese plant production rate during sampling and does not lead to an increase in PM mass concentration, which mainly depends on urban sources.

Figure 1. Biplot of PC2/PC3 from the PCA performed on the studied dataset.

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The importance of the elemental analysis for the chemical characterization of the aerosols and the advantages of the PIXE technique

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Keywords: elements, chemical composition, source apportionment, PIXE.

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The analysis of the elemental composition of atmospheric aerosol provides important information, essential for both understanding the composition of pollutants and taking necessary measures to control and minimize their effects on health and the environment. The chemical composition is crucial to understand the sources of the particulate matter, whether it's from natural sources like dust or from anthropogenic activities like industrial emissions or traffic. Since different sources have distinct elemental compositions and sometimes even specific markers, analyzing all the detectable elements, from the main to trace elements, helps to identify pollution sources both in urban and remote environments through multivariate methods such as Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF).

The Particle Induced X-ray Emission (PIXE) technique is a particular Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) technique that has proved to be a powerful tool useful for the elemental analysis of atmospheric particulate matter samples. PIXE is in fact a technique that offers numerous advantages for the study of this type of samples: it allows simultaneous quantitative multi-elemental analysis of elements with $Z > 10$; times of the analysis are extremely short when compared with other analytical techniques (about 1 minute for each sample); it has low detection limits which allows the quantification of the main elements but also of trace and ultra-trace metals with a high sensitivity (down to $\mu\text{g/g}$); it does not require any sample preparation, thus reducing any possible contamination due to the use of chemical reagents for the solubilization of the elements; it is a non-destructive technique, allowing the same samples to be subsequently analyzed with other complementary analysis techniques, expanding the range of chemical species available for a more complete chemical characterization of the particulate matter samples.

Since 2003 in Florence, at the 3 MV Tandatron accelerator of the LABEC laboratory of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) (Chiari et al., 2021), it is operative a beamline specifically dedicated to PIXE and PIGE measurements of the elemental composition of atmospheric aerosol samples. The experimental set-up of this beamline has undergone several technological upgrades over the years that have made it possible to fully exploit the advantages of PIXE technique: the use of two different types of Silicon Drift detectors (SDD) for X-

ray spectroscopy allows to measure both light and heavy elements, while the use of multiple detectors of the same type allows to improve the throughput and the sensitivity with a consequent reduction of both measurement times and detection limits. The latest upgrade with the purpose of further improving sensitivity and measurement throughput is the design of a PIXE set-up equipped with six SDD (two for light elements and four for heavy ones), and a fully digital data acquisition. For all of these reasons LABEC has been selected to host the Elemental Mass Calibration Centre (EMC2) of the European ACTRIS (<https://www.actris.eu>) research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres. EMC2 is a unit of the Center for Aerosol In-Situ measurement - European Center for Aerosol Calibration & Characterization (CAIS-ECAC, <https://www.actris-ecac.eu>). EMC2 is promoting and conducting inter-comparison and round-robin exercises for proficiency tests of individual laboratory in elemental analysis using IBA, XRF and ICP methods, as well as it is providing operation support for quality assurance and quality control for the measurement of mass concentration of particulate heavy metals and inorganic elements. Moreover, this facility is available for measurements to external users and to the ACTRIS community as a service offered by EMC2 supported by project ITINERIS, Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System (IR0000032-ITINERIS funded by EU - Next Generation EU PNRR).

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Gaseous and particulate emissions from the open burning of wastes from tree pruning and hedge trimming

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Open air biomass burning produces significant emissions of gaseous and particulate pollutants that can vary depending on the fuel burned. The chemical characterisation of emissions from the burning of green garden and tree pruning wastes is poorly documented despite the fact that this practice induces large emissions of several toxic compounds. To improve emission inventories, the aim of this research was to obtain gaseous and particulate emission factors (EFs) for this combustion source.

In the present study, 5 samples of gaseous emissions (in Tedlar bags), and particulate matter (PM₁₀ on filters) were taken during the combustion of pruning and hedge trimming residues of various species, trying to reproduce the usual procedures of landowners and gardeners, who burn the residues in the backyard or in an open field with some grass. A background air sample was also collected. The burnt residues included olive branches (*Olea europaea*), willow (*Salix atrocinerea*), red hawthorn, also known as scarlet hawthorn (*Pyracanta coccinea*), wild privet (*Ligustrum vulgare*) and Chinese privet, a highly invasive species from East Asia (*Ligustrum lucidum*). The carbonaceous content (organic and elemental carbon, OC and EC) of PM₁₀ was determined by a thermo-optical transmission technique (Alves et al., 2019).

The EFs obtained in this study (Table 1) were within the range established for flaming conditions and similar to those obtained in previous studies (Alves et al., 2019; Akagi et al., 2011; Noblet et al., 2021). The OC and EC EFs decreased as combustion progressed and biofuels were consumed. Flaming combustion involves the rapid reaction of O₂ with the gases released from the solid biofuel and is common in foliage or small diameter dry aerial biomass. Flaming combustion converts the carbon in the fuel into highly oxidised gases such as CO₂ and generates most of the EC particles. As the fire progresses, the smouldering phase begins to play a major role. Slow combustion generates CO, CH₄, non-methane hydrocarbons and primary organic aerosols (Akagi et al., 2011). This would be the reason why the highest CH₄ value occurred for the last sample from the combustion of olive (AL-3), when the smouldering phase began to take place.

Table 1. Emission factors for each sample (g kg⁻¹, dry basis).

	AL-2	AL-3	AL-4	AL-5	AL-6
CO ₂	1562	1537	1612	1627	1672
CO	67.2	80	62.3	59.3	41.9
N ₂ O	ND	0.21	0.17	0.28	0.66
NO ₂	15	27.4	16.1	9.6	8.82
HCl	0.51	0.36	0.02	0.04	0.75
HF	0.02	ND	0.01	0.02	0.03
CH ₄	2.74	6.6	4.15	3.13	2.91
C ₂ H ₆	2.93	3.51	1.84	0.89	ND
C ₂ H ₄	1.07	1.78	0.79	1.01	1.19
C ₃ H ₈	ND	ND	0.01	0.05	0.06
C ₆ H ₁₄	0.23	0.8	0.54	0.23	0.37
CHOH	3.47	2.24	0.97	1.21	0.56
TOC	7.72	11.2	6.5	4.84	3.41
OC	18.5	17.1	8.14	6.6	2.9
EC	1.45	1.3	0.91	0.53	0.4
PM ₁₀	40.9	40.1	21.6	19.1	8.33

SO₂, NH₃, C₃H₆, CH₃OH: never detected.

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The influence of carbonaceous components on the oxidative potential of PM₁₀ in a rural area of southeastern Spain

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Keywords: oxidative potential, OP^{DTT}, OP^{AA}

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Exposure to airborne particulate matter (PM) is clearly associated with various detrimental health effects as cardiovascular, respiratory or cerebrovascular diseases (Contini *et al* (2021)). The severity of these effects depends on the size and chemical composition of the particles. Most of the particle mass consists of low-toxicity components such as sulfate, ammonium nitrate, sodium chloride, and mineral dust. In contrast, low levels of transition metals and water-soluble organic compounds can have significant health effects since they act as potent oxidants capable of generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Borm *et al.*, 2007). In this context, the oxidative potential (OP) emerges as a more precise measure of PM toxicity than PM mass alone, as it reflects the ability to oxidize target molecules (Lionetto *et al* (2019)).

In this study, a total of 38 PM₁₀ daily samples were collected in a small village in southeastern Spain (Benejama, Alicante), during late winter and early spring of 2023 (22 February – 4 April) using a high-volume sampler (30 l/min) onto quartz fibre filters. PM mass concentrations were determined gravimetrically. Samples were analysed for organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) using a thermal-optical transmission analyser. The analysis of levoglucosan, a tracer of biomass burning, was conducted by anion exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection. Water-soluble organic carbon concentrations were quantified using a Total Organic Carbon analyser. Finally, the OP assays used in this work were the acellular dithiothreitol (OP^{DTT}) and ascorbic acid (OP^{AA}) tests.

The mean values of PM₁₀, OP^{AA} and OP^{DTT} during the study period were $20.2 \pm 10.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $0.11 \pm 0.06 \text{ nmol}/\text{min}\cdot\text{m}^3$ and $0.32 \pm 0.09 \text{ nmol}/\text{min}\cdot\text{m}^3$, respectively. Low correlations of PM₁₀ with OP^{AA} ($r = 0.40$) and OP^{DTT} ($r = 0.20$) were found, which suggest that PM mass alone cannot adequately assess aerosol toxicity. Regarding the correlation between the two OP methods,

Figure 1. Correlation between OP^{AA} and OP^{DTT}.

we found a moderately good correlation ($r = 0.66$), as shown in Figure 1.

In order to evaluate the sources for OP^{AA} and OP^{DTT}, a correlation analysis was conducted between both assays and the organic components of PM₁₀ (Table 1). Unexpectedly, both methods presented a strong correlation with EC concentrations, although the impact of traffic emissions in the study area was low. The OP^{DTT} was also strongly correlated with WSOC, as shown in previous studies (Hakimzadeh *et al* (2020)). On the other hand, a statistically significant correlation between OP^{DTT} and levoglucosan was observed, which suggest that biomass burning is an important source for OP^{DTT}.

Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficients among OP measurements and PM₁₀ organic components.

	OP ^{AA}	OP ^{DTT}
OC	0.33	0.43
EC	0.75	0.74
Levo	0.27	0.59
WSOC	0.58	0.84
TC	0.49	0.65

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Methanol-soluble organic carbon in PM₁₀ at a rural site in southeastern Spain

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Biomass burning is a significant source of brown carbon (BrC), which contributes significantly to radiative forcing (Ramanathan *et al* (2001)). In urban areas of southwestern Europe, sensitive to climate change, where strong emissions from residential wood burning (RWB) occur, the radiative impact of carbonaceous aerosols remains largely unknown.

This study examines the absorption properties of methanol-soluble organic carbon (MSOC) in a small village in southeastern Spain (Benejama, Alicante), where the use of RWB is very common during winter months. Measurements were conducted between late winter and early spring of 2023 (22 February – 4 April). A total of 38 daily PM₁₀ samples were collected onto quartz fibre filters. Sample extracts were analysed using UV-Vis spectrophotometry to determine the absorption of methanol-soluble organic carbon. MSOC concentrations, used as a proxy for BrC, were determined using an indirect quantification protocol (Cheng *et al* (2016)). For this, samples were analysed by the thermal-optical method to quantify the OC content before and after their extraction with methanol. The concentration of MSOC was determined by subtracting the OC mass concentration after methanol extraction from the total OC concentration.

The mean concentration of MSOC during the study period was $1.96 \pm 0.31 \mu\text{gC}/\text{m}^3$ contributing 63 % to the total OC. The strong correlation between MSOC and OC (Figure 1) indicate that they share common sources.

Figure 1. Relationship between MSOC and total OC concentrations.

Absorption of MSOC were calculated as described in Cheng *et al* (2016). The average absorption of MSOC at 365 nm was $0.69 \pm 0.39 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$. Normalization of the absorption coefficients measured at 365 nm to the extractable methanol OC mass resulted in an average mass absorption efficiency (MAE) of $0.35 \pm 0.16 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for methanol-soluble extracts.

A strong correlation between the absorption at 365 nm of methanol extracts and levoglucosan concentrations ($R^2 = 0.66$) was found (Figure 2), indicating that biomass burning is an important source of brown carbon in the study area during the cold months.

Figure 2. Correlation between the absorption at 365 nm of methanol extracts and levoglucosan concentrations.

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Optimizing the Parameters of the Black Carbon Source Apportionment Model: Unveiling Ångström Absorption Exponent Sensitivity Analysis

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Keywords: Absorption Ångström Exponent, Different Emission Sources, Black Carbon, Source Apportionment.
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Monitoring black carbon and its sources is pivotal for understanding its environmental impact, health implications, and climate effects. Source apportionment studies helps target emission reduction efforts and develop effective air quality and climate change strategies, crucial for global policymaking.

The Absorption Ångström Exponent α is a crucial optical parameter characterizing aerosol light absorption. Widely employed for black carbon (BC) source identification, it requires a-priori knowledge for liquid and solid fuel emissions. Typically set at $\alpha_{lf}=1$ for liquid fuel and $\alpha_{sf}=2$ for solid fuel (Sandradewi et al. 2008) or $\alpha_{sf}=1.68$ $\alpha_{lf}=0.9$ (Zotter et al. 2017), these parameters are however expected to exhibit site-specific variations and can be derived using ambient air measurements. Specifically, α_{lf} and α_{sf} could be approximated respectively as the 1st and the 99th percentile of curated ambient air α values (Tobler et al. 2021). Nevertheless, discrepancies arise in the determination of α_{sf} , particularly in contexts such as traffic sites, where the outcomes contradict the expected characteristics of the sites (Savadkoobi et al. 2023).

This research delves into the source apportionment model for black carbon, focusing on determining optimal parameters for α_{lf} and α_{sf} . α_{lf} is determined through frequency distribution analysis, while the study aims to identify the ideal α_{sf} using correlation analysis between eBC_{lf} and eBC_{sf} with external datasets, such as NO and specific mass fragments (mz) from ACSM (Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor) measurements.

The investigation involves calculating BC_{lf} and BC_{sf} across a range of α_{sf} values (1.1-2.6), maintaining a fixed α_{lf} derived from the frequency distribution model. The primary goal is to pinpoint the α_{sf} value that maximizes the correlation between BC_{sf} and mz60 (commonly used as a biomass burning tracer) while intentionally minimizing the correlation for BC_{lf} . This pursuit aims for a heightened correlation between BC_{sf} and mz60, while deliberately seeking a lower correlation for BC_{lf} .

It's crucial to note that lower α_{sf} values correspond to higher proportions of BC_{sf} , accentuating the significance

of optimizing this parameter for a refined understanding of the source apportionment model's outcomes.

Figure 1. Correlation Analysis of eBC, eBC_{lf} , and eBC_{sf} as a function of α_{sf} .

Figure 1 depicts the correlation trends among eBC, eBC_{lf} and eBC_{sf} as a function of α_{sf} values. Notably, at lower α_{sf} values, eBC equals eBC_{sf} , resulting in an overestimation of eBC_{sf} . As α_{sf} increases, a trend emerges towards an improved correlation with mz60, a tracer of biomass burning, reaching a peak correlation at approximately 1.8, representing the actual proportions of eBC_{lf} and eBC_{sf} . Remarkably, while mz60 attains its maximum correlation at this point, the correlation for eBC_{lf} remains relatively low, hovering around 0.3, indicating a distinct disparity in correlation strengths between the two parameters. This graphical representation offers insights into the interrelation between α_{sf} , eBC components, and their correlation with mz60, underscoring the complexities in accurately attributing eBC sources based on α_{sf} variations.

Six sites were part of the study: urban locations in Bologna, Paris Chatelet, Athens National Observatory, and Zurich, alongside a traffic site in Helsinki and an Urban Background site in Sirta Palaiseau. The dataset used for analysis is from 2023, offering current and diverse data for comprehensive insights into the study's focal point.

This work was performed within the framework of the RI-URBANS project (contract 101036245), implementing the ACTRIS strategy for the development of services for improving air quality in Europe.

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Organic and inorganic water-soluble compounds in PM_{2.5} and their sources in urban environment

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Ambient fine particulate matter fraction (PM_{2.5}) is one of major air pollutants that has harmful influence on human health, environment and climate due to its small size and complex chemical composition. Severe respiratory and cardiovascular illnesses, even premature death might be caused by elevated levels of PM_{2.5}, so the World Health Organization (WHO) advises to monitor its levels and content.

PM_{2.5} mass consists of water, mineral dust, inorganic ions, trace metals and organic carbonaceous species (OC) among which substantial proportion are water-soluble organic compounds (WSOC). Some previous studies showed that 20-80% of OC in PM_{2.5} is composed from WSOC. An important fraction of WSOC are short-chain organic acids (OA) which in urban and remote marine areas accounts for 1-5% and >10% of OC, respectively. OA can be either directly emitted in air from anthropogenic or natural biogenic sources or are produced as secondary organic aerosols (SOA) from volatile organic gases (VOC) precursors during complex gas-phase photochemical oxidation and aqueous-phase oxidation processes. Meteorological parameters (relative humidity, temperature, solar radiation etc.), aerosol liquid water content, VOCs precursors and oxidant concentrations affect the particulates load with OA (Luo et al 2020).

Ubiquitous highly oxidized short-chain OA compounds in particulate PM_{2.5} content are acetic (AA), formic (FA) and oxalic (OX) acid. The FA/AA mass ratio is considered as useful marker for the contribution of secondary and/or primary air pollution sources while OX content suggests the presence of biomass burning. Due to its low vapor pressure, OA in air can be present in gas PM_{2.5} phase. OA can serve as the cloud condensation nuclei and by increasing the hygroscopic properties of PM_{2.5} alter the cloud formation processes and indirectly affect climate. Because of high water-solubility, the short-chain OA contribute to the total free aerosol acidity and through wet and dry deposition can enhanced the water ecosystems and soil acidification. Determination of OA in PM_{2.5} content should not be underestimated due to its diverse impact on environment (Yu et al 2019).

Source apportionment receptor models (RM) are tools used to assess pollution sources. Based on mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} and water-soluble compounds in its content RM are used to achieve more accurate source

estimation e.g. its type, intensity and spatial and/or temporal distribution (European Commission 2014). In order to better quantify present air pollution sources, measurements of PM_{2.5} mass concentrations as well as the mass concentrations of water-soluble inorganic ions and OA (Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Na⁺, NH₄⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, AA, FA, OX) in its content was conducted over a 1-year period at an urban background site in the northern part of Croatian capital Zagreb. Mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} samples were determined gravimetrically while the content of water-soluble ions and OA was determined by ion chromatography with suppressed conductivity detection.

Results in this study show that daily mass concentrations of water-soluble inorganic ions and OA in PM_{2.5} were in range from under limit of quantification to 8.0 µg m⁻³. Obtained annual average PM_{2.5} mass concentration was 14.4 µg m⁻³ which is under limit value proscribed by Croatian Regulation on the levels of pollutants in ambient air (25 µg m⁻³) but above level advised by new WHO Air Quality Guidelines (5 µg m⁻³). Among measured compounds in PM_{2.5} content, the highest average contribution to the total PM_{2.5} mass was determined for SO₄²⁻, NH₄⁺ and OX, 13 %, 7 % and 2 %, respectively. PM_{2.5} mass concentrations as well as mass concentrations of Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, K⁺, AA and OX in its content show clear seasonal variations with higher levels during colder part of the year (winter, autumn season). The FA/AA mass ratio and NO₃⁻/SO₄²⁻ mass ratio show daily variations as well as seasonal variations. During colder part of the year obtained NO₃⁻/SO₄²⁻ mass ratio was higher than 1 which suggests that both mobile and stationary sources contribute to the overall air pollution at urban background station, while obtained levels of the FA/AA mass ratio during warmer part of the year indicated dominance of secondary sources.

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Carbon pollutants in PM₁ at an urban canyon location

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In cities, narrow streets surrounded by tall buildings create a "canyon" effect where pollution accumulates due to poor ventilation. The primary sources of particulate matter in such places are emissions from road traffic, including exhaust and non-exhaust emissions from incomplete fuel combustion like diesel and gasoline. Resuspension from street surfaces and tire braking also contributes. The concentration of PM₁, which is particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter below 1 μm, and its chemical composition depend, in addition to sources, on meteorological factors such as low ambient temperatures and temperature inversions, traffic, and street geometry. The concentration of exhaust fumes from motor vehicles in narrow streets can represent serious health risks for drivers, passengers, pedestrians, and people who live nearby. Long- and short-term exposure to air pollution can cause acute and chronic illnesses like cardiovascular diseases, asthma, and infectious diseases. It can also lead to premature death and adverse neuropsychological effects (Camatini *et al.*, 2016; Khomenko *et al.*, 2021; Kim *et al.*, 2015; Pateraki *et al.*, 2019; Rohr and Wyzga, 2012).

This study aimed to measure the levels of air pollution in a typical street canyon location and understand the complex relationships between different pollutants. The focus was on testing the predictability of each pollutant to improve future measurements and urban planning. The study compared the levels of elemental (EC), organic (OC), primary organic (POC), and secondary organic carbon (SOC), as well as water-soluble OC (WSOC), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and levoglucosan (LVG) mass concentrations in PM₁ particles, between working days, weekends, seasons, and years at a street canyon location in the center of Zagreb from January 1st, 2019, to December 31st, 2021. The mass concentrations of PM₁ were determined gravimetrically. The samples underwent analysis for OC, TC, WSOC, and EC with the thermal/optical transmittance method (TOT) using the EUSAAR₂ protocol. Moreover, PAHs were analyzed with a high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) with a fluorescence detector and time-programmed changes in excitation and emission. Finally, levoglucosan was analyzed using high-performance anion-exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD).

The data showed seasonal variations in mass concentrations for carbon species in PM₁, with higher

concentrations observed during colder periods and lower concentrations in warmer periods. The analysis also revealed that traffic and traffic jams could be the key contributing factors to carbon content in particulate matter, with increased numbers of vehicles standing with engines running at traffic lights. It was further observed that reduced particle concentrations are due to less dust being raised from the road itself since vehicles are idling more than moving. The lower temperature during wintertime favors the condensation of organic compounds onto pre-existing particles, leading to higher OC mass concentrations and OC content in PM₁. These findings highlight the importance of reducing traffic congestion and promoting cleaner transportation to mitigate the carbon levels in particulate matter, and ultimately improve air quality for healthier living, especially during winter and temperature inversion episodes. Investing in a healthier and sustainable environment is crucial for future generations. The higher concentrations of pollutants recorded during the winter period serve as a stark reminder of the importance of taking action immediately.

These measurements were conducted within the internal scientific project "Organic content of PM₁ particle fraction" funded by the Institute for Medical Research and Occupational Health (PI: R. Godec).

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Measurement of ultrafine Particles (2 to 800 nm) in the Rhein-Main area with a special Emphasis on Airport and Emissions

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Keywords: airport emissions, UFP study, urban environment

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In recent years, the importance of ultrafine particle (UFP) measurements has increased significantly, particularly due to their adverse health effects. For this reason, it is important to further investigate and characterise strong UFP sources, especially in densely populated urban and suburban areas, to shed more light on their impact on local air quality. Former studies have already shown that highly frequented airports are a major source of UFPs (Hudda et al. 2014, Keuken et al. 2015); these studies further showed that even over long distances of up to 10 km downwind of the airport, UFP concentrations are significantly elevated.

Figure 1: Daily half-hour averages of particle number concentration >3 nm and >10 nm measured at Schwanheim, approx. 4 km from the airfield.

In this study, we deployed a variety of instruments to characterise the UFPs from Frankfurt Airport (FRA) in the densely populated Rhein-Main area. Size and concentration levels over a size range from 2-800 nm were measured at three different locations which are located 4, 8, and 15 km away from the airport, respectively. Overall, the measurements were conducted over a duration of 6 months. In contrast to previous studies, we were able to measure nucleation mode particles with diameters < 10 nm, (which leads to a more complete characterization of all the UFP sources at the airport.) Measurements of the full aerosol size distribution and meteorological parameters (e.g. wind speed and direction) made it possible to distinguish sources at the airport from other traffic emissions and the urban background.

As a result, we found that aerosol emissions from the airport dominate the aerosol population of the neighbouring districts (up to a distance of at least 15 km) to a great extent. This can be seen when comparing particle number concentrations downwind of the airport versus urban background levels. Figure 1 shows, e. g., the average diurnal particle number concentration at the measurement station with a distance of 4 km from the airport. It is clearly visible that the particle number concentration is elevated by almost a factor of 6 during the airport operating hours (05:00 – 23:00) when the wind is arriving from the airport. The difference of the particle number concentrations with diameters above 3 nm and above 10 nm (Figure 1) indicates that a large fraction of aircraft aerosol emissions is below 10 nm in size and therefore remains mostly undetected by standardised UFP measurements. This indicates that the particle burden can be significantly underestimated when only focussing on particles larger than 10 nm.

In the presentation a detailed analysis of the measured results at the three different stations will be presented. The analysis focuses on the dependence of the diurnal pattern of the aerosol size distribution as a function of the origin of the air masses (wind direction). This way, airport emissions can be distinguished from other traffic emissions and the urban background. Furthermore, we present direct evidence that landing airplanes can contribute significantly to the smallest measurably particles < 10 nm.

Overall, we conclude that for a full assessment of the negative health effects of UFP emissions it is important to (1) increase the number of monitoring stations, especially in areas with strong sources such as airports and (2) lower the size of the smallest particles that are detected from 10 to 3 nm, in order to determine the UFP concentrations and health risks more realistically.

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Time-serial analysis of outdoor air pollution and absence of children in kindergarten due to respiratory diseases

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Children, the elderly, and those with defective immune system or with underlying chronic diseases are at highest risk of being affected by airborne infectious diseases. They also play a role as sensitive population groups for the air pollution. Children, especially preschool children, may have up to 6-10 viral colds a year (de Benedictis, 2018). Air pollution evocation of a disease would have a reason in depression of immunity, exacerbation of viral or litter bacterial infection and worsening of chronic illnesses.

The absenteeism of children, as we research, is a disease consequence. The exposure to air pollution can cause absenteeism from kindergarten, although this effect is very difficult to decouple from various other factors including of co-pollutants, evaluation is necessary.

With the support of the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic, the time-serial analysis of outdoor air pollution and absence of children in kindergarten due to respiratory diseases is being carried out. Over the course of 2.5 years (from 2022), data collection on the absences of about 280 children due to respiratory diseases is taking place in 11 kindergartens and 5 cities. In the vicinity of kindergartens, the Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI) operates stations measuring ultrafine particles and other pollutants (Mladá Boleslav, Hradec Králové, Plzeň, Lom (ACTRIS-CZ station) and Ústí n/L). The advantage of our research is the possibility to use the data gathered from these stations and recorded absences for statistical analyses such as the Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines method (MARS).

MARS is a sophisticated tool that allows to modelling complex and dynamic relationships in data. It is especially useful where traditional linear models cannot adequately capture complex data structures. MARS automatically detects not only linear, but also nonlinear relationships in the data, allowing the model to better adapt to the actual data structure and thus obtain a more accurate representation of the relationships between the input variables and the target variable (Friedman, 1991).

As a test sample for the MARS analysis (Fig.1), the location of the Lom station and kindergartens in the adjacent area was chosen. The predictors used were the previous 3 days (1-3) of the lung-deposited surface area (LDSA) and apparent temperature (AT). The dependent variable is the number of children absent from kindergarten due to respiratory disease. Although the

outcome of the MARS application appears to be promising, the concentration of black carbon will be included in other analysis as an additional predictor.

Figure 1. Number of children absent from kindergarten due to respiratory diseases, reality vs prediction, MARS.

The research leading to these results has received funding from the project for the support of the ACTRIS Large Research Infrastructure - Participation of the Czech Republic (ACTRIS-CZ - LM2023030) - Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

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Black carbon source contribution in two urban environments during summer and winter seasons

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Urban areas are significant generators of aerosol black carbon (BC) due to incomplete combustion. This BC, an atmospheric pollutant, profoundly impacts air quality, human health (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2022), and climate (Bond *et al.*, 2013). Considering the quantification of these emissions, their seasonal patterns, and their contribution to heightened pollution levels in nearby regions via long-range air mass transport and the influence of traffic and biomass burning is crucial for effective emission-reduction strategies.

To understand the complexities underlying BC concentrations, we explored their strong regional and temporal variations. Our study focuses on investigating the characteristics of light-absorbing aerosol particles and introduces an innovative approach to assess the impact of long-range transport on BC pollution in two previously understudied urban areas: Warsaw (Poland, Central Europe) and Vilnius (Lithuania, North-Eastern Europe). To accomplish this, we analyzed BC mass concentration along with several aerosol optical properties, specifically, the scattering Ångström exponent (SAE), absorption Ångström exponent (AAE), and single scattering albedo (SSA). The study is based on a method by Minderytė *et al.* (2023) and spanned the warm season from May to August 2022 and the cold season from November to February 2022/2023, enabling us to account for seasonal variability. Additionally, we examined the data for weekly and diurnal variations.

We find that generally the mean BC concentrations are higher at the more polluted site of Warsaw (1.07 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during summer and 2.04 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during winter) than in Vilnius (0.77 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during summer

and 1.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during winter). The source apportionment to biomass burning (BC_{BB}) and fossil fuel combustion (BC_{FF}) showed similar contributions for both sites with the mean BC_{BB} being significantly lower (13-19% during summer and 30-36% during winter) than the mean BC_{FF} (81-87% during summer and 64-70% during winter).

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Observations of VOC composition in UK urban environments

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Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are ubiquitous in the urban atmosphere and can significantly affect air quality through their contributions to ozone and secondary aerosol formation. Ambient VOCs have been measured in the three most populous UK cities: London; Birmingham; and Manchester since January 2021 in order to better understand the atmospheric processes and emission sources that determine their composition and concentration in these cities.

Oxygenated volatile organic compounds (OVOCs) were found to be amongst the most abundant species measured at all three locations, contributing between 18 and 25 % by mass during winter and in excess of 50 % by mass during summer months. Sources of OVOCs are complex and varied with contributions from secondary production during atmospheric processing of other organic compounds as well as primary emissions from combustion sources, solvent use and contributions from previously neglected sources such as vehicle screen wash (Cliff et al., 2023). Despite this, OVOCs are currently omitted from the UK's VOC monitoring network due to historical technical challenges in their measurement. OVOCs were found to be more concentrated during summer months, when higher levels of photochemical activity lead to increased secondary production within the atmosphere. Primary emitted, longer lived, pollutants such as lightweight alkanes followed the expected trend of greater winter time concentrations due to increased emission and lower boundary layer height due to the colder temperatures. Diurnal and seasonal cycles were observed for many species with some exhibiting a factor of two increase in observed concentrations during winter months compared with summer.

Figure 1. ethane observations for 2022 in London, showing a clear seasonal cycle for the monthly median-average data along with large-scale deviations due to localised emissions.

This data highlights that, despite the close proximity of many sources of VOCs in urban environments, meteorology plays a major role in determining observed concentrations and air quality impacts.

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Spatial mapping of air pollution in Bucharest using mobile measurements

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Exposure to high levels of particulate matter, especially nanoparticles, brings great risks related to human health (Clifford et al, 2018). Bucharest, the capital of Romania, had 2.1 million inhabitants in 2022, on an area of 240 km², of which approximately 124 km² are residential, 45 km² green areas, 30 km² of industrial-commercial, and 6 km² streets (INSSE, 2023). The city is currently facing several challenges related to air pollution, including an increase in the concentration of particulate matter and gases. In 2020, the European Commission took measures against Romania in response to its failure to meet PM₁₀ pollution limits.

Two mobile measurement campaigns were carried out, one during 2022 warm period (May-July) and the other during 2023 cold period (January-February), where the variability of ultrafine particles (<300nm), particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁), and gases (NO₂, SO₂, O₃) were acquired. The measurements were conducted repeatedly on a route of approximately 8 hours and 100 km, including diverse urban environments (residential, industrial, commercial), and different types of streets at various kinds of traffic during work days.

The main instruments used for mobile campaigns were Sniffer 4D, Ecomtrek, and Partector 2 for particles, gases, and ultrafine particles (UFP) concentrations variability measurements. For the sake of uniformity and effective data representation, processing, and filtration procedures were diligently applied.

Table 1. Comparison between seasons of UFP mass and LDSA.

Period	Mass ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	LDSA ($\mu\text{m}^2/\text{m}^3$)
Warm	8.91 \pm 19.3	56.14 \pm 71
Cold	9.92 \pm 18.7	71.58 \pm 85.9

Higher concentrations were observed overall during the cold period, as expected. Table 1 shows the average concentration of ultrafine particles and lung deposited surface area (LDSA) along the mobile route during the warm and cold periods. In the cold period, more heating systems are used, resulting in increased emissions of particles, compared to the warm period.

The spatial and seasonal variability of UFP mass concentration highlighted gradients of particle

concentrations between areas and related exposure of populations higher along main roads (Figure 1). The western area of the city showed higher levels of pollution in both seasons, which can be attributed to intense pollution from road traffic during the morning hours, as well as the presence of industrial centers and electro-thermal plants (CET). The area around Antiaeriana Street (south) recorded the highest level of 23.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during the warm period, but significant levels were also recorded in the Militari (west), Pantelimon (east), and Progresu (south) areas. On the other hand, during the cold period, the highest value of 32.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was recorded in the Drumul Taberei district, in the south-west of the capital.

Figure 1. Spatial variability of ultrafine particles during warm and cold periods

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Biomass burning tracers and organic carbon in atmospheric aerosol PM₁ and PM_{2.5}

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Keywords: levoglucosan, organic carbon, biomass burning

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Biomass is chosen as an alternative fuel to coal. It is considered a renewable and environmentally friendly fuel, as the emissions of sulphur dioxide during combustion are lower than those from coal burning. In addition, the amount of carbon dioxide produced during combustion does not exceed that taken up by plants during photosynthesis. Combustion flue gases are major source of soot, particulate matter (PM), inorganic and organic compounds. Among the latter, we can distinguish tracers – key compounds in the identification of combusted fuels. Commonly used biomass burning tracers are anhydrosaccharides – levoglucosan, mannan and galactosan.

On a mass basis, the largest source of emissions from biomass burning in Europe is the wood burning in cookers and fireplaces used for heating and cooking in residential buildings. During the summer, wood is used in open fires as well as for barbecuing, smoking, i.e. preparing food in the open air. However, illegal burning of cleaning residues and waste on allotments and in domestic gardens, as well as grass burning, remains a serious problem. Biomass burning tracers represent a proportion of the total organic carbon (OC). It is important to remember that levoglucosan, mannan and galactosan are not the only compounds released during the burning process. However, based on their concentrations, we can estimate the contribution that biomass burning makes to the total organic carbon content determined in atmospheric particulate matter. The known concentration of levoglucosan allows to calculate the estimate organic carbon content from biomass burning as well as the percentage of organic carbon from biomass burning in the determined organic carbon. The calculation uses the levoglucosan and OC emission value from wood combustion. Although the emission factors of both OC and levoglucosan vary by orders of magnitude depending on the type of wood burned, as well as the conditions and method of combustion (cooker, fireplace, boilers, open burning) (Simoneit 1999, Fine 2002).

Given these data, the LG concentration is used to calculate the percentage of organic carbon from the biomass combustion process in the determined organic carbon using the equation proposed by Sang et al (2011):

$$\text{Contribution of biomass burning to OC} = \frac{(\text{Levoglucosan} - 17.5)/(1000 \times \text{OC})}{0.082} \times 100\%$$

PM₁ and PM_{2.5} samples were collected at the measurement station in Zabrze from 29.09.2021 to 05.01.2022. The highest levoglucosan concentration was determined at 22.12.2021, it was 0,534 µg/m³ for PM₁ and 0,604 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5}. The determined OC concentration was 15,858 µg/m³ for PM₁ and 21,049 µg/m³ for PM_{2.5}.

The calculated percentage of organic carbon from biomass burning in determined organic carbon according to Sanga was 39,7% and 34,0% for PM₁ and PM_{2.5}, respectively.

The levoglucosan concentration can also be used to estimate organic carbon concentration from wood/biomass combustion. Trial combustion in fireplaces and cookers yielded an average value for the mass OC/levoglucosan ratio of 7.35, which was confirmed in trial combustion of beech and spruce in a tiled cooker (Schmidl 2008). To calculate the estimated OC concentration from biomass, Puxbaum et al (2007) and Fuller et al (2014) proposed the formula:

$$\text{OC from biomass burning} = \text{Levoglucosan} \times 7.35 \times 1.4$$

For the highest determined levoglucosan concentration the estimated organic carbon concentrations from biomass combustion according to Puxbaum and Fuller was 5,50 µg/m³ and 6,21 µg/m³ for PM₁ and PM_{2.5}, respectively.

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A city's impact during extreme heat events: PANAME observations of the Paris urban boundary layer during summer 2022 & 2023

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Many regions across Europe experienced periods of record heat during summer 2022. In France, a high number of excess deaths (>2,800) has been attributed to three heatwaves between June - August. The Paris region, the largest metropolitan area of Europe (~ 12 million inhabitants), was exposed to anomalous heat (> 40 °C). This work examines how the specific dynamics of the Paris region urban atmosphere interact with synoptic flow and advection of hot air that influence the formation of the heat waves at the larger scale.

The interdisciplinary PANAME initiative is a framework coordinating the synergy of numerous projects that are studying the Paris atmosphere using both numerical modelling at various scales and novel observations. The measurement network not only includes dense surface station measurements and turbulent flux towers, but also ground-based atmospheric profile remote sensing and additional radiosonde measurements within the city. This work exploits observations from automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC), Doppler Wind Lidars (DWL), and Microwave Radiometers (MWR) operated along a suburban-urban transect to collect simultaneous profiles of air temperature, wind, turbulence, and aerosol characteristics at high vertical and temporal resolution.

The complex dynamics of the urban atmospheric boundary layer are explored through advanced measurement products, such as low-level jet characteristics, indicators of atmospheric stability or automatically derived heights of the mixing layer. Capabilities and limitations of these products from ground-based remote sensing observations are assessed through comparison against frequent radiosoundings.

It is then analysed how the combination of synoptic-scale flow and urban heterogeneities influence near-surface stratification, with a clear impact on pollution dispersion and urban heat island intensities.

The work highlights the importance of atmospheric boundary layer dynamics as a crucial driver for near-surface conditions, especially in cities where an increasing number of inhabitants is exposed to various hazards. The continuous observations from a network of

compact ground-based remote sensing instruments are shown to be extremely valuable for an improved understanding of the complex processes that govern the urban atmosphere as they are highly variable in space and time.

Figure 1. PANAME observations of the Paris atmospheric boundary layer during a heatwave in July 2022. (top) potential temperature from MWR operated by Météo France at LISA-PRG with profiles from windsond balloon ascents by IPSL; (bottom) wind direction observed with Vaisala DWL operated by IPSL at QUALAIR-SU.

This work is conducted as part of the PANAME initiative and was supported by the the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (H2C; grant no. ANR-20-CE22-0013); the EU Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Section (ACTRIS; grant no. 871115); and the EU Horizon 2020 Green Deal (RIURBANS; grant no. 101036245).

Aerosol in-situ physical properties measured at the future ACTRIS site in Brussels with emphasis on multi-year aerosol absorption properties

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Keywords: urban aerosol, aerosol absorption coefficient, emission sources

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The Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium (RMI) is currently setting up an ACTRIS Aerosol In-situ National Facility in Uccle, Brussels. Measured parameters are the aerosol light absorption and scattering coefficients, important to characterize the influence of aerosols on the Earth's radiative balance. Further parameters will be the number concentration and the size distribution of atmospheric particles, ranging from 10 nm to 10 μm . These data are essential to study atmospheric processes like the formation, growth, origin and transport of particles, as well as for air quality studies.

With respect to air quality, particles smaller than 1 μm are important because they are inhalable deeply into the human lung. A relevant part of such (ultra-)fine particles are light-absorbing particles. The main sources for such particles in the urban atmosphere are emissions from traffic and from domestic heating. In order to be able to apply efficient mitigation measures, it is important to quantify the relative contributions of these sources to the atmospheric particle load.

The RMI gathers ambient aerosol absorption data in Brussels with a 7-wavelengths aethalometer continuously since 2014. The measurement site is located in the sub-urban, southern part of Brussels and measurements are representative for the urban background. The mass concentration of light-absorbing particles had a typical annual cycle with higher values in winter than in summer and a typical daily cycle with clear peaks during rush hour times and in the early evening. The mass concentration of light-absorbing particles showed a decreasing tendency since 2014, particularly marked in 2020, the year strongly influenced by Covid-19 measures (see Fig. 1). However, years 2021 and 2022 showed a slight increase in concentrations compared to 2020. First results for 2023 are similar to 2022.

The Absorption Angstrom Exponent (AAE; spectral dependency of the absorption coefficient) is exploited to derive the relative contribution of fresh soot and other sources to the amount of light-absorbing aerosol. The typical AAE values (calculated between 370 and 660 nm) at the RMI site showed variations both on a daily, weekly, and seasonal scale. The monthly values for the AAE reached values around 1.6 during winter and around 1.1 during summer months (see Fig. 1). When investigating averaged daily cycles, the AAE reached peak values around 1.8 during winter nights and decreased to 1.0 to 1.2 during summer months (in

particular during rush hour times). The AAE showed an increasing trend since 2014. However, years 2021 and 2022 showed slightly lower values compared to 2020. First results for 2023 are similar to 2022.

In addition, results of the first measurements with the newly installed total particle counter (TSI3750) and Aerodynamic particle sizer (TSI3321) will be presented. Such measurements for the total particle concentration and size distribution ($> 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) have not yet been done systematically for Brussels.

Furthermore, the meteorological conditions are indispensable to understand the evolution of the concentration and atmospheric dispersion of atmospheric particles. At the RMI site, auxiliary meteorological data are available, as well as data of a collocated ceilometer from which the mixing layer height is operationally derived. Results of the relationship between atmospheric particle properties and meteorological conditions will be presented.

Figure 1: equivalent Black Carbon mass concentration (at 660 nm; ng/m³) vs AAE (370-660 nm); yearly and seasonal means (s1 = winter; s2 = spring, s3 = summer; s4 = autumn; lockdown period = 18-03 to 05-05)

We are grateful for the support and financing of this research by Belgian Science Policy Office (Belspo, contract FSIRI/00/AC1) and by the RMI.

Unusual aerosol load over the Naples urban area following victory of the national football championship: study and characterization by remote sensing and near surface instruments

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Keywords: Remote sensing, aerosol, pollution.

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The monitoring of atmospheric aerosol is particularly important for its impact on climate change and air quality. Specifically, in urban areas, fireworks release several amounts of aerosol and gases into the atmosphere for a short period of time. Because of health impact effects, the scientific community has recently begun to take an interest in urban air pollution sources (Crespo *et al*, 2014).

During the night between 4th and 5th May 2023, following Naples football team victory of the Italian league title, numerous fireworks were set off throughout the city. As a result of this event, significant amounts of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} particles were released into the environment, as detected by various monitoring stations located over the city (www.arpacampania.it).

We performed an analysis using both active and passive remote sensing techniques to observe how the aerosol moved along the atmospheric column within the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL). To investigate the nature of the increased aerosol loading, these observations were complemented with the High-Resolution Time-of-Flight Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (HR-ToF-AMS), which showed an increment in concentration of fireworks components in concurrence with the start of the celebration. In addition, Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) retrieved with a sun-sky-lunar photometer CIMEL CE318-T shows a peak simultaneously to the end of the match on 4th may 2023 (21:00 UTC). Figure 1 reports a comparison between the data collected by different instruments all addressing a peak around 21:00 UTC.

The comparison between backscattering coefficients (β) retrieved before and after the celebration night by lidar suggests a major presence of aerosol in the atmosphere, following the firework display. This has been possible with a long series of lidar measurements at 355 and 532 nm performed between 4th and 5th may. In this communication, a thorough analysis of atmospheric parameters provided by various techniques will be illustrated and discussed.

Figure 1. Data retrieved with the various instruments. a) PM₁₀ concentrations measured by three air quality monitoring stations; b) Concentration of pollutants measured by the HR-ToF-AMS; c) AOD @ 440 nm retrieved by the sun-sky-lunar photometer

Crespo, J., Yubero, E., Nicolás, J.F., Caballero, S., and Galindo N. (2014) *Atmospheric Environment*, **96**, 20-26

Physicochemical PM₁ characterization for connected-flow events between Hyltemossa and Preila during winter of 2017-2018

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Keywords: chemical characterisation, long-range transport.

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Aerosol particle chemical composition and mass concentrations undergo significant changes due to long-range air mass transport. In addition, the role of sea and oceans in aerosol chemical composition remains poorly understood. While previous studies have explored shipping-related aerosol properties (Ausmeel *et al.*, 2020) or aerosol size distributions during connected flow events across the Baltic Sea (Kecorius *et al.*, 2016), few studies have comprehensively investigated the impact of PM₁ removal over the sea, leaving a gap in our understanding of aerosol dynamics.

In this study, we examined 4 months of data (December 2017 to March 2018) of PM₁ chemical composition in two observation stations: Hyltemossa in Sweden, set in a rural environment, and Preila in Lithuania, situated in a marine environment. Simultaneous measurements of aerosol chemical composition (organic matter, nitrate, ammonium, chloride, sulphate) were performed with time-of-flight Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (ToF-ACSM, Aerodyne Research, Inc) in Hyltemossa and Q-ACSM in Preila. Equivalent black carbon (eBC) mass concentrations were measured using Aethalometers AE33 and AE31 (Magee Scientific) in Hyltemossa and Preila, respectively.

The influence of PM₁ removal over the sea on submicron particle composition was studied during the 14 events (in total 100 hourly trajectories) of long-range transport between Hyltemossa and Preila. The backward air mass transport trajectories were modelled using the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model with the Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS) meteorological databases at the NOAA Air Resources Laboratory's web server. The investigation focused solely on trajectories that passed upwind of Hyltemossa within a 50 km radius, extending 500 km over the Baltic Sea downwind and arriving at Preila at an elevation of 100 meters (ASL).

Throughout the campaign, the PM₁ concentration in Preila was generally higher (11.1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) than in Hyltemossa (6.7 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). In contrast, during the investigated events, PM₁ concentration in Preila (2.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) was 40% lower than in Hyltemossa (4.3 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), indicating aerosol removal over the sea (Figure 1).

Figure 1 PM₁ chemical composition averaged for the whole campaign and during air mass transport events in both Hyltemossa and Preila stations.

Meteorological impact was taken into consideration and events with precipitation were evaluated separately. As expected, the aerosol mass removal per hour was stronger during the events with precipitation. The highest mass removal rate both for the events with no precipitation and with precipitation was observed for nitrate ($-0.04 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and $-0.06 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively). Organic matter mass was the least affected and usually would not exhibit high mass change. The results provide a better understanding of aerosol characterisation in the south-eastern Baltic Sea background environments and removal over the sea.

This work was supported by ACTRIS Sweden, which is a National Research Infrastructure funded jointly by the Swedish Research Council (Grant 2021-00177) and the six Swedish Research Performing Organizations involved.

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Individual exposition at UV radiation and atmospheric pollution in Hauts-de-France region.

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Keywords: Individual exposition, UV, pollution.

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Hauts-de-France is a region where the population is exposed to different factors that have an impact on health, among which air pollution and, secondly, mostly cloudy conditions that do not encourage the population to protect themselves from UV radiation in spring and summer. Studies conducted by the French National Cancer Institute (INCa, Defossez et al 2019, CépiDc data) show that the number of fatal cases of skin cancer is increasing in France, with the northern region having the highest number of cases. In addition, the combination of different factors such as solar radiation, pollution, high temperatures and air humidity can accelerate skin ageing and the appearance of melanomas (Krutmann et al 2014, Kim et al, 2016, Vecchi et al, 2019).

In this context, in order to estimate the conditions of potential risk submitted by the population, a participatory science campaign took place during two periods, spring and summer, in 2023 in Lille. In this study, we present the experimental set-up and the main results.

Five volunteers wore mini-sensors, light and easy to use, to measure UV index (dosimeters), the mass concentration of fine particles (PM10, PM2.5 and PM1 with Apolline sensor) and chemical species (in particular PAHs) of the environment in which they lived or worked.

The weather conditions during the two campaigns were representative of contrasted typical weather situations in Lille: they include some intense pollution, associated to sunny conditions and high temperatures and also lower temperature days, associated to wind with dispersion of pollutants and mixed clear/cloudy skies.

Figure 1. UVI measurements from dosimeters (coloured markers) and the reference instrument (pyranometer, black line) from 12 to 18 June 2023.

Figure 1 shows an example of the UVI result from the dosimeters. The reference measurements give the maximum UVI that people can receive during the day. Results show that some volunteers received the maximum amount of UVI. This is confirmed by the calculation of the standard erythemal doses (SED) which exceeded the minimum erythemal doses (MED) for a phototype II. Two volunteers exceeded these values every day, and very quickly in the morning, at around 11:00, i.e. before midday, the most critical time of the day. It is therefore very easy and quick to reach critical values.

Figure 2 shows the results of the Apolline sensors compared with the reference measurements. PM1 regularly exceeded 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (WHO threshold for PM2.5 concentration) highlighting polluted periods. All the conditions were therefore in place for observing adverse effects on health. Further analysis of the volunteers' habits and chemical analyses will complete the forthcoming results.

Figure 2. PM1 measurements from SMPS and Apolline.

This work was supported by the LEFE/INSU and CPER/ECRIN.

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Aerosol retrievals by combining lidar volume depolarization ratio and sun-photometer DoLP in the GRASP code

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The GRASP algorithm (Dubovik *et al*, 2014, Dubovik *et al*, 2021) is a well-known code for retrieving aerosol and surface properties by combinations between remote sensing observations. Ground-based instruments are regularly used for retrieving aerosol properties with GRASP algorithm (Lopatin *et al*, 2013): the sun-photometer, which measures columnar aerosol properties, with new models including the Degree of Linear Polarization (DoLP), and the lidar system, which provides vertical distribution of the aerosol optical properties (Oliveira *et al*, 2023). Regarding the particle depolarization measured by lidars, this technique is widely used for aerosol classification (Winker and Osborn, 1992; Murayama *et al*, 2004; Groß *et al*, 2011) and for the retrieval of aerosol microphysical properties (Burton *et al*, 2015; Olmo *et al*, 2008; Veselovskii *et al*, 2016), as the aerosol shape has an influence on the polarization of the echo signal. This study focuses on the evaluation of the optical and microphysical properties of the aerosols inverted by the data combination between three elastics and two depolarization channels from UPC/EARLINET lidar system and seven polarized sun-photometer channels in Barcelona, Spain.

The AERONET photometer network provides radiances, DoLP and Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) from measurements at several zenith angles at seven wavelengths of level 2.0, Version 3, which are the GRASP inputs. The UPC/EARLINET lidar system is a complete lidar with 3 elastic channels, 2 Raman channels, 1 water vapour channel and 2 depolarized channels. The Single Calculus Chain (SCC) interface (D'Amico *et al*, 2015; D'Amico *et al*, 2016; Mattis *et al*, 2016) is used to invert the Volume Depolarization Ratio (VDR) at 355 and 532 nm and 3 Range Corrected Signals (RCS) at 355, 532 and 1064 nm. These products are GRASP inputs. The combination between data from both instruments is made for three different aerosol scenarios (Table 1): i) pure dust condition (Dust), ii) mixture between dust and urban aerosol with high contribution of fine particles (Dust-Urban I), and iii) mixture between dust and urban aerosol with low contribution of fine particle (Dust-

Urban II). These conditions are typical in Barcelona's atmosphere.

The backscatter profiles at 355, 532 and 1064 nm retrieved by GRASP algorithm will be compared with those retrieved by SCC. Furthermore, the improvements by using DoLP + VDR as GRASP inputs will be evaluated by comparing the aerosol properties from the standard (4 channels of the standard photometer + 3 RCS) combination which excludes polarization measurements with the state-of-the-art combinations of 7 photometer's channels (with and without DoLP) + 3 RCS + 2 VDR. The residuals from GRASP retrievals will also be considered as an indicator of the best inversions (< 5%) according to Dubovik *et al* (2011).

Table 1. Aerosol scenarios. AE is the Angstrom Exponent (440-870 nm), SF is the Sphere Fraction.

	Dust	Dust-Urban I	Dust-Urban II
Day	7/5/2022	4/29/2022	7/20/2022
Time	8:37	16:09	7:08
AOD	0.38	0.29	0.37
AE	0.41	1.43	1.51
SF	1.42%	63.42%	17.48%

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About the spatio-temporal variability of VOC in the city and their link to air quality

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Keywords: Urban Air Quality, Mobile Measurements, VOC, PTR-ToF-MS, Photochemistry

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Urban air quality is impacted by multiple entangled factors, both of physical and chemical nature. Which factors determine whether pollutants form and accumulate in air is therefore an important question for evaluating the potential risk for environmental and human health. Despite monitoring the major known air pollutants, such as ozone (O₃), nitrogen oxides (NO and NO₂), and particulate matter (PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}), little knowledge exists about the composition and variation of volatile organic compounds (VOC) in urban air.

Especially in the urban street canyon, a comprehensive characterization of VOC can be a powerful tool to reveal relevant sources, the potential of photochemical production of secondary pollutants such as O₃ and PM, and the effect of mixing and stagnation periods given by micrometeorological conditions. Yet, street-scale VOC observations in urban environments are rare.

Here, we examined the spatio-temporal variation of VOC in the air of a street canyon in Munich city (Germany), which is characterized by frequent traffic and densely populated. For this purpose, we assembled a mobile laboratory in an air-conditioned trailer. The mobile laboratory contained a Proton-Transfer Reaction – Time-of-Flight – Mass Spectrometer (PTR-ToF-MS), NO, NO₂ and O₃ analysers, a GPS tracker, an ultrasonic anemometer, and a non-dispersive infrared gas analyser for carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water (H₂O). The PTR-ToF-MS was operated with H₃O⁺ for ionization to determine selected VOC, i.e. calibrating for methanol, acetonitrile,

acetaldehyde, acetone, isoprene, benzene, toluene and several oxidation products. To assess the VOC oxidation products more selectively and sensitively, the reagent for ionization was switched to NH₄⁺ occasionally (Müller et al., 2020).

In September 2023, we first conducted a comprehensive mobile field campaign recording data along two routes, covering the main street and the side roads of the neighbourhood. Secondly, we performed stationary measurements on the sidewalk along the main street for one consecutive week. These two data sets provide insight into typical urban composition and mixing ratios of VOC. The analysis of temporal and spatial variability of VOC and all co-measured atmospheric variables allows us to explore the underlying physical and chemical processes leading to the formation of secondary pollutants.

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Multi-year variations of submicron aerosol composition and sources in Ireland

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The air quality in Ireland was once significantly deteriorated by air pollutants emitted from domestic coal combustion activities in the 1980s. Thanks to the smoky coal ban which was put into force in 1990, the air pollution in Ireland has been improved gradually and surely (Goodman et al., 2009). However, extreme air pollutions with the mass concentration of submicron aerosols (PM₁) exceeding 300 µg m⁻³ were still observed sporadically during cold months (Lin et al., 2018), which were mainly related to domestic solid fuel combustion, and the disproportionate impacts from so-called “low-carbon” and “carbon-neutral” solid fuels (e.g., peat and wood). Moreover, due to the increasing wood stove advertisements and significant fuel price increase caused by Ukrainian-Russian war, the emissions from local solid fuel combustion activities could greatly impair the air quality in Ireland in the future. Since the situation is changing year to year, it's very critical to conduct continuous field aerosol measurements and have a deeper insight into the medium/long-term variations for more targeted and effective regulations in the future. In this study, based on the parallel real-time measurements of submicron aerosol species at three representative sites over Ireland, the multi-year variations of aerosol chemical composition and source emissions have been analyzed.

The air quality in Dublin has been improved gradually since 2016, with the annual average mass concentration of PM₁ decreased from 8.0 µg m⁻³ in 2016 to 4.1 µg m⁻³ in 2022, and the total number of days when PM₁ concentration exceeds the WHO recommendation value (15 µg m⁻³) has decreased to 11 days in 2022. Specifically, the extreme air pollutions have been reduced significantly, e.g., the maximum hourly PM₁ concentration has decreased to 77 µg m⁻³ in 2022 compared to 317 µg m⁻³ in 2016. The high PM₁ concentrations in Dublin were more related to local emissions, especially domestic solid fuel burning, characterized by large contributions from primary organic aerosols. While long-range transport also plays an important role with high fractions of inorganics especially Nitrate (NO₃). The chemical composition of PM₁ in Dublin was similar over the years, i.e., dominated by Organics (Org) and then followed by NO₃ or sulfate (SO₄). However, it's worrisome to find that the mass concentration of SO₄ has been increasing since 2021 and showed higher contribution to PM₁ especially during cold

months, indicating that the sharply increasing fuel prices recently may have led to a change in fuel usage, possibly with more coal and solid fuel combustion in households. This could indicate severe air pollution episodes that need further and more effective regulations in the near future to ensure good enough air quality.

Figure 1. Changes of average (a) mass concentrations and (b) mass fractions of PM₁ species in Dublin, the variations of maximum PM₁ mass concentration were also shown. Note that the equivalent black carbon (eBC) data were not available in 2018, 2019 and 2020.

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Wind and turbulence statistics over Măgurele using ground-based measurements

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Wind is one of the most essential variables for understanding Earth atmosphere and climate system due to its contribution to short- and long-range transportation of heat, air pollutants and air masses. Extreme wind can also have serious negative societal and economical effects, including human and animal fatalities and infrastructure damage. Wind is a critical variable that is related to physical processes in the planetary boundary layer (PBL). Accurately retrieving wind direction and speed with great spatial and temporal resolution is of great importance. There are several uses for these wind retrievals in meteorology, aviation, and the energy industry. To ensure flight safety, low-level wind shear and turbulence critical information must be obtained, which can only be done by collecting high-resolution wind data.

Data from the StreamLine XR Doppler Wind Lidar (DWL) were regularly collected from December 2019 to November 2021 for this study. Vertical measurements of wind speed were performed along with 15 minutes scanning scenarios proposed by Päsckke (2015). The "HALO Streamline Photonics Doppler lidar data postprocessing toolbox" (Halo Toolbox), presented by Manninen et al. (2018) uses this data as input files. This toolbox is used to extract data on wind characteristics, turbulent mixing sources, and the structure of the planetary boundary layer.

Figure 1 shows one example of hourly averages of horizontal wind speed (top) and horizontal wind direction (bottom) for spring season over the December 2019—November 2021 period (analysis was performed on all seasons in this period). The analysis of DWL wind field shows that, in general, the horizontal wind speed is increasing with altitude reaching a maximum of $\sim 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ in spring.

During spring time, the wind direction is predominantly from the northeast between 23–07 UTC for all altitudes. The wind is veering between 09–11 UTC from southeast to west and backing between 16–23 UTC from south to northwest. The diurnal cycle of wind direction is more pronounced in spring in comparison to the other seasons, being related to a bigger temperature difference between day and night.

The results from this study were published by Pîrloagă et al. (2023).

Figure 1. Doppler wind lidar hourly averages of horizontal wind speed (top) and horizontal wind direction (bottom) for spring season in the December 2019—November 2021 period at Măgurele, Romania

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Intensive Comparative Study of Black Carbon and Other Carbonaceous Aerosols in Four South-Eastern European Hotspots

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Air pollution poses a substantial health risk in South-Eastern Europe (SEE), particularly in countries outside the purview of European Union (EU) regulations. The air quality in these regions is frequently among the worst globally (Daul Čolović, 2019). In SEE, particularly during the winter season, carbonaceous aerosols (CA) constitute the dominant component of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). These aerosols predominantly originate from vehicular emissions, residential heating, coal-fired power plants, or other industrial processes. The oxidative potential of particulate matter, a measure of its toxicity, is largely associated with anthropogenic sources across Europe. Specifically, residential biomass burning and non-exhaust emissions from vehicles are the primary contributors (Daellenbach, 2020). Black carbon (BC) and other fractions of CA, analyzed in this study, serve as effective tracers for these sources (Costabile, 2023).

An intensive research campaign, encompassing the measurement of BC concentrations using an AE33 Aethalometer (Drinovec, 2015) was conducted across four capital cities (background urban sites) in the SEE region: Ljubljana (LJ, Slovenia), Zagreb (ZG, Croatia), Belgrade (BG, Serbia), and Sarajevo (SA, Bosnia and Herzegovina). All chosen locations are prone to poor air quality, especially in wintertime, due to stable atmospheric conditions, unique topography, and anthropogenic activities such as traffic, industry, and residential heating. Measurement campaigns spanned from August 2022 to March 2023. Concurrently, total carbon (TC) measurements were performed in SA and LJ using a TCA08 Total Carbon Analyzer (Rigler, 2020).

Measured median concentrations of BC during the campaign period were (BC [Q1, Q3]): BC_{LJ} = 1.71 [0.93, 2.89] µg/m³, BC_{ZG} = 2.05 [1.15, 3.04] µg/m³, BC_{BG} = 2.19 [1.34, 3.91] µg/m³, and BC_{SA} = 3.24 [1.59, 6.73] µg/m³. TC concentrations in LJ and SA were TC_{LJ} = 6.98 [4.25, 11.49] µg/m³, TC_{SA} = 9.98 [5.48, 19.70] µg/m³. Source apportionment of BC shows a significant contribution from wood burning, especially in the winter months. BC and BC_{bb} diurnal profiles (Fig 1.) are strongly influenced by temporal patterns of emissions from traffic

and residential heating (biomass burning). The diurnal profile for location in SA (90m above the basin - city center), exhibits unique characteristics due to the interplay of atmospheric dynamics and local emissions.

Figure 1. Display of diurnal profiles for BC and BC_{bb} for all four capital cities (LJ, ZG, BG and SA).

This research indicates that the SEE region, particularly countries not governed by EU regulations, experiences poor air quality. It highlights the necessity for similar measurements in the future to accurately evaluate the air quality and propose adequate measures. The study also encourages the establishment of an air quality index predicated on BC (Fung, 2022) and CA as such measurement network offers better time and spatial resolution and is more relevant to human health than the one based on PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀.

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Identifying pollen episodes using a synergy of in-situ and remote sensing measurements

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Bioaerosols emitted during plant pollination contribute to increase of respiratory diseases (Asher et al., 2006; Strzelczyk et al., 2020). They need to be monitored due to their significant impact on human health, which can become even greater due to climate change causing extension of pollination period. Our research aims at characterizing pollen particles with the use of unique combination of both remote (polarization lidar) and in-situ (Hirst Spore Trap) measurements by examining the pollen type and abundance near the surface. Finally, we investigate the spread of pollen within the atmospheric boundary layer and identify conditions that facilitate its dispersion.

Our goal was to conduct 8-months (March-October 2023) field campaign for measuring allergenic pollen characteristics in Warsaw urban environment focused to capture the entire pollination period of different plants. Core observations were done with use of in-situ (Hirst-type spore trap, Lanzoni VPPS2010) and remote (Mie-Raman polarization lidar, PollyXT) measurements. During observations meteorological conditions, sun-photometer, Doppler wind lidar profiling data were collected. Manual analysis of pollen samples was done via microscopic examination of pollen grain types at the ground level on a daily temporal resolution. Based on an evaluation of nearly a decade of lidar observations we proposed a new methodology that helps to identify pollination events based on the bell-like shape in volume depolarization ratio (VDR) profiles. Collection of in-situ measurements gives a unique ability for verification of bell-like shape pollination events identification methodology.

A preliminary comparison of lidar characteristics and in-situ measurements was conducted using daily pollen concentration and a determined set of conditions that match boundaries of the typical pollination case (VDR: $\bar{x}=3.4\%$, $\sigma=1.3\%$, relative humidity: $\bar{x}=55.9\%$, $\sigma=21.6\%$, temperature: $\bar{x}=18.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\sigma=7.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, wind speed: $\bar{x}=3.9\text{ m/s}$, $\sigma=1.9\text{ m/s}$, maximum of boundary layer top = 1832 m , $\sigma=441\text{ m}$, pollination time: $\bar{x}=13.6\text{ h}$, $\sigma=3.28\text{ h}$). Based on characteristic shape and size of pollen grains, we can expect high or negligible depolarization of a laser beam for each taxa. A combination of in-situ and remote detection methods allows the characterization of pollen type and its vertical extent.

Figure 1. Warsaw pollen concentrations observed between March-October 2023 with use of Hirst-type volumetric sampler

In the future we will assess to what extent the synergy of this combined approach can help in faster pollination detection and if it can be used for monitoring purposes. For this, an Intensive Operation Period (IOP) is planned in Warsaw using the pollen trap, fluorescence EMORAL lidar, and near-field NARLa lidar in unique hourly-based configuration to obtain micro-physical properties of particles near the surface.

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Is traffic still an important source of Volatile Organic Compounds in European urban areas?

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Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) play a key role in atmospheric chemistry, especially as they are precursors of secondary pollutants (ozone, secondary organic aerosols, etc.), and they are key tracers for specific sources. Despite the fact that tropospheric ozone is an adverse environmental and health problem in Europe, and high ozone episodes are underpredicted by atmospheric transport models, few studies regarding VOCs have been conducted in urban environments in Europe and covering the whole range of VOCs (non-methane hydrocarbons - NMHC, oxygenated VOCs - OVOC). Long-term high-quality VOC datasets are therefore crucial for the evaluation of emission inventories used as inputs of the chemical-transport models. In the framework of RI-URBANS project, we collected VOC datasets in urban environments, and we applied a statistical model in order to improve our knowledge regarding VOC source apportionment in Marseille – France and in Zurich – Switzerland.

For the first time, a one year and half (March 2019 - August 2020) measurement campaign has been conducted in Marseille at an urban area representative site, where in addition to a large set of instruments, two on-line thermal-desorption gas chromatography flame ionization detector (GC-FID) have been used for the continuous hourly measurement of 70 NMHCs from 2 to 16 carbon atoms covering alkanes including IVOCs, alkenes, alkynes, aromatics. In Zurich, the dataset used covers two years measurements of NMHC and OVOC by GC-FID. These datasets have been evaluated with their associated uncertainties based on ACTRIS and WMO guidelines and performed by the two CiGas topical centre units at IMT and EMPA.

Here, we will show an overview of the Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) model results applied to these datasets in Marseille and Zurich where common sources have been identified (road transport, natural gas, heating/wood burning, local emissions), and one source related to solvent use has been identified in Zurich thanks to OVOC data.

This study was conducted within Marvin Dufresne PhD funded by ADEME and IMT Nord Europe, and in the framework of the RI-URBANS project (Research Infrastructures Services Reinforcing Air Quality

Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial Areas, European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Green Deal, European Commission, contract 101036245).

Figure 1: Source apportionment results at Marseille and Zurich.

Day/night variability of Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds (PACs) at a highly impacted biomass burning city

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Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and their oxygenated products (OPAHs) (referred as PACs; Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds) are organic molecules with well-recognized toxicity and carcinogenic impacts associated with human respiratory exposure (IARC, 2010). Benzo[a]Pyrene (B[a]P) is the most extensively studied PAH, due to its known health impacts. In the light of these implications, the European Union (EC, 2004) has set an annual mean target value of 1 ng m⁻³ for B[a]P.

PAHs and OPAHs are formed during incomplete combustion processes, while OPAHs can also be formed through the reactions of PAHs with atmospheric oxidants, including ozone (O₃) and hydroxyl (OH) & nitrate (NO₃) radicals. Despite their significant impact on human health, there's a notable lack of comprehensive measurements, especially in areas that are strongly affected by residential wood burning.

Ioannina is a mountainous medium sized city, with 112,000 inhabitants, in the NW part of Greece. The main air pollution source in Ioannina is biomass burning (BB) from domestic heating, with PM_{2.5} levels reaching up to 300–350 µg m⁻³, especially during nights (Kaskaoutis et al., 2022). Previous BC measurements conducted at this site indicated that, during night, wood burning accounts for more than 90% of the particulate mass. Considering that the city is situated in a valley where local emissions of pollutants are trapped, Ioannina resembles a real-world simulation chamber. This unique setting enables effective assessment of the mechanisms and impacts of wood burning emissions on atmospheric chemistry and human health, with emphasis on PACs.

In this study, PM_{2.5} samples were collected from December 2021 to January 2022, during night and day, with 12 hours resolution. Samples were analyzed for PAHs (50 species) and OPAHs (12 species), following the approach outlined in Tsiodra *et al.* 2021. In addition to PACs, chemical components, such as organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), water-soluble OC, water-soluble ions, trace metals, anhydrous sugars and oxidative potential (OP) (expressed as DTT activity) were determined. Moreover, an Aethalometer, an ACSM and a PTR-ToF-MS were also deployed (Desservettaz et al., 2023).

The results, presented in Figure 1, illustrate the variation between daytime and nighttime for the total concentration of PAHs, OPAHs, B[a]P and BC from biomass burning (BC_{bb}). The data show that the average total concentration of PACs at night was higher compared to day by a factor of almost 3. Furthermore, the average total concentration of OPAHs, B[a]P and BC_{bb} were 3.6, 2.6 and 2.1 times higher at night vs day respectively.

Figure 1. Levels of ΣPAHs, ΣOPAHs, B[a]P in PM_{2.5} samples and BC_{bb} during days vs nights in winter 2021 - 2022.

Our study employed Positive Matrix Factorization analysis (PMF) to identify the individual emission sources during night and day. Additionally, we derived the carcinogenic risk using the toxic equivalent factor approach (BaP_{eq}). The unique dataset and methodology used in this study enabled the establishment of a relationship between PACs and their OP activity.

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Aerosol properties retrieved under high turbidity conditions and the corresponding aerosol radiative effect in the European Arctic in the period 2017-2022 by sun photometry

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Aerosols play a complex role in the Earth-atmosphere system. They acquire a special importance in the Arctic, where it has been observed a warming four times higher than in the rest of the world. The Arctic is very sensitive to global changes in climate, and the local feedback mechanisms complicate the understanding of the impacts of each variable on the energy budget.

Aerosol high turbidity events are of great importance due to their capacity to alter the system. Therefore, it is important to monitor the amount and properties of the aerosols reaching this area. To this end, a sun-sky-lunar CIMEL photometer continuously working in AWIPEV station at Ny-Ålesund (79°N, Svalbard, Spitsbergen) since June 2017. This instrument is part of the AERONET network (<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>) and provides information about aerosol load and optical and microphysical properties when sky conditions are favourable.

In this study, the available dataset from AERONET at Ny-Ålesund has been analysed in order to identify high turbidity events and characterize them. To this end, the methodology proposed by Mateos et al. (2020) using AOD at 500 nm for fine and coarse modes from AERONET, and adapted as described by Hansen et al. (2022), is employed. This way, five mayor aerosol events have been detected in the period 2017-2022, which have been tracked to identify their origin using HYSPLIT backwards trajectories (See Figure 1). For each event, the available optical and microphysical parameters are extracted from the same database and averaged, obtaining mean values which are assumed as characteristic for the event.

Finally, these properties together with the instantaneous values of aerosol optical depth (AOD) and surface properties (BRDF) have been used as input for libRadtran (www.libradtran.org) to estimate the radiative impact. This effect is quantified by the direct aerosol radiative effect (ARE), obtained as the subtraction of the global irradiance calculated considering the presence of the aerosol minus the same parameter but calculated for no presence of aerosol. This method allows to obtain instantaneous values of ARE, from which daily values can be derived. Aerosol forcing

efficiency (AFE) is also obtained by a linear fit between ARE and AOD values.

Figure 1. Map with the backward trajectories of the 5 mayor aerosol events identified in Ny-Ålesund for the 2017-2022 period.

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Profiling Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds (PACs) in a European urban center: A comprehensive analysis of Biomass Burning Impact and population exposure

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Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their oxygenated derivatives (PACs) are known carcinogenic organic pollutants in fine aerosols, which can significantly aggravate the outcomes of chronic inhalation exposure. Moreover, a variety of serious non-carcinogenic effects are linked to PACs, such as cardiorespiratory and neurodevelopment effects (Geier et al., 2018). Some studies have also indicated that symptoms might be related to even short-term exposure to high levels of PACs (Karimi et al., 2018). Their abundances in aerosols provide chemical signatures of incomplete fossil fuel or biomass burning (BB) combustion. While PACs levels are adequately characterized in European cities, less is known about their sources. Recent studies report an increasing impact of BB on particle-bound PACs (Degrendele et al., 2021).

Ioannina is an inland southern European city, affected by excessive BB. Located in NW Greece, with a population of ~0.1M, it experiences harsh winters. The area's topography, combined with intense residential heating emissions, leads to extreme winter pollution events ($PM_{2.5} > 100 \mu g m^{-3}$), under limited atmospheric dispersion conditions (Kaskaoutis et al., 2022).

In this study, we explore the levels, seasonality and sources of PAHs and OPAHs (62 species) in $PM_{2.5}$ sampled in Ioannina, during summer and winter in 2019–2020. PACs in quartz filters were determined by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), using the protocol of Tsiotra et al. (2021). Ancillary measurements for 38 other PM components (including anhydrous sugars and trace metals), Black Carbon (BC) and oxidative potential (expressed by DTT activity) were performed.

The results (Figure 1) indicate a clear connection between seasonal BB processes and BaPeq, an indicator used to collectively characterize PAC toxicity based on their relative carcinogenic potencies. Wintertime PAHs and OPAHs mean concentrations were up to 100 and 90 times higher, respectively, compared to the summer. In addition, Benzo[a]Pyrene (BaP), the only regulated PAH, had concentrations 5 times higher on average during winter, compared to the annual EU limit value, indicating that solely the BB-related cold period exacerbation of levels is adequate for a violation of the standard. Σ -PACs were strongly correlated ($r^2: 0.71$) with DTT activity in

winter (stronger than BaPeq; $r^2: 0.51$), highlighting the substantial BB impact on oxidative potential and the toxic action of non-carcinogenic congeners. Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) is also used in the study to quantify PAC sources and their specific carcinogenic risks.

The study findings highlight the importance of residential BB for urban air quality, and suggest high risks for the population exposed to such concentrations of toxic organic species for prolonged winter periods, with implications for public health in Northern Greece and the Balkan region in general.

Figure 1. Correlations of (a) BaPeq vs BC from BB, and (b) Σ -PACs vs DTT activity, for winter and summer periods.

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Results and follow-up from an international intercomparison of methodologies for the oxidative potential of PM: how to reach harmonization?

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Keywords: oxidative potential, harmonization, intercomparison, DDT assay .

Associated conference topics: Special session oxidative potential of aerosols

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Health effects, both acute and long-term attributable to ambient particulate matter (PM) exposures likely occur through multiple overlapping mechanisms such as oxidative stress, inflammation, genomic alterations, impaired nervous system function, epigenetic alterations, among others¹. It is implausible that these complex biological pathways respond equally to all components within ambient PM, but equally it is not simple to align complex heterogeneous chemistries with underlying biological complexity in disease pathways. Attempting to align these two complexities requires simplification, either by concatenating components into source components, or attempting to summarize components into biological relevant and toxicologically informative metrics. As ambient PM is known to contain both stable radicals and pro-oxidants it has been proposed that methods that can provide a measure of how they promote ROS generation (often described as oxidative potential – OP) *in vivo* may be useful for integration into health studies.

In recent years, this has led to an increased interest in estimating particulate OP and the development of assays systems, both simple chemical models and more complex cell/tissue based approaches to facilitate this. This discrimination is important, as the two approaches provide different outputs. The former, only provides a summary of the intrinsic oxidising characteristics of ambient PM, whilst the later captures indirect ROS generation, through altered metabolism and the induction of inflammation. Both have their merits and disadvantages, and their application and interpretation need to be carefully contextualised, however the acellular systems have gained greater traction, due to their simplicity and scalability, which permits better integration into epidemiological studies and alignment with aerosol measurement campaigns^{3,4}. Current acellular models for OP determination include the dithiothreitol assay (DTT), ascorbate assay (AA), 2,7-

dichlorofluorescein assay (DCFH), electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy, glutathione assay (GSH), Ferric-Xylenol Orange hydroperoxide assay (FOX), 9,10-bis (phenylethynyl) anthracene-nitroxide (BPEAnit) ROS assay (BPEAnit-Me), among others. These acellular assays display different sensitivities to particle components, allowing a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms of PM-induced ROS generation. Despite improvements in the state of the knowledge concerning PM OP there remains no consensus about assay protocols making comparison of results across studies challenging.

The EU RI-URBANS³ project has made a first attempt at harmonization and launched an international intercomparison of OP assays. The intercomparison relies on both a simplified OP DTT protocol implemented by every participating group and allows integration of other OP protocols. Nineteen laboratories declared their interest in the exercise. Four different PM suspension samples were shipped to participants. The intercomparison was launched between January 17th and February 15th to minimize ageing processes. Data treatment was done anonymously by the EU Joint Research Center. This paper will present the results of the exercise and next steps to reach harmonization. This integrative exercise is a necessary step in the evaluation of oxidative potential as a metric predictive of the effects of particulate matter upon human health.

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Synergistic Monitoring of Air Quality Policy from Space and In Situ: A Case Study on Belgium

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Keywords: Urban Air Quality, TROPOMI, synergies

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Air Quality (AQ) in the European Low Countries is driven by complex processes covering a wide range of temporal and spatial scales, from point-like emissions of primary pollutants to intercontinental transport and the formation of secondary pollutants in a region with highly inhomogeneous land use. The responsibility for AQ regulations is distributed among different levels of public authority, from international and federal to regional and local. Informed policymaking for AQ regulation and sustainable (fossil) energy consumption requires tailored monitoring of AQ and of the impact of past and future regulations taken.

In general, governmental AQ monitoring relies on in-situ measurements of surface concentration, with geographical gaps between these sparse observations filled in with numerical models incorporating meteorology and (proxies for) bottom-up emission estimates. However, a new constellation of LEO and GEO satellite sounders is becoming available, meant to support monitoring of AQ on the different relevant scales discussed above.

While offering near-contiguous observations of the entire domain (cloud cover permitting), observations from space also imply substantial challenges that complicate the uptake by policy makers. First, in view of the size of the typical Low Emission Zones (LEZ) enforced in several (European) cities, there is a need to enhance the resolution of the satellite data. Second, there is a non-trivial relation between the column amount measured by a satellite and the near-surface concentrations actually leading to adverse health impacts. Third, the integration of observations from multiple LEO and GEO platforms into a synergistic system requires due care for their (relative) biases and for their different perception of atmospheric features.

In order to facilitate the use of this new-generation satellite AQ data by (institutional) stakeholders, we are developing a prototype service for satellite-based AQ monitoring in a case study focused on Belgium.

In this paper, we demonstrate that a combination of temporal aggregation, careful data selection, and horizontal oversampling can produce a substantial improvement in horizontal resolution in S5P NO₂ column

maps, revealing policy-relevant spatio-temporal features over major cities, e.g., those implementing LEZ.

We also show how a synergistic use of these high-resolution S5P NO₂ maps and the near-surface in-situ observations as procured by the Belgian authorities allows a pragmatic conversion from columns to near-surface concentrations over the complete Belgian domain, and consequently also a confrontation to thresholds such as the WHO maximal annual exposure guidelines.

Finally, we touch upon the prospects offered by the upcoming geostationary capabilities.

Figure 1. Annual mean near-surface NO₂ concentration for each Belgian municipality in 2019, coloured following the WHO maximal annual exposure guideline of 10 microgram/m³. Based on a synergistic use of modified Copernicus Sentinel-5P TROPOMI and IRCEL-CELINE in-situ data.

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<https://lego-bel-aq.aeronomie.be>

Intercomparison of aerosol chemistry between urban and rural sites: Importance of biomass burning

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Keywords: aerosol composition, biomass burning, elemental carbon

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In recent years, several studies have focused on identifying and understanding the various chemical components that make up airborne particulate matter (PM) in the atmosphere. These particles, which vary in size and composition, can have a significant impact on air quality and thus on public health (Thangavel *et al* (2022)).

The burning of biomass is a common practice on the European continent both for residential use and for the disposal of pruning waste (Zhu *et al* (2017)). Recently there has been growing concern about the impact of these practices on the generation of atmospheric aerosols. In addition, many studies have found that the contribution even in areas where it was not expected to be significant (Jiang *et al* (2023)).

The main objective of this study was to investigate and evaluate the impact of biomass burning on fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) concentrations in two different environments in south-eastern Spain: one urban (Elche, Alicante) and one rural (Benejama, Alicante); located near the Mediterranean coast and inland, respectively. A total of 55 and 38 daily PM_{2.5} samples were collected during the winter and summer months using a high-volume sampler. The collected and conditioned filters were weighed to determine the pollutant concentration. Additionally, various chemical analyses (XRF, OC-EC, IC, WSOC) were performed to determine the composition of the particulate matter.

The average PM_{2.5} concentration at both sites was 16.8 (Urban) and 12.9 (Rural) µg/m³ respectively.

Figure 1. Correlation between PM_{2.5} in an urban and rural environment.

Figure 1 shows the correlation between PM_{2.5} concentrations in an urban and rural location. As can be seen, there is a slight (significant) correlation between

the two sites even though they are more than 60km apart. This indicates that an important part of the aerosol has a regional origin affecting both sites in the same way.

Table 1 shows the average composition of the most important elements at both sites during the summer.

A higher presence of EC, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻ and Ca is observed in the rural station, attributable to the lower vehicular traffic density compared to urban areas. On the other hand, a higher concentration of OC is recorded in the rural region due to intensified agricultural activity, waste management, biomass burning, and the presence of areas with abundant vegetation factors that influence OC emissions.

Table 1. Comparison of chemical analyses between urban and rural areas in summer with their standard deviation (SD). Concentrations are given in µg/m³.

	Urban		Rural	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
OC	2.25	0.71	2.59	0.76
EC	0.32	0.10	0.24	0.07
NO ₃ ⁻	0.27	0.31	0.23	0.17
SO ₄ ²⁻	2.43	1.28	1.90	0.94
Ca	0.86	0.71	0.58	0.40

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Ammonia measurements at a mountain site in central Germany (Taunus Observatory at Mt. Kleiner Feldberg)

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Keywords: Trace gases, aerosol particle composition, instrument intercomparison.

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Ammonia (NH₃) is an important alkaline trace gas mainly sourced from human activity, with agriculture and animal husbandry being the largest contributors. Global NH₃ emissions have been increasing over the last decades and are expected to rise even further in the future. NH₃ plays a crucial role in secondary aerosol formation, new particle formation (nucleation), as a key component in the global nitrogen cycle and as an air pollutant impacting human health (Kirkby *et al*, 2011; Behera *et al*, 2013). NH₃ can be measured using numerous instruments, but with varying accuracies and performance levels. Therefore, a standardised measuring procedure has yet to be established (Twigg *et al*, 2022). Despite its environmental significance, continuous long-term measurements such as the 5-year study in Melpitz, Germany by Stieger *et al* (2018) are rare.

We present continuous real-time measurements of ammonia, other trace gases and aerosol particle composition conducted at the Taunus Observatory, a mountain research station (825 m a.s.l.) located 20 km northwest of Frankfurt am Main, Germany (see Fig. 1). Depending on the wind direction, the station is influenced by continental background air masses or urban air masses from the adjacent Rhine-Main area.

Figure 1. Map indicating the location of the Taunus Observatory.

We measured NH₃, sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrous acid (HONO), nitric acid (HNO₃) and specific amines in the gas phase and ammonium (NH₄⁺), chloride (Cl⁻), sulfate (SO₄²⁻) and nitrate (NO₃⁻), among others, in the particle phase using a 2060 MARGA ion chromatograph (Metrohm Schweiz AG). For the MARGA, a specially designed inlet system was used to minimise sampling line artefacts. NH₃ was additionally measured using a TILDAS infrared laser absorption spectrometer (Aerodyne Research Inc.). While the MARGA has better detection limits than the TILDAS, the TILDAS allows faster measurements in the order of seconds (compared with 1-hour averages for the MARGA) and is therefore able to detect rapid changes in ammonia mixing ratios that may be related to changes in air mass origin, rapid temperature changes or local sources.

We present the results of these ambient measurements between winter 2023/24 and spring 2024. Combined with the analysis of the wind direction and back trajectories, we discuss the different influences of agriculture, urban settlements and long-range transport on the air masses sampled at the Taunus Observatory. The diurnal profiles for the different measured components are discussed and compared with the previously measured profiles from Melpitz (Stieger *et al*, 2018). Furthermore, we present the results of the intercomparison of NH₃ measurements with the MARGA and TILDAS devices.

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Using supervised neural networks to better evaluate surface turbulent heat fluxes in weather and climate numerical models

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This work, within the framework of the French ANR project MOSAI (Model and Observation for Surface-Atmosphere Interactions), proposes a novel evaluation approach to better identify the shortcomings of modelled surface sensible and latent heat fluxes in numerical simulations. Indeed, the classical time-to-time comparison between simulated and observed fluxes blends many sources of errors such as incoherent grid-scale representation (e.g. landscape types) and inaccurate environmental forcing (radiation, temperature, humidity and wind). Our method (Figure 1) aims into differently evaluating the modelled heat fluxes thanks to the long period of comprehensive, homogeneous and synergetic observations available over ACTRIS-FR supersites. At first, a data-driven statistical model is built using the observational data, to estimate the heat fluxes according to relevant environmental factors. Thus, using the modelled environmental conditions as input, the statistical model will generate fluxes that would have been observed in this environment. The comparison of the simulated fluxes with this new baseline freezes the errors due to model biases, helping to focus on the weaknesses of their numerical formulations.

A demonstration study will be presented with data gathered at the Météopole-flux station (Toulouse, France), from its implementation in mid-June 2012 to December 2022, about 10 years of continuous weather monitoring. Details on the data-driven statistical model construction and scores obtained will be given. Subsequently, the statistical model is applied on data from climate simulations over the

period 2012-2016 with RegIPSL model, a regional climate model developed at the Institute Pierre-Simon Laplace (IPSL, France). A discussion on the results of comparisons will be provided.

Figure 1. Illustration of our evaluation method.

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